

e-HIGHWAY 2050

Modular Development Plan of the Pan-European Transmission System 2050

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Document information

General purpose

This document constitutes the final version for Deliverable ‘D4.2a - Methodology for environmental and sustainability assessment and results of its application to the assessment of strategic options’. It presents the methodology, assessment framework of the Strategic Environmental and Sustainability Assessment and its application to e-Highway2050’s strategic options for 2050.

The application of the SESA methodology is addressed in two separate reports: D4.2a, the current document, and D4.2b. The need to split D4.2 report in two was requested by the eHighway2050 project coordination because delays in processing and delivering the outcomes of WP2 made it impossible to apply the SESA to final grid layouts. Consequently D4.2a displays and explains the methodology for the SESA, presents the outcomes of the assessment of the 2050’s strategic options, detailing recommendations that are expected to be considered in the design of the grids to ensure the integration of environment and sustainability issues. For this reason, the title for this deliverable was also changed.

D4.2b will further apply the same methodology to grid design layouts. Its expected delivery date is April 15 – M32.

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IST and CEP drafted this document, with contributions of KU Leuven experts. REN in its role as WP4 coordinator provided valuable inputs, namely to understanding technological and management aspects of grid operation.

Change status

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report details the methodology and assessment outcomes so far achieved with the Strategic Environmental and Sustainability Assessment (SESA) in the development of the e-Highway2050 project.

The overall **objective** of the SESA is to **assess the range of strategies inherent to the e-Highway2050 project, according to different scenarios**, using an assessment framework to alert decision-makers to uncertainties, risks and opportunities associated with strategic options that appear to support the modelling of alternative grid architectures.

The initial purpose of SESA is to advise on more sustainable options for grid design and to provide guidelines for future planning and development as well as for monitoring and follow-up implementation. It is not intended with this strategic assessment to exclude any specific set of strategic options or grid architectures at this stage; on the contrary, the intention is to identify risks and opportunities of pursuing any, or a combination of, various strategic options for grid development. SESA intends to help identify possible courses of action that will enable opportunities for the environment and for sustainability while avoiding risks, instead of providing yes or no answers. It is up to the project team involved in making decisions to choose a strategy, as a course of action, for grid-development that, where possible, takes full account of environmental and sustainability priorities, avoiding risks and capitalising on reaching opportunities.

SESA uses a strategic **methodological approach** for Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), structured around four Critical Decision Factors (CDF) [1]:

- CDF1: Social acceptance and acceptability;
- CDF2: Energy security and energy technologies;
- CDF3: Geo-political economy and regional equity; and
- CDF4: European regional governance.

These CDF, complemented by assessment criteria and indicators, establish the assessment framework designed to assess risks and opportunities associated with the e-Highway2050 strategic options. The assessment framework is based on three integrated frameworks:

- **A problem framework** to map key drivers of change and environmental and sustainability issues associated trends;
- **A governance framework** to map the suit of key responsibilities and competencies required for an effective delivery of e-Highway2050; and
- **A Strategic Reference Framework** to map the relevant policy framework, and its key objectives and targets, that serve as a referential for assessment.

The CDF establish the structure of the strategic assessment, considers the key environmental and sustainability trends and uses the macro-policy objectives and targets in the Strategic Reference Framework as a referential for assessment. The strategic assessment also considers governance arrangements and policy conflict

issues that may have implications for e-Highway2050 decisions. The strategic assessment is undertaken from the perspective of each CDF.

A clear identification of the **object of assessment** was critical in SESA. It was agreed with the e-Highway2050 project coordination that SESA object of assessment would be the **e-Highway2050 strategies that will result into grid architectures**, according to the different scenarios. The strategies behind the five scenarios selected in work package 2 (WP2), were interrogated and interpreted to identify plausible strategic options for e-Highway2050 that would determine the overall design of electricity grid architectures. The process for strategic interpretation of scenarios and formulation of strategic options is represented in Figure 1, and can be summarized as follows:

- Identify the main assumptions and priorities per scenario (e.g. the existence, or not, of no international greenhouse gas agreements);
- Understand priorities and the physical, technological and management implications of different scenarios, based on WP2's scenario description and initial grid modelling¹ (e.g. the focus on the deployment of large scale renewable solutions);
- Identify the main physical, technological and management patterns that could differentiate each scenario based on the main assumptions and priorities (e.g. dominance of centralised renewable generation);
- Group the scenarios into dominant strategic themes that clearly expose the common assumptions and priorities (e.g. Generation and regional balance; Storage; Transmission; International Strategy);
- Develop, for each strategic theme, a narrative of possible pathways – the strategic options - that could support alternative grid development priorities;
- Validate the technical, social and economic feasibility of the identified strategic options with other WPs and e-Highway2050 Coordination, relating it to different scenarios.

This process resulted in the identification of **16 strategic options**, grouped in **four strategic themes**: 1) Generation and regional balance; 2) Storage; 3) Transmission; and 4) International strategy.

¹ "D2.1 – G/D/E Scenarios 2050", July 2013 - Narrative interpretation prepared by KU Leuven.

Figure 1 - SESA and how it relates to other work packages
(in blue: activities developed within the SESA, Task 4.2; in grey: activities developed by other WP)

To capture stakeholder interests and perspectives, and to raise awareness concerning environmental and sustainability issues associated with the development of a pan-European electricity grid, four **stakeholder engagement activities** were conducted at main SESA stages:

1. **SESA Focus and Assessment Framework:** to seek inputs to the assessment framework on environmental and sustainability priorities, setting the focus for the assessment (consultation);
2. **SESA Focus and Assessment Framework:** follow-up to validate the assessment framework and methodology; identify drivers, macro-policies and key opportunities and risks associated with e-Highway2050 (webinar);
3. **SESA Preliminary Outcomes:** to discuss and validate the preliminary findings regarding environmental and sustainability risks and opportunities and identify possible SESA guidelines (consultation and workshop); and
4. **Video interviews:** to capture a range of key stakeholders' perspectives, raise the public profile of their issues and concerns, and encourage others to participate in engagement activities (social media).

Although participation rates were below expectations, valuable input was gathered and used to improve the assessment methodology / framework and the assessment itself.

In terms of strategic assessment outcomes, **risks** so far identified appear to result from a relatively restrictive set of strategic choices across electricity generation, storage and transmission. Considering that the e-Highway2050 project explores the implementation of a pan-European electricity grid over a 40 year timeframe, flexible and adaptive approaches are needed to accommodate the energy system vulnerability to multiple uncertainties resulting from climate change, technological accidents, political instability, demographic changes and consumption patterns, market volatility and other causes. Other risks relate to what appears to be

strategies that, if followed, may increase energy dependency in some regions / Member States (MS), with particular concern for Central Europe, or may aggravate EU's overall energy dependency, such as for example increased dependency from Eastern Europe' uranium, or gas from the United States.

Opportunities have also been identified which we recommend to be considered and incorporated in grid design. If ignored it may only represent lost opportunities for a more sustainable European grid. Most opportunities relate to the possible deployment of a mixed scale and technologically innovative energy system that can foster the deployment of substantial demand-side management and promote overall reduction in energy consumption, by making end-users aware and responsible for their energy usage. Combining both large-scale and smaller scale solutions in terms of generation and storage may enable positive trade-offs between large-scale efficiency and manageability, transmission losses, reducing negative environmental consequences (such as landscape or ecosystem service's loss) and increasing overall system reliability.

Likewise, a mix of transmission technologies adapted to local conditions appears to carry the most opportunities for sustainable grid development. Optimizing the existing alternating current (AC) lines with Flexible AC Transmission Systems while developing High Voltage Direct Current links and combining both underground and overhead lines can deliver the best trade-offs between the security of supply, regional equity and competitiveness, social acceptance and the energy system's governance.

These conclusions represent a recommendation for the design of the European grid, looking strategically into overall risks and opportunities. SESA is not an appropriate instrument to deliver yes or no go ahead solutions as it is not based on quantitative assessments. It provides instead an overall course of direction towards better environmental and sustainability outcomes in the long-term. SESA outcomes, and the directions provided, should be followed up by accurate modelling and cost-benefit analysis. Indeed it is already suggested that such analyses be developed in relation to the land-take and negative environmental impacts that transmission infrastructure can have on ecosystems, ecosystem services and local communities. Only by downscaling grid design proposals can such an environmental validation be conducted. It is therefore not appropriate, or even feasible, to undertake such types of assessments at the pan-European scale.

However, if the strategic risks and opportunities identified in the SESA are not accounted for, and suitable preventive measures put in place at an early stage, it may then be difficult, or even impossible, to avoid difficulties at a later stage, including irreversible losses through social and environmental damages, public opposition and increased costs. It will be harder to change course for more sustainable solutions at a later stage.

Energy infrastructure development entails public acceptance and acceptability issues, or even MS opposition. That is why it is critical that relevant stakeholders are engaged early on and that all planning efforts aim to guide the deployment of new infrastructure to the most sustainable locations.

It is also essential to consider, and clearly expose the costs and benefits of selected strategic options, not only from an economic and financial perspective but also considering social and environmental issues, to allow informed participation by regional and local stakeholders, while seeking to build wider public consensus. Governance and market development mechanisms must also be enhanced to support MS cooperation and coordination, regulate the energy system and promote technological development and market integration, while also taking account objectives and targets of enhanced regional equity foreseen in European macro-policy.

Highlights of **guidelines for grid development** include:

- Large-scale and decentralised smaller-scale generation and storage solutions must be combined to reduce vulnerabilities;
- Where geophysical conditions allow, the use of CAES – namely adiabatic - should be considered instead of PHS, to enhance the public acceptability of a centralised energy system;
- Spatial planning and constraints analysis must be used to guide overhead lines away from particularly vulnerable locations;
- The loss of biodiversity and other ecosystem services essential to local development must be avoided first, then reduced and only as a last resort compensated for;
- The strategy's implementation must be compatible with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) maturity and flexibility;
- Technologies with low technology readiness level and other key technological developments must be promoted to keep future options open;
- Alternative origins for energy import must be identified and developed, namely the Baltic states, and energy import dependence and vulnerability, at European, Member State (MS) and regional level should be monitored;
- Ensure that price/market coupling projects and agreements are developed in conjunction with energy system infrastructure improvements;
- Enhance interconnections by ensuring the reduction of lengthy authorisation processes (simplification of administrative procedures).

It is essential that a follow-up SESA be undertaken to assist grid development in terms of monitoring and follow-up studies in order to accommodate capacity to respond to uncertainty and unexpected aspects that require an environmental and sustainability perspective throughout e-Highway2050's implementation.

The methodology developed to implement SESA can be used to **assess 2030 and 2040 target periods**, but it needs to be adapted to accommodate the respective priorities, as well as other strategic-level decision-making processes during grid implementation. Strategic options for example should relate to priorities and issues at stake for 2030 and 2040. Such priorities may be the same of those considered for 2050, or they may be different. If that will be the case, the assessment of risks and opportunities, as well as relevant guidelines, will also be different. Presumably the assessment framework will likely be the same, even though the change of spatial and time scales may require some fine-tuning. SESA becomes more accountable if the process of selection of strategic options is made clear, as well as the reasons for such selection. That will enable the choice for implementation of certain grid architectures

to be better understood. It will also enable a closer integration between continuous environmental validation and energy system planning processes (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 - SESA and grid design

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ACRONYMS

AC	Alternating Current
ACER	Agency for Cooperation of Energy Regulators
CACM	Capacity Allocation & Congestion Management
CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CBA	Cost-benefit Analysis
CC	Climate Change
CCF	Continuous Cover Forestry
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CDF	Critical Decision Factor
CEE	Central Eastern Europe
CEER	Council of European Energy Regulators
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CIP	Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CSP	Centralised Solar Power
CWE	Central Western Europe
DC	Direct Current
DCC	Demand Connection
DG	Directorate-General
DHC	District Heating and Cooling
Dii	Desertec Industrial Initiative
DSM	Demand Side Management
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EB	Balancing
EC	European Commission
ECSER	Europe's engagement with Civil Society in External Relations
EEA	European Environment Agency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EESC	European Economic and Social Committee
EHS	Environmentally Harmful Subsidies
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIP	Energy Infrastructures Priorities
ELC	European Landscape Convention
EMF	Electro Magnetic Fields
ENP	European Neighbourhood Policy
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
ENTSO-G	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas
EP	European Parliament
ERGEG	European Regulators' Group for Electricity and Gas
ERI	Electricity Regional Initiative
ES	Ecosystem Services
ESD	Effort Sharing Decision

ESI	Environmental and Sustainability Issues
ETI	Energy Technologies and Innovation
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
EU EP	European Union Energy Policy
EV	Electric Vehicles
FACTS	Flexible Alternating Current Transmission Systems
FCA	Forward Capacity Allocation
FES	Flywheel Energy Storage
FP7	Seventh Framework Programme
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GI	Green Infrastructure
HT	High-Temperature
HVAC	High Voltage Alternating Current
HVDC	High Voltage Direct Current
IBA	Important Bird Area
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITC	Inter-TSO Compensation mechanism
KET	Key Enabling Technologies
KP	Kyoto Protocol
LA	Lead Acid Battery
LFCR	Load Frequency Control & Reserves
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
MFID	Market on Financial Instruments Directive
MS	Member-State
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
NEW	North Western Europe
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NIMBY	Not In My Back Yard
NMS	Non-Member State
NREAP	National Renewable Energy Action Plan
NV	Net Value Added
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPS	Operational Planning and Scheduling
OS	Operational Security
PCI	Project of Common Interest
PCR	Price Coupling of Regions
PHS	Pumper Hydroelectric Storage
PV	Photo-Voltaic
R&D	Research and Development
RD&D	Research, Development and Demonstration
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
REMIT	Regulation on Electricity Market Integrity and Transparency

RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RES-E	Renewable Energy Sources for Electricity
RfG	Requirements for Generators
RLCE2050	Roadmap for moving to a competitive low carbon economy in 2050
ROR	Run-Off River
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
SESA	Strategic Environmental and Sustainability Assessment
SET	Strategic Energy Technology
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SNG	Synthetic Natural Gas
SRF	Strategic Reference Framework
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TEV	Total Economic Value
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UHVAC	Ultra-High Voltage Alternating Current
WP	Work Package
ZEBRA	Zero Emission Battery Research

INTRODUCTION

European energy policy establishes ambitious targets for greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction, energy efficiency improvement and increasing renewable energy sources (RES) share in the energy mix. e-Highway2050 project, funded by the European Union (EU) Seventh Framework Programme (FP7), is intended to support the planning of the Pan-European Transmission Network – i.e. the electricity network to serve the EU and beyond. The European Electricity Network intends to ensure the reliable delivery of existing and potential new sources of renewable electricity as well as supporting the integration of the wider pan-European market. The project looks into the period 2020-2050 and will result in a modular development plan for implementing possible future electricity transmission grids.

Alternative pan-European grid architectures are being developed based on a range of plausible future scenarios for Europe’s energy systems. To assist the integration of environmental and sustainability issues in the development of the grid architectures, and their subsequent delivery on the ground by Member States (MS), a Strategic Environmental and Sustainability Assessment (SESA) of e-Highway2050 relevant European energy system strategic options is being undertaken by Work Package (WP) 4 – task 4.2. Future scenarios developed in WP1 enabled the understanding of the e-Highway2050 dominant strategies, setting options for overall direction in the development of the grid architectures. These possible strategic options provide the object for strategic assessment within the SESA, enabling a strategic discussion into opportunities and risks for the environment, sustainable energy systems and overall development in Europe.

This report shows the methodology, the process and the results achieved with the proactive use of SESA at a planning stage. The application of the SESA methodology is addressed in two separate reports: D4.2a, the current document, and D4.2b. The need to split D4.2 report in two was requested by the eHighway2050 project coordination because delays in processing and delivering the outcomes of WP2 made it impossible to apply the SESA to final grid layouts. Consequently D4.2a displays and explains the methodology for the SESA, presents the outcomes of the assessment of the 2050’s strategic options, detailing recommendations that are expected to be considered in the design of the grids to ensure the integration of environment and sustainability issues. D4.2b will further apply the same methodology to grid design layouts, as illustrated in Section 7.

Section 1 describes the SESA’s objectives and assessment methodology as well as the process that was conducted in task 4.2 in collaboration with other work packages and project teams. In **Section 2** the object of assessment is described and **Section 3** illustrates the development of the assessment framework, its building blocks and the resulting Critical Decision Factors (CDF), assessment criteria and indicators. **Section 4** addresses the stakeholder engagement process conducted as part of the SESA and the governance framework relevant in SESA is analysed in **Section 5**. **Section 6** presents the strategic analysis and assessment, including the policy conflict analysis.

Section 7 illustrates how the SESA methodology can be applied henceforward. **Section 8** closes this report with final remarks and conclusions.

The annexes include the Strategic Reference Framework (SRF, **Annex 1**), the trend analysis (**Annex 2**), the list of relevant stakeholders (**Annex 3**) and the results of the stakeholder engagement process (**Annex 4**).

1. SESA objectives and methodology

The overall objective of the SESA is to **assess the range of strategies inherent to the e-Highway2050 project** (see Section 2), using the assessment framework (see Section 3) to **alert decision-making to risks and opportunities** associated with strategic options that will result in grid architectures according to different scenarios, **advising on more sustainable options and providing guidelines** for future planning and development.

The risks and opportunities identified through the SESA intend to facilitate e-Highway2050 project decision-making in relation to the configuration of grid architectures. More than pointing to positive or negative effects, SESA can help to identify the conditions that enable more sustainable subsequent decisions concerning the deployment of the grid to meet the policy objectives of the wider European energy system to 2050, considering multiple scales (e.g. EU-wide, by individual MS and by relevant local level organisations). SESA includes a governance framework to guide decision models, engaging multiple energy stakeholders across Europe to ensure proper consideration of different perspectives and enabling a balance of interests.

SESA uses a strategic thinking Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) methodological approach, developed by Partidário (2012 [1]), structured around strong success factors called **Critical Decision Factors** or **CDF**. The CDF are designed to **focus attention** on the issues that really matter when taking a broad, integrated and long-term perspective. The strategic themes that result from this strong focus exercise cross-relate:

1. The e-Highway2050 objectives (i.e. what the project is trying to achieve);
2. Relevant environmental and sustainability issues and trends; and
3. Relevant priority policies.

Using CDF to conduct strategic analysis and assessment will ensure a strong focus on the key environmental and sustainability **conditions** that may enhance successful e-Highway2050 **outcomes**. Strategic options that will better **satisfy** such conditions represent **opportunities**, but if conditions **do not seem to be satisfied** then such options may represent **risks**. Guidelines for continued integrated planning and operationalization towards the achievement of opportunities, and also to try to transform risks into opportunities, are also suggested.

Table 1 - Summary of the SESA methodology (following Partidário 2012 [1])

<p>Stage 1: Understanding the context and strategic focus for the environmental and sustainability assessment – establish Critical Decision Factors (section 3)</p>
<p>NB: Stage 1 ensures that the assessment focuses on issues of strategic importance, highlighting the conditions that grid architectures for 2050 must satisfy in order to ensure sustainable outcomes in the long-term. Stage 1 involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining the problem framework: <i>what are problems and potentials concerning key environmental and sustainability issues of relevance to e-Highway2050?</i> • Defining the governance framework: <i>what governance arrangements are already in place? What additional structures and processes may be required to support the effective delivery of e-Highway2050?</i> • Defining the strategic reference framework (SRF): <i>what is the relevant policy framework for e-Highway2050 and what are the key objectives and targets? How do these support or constrain the activities of e-Highway2050? Are there any major conflicts or synergies that need to be considered?</i> <p>Defining the assessment framework: <i>integrating all of the above to identify the CDF as the lens through which e-Highway2050 strategic options will be assessed to define the sustainable conditions and pathways needed to ensure success. Development of more detailed assessment criteria and indicators to support the assessment.</i></p>
<p>Stage 2: Assessing strategic options behind candidate grid architectures, identifying pathways for sustainability and developing guidelines</p>
<p>NB: The assessment framework (CDF, assessment criteria and indicators) developed in Stage 1 is used in Stage 2 to assess the strategic options underlining grid architectures, to identify risks and opportunities determining the most appropriate pathways (one or more strategic options) to deliver e-Highway2050 sustainable outcomes . The outcomes of this assessment are to be considered during the grid architecture design process and before electing a preferred architecture for the modular development plan. Stage 2 involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A policy conflicts analysis to identify if there are any conflicts that may undermine e-Highway 2050 success – if there are, cross-relate them with the SRF to pinpoint critical policy lock-ins (Section 6.1); • A CDF trend analysis to understand key drivers of change and transformations that may implicate on e-Highway2050 decisions (detailed in Annex 2); • Assessment of strategic options in relation to the extent they may increase trend vulnerabilities or opportunities, and to find out if they will take us to where we want to get with reference to SRF (Section 2 and Annex 1); • Recommend guidelines to assist the subsequent development process; guidelines should be developed for planning and management (in terms of risks and opportunities), for monitoring and for good governance.
<p>Stage 3: Continuous process linkages, stakeholder engagement, monitoring and evaluation</p>
<p>NB: Key aspects of Stage 3 are designed to support continuous process linkages between the e-Highway2050 planning process and other related governance and technical processes involving relevant stakeholders, as well as to ensure that the implementation is followed up by continuous monitoring and evaluation. One of the key aims of Stage 3 is to ensure a continuous linkage of SESA outcomes, stakeholders' inputs and strategic decision-making.</p>

2. Object of Assessment: e-Highway2050 Strategic Options

The object of assessment in the SESA is the generation and regional balance, storage, transmission and international **strategies** that will result into grid architectures, according to the different scenarios, considering plausible **strategic options**. By the time the SESA was initiated, grid design was yet to be developed but the main five scenarios had been selected and the various boundaries that would define the decision space were also established. SESA put much effort into the interpretation of several preliminary results in other WPs in e-Highway2050, such as WP2 and WP3, as well as WP5.

The method used to understand e-Highway2050's intended strategies for grid-development involved the deconstruction of the five e-Highway2050 scenarios [2] to identify the most plausible strategic options for the delivery of Europe's energy system in 2050. The main tasks conducted to identify these strategic options were:

- 1) **Scenario interpretation** in terms of priorities and also the physical, technological and management implications based on WP1's scenario description and WP2's initial modelling (namely from D2.1 – G/D/E Scenarios 2050, July 2013) – narrative interpretation prepared by KU Leuven;
- 2) Based on this narrative, systematization of the **main assumptions and priorities** per scenario, structured according to the e-Highway2050 scenario parameters;
- 3) From the main assumptions and priorities, identify the main **physical, technological and management patterns** that typify each scenario;
- 4) Identify categories of patterns relevant to all scenarios (thematic patterns) based on main drivers, linking what is common and separating what **differentiates** scenarios;
- 5) For each thematic pattern provide a narrative of possible pathways (strategic options) that may lead to alternative grid development priorities;
- 6) Validate the technical and economic feasibility of the identified options with other WPs and e-Highway2050 Coordination.

These options are represented by four strategic themes:

- **Generation and regional balance** – issues at stake include energy mix, centralised vs. decentralised options but also energy flows the consequent regional imbalances that might result from different options. In particular we looked at different options depending on:
 - Dominant or non-dominant RES in mixed energy options;
 - Centralized RES close to source (natural resources) or decentralized RES close to demand;
 - Nuclear and fossil close to demand and/or to existing infrastructures, that may increase or maintain capacities;

- Dominant flows from North to Central Europe or from North and South to Central Europe, or alternatively no dominant flows;
- **Storage** – considers centralised storage vs. a mix of centralised and decentralised storage technology;
- **Transmission** – considering overhead vs. a mix of overhead and underground transmission, using both Alternating Current (AC) and Direct Current (DC) in high voltage;
- **International strategy** – how the EU relates to its neighbouring countries and regions, especially North Africa and Russia, is also amenable to various options.

All together 16 strategic options have been identified for the four strategic themes considered, following the methodology described. These are summarised in Table 2. For the purpose of assessment, and to be consistent with the methodology used in developing e-Highway2050, strategic options under each of the four themes, have been grouped according to scenarios. The relationship between scenarios and strategic options is indicated on Table 3. SESA explored these groups of strategic options to assess potential environmental and sustainability risks and opportunities associated with the overall strategies that will support the proposed grid architectures, according to different scenarios.

The identification of these options has gone through several iterations between WP4 and e-Highway2050 coordination, considering also valuable input from WP2 and WP3.

Table 2 - e-Highway2050 Strategic Options

Strategic Theme	Strategic Options
Generation and regional balance	RES Scale and Location Options <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● G1 - Centralised and large scale RES: Centralized large-scale RES generation facilities are preferred and located where profitability is higher. Wind, Biomass and Photovoltaic (PV) all over Europe, with off-shore wind dominant in the North and Baltic seas. Hydro mainly in Northern, Central and Southern Europe. Centralized Solar Power (CSP) in South and Southwest Europe and North Africa if Desertec exists. ● G2 - Decentralised and small scale RES: Small-scale RES generation facilities are close to demand/load. Wind mainly in Western and Central Europe. Hydro Run-off-River (ROR) mainly in Central and Eastern Europe and Hydro storage mainly in Northern Europe. PV mainly in Southwest and Southern Europe and CSP (being a centralised technology) is not relevant. Biomass is quite relevant and mainly in Eastern and Central Europe.
	Energy Mix Options <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● G3 - Dominant RES: RES share is highest in energy mix. ● G4 - RES non-dominant: Fossil and Nuclear are the dominant energy sources so new nuclear facilities are expected.
	Nuclear and Fossil Options <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● G5 - Nuclear and Fossil without Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) near existing capacity: No new capacity is developed and facilities replace

Strategic Theme	Strategic Options
	<p>existing ones. Nuclear in Western, Central and Eastern Europe; Fossil without CCS in Western and Southern Europe.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G6 - Nuclear and Fossil with CCS close to demand: New facilities are close to demand. Nuclear mainly in West Europe, East Europe but also in Central Europe, North Europe and Southwest Europe; Fossil with CCS mainly in Southwest and South Europe but also relevant in Central, Western and Eastern Europe. <p>Energy Flow Options</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G7 - High to very high flows from South and North to Central Europe, but also from North Africa to the southern regions. • G8 - High to medium flows from North to Central Europe are dominant. • G9 - Low energy flows, generation is mainly close to demand.
Storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S1 - Centralized Hydro Storage: Only pumped hydroelectric storage (PHS) is considered, located in the most profitable areas. • S2 - Centralised Hydro and CAES: Only existing PHS capacity is considered, no additional PHS storage is created (unless through improved technology on existing areas). Large-scale Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) will accommodate the necessary additional storage capacity. • S3 - Mixed scale storage: Existing PHS capacity is considered, with additional storage capacity (demand driven) achieved through centralised CAES and decentralised, medium to small-scale batteries, including electric vehicles (EV).
Transmission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T1 - Overhead Transmission: The pan-European grid connecting additional capacity is developed mainly using overhead lines, in High or Ultra-High Voltage Alternating Current (HVAC / UHVAC) with Flexible Alternating Current Transmission Systems (FACTS), as well as High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC). Submarine transmission is in HVDC. Below the cluster level, the grid remains as is (AC). • T2 - Underground HVDC and Overhead HVAC: The pan-European grid connecting additional capacity is developed using underground and submarine HVDC and well as overhead HVAC/UHVAC with FACTS, depending on regional technical feasibility and public acceptance.
International strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IS1 - Irrelevant import from North Africa: No large scale Desertec exists so import of energy from North Africa is irrelevant. Import from East is limited, kept at 2012 levels. • IS2 - Relevant import from North Africa: Large scale Desertec exists and import of energy from North Africa (CSP and PV) is a relevant share of overall demand. Import from East is limited, kept at 2012 levels.

Table 3 - Strategic Options and how they relate to Scenarios [2]

Strategic Option:			Scenario:	Large Scale RES	100% RES	Big & Market	Big, Nuclear & CCS	Small and Local
Generation and regional balance	RES Scale and Location	G1 - Centralised and large scale RES	✓	✓	✓	✓		
		G2 - Decentralised and small scale RES					✓	
	Energy Mix	G3 - Dominant RES	✓	✓	✓		✓	
		G4 - RES non-dominant				✓		
	Nuclear and Fossil	G5 - Nuclear and Fossil without CCS near existing capacity	✓	✓			✓	
		G6 - Nuclear and Fossil with CCS close to demand			✓	✓		
	Energy Flow	G7 - High to very high flows from SE and NE to CE	✓	✓				
		G8 - High to medium flows from NE to CE			✓	✓		
		G9 - Low energy flows					✓	
Storage	S1 - Centralized Hydro Storage	✓	✓	✓	✓			
	S2 - Centralised Hydro and CAES	✓	✓	✓	✓			
	S3 - Mixed scale storage		✓			✓		
Transmission	T1 - Overhead Transmission	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
	T2 - Underground HVDC and Overhead HVAC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
International Strategy	IS1 - Irrelevant import from North Africa			✓	✓	✓		
	IS2 - Relevant import from North Africa	✓	✓					

*The options that relate to more scenarios, for each theme, are highlighted.

3. Assessment Framework

The SESA assessment framework comprises the CDF, assessment criteria and indicators. The assessment framework is the lens through which e-Highway2050 strategic options for grid architectures have been assessed to define the sustainable conditions and pathways needed to deliver **sustainable, and successful, outcomes**. CDF are structured in criteria for assessment and use indicators as the assessment metrics. Accordingly, the assessment framework reflects the **critical strategic issues** of relevance to **e-Highway2050** and long-term **electricity grid development** in Europe. This ensures that the SESA can identify relevant risks and opportunities that can place the development of grid architectures in the pathway to best contribute to **sustainable outcomes** in the long-term.

The following are elements used to build the assessment framework for the 2050 grid architectures:

- a. Strategic Objective of the e-Highway2050;
- b. Problem framework;
- c. SRF (the macro-policies that set major targets);
- d. Governance framework (see Section 5);
- e. Object of assessment (what we are assessing) (see Section 2).

Informed by the integrated consideration of the above sets of issues, the following CDF for the assessment of the e-Highway2050 strategies for grid architectures have been identified:

- 1) **Social acceptance and acceptability;**
- 2) **Energy security and energy technologies;**
- 3) **Geo-political economy and regional equity; and**
- 4) **European regional governance.**

As previously explained, each of these CDF integrates environmental, social, economic, cultural and political concerns, as expressed in the diagram in Figure 3.

Of overarching importance to the assessment framework is the e-Highway2050 **strategic objective** –what the grid architectures must be able to deliver:

“to develop a grid which supports progress to a high proportion or mix of electricity from renewable energy systems (RES) and develop options for a complete pan-European grid architecture based on different scenarios”.

The following Table 4 outlines the main aspects that define the **strategic problem**, identified as boundaries in WP1.4. The assessment framework attempts to reflect on these.

Table 4 - Problem framework based on WP1 report considering boundaries, particularly WP1.4

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governance issues, legal and institutional framework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Links, and cooperation, across sectorial public and private organizations, and governmental organizations: responsibilities, contributions – institutional design; o Relationships within and cross countries; o Need for legal and regulatory harmonization to ensure equity across member-countries, equitable engagement and benefits; emphasis on international agreements (climate); o Need to ensure responsibility in each member-country. - Social equity and consumption behaviour: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Education and awareness of communities/population for the importance of sustainable behaviour; o Ensure equity in access to energy (prices, technologies, social opportunities/costs); o Changes in lifestyles and consumption behaviour; o Energy consumptions in Europe and in each MS, as well as sources of energy and type of consumption (transports, heating and electricity); o EU2050 demographic trends and implications to the energy sector; o Invest on research and development. - Energy security: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Energy sources and energy dependency (Europe, Eastern countries, Northern Africa); o Climate change effects on energy efficiency, grid vulnerability and adaptation measures; o Europe true potential concerning renewable energy sources; o Invest on research and development. - Environmental issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Climate change effects on biodiversity and ecosystem services, natural protected areas and change in natural values; o Landscape fragmentation; o Climate change impacts; o Energy efficiency measures; o Mitigation policies and resulting production and consumption changes. - Economic issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Central issue in the capacity for project implementation and pathways to take forward; o EU28 and each MS gross domestic product (GDP) trends; o Employment generation and economic role of energy based activities; o National and international investment initiatives and risk analysis of programmed activities; o Land value associated to programmed projects. - Technological issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Advantages and disadvantages of centralized or decentralized processes; o Assess available technologies and technologies in development, as well as sources and production methods. Consider interconnectivity and sustainability of grids/technologies (smart and sustainable).

The **SRF** represents the macro-policies that provide the referential for assessment, based on policy orientations and respective established targets. The purpose of the SRF is to provide strategic direction to sustainable grid development, according to the policy orientations and targets and it works as the referential to the assessment.

The SRF also aims to satisfy legal requirements by ensuring links to other relevant plans and programmes by recognizing and considering other relevant planning and programmatic orientations that may have synergies and conflicts with the object of

assessment. It is not the purpose of the SRF to list legal requirements. A legal requirement sets conditions, or restrictions, that need to be considered in trend analysis, but it does not set a strategic direction.

Table 5 lists the macro-policies that have been considered in the SRF and illustrates how they relate to the four CDF. The environmental and sustainability objectives and targets relevant to e-Highway2050 are listed in Annex 1.

Table 5 - Strategic Reference Framework for e-Highway2050

Relevant strategic macro-policies	CDF1	CDF2	CDF3	CDF4
Our life insurance, our natural capital: an EU biodiversity strategy to 2020 (Biodiversity 2020, 2011)	X			
European Landscape Convention (ELC, 2000)				X
European grid declaration on electricity network development and nature conservation in Europe (European Grid Declaration, 2011)	X	X		X
A new EU forest strategy: for forests and the forest-based sector (Forestry Strategy, 2013)	X	X		
A blueprint to safeguard Europe's water resources (Water Resource Blueprint, 2012)	X			
DIRECTIVE 2008/56/EC Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008)	X			
Proposal for a directive establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning and integrated coastal zone management (Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013)	X	X		X
Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe (Resource Roadmap, 2011)	X	X	X	X
Thematic strategy for soil protection (Soil Strategy, 2006)	X			
Green infrastructure - enhancing Europe's natural capital (GI Strategy, 2013)	X	X		
EUROPE 2020 - A strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth (Europe 2020, 2010)	X	X	X	X
Adapting to climate change: towards a European framework for action (CC Adaptation Framework, 2009)	X		X	X
Energy Roadmap 2050 (2011)	X	X	X	X
Energy 2020 (2010)	X	X	X	X
2030 framework for climate and energy policies (Energy and Climate 2030, 2014)		X		
Renewable Energy: a major player in the European energy market (Renewable Energy, 2012)	X	X	X	X
Roadmap for moving to a competitive low carbon economy in 2050 (RLCE2050, 2011)	X	X	X	X

Relevant strategic macro-policies	CDF1	CDF2	CDF3	CDF4
Energy Technologies and Innovation (ETI, 2013)	X	X	X	
European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan, 2007)	X	X	X	X
The EU Energy Policy: Engaging with Partners beyond Our Borders (EU EP 2001)		X	X	X
European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP 2003, 2006)			X	
Energy infrastructures priorities for 2020 and beyond (EIP 2020)		X	X	X
Common rules for the internal market in electricity (Directive 2009/72/EC)	X	X	X	X
Europe’s engagement with Civil Society in external relations (ECSER 2012)	X			X

Figure 3 attempts to illustrate how the CDF relate to the typical **environmental issues** in the EU Directive and to the WP1.4 boundaries - illustrating the relationship between different environmental and sustainability issues and the CDF.

Figure 3 - Relationship between EU legal environmental issues, e-Highway2050 environmental and sustainability issues, and the assessment framework

What follows represents the assessment framework (Table 6). To be noted that the CDF approach is relational, not hierarchical, and attempts to express complex, non-linear, systems. Different environmental or sustainability issues can be addressed in different ways (see Figure 3), and can also be combined in different ways, with different meanings. CDF express such combinations, using terms to reflect integrated themes, and have been selected because they communicate priorities for decision-making and for the society.

This framework has had valuable inputs from previous consultation and stakeholder engagement.

(Note that the indicators are used to understand key drivers of change and its relationship to critical trends, not as quantitative assessment tools)

Table 6 - SESA Assessment Framework

CDF 1 – Social acceptance an acceptability

Objectives / Scope: To focus on all factors that affect a sense of well-being, and consequently determine acceptance and acceptability of grid development, including social equity, individual and community benefits, environmental limits related to issues such as noise, health issues, biodiversity, ecosystem services and landscape, urbanisation, energy related behavioural trends, as well as vulnerability to climate change and extreme events.

Assessment Criteria	Indicators
Social Equity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to benefits and costs to all citizens in the area of influence, including fuel poverty - Consumption behaviours - Green behaviour (attitude towards RES technologies, nuclear, shale gas) - Public participation, acceptance & acceptability 	Difference between energy consumption and costs (for the consumer) in EU28. Changes in the level of acceptance of existing energy technology.
Biodiversity, landscape and Ecosystem services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevance of biodiversity to livelihoods and European changing lifestyles - Future Legacy: enhancement of natural and cultural values - Landscape enhancement (character, amenities) - Ecosystem services performance, including resilience to extreme events 	Ecosystem Services & Land Use Change. Integrity of ecosystems, habitats and species populations. Natural Heritage sites.
Vulnerabilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health vulnerabilities to noise, Electro Magnetic Fields (EMF) and climatic extreme events - Land vulnerability to climatic extreme events - Grid infrastructure vulnerability to climatic extreme events 	Percentage of EU28 population vulnerable to climate change impacts. Percentage of EU28 grid infrastructure assets within vulnerable areas. Local biomass and other local biofuel and small hydropower sources dependency.

CDF 2 – Energy security and technologies

Objectives / Scope: To focus on clear trends towards favouring EU and national policies concerning RES, technological enhancement to favour complementary, interconnectivity, smart initiatives that reduce costs and increase benefits and ensure energy security across and within MS policy and practice.

Assessment Criteria	Indicators
Energy Efficiency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GHG emissions of the electricity system - Policies/ Measures to increase energy/resource efficiency - Renewable energy potential and sources - Centralized and decentralized RES production 	Efficiency of conventional energy production technologies. GHG emissions of the electricity system. Percentage of EU28 with binding targets for at least 20% reduction in primary energy use compared with projected levels. Percentage of EU28 with binding targets for reduction in EU greenhouse gas emissions of at

	<p>least 20% below 1990 levels. RES potential and technologies.</p>
<p>Innovation and technological development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maturity of new technologies for medium to long-term implementation including CCS - Investments in Research and Development (R&D) - Smart grids (interoperability, efficiency, standards, market and supply chains, etc.) - New uses or shift from industry to services 	<p>Technology readiness level (for generation, transmission and storage). Investments in R&D. CCS and level of decarbonized power. Smart grid benefits and implementation. Energy shift to/from electricity. Energy matching.</p>
<p>Energy security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interconnectivity of energy sources and demand - Storage capacity for grid flexibility - Maturity of new technologies to ensure the security of supply with a given demand - Supply to demographic scenario demands - Energy security and non-dependency from countries outside of Europe 	<p>Strategic energy networks and storage facilities. Energy production per energy source. Energy import dependency and main origins per fuel type.</p>

CDF 3 – Geo-Political Economy and regional equity

Objectives / Scope: To focus on European competitiveness in its geo-political environment considering energy, balanced by the need to ensure regional equity within European MS concerning sources of energy, market accessibility and distributional equity, and implications for national/local economies and development options.

Assessment Criteria	Indicators
<p>International competitiveness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Joint transnational and national investment and trade initiatives - Contribution of economic activities of the energy sector in the trade balance - International energy trade links with European energy 	<p>European energy import-export ratio (international energy trade). Energy import dependency. Joint energy agreements. European Energy trade flows agreements with third parties (Russia, North Africa).</p>
<p>Market dynamics and regional equity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fuel and energy costs, market value of affected land - Risk assessment of projected infrastructures - Distributional effects and benefits across countries 	<p>Renewable Electricity Feed-in Tariffs in EU. Contribution of energy sources to internal markets and retail prices of electricity. Electricity market considering integration for a new energy mix. Rating for similar projects of common interest (PCIs) in Project-Bonds risks.</p>

CDF 4 – European Regional Governance

Objectives / Scope: To focus on the governance conditions to operationalize the European internal market of electricity distribution and management of the e-Highway2050 concept, including national systems capacity to deliver international/global agreements, regulations, competences, responsibilities across the Union, restricting factors at European and national levels.

Assessment Criteria	Indicators
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<p>Policies and politics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harmonization between legislation and regulations - National policies strategic priorities 	<p>Percentage of EU28 with binding targets on GHG emissions.</p> <p>Percentage of EU28 with binding targets on at least 20% of EU energy consumption to come from renewable resources.</p> <p>Support to Renewables and Fossil fuels.</p> <p>Common rules for the generation, transmission, distribution and supply for sustainable energy market.</p> <p>Key complementary policies to the EU energy policy framework.</p>
<p>Responsibilities and competences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination of European grid – strategies for joint / collaborative / articulated management - Border institutional cooperation mechanisms - Mechanisms for supporting the grid responsibilities within each MS - Stakeholders engagement mechanisms 	<p>Rules for cross-border exchanges in electricity (network codes).</p> <p>Regional cooperation between Transmission System Operators (TSOs).</p> <p>Civil society in energy initiatives.</p>

4. Stakeholder Engagement

A key aspect of e-Highway2050 and the SESA is the engagement with stakeholders to identify the conditions that grid architectures for 2050 will have to satisfy to help ensure pathways for sustainability, and a sustainable outcome overall.

The central purpose of Task 4.2 stakeholder engagement activities has been to capture stakeholder interests and perspectives concerning environmental and sustainability issues associated with the development of a pan-European grid, informing the SESA approach and findings. In particular, input was sought regarding: strategic issues of relevance to the development of Europe’s energy system, risks and opportunities that may result from different models of electricity grid-development and associated generation and storage infrastructure, criteria to keep a focused assessment and input to draft assessment outcomes.

The main target stakeholder groups for engagement activities were:

1. Governmental organisations / policy sector:
 - DG Energy;
 - DG Climate;
 - DG Environment;
 - National governments;
 - Regulatory bodies (e.g. ACER).
2. Private sector:
 - Industry representatives (including project partners);
 - Other private stakeholders.
3. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs):
 - Relevant sectorial and environmental NGOs;
 - Other NGOs (e.g. consumer NGOs).

The programme of stakeholder engagement activities has occurred in three stages as outlined in Table 7.

Table 7 - Stakeholder engagement programme

Stage	Type of engagement	Date
1. SESA Focus and Assessment Framework	Consultation on SESA focus/ approach and proposed assessment framework	October / November 2013
2. SESA Focus and Assessment Framework – Follow-up	Web conference on feedback received from first consultation (see above)	29 November 2013
3. SESA Preliminary Outcomes	Workshop in Brussels	6 May 2014
Supplementary activity for all stages	Video interviews with stakeholders	February – June 2014

Details of the methodology for each engagement activity is presented in Sections 4.1 to 4.4 below.

4.1. Consultation 1 – SESA Focus and Assessment Framework

The first stakeholder consultation was conducted via an online survey and supporting consultation document. These were disseminated amongst stakeholders via the e-Highway2050 website and direct email in October and November 2013.

The consultation sought stakeholder inputs to the CDFs and assessment framework that has been used in the SESA (see Section 3). Key questions posed to stakeholders included:

1. What are the key sustainability opportunities and risks posed by long-term electricity grid-development in Europe?
2. What are the main drivers of long-term electricity grid-development in Europe?
3. Do you have any general comments on the range of environmental and sustainability assessment factors and criteria proposed?
4. What are your thoughts on the proposed framework for assessing possible future grid architectures? Do you have any suggestions for other aspects or issues that should be considered at this strategic level?

Responses were elicited from ten stakeholders. The outcomes of this consultation helped to qualify some of the inherent uncertainty around e-Highway2050 and the SESA by understanding the priority issues and different perspectives as well as key opportunities and risks that were reflected in the subsequent development of the assessment framework. The results of Consultation 1 are detailed in Annex 4.1.

4.2. Consultation 2 – SESA Focus and Assessment Framework

Consultation 2 was a web conference on aspects of the draft SESA. It was held on 29 November 2013. Consultation 2 had the following objectives:

1. To improve and validate the proposed assessment methodology and framework;
2. To identify key opportunities and risks for long-term electricity grid development in Europe;
3. To identify key drivers and macro-policies of relevance to e-Highway 2050 from the perspectives of key stakeholders;
4. To discuss feedback from the first consultation;
5. To raise awareness of e-Highway2050 amongst key stakeholders.

The web conference approach was intended to maximise stakeholder engagement and opportunities for learning and exchange between the e-Highway2050 Task 4.2 team members and attendees/stakeholders across Europe. The web conference followed, and garnered feedback on, the first consultation conducted by online survey in October and November 2013 (see Section 4.3). The agenda for the web conference is outlined in Table 8:

Table 8 - Consultation 2 agenda

Session No.	Session
1	Introductions and welcome
2	What is the e-Highway2050 project?
3	How do we propose doing the strategic environmental and sustainability assessment methodology?
4	What is the proposed assessment framework?
5	What's next?

The engagement of stakeholders was poor in Consultation 2 and outcomes were not considered significant, even though some suggestions, presented in the Annex 4.2, are interesting.

4.3. Consultation 3 - SESA preliminary outcomes

A workshop on the draft SESA was held in Brussels on 6 May 2014 with the following objectives:

1. To discuss and validate the preliminary strategic environmental and sustainability assessment findings with stakeholders;
2. To discuss possible measures to integrate environmental and sustainability risks and opportunities with grid-development;
3. To raise awareness of e-Highway2050 amongst key stakeholders.

The 40 workshop attendees included e-Highway consortium members, academics, TSOs, NGOs and DG Research and Innovation.

Attendees were invited to respond to the presentations outlined in Table 9 below, and to actively participate in a 'carousel' exercise to provide feedback on CDF specific opportunities, risks and possible guidelines for e-Highway2050 planning and management, governance and monitoring.

Table 9 - Consultation 3 agenda

Session No.	Session
1	The e-Highway2050 Strategic and Environmental Sustainability Assessment (SESA): The story so far.
2	<i>Preliminary assessment findings:</i> What has the initial assessment of strategic options found in terms of risks and opportunities for sustainability and what are your views on these?

Session No.	Session
3	<i>Preliminary SESA guidelines and recommendations:</i> What are the initial proposed measures for integrating considerations of key risks and opportunities with grid development and what are your views on these?
4	Closing Remarks and Next Steps.

Results of the workshop can be found at Annex 4.3.

4.4. Video interviews with stakeholders

Video interviews with stakeholders from key cross-sector organisations have been conducted as an additional engagement activity. The purpose was twofold:

1. To capture a range of key stakeholders' interests and perspectives concerning the development of a Pan-European grid and related environmental and sustainability issues;
2. To use as promotional tools for the workshop in May and final report, with the aim to encourage other stakeholders to get involved in the project.

Between March and May 2014, six stakeholder interviews were conducted and filmed remotely using Skype recording software, or face-to-face by camera.

The following interview questions were developed by adopting standard best practice principles, based around a schedule of common questions to enable comparison across interviews:

1. Do you see opportunities in the development of an electricity transmission Supergrid in Europe?
2. What could be the drawbacks, or risks, of such a pan-European network for electricity transmission?
3. What should be done to enable opportunities and prevent risks?
4. Do you think other people should get involved in the e-Highway2050 project, and if so, who and why?

Resultant footage has been edited to produce six short (2-3 minute) 'talking head' videos for the e-Highway2050 YouTube channel². Prior to publishing each video online, interviewees were given the opportunity to review their video and to permit online publication. Video interviewees' affiliations and key themes of each interview are detailed in Annex 4.4.

² e-Highway2050 YouTube Channel: <https://www.youtube.com/user/e-Highway2050>.

5. Governance Framework

The governance framework is an important and relevant element in SESA. It highlights the level of competence and responsibility of the relevant stakeholders and the power relations and opportunities to engage them. In the context of e-Highway2050 four types of stakeholders are recognized and considered in shaping the governance framework: public authorities, economic agents, other public and private entities, and citizens.

SESA will explore the three elements of the European energy system that, in our understanding, describe and explain how power is being exercised:

1. The vision and strategy of the EU energy governance system;
2. The structure of the energy system, in particular the organisational structure and the institutional framework of the system;
3. The implementation mechanisms under the European energy strategy.

EU energy (electricity) governance system

The European Commission (EC) builds the energy system around three established, and well recognized, policy objectives: competitiveness, security of supply, and sustainability (see Annex 2, CDF4).

The evolution of the European energy market started with the liberalization of the internal electricity and gas markets in the 90's. The vision of transforming the energy system into a network- and market-oriented system created the need to shift from more monopolised practices to regulated policies. Since 1996 three sets of liberalisation packages were published for electricity and gas. The latest, the Third Energy Package, in 2009, was built upon three main elements: effective separation of TSOs from supply and production; the creation of the Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER) to protect public interest; and the creation of the European Network of Transmission System Operators for electricity and gas (ENTSO-E and ENTSO-G) to provide an arena of cooperation between TSOs. Responsibilities and competences of the energy-related actors changed^{3,4} - a new institutional framework was set, namely for:

- EC – responsible for legislative initiatives, following the process of drafting framework guidelines and network codes, and with a supervisory role as well;
- ACER - developing technical rules at EU level together with ENTSOs and the EC, to decide on cross-border issues and monitor market functioning;
- ENTSOs – with a role in the architecture of the internal market, transposing ACER's framework guidelines into network codes and promoting regional cooperation between TSOs;
- National regulators – responsible for the liberalisation of national energy markets and the application of market mechanisms into national energy markets.

³ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_SPEECH-11-145_en.htm?locale=en [accessed 30/04/14].

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/legislation/doc/20110302_entry_into_force_third_package.pdf [accessed 30/04/14].

Also in 2009 the legal action of the EU based on the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union was defined. It changed the structure of energy governance in the EU considering it as a sector where the EC needed to share competences with the MS to a multi-level approach to the system.

The European energy governance system includes three types of policy instruments: **regulatory instruments**, **economic instruments** and **promotion instruments**, the most relevant for the present analysis being:

- Regulatory instruments: emissions limits and performance standards (Energy 2020 Energy and Climate 2030 and Energy Roadmap 2050); transparency obligations (Renewable Energy Directive - RED); or regulations and directives (those from the Third Energy Package);
- Economic instruments: taxation, subsidies and support schemes (Energy 2020, Energy and Climate 2030, Directive 2009/72/EC); Emission Trading System (Directive 2003/87/EC emended by Directive 2009/29/EC; Energy and Climate 2030); or liberalisation of market (Third Energy Package);
- Promotion instruments: public disclosure (Citizens Energy Forum; Opinion 2013/C 161/01 from the European Economic and Social Committee); rating (Decision 1364/2006/EC on TEN-E networks list and rank); or certification (Green Certificates, Ecolabel, labelling).

Table 46 and Table 47 in Annex 3 present the relevant stakeholders and their responsibilities and competences in the European energy governance system, which is also represented in Figure 2. This institutional analysis provides the information needed to consider gaps or overlaps in responsibilities, and the rules used in decision-making moments of the policy formulation process.

Figure 4 - Stakeholders relations mapping⁵

From the stakeholders mapping is possible to observe the hierarchical system that represents the multi-level governance of the EU: establishment of the constitutional laws and sector specific regulation by the European Parliament (EP) and EC, brokered by the DG Energy into MS legislations, as well by the two organisms more recently created, ACER and ENTSO that regulates the implementation of the rules into the national TSOs, as well the engagement of consumers and the consideration of vulnerable consumers in the establishment of the national unbundling rules.

Since the EU works on a multi-level approach for the allocation of power and responsibilities among the different levels of decision (from EU-level to MS-level), the system of responsibilities and competences is very well designed for the purpose of achieving its policy objectives and the institutionalization of the internal energy market. But in practice there are some **issues** in relation to the **cooperation design between relevant stakeholders**, the **relationships between MS** (and even within the MS system), the **regulatory harmonization between MS**, **MS responsibilities** in the energy system (see Table 47), and **changes of the energy governance system parameters over time** (currently TSOs have the liberty to define their own unbundling rules, leading to discrepancies in the rules defined by TSOs from different MS, and consequently to the expected internalisation of the energy market; see also Trend Analysis of CDF4). Likewise, the way policy instruments are understood, transposed by MS, and applied may open

⁵ The stakeholders mapping was developed under what is defined in Table 47.

gaps that may be seen as constraints to the expected internal energy market (e.g. the way the EU laws are transposed into MS requires, theoretically, the engagement of the most relevant national stakeholders in order to accomplish a transposition tailored to MS specificities; in practice, as seen in the Trend Analysis of CDF⁴, few engagement mechanisms exist)

The analysis of gaps and overlaps concerning responsibilities and competences of the stakeholders for the presented instruments can be done based on the cross-analysis of Table 47 and Figure 4. Two remarks (in relation to the Environmental and Sustainability Issues – ESI - presented in section 3):

- Possible overlaps in responsibilities for ESI 46 and ESI 67: even with the EU having formal regulatory authority with influence on key stakeholders in climate change and energy security decision arenas, these policies use multiple instruments, each with specific responsibilities, directly and indirectly related to them (e.g. promotion of the use of renewables implies that RES enters in the electricity market, currently not happening, and due to territorial specificities of some MS, it also implies coordination among stakeholders for responsibilities over energy infrastructures, and maybe diversification of suppliers to secure supply, that according to the energy policies is an option that only MS can take);
- Possible gaps in responsibilities for ESI 18, ESI 39 and ESI 8: from all the instruments presented, few are directly targeted at the population / consumers, 10 biodiversity and natural values, and none for urbanization. If the e-Highway2050 projects seek the development of a pan-European electricity grid, it is important to seek for coherence and integration between rules and regulations for population, natural resources and urbanization (as is possible to see on the Trend Analysis of CDF¹, the European population tends to increase, and consequently urbanization, that can cause stress with the existing European natural values (Natura 2000 Network, etc.) and also with intentions to expand the existing grid of electricity.

Given the complexity of the European energy system, future grid development and other energy-related issues may encounter problems of application – e.g. market instruments may disregard the importance of prices for consumers; share of responsibilities of a pan-European grid may have issues with each national TSO having its own liberalization system, plus the competence of ENTSO to coordinate TSOs from 28 different territorial realities. Further, four considerations are important to be referred, when looking to the European energy system and compare it with the Policy Conflict Analysis (Section 6.1):

- No energy-related instrument is directly targeted at land take and land use, or the protection of ecosystem's natural values (ecosystem services);
- Support schemes and subsidies (two of the existing economic instruments) actually have different priorities (support schemes more directed to fossils and nuclear sources of energy, and subsidies increasing in the field of RES);

⁶ Climate change mitigation policies and adaptation.

⁷ Energy security.

⁸ Population, health and social/cultural values.

⁹ Biodiversity, landscape and natural values.

¹⁰ Urbanization.

- Cooperation mechanisms from the RED are not being applied as expected (see also CDF 4 assessment). Since TSOs are responsible for the development of their internal regulations based on the European rules, the different perspectives for the liberalization of the electricity market lead to the development of different regulations by each TSO, decreasing the level of cooperation and increasing the sense of competition;
- The way that Directive 2009/72/EC (on internal energy market) is being applied across MS is not consistent, leading to market fragmentation and constraining the harmonisation of MS's regulatory frameworks.

6. Strategic Analysis and Assessment

6.1. Policy Conflict Analysis

This Section provides an analysis of possible policy conflicts between EU strategic macro-policies that are part of a contextual policy framework for the e-Highway2050. The relevance of identifying potential policy conflicts is that such conflicts may determine contextual risks to the development of e-Highway2050 and influence sustainability outcomes. Conflicts may occur:

- Between different established objectives/targets for energy/electricity issues, with effects on the MS legal systems (multi-sector policies);
- Between the policy-formation processes (on the EU regulation level) and the MS implementation stage at the operational level (multi-level governance).

This analysis is not geographically based.

European governments have agreed to create an internal energy market by 2014. But today, market integration is facing serious delays (...) Instead, we see uncoordinated policies and political interventions in electricity markets (...) We see conventional generation under pressure, renewables growth independent of the market situation, and rising end-user prices as a result of increasing subsidies and taxes.¹¹

EURELECTRIC Secretary General Hans ten Berge

The relevant macro-policy objectives of the policies listed in Table 5 were analysed. Most of the relevant policies considered agree:

- that cross-thematic and multi-scale **policy coordination** is necessary and that **stakeholder engagement, cooperation among MS and with neighbouring countries** are essential to reach EU's long-term development goals;
- on the **need for increasing the share of RES** and, subsequently, **storage**, for the **reduction of GHG emissions** and for **improved resource efficiency. R&D and technological innovation** – namely of smart technologies and demand-side management solutions – are common ground for reaching these goals.

Conflicts are found between policies focused on natural resources and those focused on the energy sector. Oddly enough, such conflicts result from **RES strategy conflicting with biodiversity and ecosystem services protection** goals. The main issues found are:

- **Biodiversity and ecosystem services protection vs exploring biofuels:** the EU aspires at maintaining and enhancing biodiversity and restoring ecosystem

¹¹http://www.elecpor.pt/pdf/20130516_Current%20EU%20Energy%20Policies%20Put%20Internal%20Energy%20Market%20and%20Cost.pdf [accessed 06/01/14].

services¹², but biofuels are one of the pillars for increasing the RES share in energy generation¹³. From a strategic point of view, these goals might be incompatible because supporting extensive biofuel crops “could lead, directly or indirectly, to a decrease of the net greenhouse gas benefits and increased pressure on biodiversity, water management and the environment in general” (Renewable Energy, 2012) which is why a few policies¹⁴ refer the development of 2nd and 3rd generation biofuels and sustainable agriculture and forestry as means to avoid this possible conflict;

- **Preventing land take vs Biofuels and Decentralized energy generation:** the EU is clear on its aim to achieve no net land take by 2050 (Resource Roadmap, 2011) including by agriculture and forestry which might be a constraint to the biofuel market promoted by the energy sector. Also, decentralized generation¹⁵ might promote urban dispersion that might result in further land take;
- **Soil protection vs Gas with a key role** – even though the EU is strongly betting on RES, gas still stands with a key role in energy generation¹⁶ including “unconventional gas” (Energy 2020) which might conflict with soil protection goals¹⁷;
- **Protect marine ecosystems vs Off-shore energy:** Developing off-shore oil and gas, but also wind and wave energy generation¹⁸ - especially if it's large-scale - might cause additional pressure on marine ecosystems whose protection is recognised as necessary by the EU¹⁹.

Another potential conflict occurs at the European energy policy level: is the priority **investing on an internal market or on an international market with neighbouring countries**? The EU energy policy aims at extending EU's energy market to **neighbouring countries** (EU EP (2001) “Build up the external dimension of EU internal energy market”), relying more on institutional regulations within its neighbours than on a regulatory reliability of its own internal market.

A third potential conflict relates the low carbon economy in 2050 policy, setting out the goal to reduce “Europe's energy bill and its **dependency on fossil fuel imports**” (RLCE2050, 2011) in line with Energy 2020's increased share of RES in energy consumption targets. Conversely, other policies maintain nuclear and gas as key energy sources:

- “(...) gas can gain importance as the back-up fuel for variable electricity generation. This calls for diversified imports, both pipeline gas and Liquefied Natural Gas

¹² Biodiversity 2020, 2011; ELC, 2000; European Grid Declaration, 2011; Forestry Strategy, 2013; Water Resource Blueprint, 2012; MSFD, 2008; Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Soil Strategy, 2006; GI Strategy, 2013; Europe 2020, 2010; CC Adaptation Framework, 2009.

¹³ Forestry Strategy, 2013; Energy Roadmap 2050; Energy 2020; Renewable Energy, 2012; RLCE2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC; ETI, 2013; SET-Plan, 2007.

¹⁴ Energy Roadmap 2050, Energy 2020, RLCE2050, ETI and the SET-PLAN.

¹⁵ Energy Roadmap 2050; Energy 2020; Renewable Energy, 2012; RLCE2050, 2011.

¹⁶ Energy Roadmap 2050, Energy 2020, EIP 2020 and EU EP, 2011.

¹⁷ ELC, 2000; Forestry Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Soil Strategy, 2006.

¹⁸ Energy Roadmap 2050; Energy 2020; Renewable Energy, 2012; ETI, 2013; SET-Plan, 2007; EIP 2020; EU EP, 2001.

¹⁹ Biodiversity 2020, 2011; MSFD, 2008; Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011.

terminals, while domestic gas networks are required to be increasingly interconnected.” Energy 2020;

- “Nuclear energy will be needed to provide a significant contribution in the energy transformation process” Energy Roadmap 2050) even though Europe’s gas inland reserves in the UE have been decreasing since 2000 and that pressure for closing and decommissioning nuclear power reactors in the EU is rising (see Annex 2).

Another potential conflicts contrasts the high priority on CCS and the EU decarbonisation targets²⁰ In the long run CCS can discourage **low carbon technology development** (and funding) if the incentives to carbon efficiency of the emitting activities can be narrowed by carbon capture mechanisms.

In terms of **energy generation scale**, the EU energy policy presents distinct visions, creating confusion between the respective macro-objectives:

- Energy 2020 refers to an “(...) increase in decentralised as well as large scale renewable power generation”, but also focus the need to “(...) ensure integration of large scale generation from renewable sources”;
- EU EP (2001) fosters the promotion of “(...) decentralised renewable power production, promoting private initiatives and maximising the local value added”;
- Energy Roadmap 2050, like Energy 2020, promotes the “(...) integration of large scale generation from renewable sources”, as well as, like RLCE 2050, the “shift towards locally produced energy sources”.

All of these distinct objectives raise possible conflicts between small/large energy systems, maintenance costs or even energy storage capabilities.

EU aims to phase out **Environmentally Harmful Subsidies (EHS)** by 2020 (Resource Roadmap, 2011) as well as “moving as rapidly as possible towards schemes that expose producers to market price risk” encouraging technology competitiveness (Renewable Energy, 2012) in line with Energy 2020 and Europe 2020’s goals. On the other hand, the Energy Roadmap 2050 states that **support schemes** should be kept in place to promote a switch to RES: thus the priority concerning these mechanisms is unclear.

Finally, the Energy Roadmap 2050 sets out the objective of “ensuring that pricing schemes remain transparent and understandable to final consumers” by reflecting on the “social aspects of energy pricing in the energy policy of MS”. However, it is not clear the **accounting mechanism for pricing instruments** in reaching cost-efficient energy, particularly considering the MS sovereignty in choosing their own energy mix.

²⁰ EU energy policy is also prioritizing low-carbon technologies (Energy Roadmap 2050; Europe 2020), low carbon energy market (Energy 2020), low carbon roadmaps (RLCE 2050) and low carbon integrated system with neighbouring countries (SET-PLAN).

6.2. Strategic Assessment

CDF1 - Social acceptance and acceptability

CDF1 – “social acceptance and acceptability” focuses on all factors that affect a sense of **well-being**, and consequently determine **acceptance** and **acceptability** of grid development, including **social equity, individual and community benefits, environmental limits** related to issues such as noise, health issues, biodiversity, ecosystem services and **landscape, urbanisation, energy related** behavioural trends, as well as **vulnerability to climate change** and extreme events.

i. Critical trends

CDF1 has the following critical trends (detailed in Annex 2):

- Increasing household and workplace **electricity consumption**;
- **Fuel poverty** across Europe is predicted to increase;
- The total area of **agro-ecosystems and wetlands is decreasing** whilst **forest ecosystems are increasing**;
- Key **provisioning ecosystems services** (food and fuel) are being enhanced;
- The status and trends of key **regulating** and **cultural ecosystem services** is mixed and in some instances being degraded;
- Increased **vulnerability of coastal areas** (due to increased flood risk) and **southern European countries** (due to hotter and drier climatic conditions);
- Continuing decline in **biodiversity** and failure to stem biodiversity loss in Europe.

Each critical trend is driven by key internal and external driving forces (drivers) that explain the extent to which the trends are aligned with EU macro-policies, objectives and targets. Table 10 illustrates the relationship between these drivers and macro-policies. Table 11 provides a SWOT analysis in relation to the trend analysis and macro-policy alignment.

Table 10 - Critical trends and respective drivers - CDF 1 Social acceptance and acceptability

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
<p>Increase in the number of household appliances, consumer electronics, information and communication equipment; Increased disposable income; Market condition (relatively low price of electricity i.e. prices don't reflect the full cost of electricity generation); Climate change leading to a rising demand for temperature control technologies; Electrification of the transport sector.</p>	<p>Increasing electricity consumption by households and workplaces driven by changes in consumption behaviours.</p>	<p><u>Not aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote innovative and carefully considered use of taxation and pricing to encourage behaviour change or to fund investments (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012); - Increase the use of innovative approaches and technologies (e.g. social accountability) to promote demand reduction, increased energy efficiency and reduced fossil fuel reliance (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC; SET-PLAN, 2007; ECSER, 2012); - Promote a more resource efficient, green and competitive economy (Resource Roadmap, 2011).
<p>Procedural injustice; Distributional injustice; Injustice in recognition; Market conditions (e.g. final energy price); Individual circumstances (e.g. income level, education, literacy / numeracy etc.); Living conditions (e.g. quality of housing stock); Social / natural environment (e.g. climate, state of the economy).</p>	<p>Fuel poverty across Europe is predicted to increase.</p>	<p><u>Not aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovative use of taxation and pricing/encourage behaviour change (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012); - Innovative approaches/technologies/demand reduction (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC; SET-PLAN, 2007; ECSER, 2012).

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
<p>Drivers affecting agro-ecosystems: urbanisation, land abandonment, afforestation, conversion to intensive agriculture and agricultural subsidies;</p> <p>Drivers affecting forest ecosystems: afforestation, bio-energy policy and regeneration;</p> <p>Drivers affecting wetland ecosystems: agricultural intensification/development, conversion to forest (commercial planting) and semi-natural areas (natural succession and climate change).</p>	<p>The total area of agro-ecosystems and wetlands is decreasing whilst that of forest ecosystems is increasing.</p>	<p><u>Not aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poverty reduction (Europe 2020, 2010); - Energy product availability (Energy 2020, 2010; Directive 2009/72/EC; ETI, 2013); - Support to vulnerable consumers energy efficiency investments (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC); - Fair distribution of costs/benefits from electricity-grid (Energy 2020, 2010).
<p>Bio-energy policy;</p> <p>Agricultural intensification.</p>	<p>Key provisioning ecosystems services (food and fuel) are being enhanced.</p>	<p><u>Aligned / not aligned with (mixed alignment):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable use/management of all resources including biodiversity (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Forestry Strategy, 2013); - Conserve/enhance/properly value Europe’s natural resource base (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011); - Balance energy forestry with traditional forest uses (Forestry Strategy, 2013); - Protect, enhance and restore soils (Soil Strategy, 2006).

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
<p>Intensification of land management; Habitat fragmentation; Climate change.</p>	<p>The status and trends of key regulating (e.g. water, climate and hazard regulation) and cultural ecosystem services (e.g. landscape) is more mixed and in some instances being degraded.</p>	<p><u>Aligned / not aligned with (mixed alignment):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable use/management of all resources including biodiversity (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Forestry Strategy, 2013); - Conserve/enhance/properly value Europe’s natural resource base (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011); - Protect, enhance and restore soils (Soil Strategy, 2006); - Halt biodiversity loss and ecosystem service degradation by 2020 (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Proposed MSP and ICZM Directive, 2013); - Reduce fragmentation and degradation of forests (GI Strategy, 2013); - Protect ecologically sensitive areas (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; European Grid Declaration, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013).
<p>Climate change; Changing population demographics (including distribution).</p>	<p>Increased vulnerability of coastal areas (due to increased flood risk) and southern European countries (due to hotter and drier climatic conditions).</p>	<p><u>[Potentially] not aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem/green infrastructure approaches to climate change mitigation and adaptation (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013); - Climate resilient coastal/marine areas (Proposed MSP and ICZM Directive, 2013); - Physical infrastructure resilience to climate change (CC Adaptation Framework, 2009); - Protect forests and biodiversity from climate risks (Forestry Strategy, 2013).

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
<p>Urbanisation, land abandonment; Afforestation and conversion to intensive agriculture, bio-energy policy; Intensification of land management; Habitat fragmentation; Climate change.</p>	<p>Continuing decline in biodiversity and failure to stem biodiversity loss in Europe.</p>	<p><u>Not aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote the sustainable management and use of all resources including biodiversity/natural capital, energy, land and marine resources (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Forestry Strategy, 2013); - Conserve, enhance and properly value Europe’s natural resource base, natural processes and the ecosystem services they provide (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011); - Protect and enhance ecologically sensitive areas and all species and habitats covered by EU nature legislation (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; European Grid Declaration, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013); - Halt biodiversity loss and degradation of ecosystem services by 2020, including in the marine environment (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013); - Fully implement the Birds and Habitats Directives by 2020 (Biodiversity 2020);

ii. **SWOT**

Table 11 - SWOT analysis - CDF1 Social acceptance and acceptability

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Apparent decoupling of energy consumption from economic growth;</p> <p>The European public favours RES generation over other generation sources (<i>correct as of 2006 Eurobarometer survey</i>);</p> <p>Increased use of agricultural land for biofuel production;</p> <p>Increased forest ecosystem extent enhancing the supply of some regulating ecosystem services.</p>	<p>Apparent decoupling of energy consumption from economic growth may be a product of structural changes in Europe’s economy and ‘outsourcing’ energy intensive manufacturing to Less Economically Developed World;</p> <p>Significant conflict between several critical trends and EU macro-policies;</p> <p>Electricity prices and price rises are not consistent across Europe;</p> <p>The conservation status of the majority of habitats and species of European interest within wetland, forest and agro-ecosystems is unfavourable.</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>GDP increases facilitating energy efficiency improvements and increased EU competitiveness;</p> <p>Increased harmonisation of European energy markets can help to mitigate energy price distortions and associated fuel poverty issues;</p> <p>The European public favours RES generation over other generation sources (<i>correct as of 2006 Eurobarometer survey</i>);</p> <p>Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reform supporting enhanced regulating ecosystem services from agricultural land;</p> <p>Decentralised energy systems may be less vulnerable to disruption by climate change;</p> <p>Increase forest ecosystem extent helping to reverse historic fragmentation.</p>	<p>Vulnerability of people and infrastructure to climate change, particularly in southern Europe and coastal regions;</p> <p>The ‘rebound effect’/Jevon’s paradox resulting in sustained energy consumption despite energy efficiency improvements;</p> <p>Electrification of transport sector is dependent on affordability and infrastructure availability – access to the costs and benefits of electrified transport may not be consistent across the EU;</p> <p>Climate change impacts (e.g. caused by heat waves) on electricity usage (e.g. for air conditioning) are not consistent across Europe;</p> <p>High energy prices exacerbating existing fuel poverty inequalities ;</p> <p>Conversion to intensive agriculture (e.g. for biofuel production) leading to degradation of regulating services/agro-ecosystems climate resilience;</p> <p>Afforestation of wetland (by natural succession or commercial planting) leading to degradation of carbon storage ecosystem services;</p> <p>Intensification of silvicultural practices in favour of specific provisioning services (e.g. biomass) reducing the diversity of forest ecosystem services;</p> <p>Increased demand for cooling in southern Europe due to climate change;</p> <p>Vulnerability of MS reliant on generation sources at risk from climate change impacts;</p> <p>Continuing loss of biodiversity as a result of competition for land.</p>

iii. Strategic Assessment

Assessment criterion 1: Social Equity

Centralised and large scale RES (G1) could lead to a less equitable distribution of energy system benefits due to the inherent risks associated with an energy system based on regional imbalances. Furthermore, energy system costs associated with **G1** may also not be evenly distributed e.g. communities in remote or coastal locations may be disproportionately affected and MS with more productive RES would have to support the costs of new generation infrastructure. Also, the centralised permitting frameworks required under **G1** may reduce energy planning participation opportunities and local level control, potentially eroding social equity.

Conversely, **small scale decentralised generation (G2)** raises opportunities for progressing the social equity agenda: (1) scope for greater public participation in energy planning/opportunities for community ownership of energy assets; and (2) opportunities to promote increased awareness of energy usage and relationships with climate change and other sustainability issues. This is crucial given the observed trend of increasing household electricity consumption which works against key EU macro-policy objectives including (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012). **G2** also raises risks for social equity as a greater number of communities will be exposed to smaller scale, more dispersed energy system costs, potentially leading to greater opposition and energy planning delays.

At the EU level, a **dominant RES (G3)** strategy may provide more even access to energy system benefits (i.e. sustainable, cheaper/more consistently priced electricity) as a RES-based, EU-internal energy system will be less vulnerable to EU-external supply chain shocks and volatility²¹. This is crucial given increasing fuel poverty and inconsistent electricity pricing across the EU which works against key EU macro-policies e.g. Europe 2020, Energy 2020 and the Energy Roadmap 2050.

A **RES non-dominant (G4)** strategy, **nuclear and fossil fuel without CCS near existing capacity (G5)** and **nuclear and fossil fuel with CCS close to demand (G6)** could face problems of public acceptance and acceptability as nuclear and thermal generation technologies are currently less favoured than RES generation by EU citizens. However public acceptance and acceptability of different generation technologies could be in flux²² and support for thermal and nuclear generation technologies may grow or diminish further in the future. Reduced output of thermal and nuclear plants during heat waves (see *Assessment Criterion Vulnerabilities*) could raise secondary risks in terms of equitable access to energy system benefits and costs – e.g. market disruption during heat waves/associated electricity price rises may prevent some citizens from accessing air conditioning. This risk is likely to be a particular concern for Southern European countries

²¹ Recognising however that there may be a less equitable distribution of benefits at the MS level under some RES scale and location options as explained above.

²² This issue is pronounced by poor data availability at the EU level – the most up to date Eurobarometer study gauging public acceptance of different sources of energy is from 2006 (see Annex 2).

(due to climate change), many of which have also experienced the most pronounced household electricity price rises (e.g. Cyprus, Malta, Greece and Spain).

Due to sustained GHG emissions, **G5** will contribute to increased climate change and associated risks e.g. mass migrations, greater competition for resources and less social equity. Increased nuclear generation could provide a counter to these risks but generates other risks e.g. in terms of waste management, disaster risk management and security of supply. **G5** and **G6** will also contribute to continued resource depletion (fossil fuel and nuclear), compromising future generations, making for a less equitable energy system with uneven distribution of some energy system costs (e.g. emissions/pollution).

Conversely, thermal and nuclear generation technologies can be sited close to demand with no loss of efficiency producing a constant supply of electricity, helping to maintain fair access to energy system benefits²³. Therefore **G5** and **G6** may support more consistent electricity pricing across the EU in line with key EU macro-policies (Europe 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC). However the picture is highly complex due to thermal/nuclear generation performance under high temperatures (see above and *Assessment Criterion Vulnerabilities*). **G6** may be more socially acceptable due to the option's greater potential to mitigate climate change risks through CCS.

High to very high flows from South and North to Central Europe (G7) and **high to medium flows from North to Central Europe (G8)** may cause electricity price distortion across the EU due to the inherent management risks of an energy system based on regional imbalances. **G8** raises a specific risk in terms of uneven distribution of some energy system costs associated with new transmission infrastructure; as regional imbalances are addressed through flows from North to Central Europe only, Northern Europeans may be disproportionately affected.

Centralised hydro storage (S1) poses a risk of uneven distribution of energy system costs. Finding sites can be challenging due to the environmental costs associated with the infrastructure (e.g. impacts on biodiversity/aquatic ecosystems, landscape, recreation). Conversely, **centralised hydro storage (S1)**, **centralised hydro and CAES (S2)** and **mixed scale storage (S3)** can reduce the need for thermal and nuclear peaking units, potentially improving the overall public acceptance and acceptability of the energy system²⁴. **S2** and **S3** may be more socially acceptable than hydro storage (**S1**) as some environmental risks (e.g. visual, aquatic ecosystems, loss of recreational areas) may be less. Conversely, **S2** and **S3** raise risks due to diabatic CAES which requires thermal energy inputs (gas) and will therefore contribute to continued resource depletion (fossil fuels).

Overhead transmission (T1) raises risks of poor public acceptance and acceptability due to visual impacts and perceived/actual health impacts of overhead HVAC lines. Conversely, **underground HVDC and overhead HVAC (T2)** raises opportunities as underground transmission infrastructure is likely to be more socially acceptable.

²³ This strength/opportunity is reliant on a consistent supply of fuel therefore it is important to recognise that there are key risks associated with EU-external supply – see CDF 2 and 3.

²⁴ Noting that this opportunity applies to all storage options assuming they can provide the same capacity.

Assessment Criterion 2: Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services

Centralised and large scale RES (G1), dominant RES (G3), both of the energy flow options (G7 and G8), centralised hydro storage (S1), both of the transmission options (T1 and T2) and relevant import from North Africa (IS2) raise a number of risks in terms of biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services. For example, the provision of new centralised infrastructure of this scale has the potential to cause a range of pressures that may affect the integrity of landscapes, ecosystems, communities (of species), habitats and individual species populations (e.g. landscape disruption and degradation of ecosystem processes). This is a particular issue given critical trends concerning the unfavourable conservation status of the majority of habitats and species of European interest found within e-Highway2050 relevant²⁵ ecosystems. This trend works against several key EU macro-policy objectives including (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Forestry Strategy, 2013; Proposed MSP and ICZM Directive, 2013).

Similarly, the land take associated with the provision of new large scale centralised infrastructure may alter the type and distribution of ecosystem services across the EU. This may become a particular issue where key regulating (e.g. water, climate and hazard regulation) and cultural (e.g. landscape) services are eroded as their current status and trends in the EU is mixed and in some instances services are being degraded. Similarly to the above, this trend is all the more significant as it works against the objectives of key EU macro-policies including (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011). More specific risks relating to key strategic options are as follows: (1) risks associated with energy flow options are likely to be spatially differentiated – across the whole of the EU under **G7** and more focused on North and Central Europe under **G8**; (2) for **centralised hydro storage (S1)** risks are likely to be focused on aquatic ecosystems/ecosystem services; and (3) **relevant import from North Africa (IS2)** raises specific risks for biodiversity and ecosystem services in marine and coastal areas along the Mediterranean – there may be key risks associated with fisheries, cable landing station infrastructure in the coastal zone and biodiversity based tourism activity.

On the other hand, **centralised and large scale RES (G1)** may act as a driver for the large scale production of forest biomass which has the potential to deliver multiple benefits for landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services, if designed well.

Decentralised and small scale RES (G2) is more balanced in terms of risks and opportunities for biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services. **G2** may drive the small scale production of forest biomass which is likely to be compatible with multiple benefits for landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services. Forest biomass production may also help to address critical trends concerning the conservation status of habitats and species of European interest found within e-Highway2050 relevant ecosystems²⁶ as well as helping to enhance the status of key regulating and cultural ecosystem services which are in decline in some areas (e.g. water and climate regulation, landscape). This would support

²⁵ Identified as agro-ecosystems, forests and wetlands, all of which provide ecosystem services that are critical for the functioning of the EU's energy system – see Annex 2.

²⁶ See note 22 page 42.

objectives from key EU macro-policies (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011; European Grid Declaration, 2011). Conversely, there is potential for cumulative damage to occur – i.e. **G2** could contribute to multiple small scale impacts particularly if landscapes and ecosystems are significantly changed in each small intervention.

RES non-dominant (G4), nuclear and fossil fuel without CCS near existing capacity (G5) and nuclear and fossil fuel with CCS close to demand (G6) present risks over increased volumes of nuclear waste and uncertainties around storage/management of waste and implications of any accidents for biodiversity, landscapes and ecosystem services. Whilst nuclear generation could provide a counter to some of the climate change risks associated with **G5** it generates other risks (e.g. in terms of waste management, disaster risk management and security of supply). **G5** may also increase the risk of climate change raising concerns for the resilience of ecosystems, landscapes, habitats and species populations.

Centralised hydro and CAES (S2) and mixed scale storage (S3) both raise opportunities as a combined strategy may reduce the need for additional centralised hydro storage, maintaining pressure on landscape, biodiversity, aquatic ecosystems etc. at current levels (i.e. no net increase).

Assessment Criterion 3: Vulnerabilities

Centralised and large scale RES (G1) and decentralised and small scale RES (G2) raise opportunities and risks that are the inverse of each other. Under **G1**, as generation takes place close to the resource rather than demand, exposure to perceived or actual health risks (e.g. noise, flicker nuisance from wind) associated with generation/transmission technology may be reduced as generation is located away from population centres). **G1** raises potential risks in terms of energy generation infrastructure vulnerability to extreme climatic events²⁷. This is a particular issue given critical trends on increasing energy system infrastructure vulnerability to climate which work against objectives from CC Adaptation Framework, 2009. Conversely, there may be potential for enhanced climate change resilience under **G2** due to the distributed nature of the energy system whereby more nodes/generation points means that exposure to climate change risks is more evenly distributed.

Dominant RES (G3) and RES non-dominant (G4) may be vulnerable to climate change for different reasons. **G3** is vulnerable due to reliance on centralised PHS which may be vulnerable to drought risk with key strategic infrastructure located in Southern Europe and South Central Europe (e.g. in the French, Italian and Swiss alps) being particularly exposed. Under **G4**, thermal and nuclear generation capacity located in southern Europe may be vulnerable as increased temperature can reduce cooling efficiency. This risk also applies to **G5** and **G6**.

²⁷ Recognising however the exact nature of the risk will depend on where the infrastructure is located and specific local climate change impacts: (a) Southern Europe is likely to be most vulnerable due to heat waves and droughts; (b) coastal regions are likely to be vulnerable to sea level rise and coastal flooding; (c) hydropower is vulnerable to drought and low flows; and (d) offshore wind generation is vulnerable to sea level rise and increased frequency of storm events.

Underground HVDC and overhead HVAC (T2) may be vulnerable to climate change risks where underground lines, particularly in Southern Europe, are exposed to prolonged periods of drought which may cause changes in soil conditions and associated ground movements, impacting cable function.

All storage options (**S1, S2 and S3**) are potentially vulnerable to key climate change impacts, namely the loss of efficacy experienced by centralised PHS during drought conditions. This is likely to affect PHS in Southern and Central Europe in particular and is important in the context of critical trends concerning increasing energy system infrastructure vulnerability to climate threats and related EU macro-policies (see above).

Centralised hydro storage (S1) is likely to be the most vulnerable storage option due to 100% reliance on PHS. **Mixed scale storage (S3)** is likely to be the least vulnerable due to the range of storage methods available under this option.

Table 12 summarises the assessment and proposed planning and management guidelines to address the issues identified by the assessment for CDF1.

Table 12 - Summary of the assessment and Guidelines related to opportunities - CDF1 Social acceptance and acceptability

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
SOCIAL EQUITY	G2	(+) Likely to provide equal access to energy system benefits and costs	Develop and implement new planning and assessment mechanisms where necessary to support the planning of decentralised infrastructure; Ensure that multiple scale, robust governance arrangements are in place, to provide a framework for multiple energy system stakeholders engagement in delivery and management; Ensure continued engagement with the public and affected communities during implementation to promote increased awareness of climate change and sustainability issues, promote green behaviours and to capture data on changing community needs to ensure continued service delivery improvements (e.g. by TSOs, energy companies etc.).
	G2	(+) Opportunities for greater public participation in energy planning and governance including community ownership of energy assets	
	G2	(+) Increased awareness of energy usage and relationships with climate change and other sustainability issues, potentially encouraging greater uptake of greener behaviours	
	G3	(+) Even access to energy system benefits - RES-based EU-internal energy system less vulnerable to external volatility	
	G2	(-) Greater number of communities exposed to energy system costs, potentially leading to increased opposition and energy planning delays	
	G5	(+) Thermal and nuclear generation technologies can be sited close to demand with no loss of efficiency producing a constant supply of electricity, helping to maintain fair access to energy system benefits	
	G6	(+) Thermal generation with CCS technology may increase the acceptability of thermal generation to EU citizens and mitigate climate risks	
	S1	(+) Can reduce the need for thermal and nuclear peaking units, potentially improving the overall public acceptance and acceptability of the energy system	
	S2, S3	(+) More socially acceptable due to the lesser environmental impacts of CAES technology	Where geophysical conditions allow, consider the use of CAES storage technology at vulnerable locations (e.g. watercourses with high recreational or biodiversity value), instead of pumped hydro storage, to enhance the public acceptability of the energy system.
	T2	(+) Underground transmission infrastructure is likely to enjoy	Engage the public and affected communities to help

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
		high levels of public acceptance and acceptability	guide strategic grid infrastructure development to suitable locations and promote increased awareness and understanding of energy system costs and benefits;
	T1	(-) Poor public acceptance and acceptability of transmission infrastructure due to visual impacts and perceived/actual health impacts of overhead HVAC lines	Effective use of spatial planning and constraints analysis to guide transmission infrastructure deployment to the most suitable locations/routes.
	G1, G7, G8	(-) Less equitable distribution of energy system benefits due to the inherent risks associated with an energy system based on regional imbalances	Upfront public participation in planning of transmission grid;
	G1, G4	(-) Public acceptance and acceptability could be in flux - support for this type of generation system may change in the future	Design electricity grids and markets to assure equitable distribution of energy system benefits, especially where fuel poverty is critical;
	G1	(-) Centralized permitting frameworks may reduce participation opportunities at local level, reducing social equity	Design electricity grids and markets to ensure more deprived/less affluent communities do not bear the greatest burden of energy system costs;
	G1, G5, G7, S1	(-) Uneven distribution of some energy system costs and benefits	Use stakeholder engagement, constraints analysis and existing planning mechanisms (e.g. spatial planning and SEA/Environmental Impact Assessment - EIA) to guide new infrastructure and transmission infrastructure deployment to the most suitable locations.
	G4, G5, G6	(-) Could face problems of public acceptance and acceptability as nuclear and thermal generation technologies are not favoured by EU citizens	
	G4	(-) Reduced output of thermal and nuclear generation during heat waves may have secondary effects in terms of access to benefits and costs	Ensure that the design of electricity grids and markets contributes to the equitable distribution of energy system benefits.
	G5	(-) Increased risk of climate change (due to sustained GHG emissions) and associated social equity concerns	
	G4, G5, G6	(-) Continued resource depletion (fossil and nuclear), compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs, making for a less equitable energy system	

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	S2, S3	(-) Diabatic CAES requires thermal energy (gas) and will therefore contribute to continued resource depletion (fossil fuels) and associated social equity issues	
BIODIVERSITY, LANDSCAPE AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES	G1, G2	(+) Forest biomass production may help deliver multiple benefits for landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services	
	G4, G5, G6	(+) May have a smaller land take footprint per unit of energy produced, reducing energy development related pressure on land resources and ecosystem services	
	G4, G5, G6	(+) Limited requirement for grid reinforcements and therefore limited additional pressure on landscape, ecosystem and species population integrity	Ensure that any essential grid reinforcements are planned and designed to minimise pressure on biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services; Identify opportunities for energy development (e.g. through the planning and construction of new transmission infrastructure) to enhance structural and functional landscape connectivity (e.g. development of wildlife corridors and stepping stones).
	S2, S3	(+) Combined strategy may reduce the need for additional centralised hydro storage, maintaining pressure on landscape, biodiversity and aquatic ecosystems at current levels (no net increase)	If it is possible to remove centralised hydro storage capacity from the energy system (i.e. as a result of increased CAES usage), consider how this can be undertaken to deliver maximum environmental benefit – e.g. focus on priority catchments that are adversely affected by morphology pressures.
	G1, G7, G8, S1	(-) Infrastructure pressure affecting the integrity of landscapes, ecosystems, communities (of species), habitats and individual species populations	Seek to avoid first, then reduce (mitigate) and only as a last resort compensate for loss of biodiversity and other ecosystem services;
	G1	(-) Infrastructure related land take altering the type and distribution of ecosystem services across the EU	Always seek to deliver no net loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services, and ideally net gain; Use a green infrastructure levy on RES development to fund strategic mitigation measures; Ensure that mitigation recommendations and measures are delivered effectively in accordance with any planning conditions prescribed by planning

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+ Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
			<p>consents;</p> <p>Use environmental planning and spatial planning effectively to guide any new centralised hydro storage to the most suitable locations (e.g. away from the most vulnerable and/or valued catchments).</p>
	G2	<p>(-) Decentralised RES generation could contribute to multiple small scale impacts particularly if landscapes and ecosystems are significantly changed in each small intervention</p>	<p>Ensure continued engagement with the public and affected communities during energy system implementation. This should be designed in order to: 1) promote increased awareness of climate change and sustainability issues; 2) promote green behaviours; and 3) to capture data on changing community needs, thereby ensuring continued service delivery improvements (e.g. by TSOs, energy companies etc.).</p>
	T2	<p>(+) Small land take associated with underground HVDC transmission infrastructure reduces pressure on landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services</p>	<p>Effective use of spatial planning and constraints analysis to guide transmission infrastructure deployment to the most suitable locations/routes;</p> <p>Undergrounding where appropriate and where impacts on biodiversity are temporary and reversible.</p>
	T2	<p>(-) Underground cable systems may constrain land use options to a degree due to buffer distance that can't be developed</p>	<p>Work with landowners/managers to find suitable land use/management options (e.g. agriculture, forestry, semi-natural habitat, wildlife corridor etc.)</p>
	T2	<p>(-) Land take within pan-European electricity highway corridors may constrain land use/management options including biodiversity/habitat</p>	<p>within electricity highway corridors to ensure that land delivers multiple benefits;</p> <p>Use stakeholder engagement and constraints mapping to steer strategic grid infrastructure development away from sensitive and vulnerable locations (e.g. Natura 2000 sites and protected landscapes) and to enhance structural and functional landscape connectivity (e.g. development of wildlife corridors and stepping stones).</p>
G5	<p>(-) Increased volume of nuclear waste and concerns over its storage/management and implications of any accidents for biodiversity, landscapes and ecosystem services</p>		

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	G5	(-) Increased risk of climate change and concerns for the resilience of ecosystems, landscapes, habitats and species populations	
	IS2	(-) Increased pressure on marine ecosystems, habitats, species and ecosystem services (including commercial fisheries) in the Mediterranean sea as a result of submarine cable systems linking North Africa to continental Europe	Effective use of integrated marine/land spatial planning and constraints analysis to guide transmission infrastructure deployment to the most suitable locations/routes (e.g. less vulnerable areas in terms of marine habitats, fisheries, recreational areas).
	IS2	(-) Risks also associated with pressure caused as a result of cable landing station infrastructure	
VULNERABILITIES	G1	(+) Reduced exposure to perceived or actual health vulnerabilities if generation happens where the resource is best/away from population centres	Consider how appropriate use of transmission technology can minimise health vulnerabilities associated with transmitting flows from energy generation to energy demand regions (e.g. use underground cables in vulnerable locations); Use upfront public engagement as early as possible to help deliver these types of mitigation strategies most effectively.
	G2	(+) Enhanced climate change resilience due to the distributed nature of the energy system/ more nodes and generation points	Ensure continued engagement with the public and affected communities during implementation to promote increased awareness of climate change and sustainability issues, promote green behaviours and to capture data on changing community needs to ensure continued service delivery improvements (e.g. by TSOs, energy companies etc.).
	S3	(+) Mixed strategy less reliant on centralised hydro storage therefore less exposed to drought related climate risks	Where possible, prioritise CAES and decentralised storage over centralised hydro storage.
	T1	(+) Overhead transmission infrastructure located in Southern Europe is not vulnerable to key climate change impacts	Effective use of spatial planning and constraints analysis to guide transmission infrastructure deployment to the most suitable locations/routes (e.g. less vulnerable areas in terms of soils, hydrology, hydrogeology etc.).

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+ Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	G1	(-) Infrastructure vulnerability to extreme climatic events, depending location and specific local climate change impacts	
	G3	(-) Reliance on storage infrastructure may expose the energy system to key climate change risks	Develop a portfolio of storage options to minimise exposure to climate change risks (i.e. avoid reliance on pumped hydro storage).
	G4, G5, G6	(-) Thermal and nuclear generation infrastructure located in southern Europe may become increasingly vulnerable to extreme climatic events	
	G7, T2	(-) Underground lines transmitting high flows from Southern Europe will be particularly vulnerable to prolonged periods of drought causing changes in soil conditions and associated ground movements	Use spatial planning and constraints analysis to guide underground lines away from particularly vulnerable locations (e.g. in terms of soils, hydrology, hydrogeology etc.).
	S1, S2	(-) Loss of efficacy during droughts – likely to affect centralised hydro storage in Southern Europe and South Central Europe in particular	

iv. Monitoring Guidelines

Table 13 identifies the relevant issues that should be monitored, considering the opportunities and risks described above for CDF1. These monitoring guidelines aim to inform a more extensive periodic follow-up program for e-Highway2050's implementation. These monitoring guidelines aim to inform a more extensive periodical follow-up program for e-Highway2050's implementation.

Table 13 - Monitoring guidelines and indicators for follow-up - CDF1 Social acceptance and acceptability

Monitoring Guidelines	Monitoring Indicators
Monitor the public acceptance and acceptability of different aspects of the EU energy system.	EU citizen's acceptance of energy technologies.
Monitor public participation in energy system planning and delivery.	Response rates to energy system related consultations; Number of community energy schemes.
Monitor the distribution of energy system costs and benefits.	Scale and location of installed generation capacity; Number and location of public complaints concerning energy generation nuisance and health issues; Composite levels of fuel poverty (by MS); Electricity prices (by MS); Heat wave related deaths.
Monitor energy system infrastructure pressure on biodiversity, landscapes and ecosystem services.	Number and location of energy system infrastructure projects sited within or adjacent to Natura 2000 sites, Important Bird Areas and other designations; Conservation status of habitats and species of European interest within affected areas; Landscape metrics (area of habitat patches and structural/functional habitat networks).
Monitor forest biomass production.	Status and extent of forest ecosystems; Scale and location of uptake of CAP Pillar II forestry grant support; Area of forestry under continuous cover forestry (CCF) management.
Monitor energy system infrastructure vulnerability to extreme climatic events.	Lost output due to extreme climatic events; Frequency, location and severity of droughts, floods etc.
Monitor uptake of greener behaviours.	Smart meter installation in households; Energy efficiency measures in households.
Monitor EU domestic fossil fuel exploitation and GHG emissions.	Energy sector GHG emissions; GHG emissions by sector; Exploitation rates of EU domestic fossil fuel reserves.
Monitor energy sector related waste and waste management.	Volume of nuclear waste produced.

v. Governance Guidelines

Table 14 proposes governance guidelines. These guidelines try to ensure cooperation and sharing of responsibility among relevant stakeholders in grid development.

Table 14 - Governance Framework for follow-up - CDF1 Social acceptance and acceptability

Organization	Governance Guidelines
DG Energy	<p>Promote increased awareness of energy usage and relationships with climate change and other sustainability issues;</p> <p>Undertake further research and consultation with stakeholders, the public and affected communities to gauge current support for different generation technologies;</p> <p>Impose a requirement for further harmonisation of energy policy, price coupling initiatives etc. (this should aim to protect MS that are net energy importers in particular);</p> <p>Robust governance arrangements should be put in place, at a range of scales, to provide the necessary framework whereby multiple energy system stakeholders (including affected communities) can engage in delivery and management;</p> <p>Promote R&D to speed up the market readiness of emerging storage technologies;</p> <p>Promote R&D in climate resilient generation technologies;</p> <p>Promote R&D to maximise the efficiency of nuclear and thermal generation technologies</p> <p>Ensure effective investment in CCS R&D;</p> <p>Promote R&D into improved efficiency of pumped hydro storage (noting that electrical efficiency is currently ~80%);</p> <p>Promote R&D that speeds up the market readiness of adiabatic CAES storage technologies (eliminates the need for gas inputs).</p>
European Parliament	<p>Consider the appropriateness and utility of existing mechanisms for planning a decentralised energy system (e.g. existing arrangements for spatial planning and planning support mechanisms such as SEA and EIA) and to develop new mechanisms where necessary;</p> <p>Forestry related grants and incentives (e.g. Pillar II of CAP) should be designed to deliver multiple benefits.</p>
MS	<p>Put in place wider resilience measures to protect the most vulnerable during heat waves;</p> <p>Identify opportunities for energy development to enhance structural and functional landscape connectivity;</p> <p>Ensure effective use of spatial planning and constraints analysis to guide large scale RES deployment away from the most ecologically sensitive terrestrial and marine areas (e.g. areas of land with a distinct primary use such as national parks, Natura 2000 sites, Important Bird Areas (IBAs), prime agricultural land, carbon rich soils);</p> <p>Effective integrated land use planning and sensitive landscape design to ‘fit’ RES development within the landscape, protecting ecosystem function and biodiversity;</p> <p>Energy forestry should be designed as part of an integrated approach to land management, adhering to the principles of multifunctional forestry;</p> <p>Robust governance arrangements should be put in place, at a range of scales, to provide the necessary framework whereby multiple energy system stakeholders (including affected communities) can engage in delivery and management;</p> <p>Consider key climatic vulnerabilities in the planning and design of large scale, centralised RES;</p> <p>Ensure that all aspects of energy development are considered within integrated/cross-sector</p>

Organization	Governance Guidelines
	<p>land use plans to avoid conflicts and maximise the delivery of multiple benefits;</p> <p>Consider full range of land take related life cycle impacts (e.g. resource extraction, GHG emissions and waste management) during options appraisal and planning/design of energy generation development;</p> <p>Ensure that the implications of increased nuclear generation capacity are fully considered;</p> <p>Ensure that new thermal generation capacity can be adequately serviced by CCS provision (e.g. in terms of the required geophysical conditions and necessary infrastructure).</p>
Regulators	<p>Use capacity market design and management to reduce regional energy system climate change vulnerability.</p>
NGOs	<p>Engage early in, and promote benefits of, opportunities for public participation to ensure strong public voice in energy decision making.</p>

CDF2 - Energy security and technologies

CDF2 – “Energy security and technologies” focuses on trends towards favouring EU and national policies concerning **RES, technological enhancement** to favour **complementarity, interconnectivity** and **smart** initiatives that **reduce costs** and **increase benefits** and also ensure **energy security** across and within MS policy and practice.

i. Critical trends

CDF2 has the following critical trends (detailed in Annex 2):

- Considerable **improvement in energy savings** regarding both primary and final energy consumption. Manufacturing industry with average loss of energy efficiency between 2000 and 2010;
- **Reduction of GHG emissions** compared to 1990. Decoupling between energy demand increase and emissions;
- Overall **improvements in electricity and heat generation efficiency** by conventional energy production technologies – higher in autoproducers;
- Steady **growth of patent numbers in technology**, but barriers still exist on the industrial deployment of Key Enabling Technologies;
- **Growing number of CCS** pilot projects deployed and **increase in the number of R&D**, demonstration and deployment projects as well as initiatives related to **Smart Grids**;
- **Rising energy import dependency**, mostly from the East, resulting in vulnerability to supply disruptions;
- European position regarding **nuclear power** decommissioning on a trend of **increasing fragility**.

Each critical trend identified is driven by key internal and external driving forces (drivers) that explain the extent to which the trends are aligned with EU macro-policies, objectives and targets. Table 15 illustrates the relationship between these drivers and macro-policies. Table 16 provides a SWOT analysis in relation to the trend analysis and macro-policy alignment.

Table 15 - Critical trends and respective drivers - CDF2 Energy Security and Technologies

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
<p>GDP growth, low economic performance, structural changes, fuel switches, policy packages' implementation in MS and efficiency improvements drive energy efficiency improvements, but economic crisis affects the industrial sector's efficiency.</p>	<p>Considerable improvement in overall energy savings regarding both primary and final energy consumption. Manufacturing industry with average loss of energy efficiency between 2000 and 2010.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve energy efficiency by 20% in 2020 (Europe 2020, 2010).
<p>Economic restructuring with a shift from heavy manufacturing industries to service-based economies; Fuel switch in power generation from coal to natural gas and RES; MS GHG reduction policy; Growth in District Heating and Cooling installed capacity.</p>	<p>Reduction of GHG emissions compared to 1990. Decoupling between energy demand increase and emissions.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By 2020, reduce GHG emissions at least 20% compared to 1990 or 30% if the conditions are right (Europe 2020, 2010); - By 2020, economic growth and wellbeing is decoupled from resource inputs (Resource Roadmap, 2011).
<p>Autoproducers designed to be more suitable for the heat and electricity demand on location; Decline pushed by increased utilisation of existing lower efficiency coal plants in the last 4 years; More support from local communities and regional authorities for DHC efficiency.</p>	<p>Overall improvements in electricity and heat generation efficiency by conventional energy production technologies - higher in autoproducers.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By 2020, increase energy efficiency by 20% (Europe 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011).
<p>KET developments; GHG reduction efforts and policy support.</p>	<p>Growing number of CCS pilot projects.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applying CCS from 2030 onwards (Energy Roadmap 2050).
<p>Raising investment on technology R&D resulting in patents; Shift of public funding from nuclear to electricity and gas infrastructure and sustainable energy; Absence of large-scale demonstrators and pilot test facilities and lack of support to commercialise results of research.</p>	<p>Steady growth of patents in technology but barriers still exist on the industrial deployment of Key Enabling Technologies.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Speed up development and demonstration projects, new and flexible infrastructures; Main technologies: 2nd generation biofuels, smart grids, smart cities and intelligent networks, CCS, electricity storage and electro-mobility, next generation nuclear, renewable heating and cooling, flexible gas capacities. (Energy 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011; Energy Roadmap
<p>Public and private investments in R&D,</p>	<p>Increase in the number of R&D,</p>	

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
demonstration and deployment activities; Increasing confidence in the viability of Smart Grid projects; Technological, regulatory, economic and behavioural changes.	demonstration and deployment projects as well as initiatives related to Smart Grids – mostly smart meters.	2050, 2011).
National compartmentalisation and monopolistic nature of energy markets, especially in Central and Eastern Europe, primary energy demand, EU oil and gas production, mainly in the North Sea; Decreasing EU oil and gas reserves as well as the calorific value per ton of coal; Increasing pressure for closing and decommissioning nuclear power reactors in the EU, following the Fukushima accident.	Rising energy import dependency, mostly from the East resulting in vulnerability to supply disruptions; Added pressure to the exploring unconventional gas sources.	<u>Not aligned with:</u> - Securing energy supplies (EIP 2020; Energy 2020).

ii. **SWOT**

Table 16 - SWOT Analysis - CDF2 Energy Security and Technologies

Strengths	Weaknesses
Conventional energy production (thermal) producing heat sold to 3 rd parties (Combined Heat and Power - CHP plants). On average, over 80% of heat supplied by district heating originates either from RES or heat recovery; Exponential rise in the overall EU production of biofuels despite the reduction in recent years; Increase in the installed capacity for geothermal, wind and photovoltaic energy.	Energy production uses the highest amount of water in the EU; Severe difficulties in covering the cost of conventional thermal generation and disincentive for the building of new thermal power capacities.
Opportunities	Threats
Large RES-Electricity (RES-E) potential in wind, photovoltaic and biomass for both the MS and non-MS (NMS). In MS wave & tidal and thermal solar energy also have promising potential;	Storage technologies, other than mechanical pumped hydro with relative low number of facilities in the pilot or demonstration stages might cause the storage status quo (hydro as main tech.) to maintain;

<p>New, more demanding, GHG reduction and RES share targets to be met by the EU as a whole through supply diversification, reliance on indigenous energy sources, interconnection capacity between MS and R&D innovation;</p> <p>Additional CO₂ reduction can be achieved with increased penetration of District Heating and Cooling (DHC). District cooling 5 to 10 times more efficient than electric equipment can greatly contribute to avoiding electricity peak loads during summer;</p> <p>Largest, and growing, percentage of EU R&D investment in energy is aimed at sustainable energies;</p> <p>Wind energy has the potential of reducing water consumption by the energy sector;</p> <p>North-Central EU electricity corridors, connecting central EU to the Baltic, the Northern Sea's offshore grid and the Southern Gas Corridor are considered a priority although investment gaps might threaten the implementation;</p> <p>Reducing import dependency is a strategic goal.</p>	<p>Three quarters of Europe's pumped storage capacity installed in just eight countries;</p> <p>Desertec Industrial Initiative not interested in export solar power generated from the Sahara to Europe;</p> <p>High import dependency, mostly from the East;</p> <p>Inland gas and oil reserves as well as the calorific value per ton of coal is decreasing in the EU;</p> <p>Power sector calling for capacity payments to ensure enough backup generating capacity remains in service;</p> <p>Macro-policy unclear on centralised vs decentralised energy generation.</p>
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iii. Strategic Assessment

Assessment Criterion 1: Energy Efficiency

Overall, RES is more competitive than fossil fuels in electricity generation and promotes low-carbon energy in line with EU's macro-policies (e.g. Energy 2020, Europe 2020, RLCE2050, Energy and Climate 2030) and further improves the current trend of reducing GHG emissions. **Large-scale generation, where most profitable (G1)**, fosters more efficient RES generation units, although a strictly centralized generation strategy may not be the most cost-efficient solution for energy islands. **Decentralized and small-scale RES (G2)** generation could reduce energy losses in the transmission grid and also allow capturing and re-using locally generated heat, through CHP plants and DHC. This could increase the overall efficiency of the energy system (European Grid Declaration 2011, RLCE2050). Yet, RES generation close to demand rather than to resources compromises generation efficiency and productivity. Having **RES as the dominant energy source (G3)** is likely to make existing fossil fuel plants comparably less efficient and lead to their suboptimal performance, aggravating the usage of low-efficiency coal plants. A **RES non-dominant energy mix with small scale RES (G4)** may promote a less efficient use of RES capacities acting also against decarbonisation and GHG reduction macro-policy goal (unless CCS is in place), aggravated by the additional energy consumption for transporting primary fuels.

Maintaining **fossil energy sources without CCS (G5)** threatens the achievement of EU's GHG emissions reduction goals and those for a low-carbon generation (Energy 2020, RLCE2050, Europe 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050). Developing **additional nuclear and fossil fuel capacity, with CCS, close to demand (G6)** might promote the investment in local and more efficient thermal autoproduction and mitigate overall energy losses in transmission (European Grid Declaration). Yet, there is the risk that CCS might demote technological development of energy efficient solutions. This option is threatened by the nuclear decommissioning trend and by public acceptance issues.

High energy flows (G7, G8) imply a more efficient use of RES, with more productive regions providing for increasing capacity, thus contributing to decarbonisation of the economy and promoting cooperation among TSOs (Energy and Climate 2030; Energy Roadmap 2050). An energy system based on **low energy flows (G9)** may result in an inefficient use of RES, making regions with lower RES potential dependent on fossil fuel and nuclear energy, and divesting in a pan-European grid.

HVDC (T1, T2) allows efficient long-distance bulk power delivery enhancing transmission capacity while HVAC has higher energy losses and limits line length when compared to HVDC. But, most of the existing grid is in AC, so developing the electricity highways in DC might turn out too costly. Hence, developing HVAC using FACTS (**T1, T2**) increases the efficiency of the existing electricity system. **Overhead lines (T1)** may constrain HVDC's potential due to physical limits. A mix of **underground HVDC and overhead HVAC (T2)** has fewer physical and technical restrictions to HVDC transmission potential.

Centralized PHS (S1) contributes to overall electrical efficiency but wind powered PHS can further increase it by storing excess RES electricity, thus contributing to and efficient use of its potential. A **centralised hydro strategy with CAES (S2)**, preferably adiabatic CAES, reduces storage energy losses while increasing the number of large-scale storage facilities. However, as previously mentioned, CAES competes for the same types of sites as CCS. Implementing **mixed scale storage (S3)** promotes trade-offs between storage efficiency and transmission losses and provides flexibility to regions where large-scale solutions are not competitive. Additionally, small-scale storage from EV would contribute to transport sector GHG reduction goals. **Decentralised storage** using batteries also enables demand side management (DSM), possibly reducing overall energy consumption, especially when combined with smart grids (Renewable Energy 2012).

Assessment Criterion 2: Innovation and Technological Development

Implementing a **centralized and large scale RES strategy (G1)** promotes the technological development of large-scale and centralized technologies such as next generation offshore wind, DHC and CSP. Improving research enables market actors to drive down RES costs allowing its large-scale use, although it might inhibit investment in decentralised technologies (SET-PLAN 2007 and 2012, Energy 2020, RLCE2050, Energy Roadmap 2050). Similarly, backing **decentralized and small scale RES (G2)** promotes investment for R&D in local generation and energy efficiency (DHC, batteries, biofuels) enabling the development of smart and local grids. Investment in centralised generation technologies, however, might be inhibited. Thus decentralised, smaller-scale generation and storage solutions should be implemented hand-in-hand with large-scale solutions (e.g. Energy Roadmap 2050, Energy 2020).

If a **RES dominant** energy mix is in place (**G3**), RES-related technological development is likely to be promoted, capitalizing on the trend of increasing R&D investment in sustainable energy. It may however inhibit R&D not related to RES such as CCS (per se or related to biomass), flexible gas technologies, next generation nuclear as well as 2nd and 3rd generation biofuels or cleaner thermal generation, which would be promoted in a **RES-non dominant strategy (G4)**. Conversely, G4 strategy may promote emerging technologies that are highly risky for the biophysical and social environment such as tar oil sands, shale gas and hydraulic fracking.

Having **no new fossil fuel or nuclear capacity (G5)** might inhibit CCS and nuclear energy technological development but, on the other hand, adding **nuclear and fossil fuel capacity with CCS (G6)** depends on CCS maturity and its commercial-scale deployment.

Relying on **centralized hydro storage (S1)** might limit technological development of other large-scale storage technologies, avoidable by using **centralised hydro and CAES (S2)**. Also, relying strictly on **large-scale storage** may also inhibit the funding of research in battery storage technology, a key element to smart and microgrids. **Mixed scale storage (S3)** promotes the technological development of innovative storage solutions such as EV's, H₂ and synthetic gas, as well as smart grids.

Using HVDC cables and lines for long-distance transmission (**T1, T2**) promotes the technological development of HVDC components and associated R&D activities. Any

options that may inhibit sustainable technological development is not in line with Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050 or the RLCE2050.

Assessment Criterion 3: Energy Security

Large-scale generation, where most profitable (G1) fosters high efficiency of RES generation, reducing the energy dependence from abroad (Energy 2020). On the other hand, to provide the necessary grid flexibility, this option depends on the realisation of large-scale storage. Also, relying exclusively on centralized and large scale RES generation discourages small producers and local generation, against EU policy favouring a more resilient and flexible energy system (Renewable Energy, Energy Roadmap 2050, EU EP). In a centralized strategy, regions that depend on the pan-European infrastructure for energy supply are necessarily more vulnerable to energy outages, hence, energy islands might remain, compromising Energy Roadmap 2050's target. A **decentralized and small scale RES generation strategy (G2)** should improve the energy system's resilience to extreme climatic events or other accidents, thus contributing to overall energy security. It also offers the system flexibility for generation to match local demand patterns for electricity and heat (ETI, 2013). However, a more complex and distributed system may require higher investment to guarantee the system's security, viability and resilience.

A **RES-dominant energy mix (G3)** reduces energy dependence from abroad, but may increase vulnerability to power outages due to RES's intermittence, which could be mitigated by connecting storage facilities. A **RES non-dominant and small scale (G4)** option can reduce energy islands without depending on substantial transmission and storage investment since non-RES generation does not depend on local resource productivity. Yet, it risks increasing energy import dependency since Europe's inland gas, oil, coal and uranium reserves are decreasing.

Having **no new nuclear or fossil fuel capacity (G5)** might threaten overall reliability of supply, especially in regions where RES is not yet fully efficient. **Developing nuclear and fossil fuel capacity close to demand (G6)** reduces the vulnerability to RES intermittence where a RES dominant strategy is adopted, thus increasing the reliability of supply (Energy 2020). However, relying on gas in regions with high import dependency is likely to increase vulnerability to power outages.

High energy flows towards Central Europe (G7, G8) reinforces the strengthening of the regional network in North-South flow directions. It also serves to accommodate wind generation from the Northern and Baltic Seas and to connect new generation hubs with major store facilities (currently in the Alps and Nordic Countries) and with major consumption centres (Central Europe) (EIP 2020). On the other hand, an energy system that results in high energy flows is likely to create major imbalances, and possible tensions, in terms of energy provision, capacity and demand within regions in Europe. With **low energy flows (G9)** vulnerability to neighbours' political instability may be reduced, but a high level of fossil fuel/ nuclear energy has to be maintained, thus maintaining energy dependence from abroad, acting against EU macro-policy (EIP 2020).

A strategy that relies on hydro storage (**S1 and S2**) is readily deployable with PHS, allowing an efficient management of the energy system, exploring daily load patterns,

thus increasing its reliability, although this option is limited to adequate PHS and or CAES locations. Also, small producers and local generation foreseen in macro-policy can be discouraged (Energy Roadmap 2050). **Distributed energy storage, including centralised solutions (S3)** creates redundant, reliable backup systems, making the energy system less vulnerable and flexible, thus increasing system's reliability while providing additional storage capacity. Conversely, a decentralised system has more management issues.

T1 and T2 transmission options depend on the maturity for HVDC components so it is important to assess if HVDC components' technology readiness level (TRL) and investment return rate is compatible with the strategy's implementation. Due to the exposed situation of overhead lines (**T1, T2**), disturbances occur more frequently than in underground cables making the grid relatively vulnerable to outages. This technology also requires more maintenance, but repair times are shorter than in underground solutions. Combining underground HVDC and overhead HVAC (**T2**) increases the grid's reliability because underground cables are less vulnerable to accidents. Repair times to underground cables are usually longer and higher costs may restrict their use in most remote areas. Also, transmission expansion and overall grid development, particularly overhead lines are subject to issues of public acceptance and acceptability as well as possible conflicts from countries who are not willing to undertake the costs of grid expansion if the benefits of this expansion are clearly reflected in their own territory.

IS1 and IS2 international strategy options maintain energy dependency from the East (currently main energy import origin) and vulnerability to geopolitical tensions in neighbouring countries. **IS2** Desertec based strategy has experienced a fading interest from investors and alternative origins for energy import – namely the Baltic States – should be identified and enabled.

Table 17 summarises the assessment and proposed planning and management guidelines to address the issues identified by the assessment for CDF2.

Table 17 - Summary of the assessment and Guidelines related to opportunities - CDF2 Energy Security and Technologies

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
ENERGY EFFICIENCY	G1, G3	(+) More efficient generation units and more competitive RES vs. fossil fuels in electricity generation, promoting low-carbon energy; (+) Promotion of a low-carbon economy and contribution to RES incorporation goals.	Provide extensive cost-benefit analysis with environmental valuation when planning new large scale RES and compare its viability with decentralized solutions, in order to support the business case for TSOs; Promote CHP facilities as a means to making energy generation more carbon-efficient.
	G2	(+) Reduced energy losses in the transmission grid; (+) Promotes more efficient use of energy resources by local communities; (+) Capture and re-use of locally generated heat, through CHP plants.	
	G3	(+) Promotes more efficient waste and biomass management; (+) Promotes DHC from RES might also result in additional CO2 reduction.	Expansion of energy from waste schemes should go hand-in-hand with measures to ensure optimal conversion efficiency through investment in advanced energy recovery technologies.
	G6	(+) Promote local thermal autoproduction - more efficient; (+) Mitigate energy losses in transmission, in case a centralized RES strategy is adopted.	
	S1, S2	(+) PHS has very high electrical efficiency (80%) and CAES has medium to very high (50% - 70%), thus reducing storage energy losses.	Develop wind powered PHS in order to increase efficiency. Develop PHS capacity in the most profitable areas: Alps, Norway, Iberian Peninsula; Promote the development of adiabatic CAES, more efficient than diabatic and still in early development stages; Invest in long life time CAES solutions.
	S3	(+) Create positive trade-offs between storage efficiency, transmission losses and overall system reliability; (+) GHG reduction through the promotion of EV. (+) Decentralised storage enables DSM, allowing consumers to shift consumption from peak-hours and the adoption of energy efficient behaviours.	Deploy decentralised storage solutions where transmission costs / energy losses from large-scale storage may threaten access to the grid; Develop and implement smart grids and facilitate load management options.

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	T1, T2	(+) HVDC allows efficient long-distance bulk power delivery enhancing transmission capacity; (+) Using FACTS increases the efficiency of the electric system possibly reducing the need for new AC lines/cabling.	Use innovative technologies and optimise the existing grid by extending the lifetime of assets and by using the existing grid to its full potential.
	T2	(+) Conductor size in underground cables is larger than corresponding overhead line, thus reducing transmission losses even further.	
	G3	(-) Existing fossil fuel plants making become less efficient working in under-optimal conditions.	Develop assertive decommissioning plans and compare risk/benefit profiles of options in terms of private and public services' total economic value.
	G1	(-) May not be the most cost-efficient solution to provide for all European regions, namely for current energy islands, due to high investment in storage and transmission.	Combine large-scale and decentralised, smaller-scale generation and storage solutions to reduce vulnerabilities.
	G2, G9	(-) Compromises generation efficiency and productivity; (-) Threatens RES competitiveness against fossil fuels.	
	G4, G5	(-) Fossil fuels as a dominant energy source against macro-policy unless CCS is in place; (-) Inhibit more efficient use of RES capacities within Europe; (-) Need to transport primary fuels demanding additional resource consumption.	Ensure CCS TRL and flexibility is compatible with the strategy's implementation; Ensure this strategy is accompanied by the development and deployment of carbon-efficient generation technologies and processes; Significant levels of RES must be in the energy mix to reduce GHG emissions; Resources used in the transportation of raw fuels must be accounted for as well as future trends and political will concerning nuclear decommission when estimating additional capacity; Consider a stress test scenario of zero fossil and nuclear fuel subsidies (direct or indirect) and analyse the viability and sustainability (including financial and political) of

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
			maintaining this grid profile with small scale RES.
	G6	(-) CCS full deployment might demote technological development of energy efficient solutions / processes for emitting activities, encouraging deeper 'lock in' to a fossil-reliant development; (-) Threatened by current nuclear decommissioning trend.	Use resource efficiency as a benchmark; Reflect resource consumption into final energy prices to promote resource-efficient production; Refurbish existing plants and refine the enrichment processes in existing nuclear plants.
	G9	(-) Does not require investment in pan-European grid and might result in inefficient use of existing grid; (-) Against EU macro-policy favouring the strengthening of regional networks.	
	S2, S3	(-) May be less viable as part of a mixed generation portfolio based energy system, where CCS is used in conjunction with thermal generation.	Consider multiple uses for these sites, considering the different life times, TRL, overall improvement of the energy system and benefits for local communities of the different solutions (CAES/CCS). This way the necessary investment may be optimized.
	S3	(-) Increasing system complexity may result in significant inefficiency.	Promote the technological development of electrical efficiency in small-scale storage solutions.
	T1, T2	(-) HVAC has higher energy losses and limits line length when compared to HVDC; (-) Overhead lines constrain HVDC's potential due to physical limits (weight, materials, and line's exposure to natural elements).	Preform an extensive cost-benefit analysis, accounting for public, environmental and social risks and benefits, to assess the trade-offs between energy losses, the cost of new lines / cabling, wellbeing and the access to cheaper energy for consumers;
	T2	(-) Infrastructure costs may risk overall monetary efficiency of energy system.	Include the computation of losses as one of the design parameters of power transmission systems; Promote R&D to develop superconductive conductors' technology to drastically reduce AC losses.
INNOVATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT	G1	(+) Promotes technological development of large-scale and centralized technologies which may drive down RES costs.	Promote technologies with low TRL and Key Enabling Technologies (KET) to keep future options open.
	G2	(+) Promote investment in smart and microgrids and other technologies related to local generation and energy	Account for the public goods and services not properly captured by the financial statements in order to estimate the

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
		efficiency.	opportunity cost of R&D in the development of promising technological breakthroughs – as a way of gathering public acceptance and support to R&D.
	G3	(+) Promotes investment in RES-related technologies, both large and small scale, such as storage, smart grids, next generation biofuels, electric-vehicles, CSP, ocean and wind energy, DHC, etc.; (+) In line with increasing R&D investment in sustainable energies.	
	G4	(+) Promotes CCS, next generation nuclear and flexible gas technological development. CCS development may be combined with biomass fuels contributing to CO ₂ reduction.	
	S2	(+) Promotes technological development of more efficient adiabatic CAES.	
	S3	(+) Promotes technological development of innovative storage solutions such as EV or H ₂ /synthetic natural gas, as well as smart grids.	
	T1,T2	(+) Promotes the technological development of HVDC components.	Promote R&D to develop HVDC components technology.
	G1	(-) Inhibits investment in decentralised generation technologies.	Develop decentralised, smaller-scale generation and storage solutions where these might have higher economic rational: Account for the public goods and services not properly captured by the financial statements in order to estimate the opportunity cost of R&D in the development of promising technological breakthroughs – as a way of gathering public acceptance and support to R&D.
	G2	(-) Inhibit investment in centralised generation technologies such as next generation windmills and CSP.	
	G3	(-) Inhibit the development of innovative tech. <u>not</u> related to RES, which may have advantages for specific highly concentrated urban and industrial settings.	

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
INNOVATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT	G4	(-) Demotes RES-related innovative technological development; (-) Promotes emerging technologies highly deleterious for the biophysical and social environment.	Provide extensive cost-benefit analysis with environmental valuation when planning non-conventional fossil fuel sources and compare its viability with RES, in order to support the business case and provide extensive political.
	G5	(-) Inhibit CCS and nuclear energy related technological development.	Promote CCS as a production factor opposed to being an imposed technological cost for CO ₂ mitigation (e.g. Biomass with CCS or production of synthetic gas).
	G6	(-) Depends on CCS maturity; (-) Threatened by R&D funding cuts to nuclear energy.	Assess if CCS TRL and investment return rate is compatible with the strategy's implementation; Promote and incentivize the development of efficient technologies and processes to effectively reduce carbon emissions instead of offsetting them; Mobilize private funding for nuclear R&D.
	S1	(-) Limits future options by inhibiting technological development of other large-scale storage technologies.	Consider and enable alternative, multi-scale storage technologies depending on its adequacy to local conditions and storage needs, considering the economic rational of investment;
	S1, S2	(-) Demotes the development of decentralized storage technologies and its massive deployment (e.g. EV) as of smart and microgrids, as well as breakthroughs in battery technology, which still has environmental impact issues.	Anticipate phase-out and recycling costs of battery energy storage systems considering social and environmental costs and benefits; Invest in the development of less environmentally harmful battery technologies.
ENERGY SECURITY	G1, G3	(+) Promote Europe's RES potential, reducing energy dependence from abroad.	Consider worst-case scenario regarding European RES full potential and assess the viability of market-based options for importing 'foreign' RES.
	G2	(+) Improve the energy system's robustness; (+) Improves system flexibility for generation to match local demand patterns for electricity and heat.	
	G4	(+) Reduce energy islands without substantial transmission investment.	
	G6	(+) Reduces vulnerability to RES intermittence increasing	Provide extensive cost-benefit analysis with environmental

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
		the reliability of supply.	valuation when planning fossil and nuclear fuel sources and compare its viability with RES, in order to support the business case and provide extensive political and social acceptance.
	G7, G8	(+) In line with macro-policy objectives of strengthening the regional network in North-South flow directions (EIP 2020).	
	G9	(+) Reduced vulnerability to neighbours' political instability.	
	S1, S2	(+) PHS is a readily available storage technology; (+) Large-scale storage allows efficient management of the energy system increasing its reliability.	
	S2	(+) Using CAES (in addition to PHS) increases Europe's large-scale storage capacity.	
	S3	(+) Creates redundant, reliable backup systems, making the energy system less vulnerable; (+) Modular systems are viable alternatives for energy islands where large-scale storage or transmission infrastructure are not viable; (+) Batteries are able to increase system's reliability while providing additional storage capacity.	Provide cost-benefit analysis with environmental valuation when planning storage solutions in order to support the business case for investors.
	T2	(+) Supply disruptions are less frequent than in overhead lines and the reliability of submarine cables is very high.	
	G1	(-) Depends on the realisation of large-scale storage; (-) Centralized generation as single option against EU macro-policies; (-) Increased vulnerability to energy outages of regions that depend on pan-European grid, hence, energy islands might remain.	Combine large-scale and decentralised, smaller-scale generation and storage solutions to reduce vulnerabilities.
	G2	(-) Threatens the system's integrity and management possibly requiring higher investment to guarantee	Engage local stakeholders to develop innovative generation

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
		system's security and resilience; (-) Aggravated local energy security vulnerabilities.	solutions, especially where RES are not very productive; Define risk/benefit profiles for decentralized RES solutions and monitor their performance against RES benchmarks.
	G3	(-) Increased vulnerability to power outages.	Adequately distributed and connected storage is necessary to cope with RES intermittence; Engage local stakeholders to develop innovative generation solutions, especially where RES are not very productive.
	G4, G9	(-) Increasing energy import dependency.	Ensure that a high percentage of RES is kept in energy mix to reduce energy import dependency to a minimum; Provide extensive cost-benefit analysis with environmental valuation when planning non-conventional fossil fuel sources (e.g., shale gas, tar sands, frozen methane) and compare its viability with RES, in order to support the business case and provide extensive political and social acceptance.
ENERGY SECURITY	G5	(-) Threaten overall reliability of supply, especially in regions where RES is not productive.	Consider a stress test scenario of zero fossil and nuclear fuel import and analyse the viability and sustainability (including financial and political indicators) of maintaining this grid profile without inbound RES.
	G6	(-) Gas as main energy source in regions with high import dependency for gas might constitute a risk to energy security; (-) Increased vulnerability to power outages in Southwest Europe; (-) Threatened by severe difficulties in covering the cost of conventional thermal generation and discouragement for the building of new thermal power capacities.	Consider regional vulnerability to climatic events and endogenous fuel resources when distributing energy mix and capacity per fuel type / energy source.
	G7	(-) Likely to create major imbalances, and possible tensions, in terms of energy provision, capacity and demand within regions in Europe; (-) Central Europe is left dependent on regional energy imports, although it may access cheaper energy.	Keep a share of backup / reserve capacity in the regions where high levels of imbalance are expected; Develop and implement smart grids as a way of mitigating regional imbalances; Consider a stress test scenario of zero energy imports and

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
			analyse the viability and sustainability (including financial and political indicators) of maintaining this grid profile without the very high flows from south and north to central Europe; Develop and implement smart grids as a way of mitigating regional imbalances.
	S1, S2	(-) Threatened by limited availability of adequate PHS (S1) and CAES (S2) locations, high investment costs and long lead times reducing the capacity of EU to create additional storage capacity; (-) Discourage small producers and local generation; (-) Energy system dependent on MS that provide high levels of storage - energy islands might remain.	Implement SEA to identify areas/sites that are sufficiently robust to accommodate PHS/CAES and those where the environment is sensitive and should be avoided, before the project level; Mix centralised and decentralised storage and enable load management (including DSM) technologies to reduce overall energy consumption and enable decentralise generation.
	S3	(-) Rare materials used in some batteries don't exist in Europe, aggravating the energy system's dependence from imports; (-) Decentralised system vulnerable to management issues.	Develop a robust architecture and management/control scheme for storage (standardizing the interfaces between storage and other grid elements, protocols for data exchange and control rules and industry and safety standards).
ENERGY SECURITY	T1, T2	(-) NIMBY effect might threaten transmission expansion; (-) Repair times to underground cables are usually longer; (-) Depends on the TRL for HVDC components; (-) Higher costs of underground and submarine cables may restrict their use in most remote areas, possibly resulting in the maintenance of exiting energy islands.	Engage MS and relevant stakeholders at regional and national levels to raise awareness to the advantages of a pan-European grid, reducing possible NIMBY effect; Perform an extensive cost-benefit analysis, accounting for public, environmental and social risks and benefits, to assess the trade-offs between energy losses, the cost of new lines / cabling, wellbeing and the access to cheaper energy for consumers; Assess if HVDC components' TRL and investment return rate is compatible with the strategy's implementation.
	IS1, IS2	(-) Maintenance of energy dependency from the East and vulnerability to geopolitical tensions in neighbouring countries.	Identify and develop alternative origins for energy import – namely the Baltic states.
	IS2	(-) Strategy threatened by Desertec Industrial Initiative's	

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+ Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
		low interest in exporting solar power from North Africa to Europe.	

iv. Monitoring Guidelines

Table 18 identifies the relevant issues that should be monitored, considering the opportunities and risks described above for CDF2. These monitoring guidelines aim to inform a more extensive periodical follow-up program for e-Highway2050's implementation.

Table 18 - Monitoring guidelines and indicators for follow-up - CDF2 Energy Security and Technologies

Monitoring Guidelines	Monitoring Indicators
Monitor the resource-efficiency per energy source, namely in the industrial and residential sectors.	Ecoefficiency Index; Carbon and water footprint per energy source; Mitigation, replacement and/or repair costs ²⁸ ; Profile of Energy intensity (MW/GDP); Water intensity (m3/GDP); Material intensity (Direct Material Input[DMI]/GDP) at regional and national level ²⁹ ; Impact on the economic welfare of CHP (fuel, biomass) and DHC on households.
Monitor the return of investment and needs for further investment (public and private) in KET.	Patents derived from KET; TRL time lag and R&D investment intensity; Long term 'Extended CBA' analysis ³⁰ .
Monitor the energy savings regarding the relation between primary and final energy consumption.	Energy Matching Sankey diagrams.
Monitor the economic and social efficiency of energy generation, storage and transmission.	Plot GDP vs GHG per energy source, GDP vs Water Use per energy source.
Monitor the impact of CCS technology.	Number of CCS projects deployed, changes in emissions patterns with CCS ³¹ .
Monitor energy import dependence and vulnerability, at country and regional level.	Risk profile per energy import source ³² .
Monitor the grid's efficiency, security and stability.	Storage capacity delivered by EV; Smart metering market penetration and household implementation;

²⁸ Other possible indicators: waste and pollution generation per energy source; resource crunch effects on the demand for complex materials.

²⁹ Other possible indicators; Account for energy intensity per Net Value Added (NVA) per industrial sector.

³⁰ Other possible indicators: Total Economic Valuation (TEV) of the (public, shared and private) goods and services per energy generation, storage and transmission technology.

³¹ Other possible indicators: Plot CCS effectiveness vs resource efficiency (To make sure that CCS won't facilitate the inefficient use of resources like coal and biomass, that have many other impacts in terms of waste and pollution generation other than GHG).

³² Other possible indicators: long term 'Extended CBA' analysis evolution; TEV of the (public, shared and private) goods and services per energy generation, storage and transmission technology.

	Efficiency (intermittency vs stability) of wind and hydro generation combined with storage technologies (like CAES, pumped hydro, power to gas) ³³ .
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v. Governance Guidelines

Table 19 proposes governance guidelines that seek to ensure cooperation and sharing of responsibility among relevant stakeholders in grid development.

Table 19 - Governance Framework for follow-up - CDF2 Energy Security and Technologies

Organization	Governance Guidelines
DG Energy	Promote cooperation among all European TSOs in order to coordinate the construction of the pan-European grid; Increase consumer awareness regarding DSM, load management and energy efficiency; Achieve the conditions for all necessary cooperation between the energy markets in electricity and gas, including use of infrastructure for the development of alternative storage technologies; Develop collective approaches to contracting and managing decentralized energy facilities that may enable small and medium enterprises (SMEs) as well as larger companies to benefit from decentralized energy systems; Market functioning and governance arrangements must insure that those countries that depend on neighbours' capacity are not left in a vulnerable position in terms of energy security.
DG Research & Innovation	Foster the creation of strategic alliances and exploit synergies between stakeholders involved in R&D and demonstration projects (including MS) as to reach market competitiveness.
DG Competition European Competition Authorities	Promote cooperation among all European TSOs in order to coordinate the construction of the pan-European grid; Create strategic alliances and exploit synergies between stakeholders involved in R&D and demonstration projects (including MS) as to reach market competitiveness; Develop collective approaches to contracting and managing decentralized energy facilities that may enable SMEs as well as larger companies to benefit from decentralized energy systems; Market functioning and governance arrangements must insure that those countries that depend on neighbours' capacity are not left in a vulnerable position in terms of energy security.
DG Consumers National and Regional Consumer's associations	Increase consumer awareness regarding DSM, load management and energy efficiency.
DG Energy	Ensure CCS deployment does not inhibit technological development towards a more carbon-efficient energy sector (or other sectors such as industry); Develop cooperation and energy treaties with multiple neighbouring countries avoiding

³³ Other: outage probability per generation, storage and transmission technology.

Organization	Governance Guidelines
	over-concentrated energy import origins and vulnerability in terms of energy dependence from abroad.
DG Climate Action	Ensure CCS deployment does not inhibit technological development towards a more carbon-efficient energy sector (or other sectors such as industry); Achieve the conditions for all necessary cooperation between the energy markets in electricity and gas, including use of infrastructure for the development of alternative storage technologies.
EEA	Increase consumer awareness regarding DSM, load management and energy efficiency; Account for the public goods and services not properly captured by financial statements in order to estimate the opportunity cost of R&D in the development of promising technological breakthroughs – as a way of gathering public acceptance and also support to R&D.
OECD	Use resource-efficiency as a benchmark for economic productivity.
European Nuclear Safety Regulator Group	Promote /engage in cooperation for nuclear safety.
ENTSO-E	Promote cooperation among all European TSOs in order to coordinate the construction of the pan-European grid; Establish a Grid Code for the pan-European Overlay Grid to improve the interoperability of different individual projects and technologies of different manufacturers; Create strategic alliances and exploit synergies between stakeholders involved in R&D and demonstration projects (including MS) as to reach market competitiveness; Invest in research and pilot / demonstration projects on Biomass with CCS to better understand regional potential, drivers and obstacles to developing this technology with negative emissions potential; Develop collective approaches to contracting and managing decentralized energy facilities that may enable SMEs as well as larger companies to benefit from decentralized energy systems; Promote the collaboration between business and government to bring public opinion behind decentralized energy is essential to achieve scale up to an effective level of operations; Market functioning and governance arrangements must insure that those countries that depend on neighbours' capacity are not left in a vulnerable position in terms of energy security;
ACER	Promote cooperation among all European TSOs in order to coordinate the construction of the pan-European grid; Develop cooperation and energy treaties with multiple neighbouring countries avoiding over-concentrated energy import origins and vulnerability in terms of energy dependence from abroad.
European Technology Platforms	Cooperate on the establishment of a Grid Code for the pan-European Overlay Grid to improve the interoperability of different individual projects and technologies of different manufacturers; Create strategic alliances and exploit synergies between stakeholders involved in R&D and demonstration projects (including MS) as to reach market competitiveness; Invest in research and pilot / demonstration projects on Biomass with CCS to better understand regional potential, drivers and obstacles to developing this technology with

Organization	Governance Guidelines
	negative emissions potential.
MS	<p>Account for the public goods and services not properly captured by financial statements in order to estimate the opportunity cost of R&D in the development of promising technological breakthroughs – as a way of gathering public acceptance and also support to R&D;</p> <p>Develop clear connection requirements to enable large share of decentralized investment;</p> <p>Insure that those countries that depend on neighbours’ capacity are not left in a vulnerable position in terms of energy security;</p> <p>Use resource-efficiency as a benchmark for economic productivity;</p> <p>Invest in research and pilot / demonstration projects on Biomass with CCS to better understand regional potential, drivers and obstacles to developing this technology with negative emissions potential.</p>
Regulators	<p>Create strategic alliances and exploit synergies between stakeholders involved in R&D and demonstration projects (including MS) as to reach market competitiveness;</p> <p>Target research and development to storage technologies with a potential for low raw-material cost and low-cost mass production techniques [4];</p> <p>Invest in research and pilot / demonstration projects on Biomass with CCS to better understand regional potential, drivers and obstacles to developing this technology with negative emissions potential;</p> <p>Achieve the conditions for all necessary cooperation between the energy markets in electricity and gas, including use of infrastructure for the development of alternative storage technologies;</p> <p>Develop cooperation and energy treaties with multiple neighbouring countries avoiding over-concentrated energy import origins and vulnerability in terms of energy dependence from abroad;</p> <p>Develop clear connection requirements to enable large share of decentralized investment;</p> <p>Market functioning and governance arrangements must insure that those countries that depend on neighbours’ capacity are not left in a vulnerable position in terms of energy security;</p> <p>Review Inter-TSO Compensation mechanism making it able to cover also investment costs, in order to allow the local TSOs of the crossed countries to retrieve money in proportion to the usage of the local networks.</p>
Regional Energy NGOs	Achieve the conditions for all necessary cooperation between the energy markets in electricity and gas, including use of infrastructure for the development of alternative storage technologies.
DSOs	Develop collective approaches to contracting and managing decentralized energy facilities that may enable SMEs as well as larger companies to benefit from decentralized energy systems.
Grid investors (including TSOs)	Account for the public goods and services not properly captured by financial statements in order to estimate the opportunity cost of R&D in the development of promising technological breakthroughs – as a way of gathering public acceptance and also support to R&D.
Research institutions and companies carrying out R&D Banks and	Target research and development to storage technologies with a potential for low raw-material cost and low-cost mass production techniques [4].

Organization	Governance Guidelines
Funds	
NGOs Civil Society	Use resource-efficiency as a benchmark for economic productivity; Promote the collaboration between business and government to bring public opinion behind decentralized energy; Increase consumer awareness regarding DSM, load management and energy efficiency.

CDF 3 - Geo-Political Economy and regional equity

CDF3 - "Geo-Political Economy and regional equity" focuses on **European competitiveness** in its geo-political environment considering energy, balanced by the need to ensure **regional equity** within European MS concerning sources of energy, **market accessibility** and distributional equity, and **implications for national/local economies and development options**.

i. Critical trends

CDF3 has the following critical trends (detailed in Annex 2):

- **Expansion of the Energy Community**, connecting EU MS and neighbouring countries;
- Increase in the number of MS using **renewable energy policy support measures**;
- **Feed-in tariffs** may decrease in the future;
- Attempts to **increase equal access to funding** for structural investments across Europe;
- **Increasing harmonisation** of the European energy market through market coupling and from the price coupling of regions initiative.

Each critical trend is driven by key internal and external driving forces (drivers) that explain the extent to which the trends are aligned with EU macro-policies, objectives and targets. Table 20 illustrates the relationship between these drivers and macro-policies. Table 21 provides a SWOT analysis in relation to the trend analysis and macro-policy alignment.

Table 20 - Critical trends and respective drivers CDF3 - Geo-Political Economy and regional equity

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
Energy security; Demand for affordable energy; Foreign policy.	<p>Expansion of the Energy Community, connecting EU MS and neighbouring countries.</p> <hr/> <p>European Energy trade flow agreements exist with North Africa, the Middle East and Russia.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expand and diversify links between the European network and neighbouring countries (focus on North Africa), address import of electricity and achieve a level playing field on market and carbon regulation (Energy Roadmap 2050); - Secure energy and promote free and transparent energy markets (EU EP, 2011); - Build up the external dimension of EU internal energy market (ENP, 2006); - Achieve EU-Africa 2020 energy targets of reliable and secure supply of energy and increased access to sustainable energy (EIP 2020; EU EP; Renewable Energy, 2012); - Viability and continuous functioning of the existing oil and gas infrastructure in the East (EU EP, 2011); - Negotiate EU-level agreements with third countries to facilitate large-scale infrastructure projects (EU EP, 2011); - Ensure the consistency and mutual reinforcement of EU external energy policy with other EU external activities (Energy Roadmap 2050).
Green certificates; Feed-in tariffs.	<p>MS aiming to increase electricity generated by renewable energy sources.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop existing and new dialogues with major energy suppliers to include renewable energy and liquefied natural gas (EU EP, 2011).
Stabilising the renewable energy market.	<p>Increase in the number of MS using renewable energy policy support measures.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain cost-effective, well-targeted public and private support schemes (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; RLCE2050, 2011).
Decrease in costs of renewable technologies and fears on EU competitiveness; Economic and technological maturity.	<p>Feed-in tariffs may decrease in the future.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop free and transparent energy markets (EU EP, 2011); - Create a more stable environment for economic activity (ENP, 2006); - Promote a market driven energy technology sector and the faster market roll-out of sustainable energy technologies (SET-PLAN, 2007; ETI, 2013; Renewable Energy, 2012).
EU European Investment Bank (EU-EIB) Project Bond Initiative enhancement of project credit quality.	<p>Attempts to increase equal access to funding for structural investments across</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate MS national markets at regional levels, towards the creation of a fully liberalised EU market (Directive 2009/72/EC); - Integrate the Baltic States into the European (EIP 2020, 2010);

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
	Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote a market driven energy technology sector and the faster market roll-out of sustainable energy technologies (SET-PLAN, 2007; ETI, 2013; Renewable Energy, 2012); - Support a future integrated European network CCS (EPI 2020, 2010); - Expose producers to market risks, do not hinder innovation or competition and phase-out inefficient and harmful subsidies (Resource Roadmap, 2011; Energy 2020, 2011; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012); - Avoid internal market fragmentation (Renewable Energy, 2012; Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); - Upgrade energy infrastructure in MS that joined as of 2004 and less developed regions (Energy 2020, 2011); - Restore macro-economic stability and address macro-imbalances (Energy 2020, 2011).
<p>EU Third Energy Package that introduces several directives to increase cross-border energy exchanges;</p> <p>A 2002 EU Council target for all MS to have a level of electricity interconnections of at least 10% of their installed production capacity by 2005;</p> <p>Market Coupling within regions;</p> <p>RED and 2020 Renewable Energy targets.</p>	Increasing harmonisation of the European energy market through coupling.	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>(objectives mentioned above);</i> - Implement a well-functioning carbon pricing and trading system (RCLE2050, 2011); - By 2050, build a pan-European integrated energy market and guarantee security of supply; - Establish appropriate environmental standards for energy markets (Energy 2020, 2011) and promote the use of market based instruments that incentivise sustainable production and consumption (Resource Roadmap, 2011); - Eliminate barriers to trade (Renewable Energy, 2012); - Ensure access to markets for flexible suppliers of all types (including new players and SMEs) and ensure that the market rewards flexibility.
Price Coupling of Regions initiative.	Increasing attempts to harmonise European energy market prices arising from the price coupling of regions initiative.	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>(as per the above).</i>

ii. **SWOT**

Table 21 - SWOT Analysis CDF3 - Geo-Political Economy and regional equity

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Expansion of the Energy Community supporting increased energy system resilience and less acute exposure to external events/volatility;</p> <p>Existence of European energy trade flow agreements with key third party countries (e.g. North Africa, Russia) helping to ensure security of supply and energy policy coordination;</p> <p>EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative helping to support consist access to financing for structural energy system investments across Europe.</p>	<p>Increase in EU energy imports/import dependency;</p> <p>Limited/variable interconnection capacity between MS across Europe (especially Baltic States, the Iberian Peninsula and the UK).</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>Increasing EU energy imports and energy dependency stimulating demand for domestic energy sources (e.g. renewables) and associated electricity transmission and storage infrastructure;</p> <p>Increasing availability of MS renewable energy support measures (e.g. to meet key macro-policies such as Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050) stimulating continued growth in domestic RES generation;</p> <p>Phasing out renewable energy support measures as a means of driving competitiveness;</p> <p>Developing bilateral and multilateral agreements to help secure and lock in third countries to deliver pan-European energy security;</p> <p>Continued roll-out and improvement of market-coupling (harmonisation) schemes across Europe;</p> <p>The need for improved interconnection capacity between MS to facilitate market-coupling, wider exploitation of RES generation, improved energy security etc.</p>	<p>Vulnerability of EU to external events (e.g. unrest in Ukraine and Russian gas supplies to EU MS);</p> <p>Inconsistent distribution of costs and benefits of the energy system across Europe (e.g. if uptake of EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative is inconsistent);</p> <p>Phasing out renewable energy support measures potentially making RES generation less viable;</p> <p>Inconsistent application of renewable energy support measures across Europe distorting energy prices between MS.</p>

iii. Strategic Assessment

Assessment Criterion 1: International competitiveness

A **dominant RES strategy (G3), especially centralised and large-scale (G1)** may enhance the viability of EU energy export potential, facilitating energy export when there is surplus. This could support the development of energy trade agreements with 3rd countries while reducing the vulnerability to external energy price volatility. Also, RES development (both large and small-scale as in **G2**), as well as the development of new storage technology (**S2, S3**), may stimulate the export of ‘home-grown’ RES technologies, further supporting the energy sector’s contribution to international trade. These opportunities are likely to further encourage the expansion of the Energy Community in line with objectives from EU macro-policies focusing on the deepening of trade relationships with international partners (Energy Roadmap 2050, ENP and EU EP).

Decentralised and small-scale RES (G2) may discourage international trade initiatives and access to international energy markets. This could work against positive trends in expansion of the Energy Community and the development of European Energy trade flow agreements. Options for international energy trade must be considered in grid planning through the use of energy system aggregators in case of decentralised RES based generation.

A **RES non-dominant strategy (G4, G5 and G6)** is inherently vulnerable to external market and political volatility due to energy import reliance (e.g. Russian gas and uranium). It also poses a risk for international competitiveness through its inherent need to maintain and develop existing international energy trade links and initiatives to ensure sufficient supplies of fossil and nuclear fuel, which leaves Europe in a fragile negotiating position.

The ability to transmit **high energy flows across Europe (G7, G8)**, which relates to centralized generation and storage strategies (**G1, S1, S2**) including cross-border capacity and ability to manage regional imbalances, may support greater electricity market integration, both internally and externally. This opportunity is supported particularly by the EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative, and its role in helping to support consistent access to financing for structural energy system investments across Europe, and increasing availability of MS renewable energy support measures (e.g. Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050) stimulating continued growth in domestic RES generation.

There is a concern that HVDC grid connections (**T1, T2**) may not be compatible with North African infrastructure (e.g. if **import from North Africa is relevant (IS2)**). To avoid this risk at the planning stage it is important to work closely with North African partners to ensure that grid connections are compatible. Equally, existing European energy trade flow agreements with North Africa combined with the influence of key EU macro-policies that support the development of international partnerships, e.g. .Energy Roadmap 2050) should help address practical issues of infrastructure compatibility early on in planning.

To note however that **relevant import from North Africa (IS2)** strategy is vulnerable to external market and political volatility due to energy import reliance. Conversely, the

expansion of EU energy markets may support greater opportunities for international energy trade.

Assessment Criterion 2: Market dynamics and regional equity

Current trends indicate that MS are aiming to increase the portion of RES-E; there is an increase in the number of MS using renewable energy policy support measures and there are on-going attempts to increase equal access to funding for structural investments across the EU. However, there is a risk of MS withdrawing RES support schemes which would delay energy strategy implementation in a **RES-dominant energy system (G3)**. Also, a **centralised and large scale RES (G1)** strategy may affect equitable distribution of energy system costs and benefits and create regional tensions. Poor access to finance (e.g. heterogeneity and uncertainty of MS support schemes, poor uptake of Project Bond Initiative) may constrain energy system development and risks may not be evenly distributed (e.g. variation in MS credit scores), potentially resulting in electricity price differentials and regional equity/cohesion impacts. This goes against EU macro-policy objectives that promote a market driven sustainable energy technology sector and seek to support greater convergence and transparency in the market (e.g. Energy 2020, EU EP).

A **decentralised and small-scale RES (G2)** strategy may not be viable in all locations/contexts and, due to the limited emphasis on transmission between macro regions, some regions may become isolated from the energy market. This could lead to electricity price differentials across the EU, affecting regional equity and cohesion. This goes against key positive trends of increasing harmonisation of the EU energy market and EU macro-policies objectives to create a fully liberalised EU market and an integrated European network for CCS. These risks can be reduced by ensuring provision of sufficient transmission and storage capacity to address potential regional imbalances. During implementation, energy system stakeholders are advised to keep electricity market function under review and be prepared to implement grid reinforcements and increase storage capacity where regional imbalances occur.

Having **high to very high energy flows towards Central Europe (G7, G8)** may mean that Central European MS may become more exposed to EU internal energy market fluctuations, potentially affecting their ability to function competitively, in EU and global markets. Grid reinforcements and storage enhancements must be designed to support greater market integration and regional equity. Also, greater regulation of the pan-European electricity market may help manage these issues. These risks could potentially be avoided through greater regulation and management of the pan-European electricity market. On the other hand, **low energy flows (G9)** inhibit market competition and so potentially aggravate market inefficiencies because it implies that regions can meet their own demand. These risks and opportunities could be addressed by ensuring that all key strengths and weaknesses of a decentralised generation system are fully taken into account in energy system planning and ensuring that the adequacy of the energy system is checked and validated thoroughly during planning processes.

There may be difficulty finding sites for centralised storage (**S1, S2**) for additional capacity due to the required physiographic conditions and conflicts with other energy infrastructure requirements as CAES (**S2**) requires similar site conditions to CCS. This may

affect the viability of the energy system. Under **S1**, the reliance on Central Europe (e.g. Alps) and Northern Europe (e.g. Norway) may affect the regional equity of the energy system. This risk is particularly important as real estate values may diminish within areas affected by new strategic storage infrastructure projects. **Mixed-scale storage (S3)** is less exposed due to the range of storage considered and contributes to a more even distribution of storage infrastructure costs and benefits.

Overhead transmission (T1) poses a risk as the strategy's focus on overhead HVAC transmission infrastructure, including for pan-European connections, may adversely affect real estate values. The efficiency of pan-European transmission via **HVDC (T1, T2)** may contribute to lower energy costs and support consistent energy pricing across Europe. Furthermore, the potential for significant use of **underground and submarine HVDC in T2** should minimise the impacts on real estate values within areas affected by new transmission infrastructure. On the other hand, the high start-up and maintenance costs of underground and submarine HVDC may contribute to higher energy costs and potentially less consistent energy pricing across Europe, depending on maintenance responsibility distribution.

There is also a potential risk of real estate values (land and property) diminishing within areas affected by new strategic energy infrastructure projects, conditioning development options in the regions and MS where the projects are deployed – this may be a particular concern where values are heavily influenced by landscape (e.g. infrastructure affecting tourism hotspots).

Table 22 summarises the assessment and proposed planning and management guidelines to address the issues identified by the assessment for CDF3.

Table 22 - Summary of the assessment and Guidelines related to opportunities - CDF3 Geo-political economy and regional equity

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS	G1, G2	(+) Viability of EU energy export and import potential and development of energy trade agreements with 3 rd countries; (+) Contribution to EU international energy and technology trade; (+) Support the expansion of the Energy Community.	Consider options for international energy trade through the use of energy system aggregators.
	G4	(+) Support and promote wider international trade links and initiatives.	Ensure that strategic grid infrastructure is planned and designed to facilitate international energy trade where relevant.
	G3	(+) Contribution to EU international energy and technology trade.	
	G7, G8	(+) Support greater electricity market integration.	Ensure that price/market coupling projects and agreements are developed in conjunction with energy system infrastructure improvements; Consider introduction of additional energy market tax and incentive mechanisms to protect and promote market integration and regional equity.
	S2, S3	(+) Contribution to EU international trade, exporting CAES technology (S2) and other demand driven storage technologies (S3).	
	IS2	(+) Expansion of EU energy markets and greater opportunities for international energy trade.	
	G4, G5, G6, IS2	(-) Vulnerable to external market and political volatility; (-) Dependence on external fossil and nuclear fuel leaves Europe in a fragile negotiating position.	
	G2	(-) Discourages international trade initiatives and access to international energy markets.	
	T1, T2	(-) HVDC grid connections may not be compatible with North African infrastructure.	Work with North African partners to ensure that grid connections are compatible.

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
MARKET DYNAMICS AND REGIONAL EQUITY	S3	(+) Even distribution of storage infrastructure costs and benefits.	
	T2	(+) Efficient pan-European transmission via underground HVDC may contribute to low energy costs and consistent energy pricing across EU.	
		(+) Minimal impacts on real estate values within areas affected by new strategic transmission infrastructure projects.	
		(+) Ability to transmit high flows, including cross-border capacity and ability to manage regional imbalances, may support greater electricity market integration.	
	G1, G2, G3, G4, G5, G6, S1, T1, IS2	(-) May affect equitable distribution of energy system costs and benefits; (-) Poor access to finance may constrain energy system development resulting in electricity price differentials and regional equity impacts; (-) Real estate values may diminish within areas affected by new infrastructure.	Engage with stakeholders, the public and affected communities early-on to ensure that strategic energy infrastructure projects are located away from areas where real estate values are particularly influenced by landscape quality; Use spatial planning and constraints analysis to steer strategic energy infrastructure projects away from areas where real estate values are particularly influenced by landscape quality.
	G2	(-) May not be viable in all locations/situations [10], resulting in electricity price differentials across the EU.	Provide sufficient transmission and storage capacity to address potential regional imbalances.
	G3	(-) Withdrawal of MS RES support schemes may delay or threaten implementation.	
	G7, G8	(-) Less market integration and regional equity; (-) Central Europe exposed to EU internal energy market fluctuations.	Ensure that grid reinforcements and storage enhancements are designed to support greater market integration and regional equity.
MARKET DYNAMICS AND REGIONAL EQUITY (CONT.)	G9	(-) Reduced energy market competition and greater market inefficiency.	Ensure that all key strengths and weaknesses of a decentralised generation system are fully taken into account in energy system planning; Ensure that the adequacy of the energy system is checked and validated thoroughly during planning processes.

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+ Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	S1, S2	(-) Difficulty of finding sites where additional capacity can be installed threatening the whole energy system.	Consider and enable alternative, multi-scale storage technologies depending on its adequacy to local conditions and storage needs, considering the economic rational of investment.
	S1	(-) Reliance on Central Europe and Northern Europe affecting regional/distributional equity.	
	T2	(-) High start-up and maintenance costs of underground and submarine HVDC may contribute to high energy costs and less consistent energy pricing across Europe.	

iv. Monitoring Guidelines

Table 23 identifies the relevant issues that should be monitored, considering the opportunities and risks described above for CDF3. These monitoring guidelines aim to inform a more extensive periodic follow-up program for e-Highway2050's implementation.

Table 23 - Monitoring guidelines and indicators for follow-up - CDF3 Geo-political economy and regional equity

Monitoring Guidelines	Monitoring Indicators
Monitor levels of EU and MS level energy independence	Energy import dependency (EU and MS levels); EU energy import-export ration.
Monitor MS support for RES generation	Renewable electricity Feed-in Tariffs in the EU.
Monitor EU internal market dynamics	EU internal energy flows; Electricity prices (by MS); Energy import dependency (at the MS level).
Monitor uptake of finance for energy infrastructure development.	Uptake of EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative for energy infrastructure projects (at the MS level); MS credit ratings.
Monitor the effect of strategic energy infrastructure development on real estate values.	Land and property values within areas affected by strategic energy infrastructure projects; Land and property values within areas of key landscape quality affected by strategic energy infrastructure projects.
Monitor international energy trade.	Joint energy agreements; European energy trade flow agreements with third party countries.
Monitor EU vulnerability to external energy supply chain shocks.	Energy import dependency (EU level); European energy trade flow agreements with third party countries; Energy prices on global markets (gas, oil, nuclear fuel); EU fuel reserves.
Monitor regional equity of the energy system.	Scale and location of generation, storage and transmission infrastructure.

v. Governance Guidelines

Table 24 proposes governance guidelines. These guidelines try to ensure cooperation and sharing of responsibility among relevant stakeholders in grid development.

Table 24 - Governance Framework for follow-up - CDF3 Geo-political economy and regional equity

Organization	Governance Guidelines
International Associations (Energy Community) and third party countries	<p>Encourage and facilitate greater levels of third country participation in the Energy Community;</p> <p>Encourage and facilitate bilateral and multilateral agreements between MS with significant generation capacity and third countries;</p> <p>Keep the regional and global geopolitical situation under review to pre-empt supply chain stresses and volatility.</p>
DG Energy	<p>Engage with stakeholders and affected communities to gauge the desirability and acceptability of further exploitation of EU internal fossil fuel resources to reduce the vulnerability of the energy system to external volatility;</p> <p>Promote and support energy sector R&D across all key technologies to accelerate market readiness;</p> <p>Promote the appropriate sustainment and greater harmonisation of MS RES support schemes.</p>
European Parliament	<p>Transparent consideration of the pros and cons of less international trade vs. EU energy self-sufficiency;</p> <p>Explore synergies between energy related trade links and initiatives and other relevant sectors (e.g. finance and technology);</p> <p>Consider introduction of additional energy market tax and incentive mechanisms to protect and promote market integration and regional equity.</p>
Regulators	<p>Where relevant, ensure that energy market design does not discourage or prevent international trade;</p> <p>Ensure that price/market coupling projects and agreements are developed in conjunction with energy system infrastructure improvements;</p> <p>Consider introduction of additional energy market tax and incentive mechanisms to protect and promote market integration and regional equity;</p> <p>Promote the appropriate sustainment and greater harmonisation of MS RES support schemes.</p>
MS	<p>Engage with stakeholders and affected communities to gauge the desirability and acceptability of further exploitation of EU internal fossil fuel resources to reduce the vulnerability of the energy system to external volatility;</p> <p>Keep the regional and global geopolitical situation under review to pre-empt supply chain stresses and volatility;</p> <p>Ensure sufficient fuel reserves to accommodate periods of supply chain stress and volatility;</p> <p>Consider alternative or secondary generation technology options in energy system design;</p> <p>Consider introduction of additional energy market tax and incentive mechanisms to protect and promote market integration and regional equity;</p> <p>Put in place energy system preparedness and resilience measures at the MS level;</p> <p>Assess the economic impact of residual risks of strategic energy infrastructure</p>

Organization	Governance Guidelines
	<p>development on businesses reliant on landscape quality and provide adequate compensation where alternative routes, locations and technologies are not viable;</p> <p>Engage with stakeholders, the public and affected communities early-on to ensure that strategic energy infrastructure projects are located away from areas where real estate values are influenced by landscape quality;</p> <p>Effective use of spatial planning and constraints analysis to steer strategic energy infrastructure projects (including new thermal and nuclear generation capacity) away from areas where real estate values are particularly influenced by landscape quality.</p>
<p>Finance, funds and banks</p>	<p>Promote the EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative, particularly to MS with poor credit ratings.</p>

CDF 4 - European Regional Governance

CDF4 European Regional Governance focuses on the European **governance conditions**, to operationalize the European internal market of electricity distribution and management of the e-Highway2050 concept, including the **harmonization among MS of legislations and regulations and national policies strategic priorities**, as well the responsibilities and competences across the Union for **coordination and management of the electricity European grid, institutional cooperation among MS and engagement of key stakeholders** at European and national level.

i. Critical trends

CDF4 European Regional Governance face the following key trends (detailed in Annex 2):

- High **allocation of support schemes** for coal and oil products;
- Increase of **regional cooperation** between TSOs under the Electricity Regional Initiative (ERI);
- **End of national binding targets** for renewables after 2020, creating a EU level target of 27% to be achieved in 2030;
- **New approach** to the development of EU policy for security of supply;
- Development of **common rules** (network codes) for future energy regional sector;
- **Cooperation mechanisms** insufficiently used, a future challenge for market integration;
- **New mechanisms** to increase the level of transparency, cooperation and participation in energy initiatives (Transparency Platform, Citizen's Energy Dialogue and European Energy Dialogue).

Each critical trend identified is driven by key internal and external forces (driving forces) that give perspective to understand the trends that may (or may not) be aligned with macro-policies' objectives and targets. Table 25 provides the relationship between the drivers responsible for CDF4's key trends and path tendency of alignment with SRF macro-policies environmental and sustainability objectives and targets.

Table 25 - Critical trends and respective drivers CDF4 - European Regional Governance

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
<p>EU policy on imports and external relations with third countries;</p> <p>Large privatization of oil production, transport and storage industries;</p> <p>High costs associated to the development of renewables technologies.</p>	<p>High allocation of support schemes for coal and oil products.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Keep Europe’s presence in domestic oil refining (Energy Roadmap 2050). <p><u>Not aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low carbon sources in 2020 responsible for 2/3 of electricity generation (Energy 2020); - Reduce GHG emissions by at least 20% in 2020 (Energy 2020); - Increase the share of RES in final energy consumption (Europe 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050, RLCE2050); - Accelerate the development of alternative fuels (RLCE2050); - Support the decarbonisation of the European energy market (Europe 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050); - Deliver sustainable alternative fuels to the European energy mix (ETI 2013); - MS-level development of national low carbon roadmaps (RLCE2050).
<p>Intention to create a Pan-European approach for electricity market.</p>	<p>Increase of regional cooperation between TSOs under the ERI.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a Pan-European electricity market (Energy Roadmap 2050, Energy 2020); - Cooperate with key partners to support technological, research and industrial development (EU EP); - Ensure convergence and transparency in national approaches to avoid internal market fragmentation (Renewable Energy 2012, Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050); - Encourage cross-border and trans-national cooperation and development (SET-PLAN 2007); - Ensure coordination of all network codes for the relevant TSOs (Directive 2009/72/EC).
<p>Different energy mixes in MS;</p> <p>Different policy priorities in MS can make joint agreement and the achievement of the expected targets more difficult;</p> <p>Improve complementarity</p>	<p>End of the national binding targets for renewables after 2020, creating a EU level target of 27% to be achieved in 2030.</p>	<p><u>Aligned with:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure convergence and transparency in national approaches to avoid market fragmentation (Renewable Energy 2012, Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050).

Drivers	Critical Trends	SRF Macro-policies
and coherence between MS objectives and instruments.		
Increase of EU vulnerability to fluctuations in energy supply; Differences across EU in energy prices due to MS free choice for national energy mixes.	New approach to the development of EU policy for security of supply.	<u>Aligned with:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prioritize energy storage technologies in future research (Renewable Energy 2012, SET-PLAN 2007); - Deliver competitive solutions to ensure the security of supply (ETI 2013); - Mainstream “energy security, access and sustainability” in EU external financial frameworks (EU EP).
Increase of cooperation between MS and TSOs; Intention to develop an internal energy market.	Development of common rules (network codes) for future energy regional sector.	<u>Aligned with:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elaborate strategies to the development of Trans-European energy networks (SET-PLAN 2007); - Ensure integration of MS national markets to create a fully liberalised EU market (Directive 2009/72/EC); - Ensure convergence and transparency in national approaches to avoid market fragmentation (Renewable Energy 2012, Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050); - Facilitate strategic planning at technology and energy system levels (SET-PLAN 2007); - Encourage cross-border and trans-national cooperation and development (SET-PLAN 2007); - Ensure coordination of all network codes for the relevant TSOs (Directive 2009/72/EC).
Low degree of support schemes for renewables in comparison with fossil fuels; Low flow of information between MS, with some MS maybe having private policies on energy sensitive issues; Low support from the EU for the implementation and use of cooperation mechanisms.	Cooperation mechanisms have not been sufficiently used, considered a challenge for market integration.	<u>Not aligned with:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase use of cooperation mechanisms (Renewable Energy 2012); - Cooperate with key partners to support technological, research and industrial development (EU EP); - Ensure convergence and transparency in national approaches to avoid market fragmentation (Renewable Energy 2012, Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050); - Encourage cross-border and trans-national cooperation and development (SET-PLAN 2007); - Work towards stronger multilevel mechanisms for a global governance (Resource Roadmap 2011); - Promote the increased use of cooperation mechanisms (Renewable Energy 2012).

ii. **SWOT**

Table 26 - SWOT Analysis - CDF4 European Regional Governance

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Existing common rules for the internal market in electricity (generation, transmission, distribution and supply);</p> <p>Electricity Regional Initiative and regional cooperation between TSOs;</p> <p>Development of network codes, and consistency of the common rules with the European energy policy;</p> <p>RED cooperation mechanisms for intra-European cooperation;</p> <p>Recognition of the role of civil society in participating in the European energy policy process (e.g. promotion of the European Energy Dialogue);</p> <p>All MS with 2020 GHG and RES fixed targets.</p>	<p>MS differences in the specifications of internal energy systems and policy instruments;</p> <p>Low rate of application of RED cooperation mechanisms;</p> <p>Considerable infringements in the transposition in energy policies by MS;</p> <p>High level of support schemes for fossil fuels.</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>Kyoto Protocol (KP) and Effort Sharing Decision (ESD) as means for MS commitments in achieve EU targets;</p> <p>New governance approach to EU policies on security of supply;</p> <p>Citizen’s Energy Forum as an incentive for public engagement in new EU energy initiatives and integration of regulations and consumers;</p> <p>Online public Transparency Platform to disclosure of information about EU policies;</p> <p>EU macro-policies coordination to long-term development goals.</p>	<p>New targets defined in the 2030 framework for RES share and GHG emissions;</p> <p>Difficulties in achieving some macro-objectives of EU energy policies on themes (e.g. share of RES, decarbonisation of market, transparency and exchange of information);</p> <p>Critical policy conflicts at strategic levels between different EU macro-policy objectives (e.g. RES strategy and ecosystem service protection; neighbouring issues; CCS; accounting mechanisms).</p>

iii. Strategic Assessment

Assessment Criterion 1: Policies and Politics

A **centralized and large scale use of RES (G1)** can enhance MS interest and adherence to the development of national strategies for RES (in line with Europe 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050 and RLCE2050) and promote a more dynamic market functioning. New support schemes for RES technologies in MS institutional frameworks are likely to also emerge from the adoption of a **decentralized and small scale RES option (G2)**. Both **non-dominant RES (G4)** and **nuclear and fossil without CCS (G5)** options create a risk of further promoting support schemes for fossil fuels, contradicting the EU macro-objective of decarbonisation of the energy system. **G3 (dominant RES share in energy mix)** likely to have the opposite effect, imposing the need for a RES legal and institutional framework.

Options for **centralized and large scale RES (G1)**, **dominant RES (G3)**, **nuclear and fossil fuel without CCS near existing capacity (G5)**, **very high to medium energy flows (G7 and G8)**, and **centralized hydro storage (S1 and S2)** may determine regional imbalances and provoke unsustainable and non-competitive internal market of electricity due to biased competitive market caused by the differences between MS strategies for the energy sector, forms of renewables support, and different territorial specificities.

For **G1 and G3**, there is also the risk of reducing predictability among state-level policy-makers (decrease the level of regulatory reliability and increase power asymmetries), not aligned with the Energy Roadmap 2050 (pan-European electricity market integration). Potential conflicts between EU macro-policies may be more evident under options **G1, G2, G3, G4, G9 and IS2** (i.e. centralized vs decentralized energy generation, share of RES vs fossils in energy mix, internal market vs international position of EU, respectively).

Promoting **CCS close to demand (G6)** creates an opportunity to change political landscape and discourses on new technologies and regulations (in line with RLCE2050 objective of low carbon investments), generating new governance mechanisms for deployment and use of CCS under the European Energy Programme for Recovery.

Both options **G7 and G8** promote the alignment of MS strategies under the ERI (enhanced regional cooperation and co-ordination among TSOs) encouraging the use of cooperation mechanisms like systems of cross-border trades (e.g. by developing mechanisms for cross-border flows), in line with the objectives of Renewable Energy 2012 and SET-PLAN 2007. But a **low energy flow option (G9)** can boost cross-border cooperation for market harmonisation through the development or improvement of national actions plans. However, framing national objectives to reach a competitive and sustainable market can lead to a decrease of cooperation, increase of competition and market distortion (for example empower certain regions at the expense of the most vulnerable ones).

Options on **centralized hydro storage (S1)** and **centralized hydro and CAES (S2)** require institutional reforms to match different forms of RES, achieved by new or improved institutional frameworks that enhance operational efficiency of RES in the market, boosting renewable sources at state-level energy. A **mixed scale storage option (S3)** provides the opportunity to harmonize MS dedicated strategies for different storage

technologies (in line with the Renewable Energy 2012 and SE-PLAN 2007 policies that promote the prioritization of energy storage technologies). This may encourage decision-makers to coordinate state and EU-level investment decisions for future investment regulations, considering the risk of the high costs of a small application of batteries and the need for future investment policies.

Finally **IS1** may foster EU internal electricity market, re-affirming the international position of EU and its model of internal market, promoting the improvement of policy coherence inside its borders.

Assessment Criterion 2: Responsibilities and Competences

G1, G2 and **G3** presents the opportunity to foster the application of cooperation mechanisms (such as ITC mechanisms to compensate cross-border losses) to achieve regulatory stability between all MS. On the other hand, **G1** can discourage small producers to participate in the development of the energy market and energy initiatives, and overrule MS-level planning processes for grid development (due to current status of permitting frameworks).

Decentralized and small scale RES strategy (G2) may increase public ownership in local energy assets, promoting the engagement of small producers and consumers in energy initiatives and in the enhancement of the internal electricity market (more diversification of supply). This can boost public coordination and cooperation if new context-influenced public policies to RES are developed. However conflicts between local producers and state and EU-level actors can become a threat (considering the risk of uneven distribution of energy system costs and benefits).

Both **G2** and **G9** may decrease the level of institutional support for shared responsibilities due to competition (**G2** from the perspective of different levels of power distribution to decentralized generation facilities and **G9** from the level of energy flows). Also the deployment of both are directly associated to the existing national mechanisms for coordination and innovation, currently insufficient.

Energy mix options (G3 and G4) may promote the development of state-level strategies for coordination between stakeholders. But, since fossils and other non-RES are still an important piece of the European energy system, with lobbies and investments leading the way, the risk of opposition to a dominant RES strategy (**G3**) may exist in countries with solid strategies for fossils (**G4** has the associated risk of opposition from countries with solid strategies for RES and for the deployment of RES technologies).

The success of **nuclear and fossil fuels with or without CCS (G6 and G5)** depends on coordination of regional security among stakeholders (EU administrations, MS administrations, regulators, consumers, etc.) due to the risk of increasing political tensions inside the EU (tensions directly related to different levels of decision, existing rules and regulation, investment policies, network mechanisms for GHG emissions, and security arrangements to stabilize market in vulnerable regions). **CCS close to demand (G6)** can raise awareness to the need of social compatibility with the European objectives instruments and enhance the role of final consumers in promoting the development of new technologies (in line with the objectives of transparent discussions, dialogues and

engagement of all relevant stakeholders, stated by EIP 2020, European Grid Declaration and ECSER 2012).

Likewise **G7 and G8** can enhance the development of consumers engagement mechanisms in the management of the grid (such as the deployment of smart meters and grids under ICT mechanisms), and also create cross-border institutional mechanisms to support the most vulnerable regions (e.g. cross-border transfer agreements). Further, if considering low flows of energy (**G9**) new national approaches between stakeholders are likely to emerge in order to minimize possible political risks of security.

Both **S1 and S2** may lead to market and political tensions across MS due to regional imbalances related to the capacity for high scale hydro systems, and also due to divergent opinions on possible opportunities for centralized PHS. **S3** on the other hand may diversify relationships between entities and share responsibilities on grid development and transmission, and also enhance cooperation between MS administrations/regulators and private entities.

Both **transmission options (T1 and T2)** create opportunity to enhance relationships between state-level administrations and regulators for a combined effort in the development of context-related policy goals, such as investment support for infrastructure, regulatory reliability, coherence of instruments and cross-border interconnections.

Table 27 summarises the assessment and proposed planning and management guidelines to address the issues identified by the assessment for CDF4.

Table 27 - Summary of the assessment and Guidelines related to opportunities - CDF4 European Regional Governance

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
POLICIES AND POLITICS ³⁴	G1	(+) May increase MS level interest and adherence to RES policies; (+) Increase the dynamics of market functioning may contribute to EU strategic objective of security of supply based on RES.	Support the development of future RES strategies to help the institutionalization of RES objectives into MS-level policy development.
	G2	(+) Promote new (and harmonize the existing ones) support schemes for RES technologies.	Encourage healthy competition between MS framed by harmonized institutional regulations, without disregarding MS specificities
	G7, G8	(+) Opportunity to MS alignment strategies to promote regional cooperation and co-ordination (under ERI).	Encourage the development of a system of cross-border trade (e.g. governance mechanisms for cross-border flows).
	IS1	(+) Foster EU internal electricity market strategy and EU position in international energy sector (promote EU policies beyond its borders); (+) Improve policy coherence and complementarity between MS objectives and instruments.	Promote the Europeanization of the electricity market internally and externally (move towards effective and better integration / harmonization of MS energy mix).
	G3	(+) Contribute to the converging of MS decarbonisation policy objectives.	Support the development of future policy strategies that promote the institutionalization of RES strategy into MS policy objectives.
	G4	(-) Undermines the viability of RES investments and policy-RES development.	
	G6	(+) Change political landscape (and political discourses) on regulations for the development of new technologies; (-) Risk of compromise energy policy objectives integration with climate policy objectives.	Promote the development of clear and coherent climate-energy policy framework for predictability and reduction of regulatory risks; Create institutional frameworks based on regulatory reliability for technologies initiatives with decarbonisation focus.

³⁴ For options G1, G2, S1 and S2 it is important to consider, regardless the opportunities and risks identified, the notion of complementarity between centralized vs. decentralized options in future policy and/or project-level developments.

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	G9	(+) Opportunity to increase the rate of cross-border cooperation mechanisms through the development (or improvement) of national action plans; (-) Increase competition but decrease cooperation, possibly leading to market fragmentation and distortion.	Establish stable and strong institutional arrangements (for accountability mechanisms) and rule framework forms (for consolidated and equitable regulatory mechanisms).
	S1, S2	(+) Opportunity for future institutional reforms to match different RES sources; (-) Limits political advances (regulatory mechanisms or governance approaches) due to the expected phase out of supporting schemes for mature technology.	Promote a reform in institutional frameworks (EU and state level) to enhance operational efficiency of RES in the market; Encourage decision-makers to set up new (or renewed) investment policies to overcome the phase-out of mature technologies; Encourage the development and definition of a set of regulatory rules to improve resilience and stability of markets.
	S3	(+) Harmonization between strategies and development of new ones for policy integration and state-level strategies coherence; (-) Need for future investment policies due to high costs associated to a small-scale application of batteries.	Encourage decision-makers to coordinate investment decisions for future investment regulations.
	G1, G3	(-) Fragmentation of market may reduce predictability among policy-makers.	Expose and explain profitability and efficiency of large scale RES; Encourage and promote future development of the harmonisation of energy markets for an EU-level unified market.
	G4, G5	(-) Risk of maintenance or increase of current support schemes for fossils, contradicting EU macro-objectives.	

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	G1, G3, G5, G7, G8, S1, S2	(-) May determine regional imbalances and provoke unsustainability and non-competitive internal market of electricity.	Encourage healthy competition between MS framed by harmonized institutional regulations, without disregarding MS specificities; Encourage the development of “best practices” rather than (only) regulatory compliance; Encourage the development and definition of a set of regulatory rules to improve resilience and stability of markets; Contribute to discussion of new (or improved) public policy goals.
	G1, G2, G3, G4, G9, IS2	(-) Potential policy conflicts between EU macro-policies may be more evident under this option.	Clarify policy macro-objectives (centralized vs. decentralized energy generation; share of RES vs. fossils in energy mix; internal market vs. international position of EU); Share a clear and coherent strategy for the European energy market.
RESPONSIBILITIES AND COMPETENCES	G1, G2, G3	(+) Encourages the application of cross-border cooperation mechanisms (trades and subsidies rates).	Promote the application of cross-border mechanisms (and level of acceptability); Create long-term planning security for infrastructure projects (and for regulatory stability).
	G6	(+) Opportunity to enhance the role of final consumers in activities related to CCS deployment acceptance by general public.	Raise awareness to the need of social compatibility with the development of European instruments for new technologies deployment.
	G7, G8	(+) Opportunity to create cross-border institutional mechanisms (like engagement and cooperative mechanisms) to support the most vulnerable regions.	Create opportunities to institutionalized regulatory instruments for joint cooperative approaches (minimize political risks of security and ensure democratic oversight).
	G9	(+) National governance approaches between neighbouring MS regulators and administrations.	
	S3	(+) Opportunity to diversify relations and share responsibilities between existing and new public or private entities; (+) Enhance cooperation between MS administrations / regulators and private entities.	

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	T1 and T2	(+) Engage state-level administrations and regulators for collaborative efforts in the development of context-related public policy goals.	Promote cooperation and co-ordination to overcome possible uncertainties and unpredictability on transmission planning; Enhance interconnections by ensuring the reduction of lengthy authorisation processes (simplification of administrative procedures).
	G2	(+) Increase public ownership of local energy assets; (+) Public coordination and cooperation through new context-influenced public policies to renewables; (-) Likely conflicts between local producers and TSOs, generation and distribution stakeholders (uneven distribution of energy costs and benefits).	Provide on-going results of the benefits of public involvement and engagement; Promote the participation of local communities in local energy planning; Support community engagement through the development of local-governance models and formalized agreements.
	G3, G4	(+) Promotes national strategies for European coordination in energy issues; (-) Risk of opposition from countries with solid strategies for RES and non-RES (opposite strategies for energy mix).	Engage in dialogues and negotiations with countries with opposite visions for their energy mix; Promote the engagement of all relevant stakeholders in initiatives and dialogues for future planning and development strategies.
	G1	(-) Discourage small producers to be engaged in energy initiatives; (-) Overrule MS level planning processes due to current administration procedures.	Ensure early and effective engagement of affected communities in areas where centralized RES may be deployed in relation to grid planning and management.
	G2, G9	(-) Decrease of institutional support for shared responsibility due to competition (relations erosion between MS administrations and regulators); (-) Dependence on (insufficient) national mechanisms for coordination and innovation.	Encourage healthy competition between MS framed by harmonized institutional regulations, without disregarding MS specificities; Encourage future (coherent) decisions without neglect the multi-level governance system of EU.
	G5, G6	(-) Success depends on regional security coordination among stakeholders (risk of increasing political tension).	Encourage the development of national institutional arrangements to promote regional security coordination activities among stakeholders; Promote the engagement of all relevant stakeholders in initiatives and dialogues for future planning and development strategies in the implementation of the grid.

Assessment Criteria	Strategic Options	(+ Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines
	S1, S2	(-) Risk of divergent opinions (causing political tension and instability) from different territorial contexts (capacity vs. non-capacity to high scale hydro systems).	Promote dialogue and joint initiatives to reach consensus on multilateral opportunities of centralized PHS.

iv. Monitoring Guidelines

Table 28 identifies the relevant issues that should be monitored, considering the opportunities and risks described above for CDF4. These monitoring guidelines aim to inform a more extensive periodical follow-up program for e-Highway2050's implementation.

Table 28 - Monitoring guidelines and indicators for follow-up - CDF4 European Regional Governance

Monitoring Guidelines	Monitoring Indicators
Monitor the harmonisation of regulations to ensure an equitable burden sharing affordable for all MS (in relation to the 2030 European Framework).	Number of MS that develop national plans under the 2030 European Framework; MS specific burden share; MS individual regulatory measures for energy security.
Monitor the development of future investment policies that regulates supporting schemes for renewables and fossils.	Forms of support measures for RES (support schemes, subsidies, taxation, environmental standards, and investment measures).
Monitor potential policy conflicts between EU macro-objectives.	Level of compatibility between macro-objectives of the EU energy strategy.
Monitor collaborative initiatives between MS administrations and regulators; Monitor the level of engagement of relevant stakeholders in energy initiatives.	Number of inter-agency initiatives (between the various EU administrations); Number of cross-border balancing mechanisms; Number of cross-border cooperation initiatives; Average time spent in administrative and permit grant procedures; Regional cooperation between TSOs; Institutional engagement mechanisms for civil society participation in grid development and energy initiatives.

v. Governance Guidelines

Table 29 proposes governance guidelines that seek to ensure cooperation and sharing of responsibility among relevant stakeholders in grid development.

Table 29 - Governance Framework for follow-up - CDF4 European Regional Governance

Organization	Governance Guidelines
EC	Create targeted regulatory instruments and initiatives to deal and possible overcome possible effects of market distortion; Contribute to set up an energy market providing citizens and business with affordable energy, competitive prices and technologically advanced energy services; Enhance the conditions for secure energy supply in a spirit of solidarity between MS; Promote the complementarity and integration between macro-objectives of energy policies and other sectorial EU policies;

Organization	Governance Guidelines
	<p>Promote coordination and co-operation between EU administrations to build cooperative approaches;</p> <p>Develop competition regulations to provide regulators the power of effectively implement market requirements;</p> <p>Promote the prosecution of the European Energy Dialogue for flexible interaction and conversations between MS administrations, regulators and citizens;</p> <p>Review the existing national plans and future ones in order to achieve complementarity and harmonisation among national energy goals, actions and objectives;</p> <p>Maintain awareness of strategic risks identified by current (and future) policies and interventions;</p> <p>Review the model for the European internal electricity market to meet the challenges of the 2030 European Framework.</p>
ACER	<p>Always comply with the responsibility of speaking on the rules of procedures of ENTSO-E and monitor the execution of the regulated tasks;</p> <p>Adopt individual decisions on technical issues and make recommendations with the aim of promoting the exchange of good practices between regulatory authorities and market players;</p> <p>Analyse the compliance of regulatory authorities with the applicable Community rules;</p> <p>Provide the terms and conditions to cross-border infrastructures;</p> <p>Give particular attention to the role of prices and to the existing prices instruments as incentives for energy savings or efficiency investments.</p>
MS Public Authorities	<p>Transpose, according to the pre-defined timeline, the Third Energy Package and future regulations of the European Energy Strategy;</p> <p>Enhance effectiveness of Regional Initiatives and their contributions to the integration of the internal electricity market;</p> <p>Prepare national plans for swift deployment of smart grids and to comply with the 2030 European Framework (iterative process);</p> <p>Promote dialogue between state, regional and local stakeholder's organisations.</p>
Regulators	<p>Act as a platform for cooperation, information exchange and assistance between Europe's national regulators;</p> <p>Ensure compliance of TSOs and DSOs on the existing and future regulations;</p> <p>Cooperate in cross-border issues with the neighbourhood regulatory authority;</p> <p>Ensure the transparency of obligations and the availability of data to all interested stakeholders;</p> <p>Follow the implementation of rules relating to the roles and responsibilities of TSOs, DSOs, suppliers and customers.</p>
ENTSO-E and national TSOs	<p>Harmonise the unbundling options available to national TSOs in order to create stability and predictability on the European internal market;</p> <p>Promote a full interconnection to reduce the lengthy of authorization processes (permit granting);</p> <p>Offer a platform for market by proposing and implementing standardized and transparent frameworks that facilitate competitive and integrated markets;</p> <p>Support the EC in setting interconnection objectives for a better connecting power system;</p> <p><i>(National TSOs)</i> Provide to the operator of any other system with which is interconnected sufficient information to ensure the secure and efficient operation, coordinated development and interoperability of the interconnected system;</p>

Organization	Governance Guidelines
	Promote the application of cross-border mechanisms.
Relevant entities (non-energy related)	Ensure the fulfilment of EU rules and regulations on energy policy in relation to their areas of activity and institutional context; Promote fair competitiveness in the European internal electricity market.
Third Party Countries	Provide information about their interests in European energy initiatives on the contexts of existing agreements; Develop voluntary instruments, together with the EU, to improve the status relation and the quality of global energy governance.
NGOs	Contribute to a democratic development of the European energy strategy together with decision-makers, regulators, market entities and civil society; Engage in regular dialogue with public authorities to pursuit a better implementation of EU energy initiatives and policy-making; Promote public awareness and the participatory involvement of civil society in energy policy-making.
Media	Disclose information to all the existing relevant stakeholders and to those with particular interest in the development of the European energy strategy.
Civil Society	Actively participate in current and future energy initiatives and policy-making to ensure inclusive and effective policies (e.g. Citizen’s Energy Forum; European Energy Dialogue); Act as knowledge brokerages in the share of public knowledge, views and values (cultural, historical, environmental priorities and perceptions) to adjust and tailored energy agenda to context-situations.

7. Application of the SESA methodology to subsequent stages of grid design and development

As often-mentioned SESA’s purpose is to advise on more adequate grid options from an environmental and sustainability perspective. It should therefore be highlighted that SESA is an environmental and sustainability assessment methodology designed to be a companion to the development of the grids (see Figure 5). Because environment and sustainability assessment cannot be standardized, SESA’s success depends on a learning by design approach. This means that the success of SESA application is a function not of established models or algorithms, or input-output matrices that apply to whatever will be the WP2 grid design outcome, but it **requires an adequate adaptation to fit for purpose**. D4.2a was designed following strategic assessment concepts and a whole suit of assumptions that support grids design, including strategic options. But the application of SESA to e-Highway2050 requires a dialogue with WP2 and an assessment of more concrete outcomes, which are still unavailable at the time of closing this report. In order for SESA to be effective, as well as to improve the whole sustainability of e-Highway2050, it is desirable that SESA methodological details get adjusted to WP2 outcomes and that WP2 be adjusted taking into account SESA recommendations (some already available in this report). What D4.2a delivers at this point is therefore a SESA of the broad concept of e-Highway2050, but still misses the fine-tuning as well as the validation of grid architectures, yet to be delivered.

Figure 5 - SESA and grid design

7.1. How to apply the SESA to subsequent stages of 2050 grid architectures

As illustrated in Figure 5 the SESA methodology was established and applied to the e-Highway2050 strategic concept resulting from the development of the scenarios and the European grid model. The strategic options considered in SESA were based on the 2050 scenarios, and were intended to acknowledge the main aspects relevant for grid design where strategic decisions need to be made. As previously mentioned strategic options were discussed and validated by e-Highway2050's coordination. It is expected that the outcome of grid designs, prepared by WP2, will have considered the risks and opportunities for environment and sustainability resulting from the assessment of strategic options, as above exposed, for the strategic themes identified:

- Generation and regional balance;
- Storage;
- Transmission; and
- International strategy.

Subsequently it is desirable that an interaction takes place between SESA and grid development during the running of simulations to allow fine-tuning of both the SESA and the grid development, before validation of the grid architectures takes place. This validation will allow:

1. Identify to what extent risks and opportunities previously identified for the whole strategic concept may still persist for each grid;
2. Identify other possible risks and opportunities that may arise from a more detailed analysis of grid architectures, keeping an environmental and sustainability perspective;
3. Revise, confirm and implement the relevant planning and management, governance and monitoring guidelines or avoid or reduce risks and enhance opportunities.

In order to enable the above three objectives, it is important first that the simulation outcomes be assessed in terms of risks and opportunities from an environmental and sustainability perspective, using the assessment framework established (CDFs). Second, it is important to validate the grid architectures. The following steps are suggested to be completed for D4.2b:

- Verify which strategic options relate to each proposed grid architecture considering the way they convey to the scenarios (see Table 3, page 8). Check to see if all the strategic issues are covered (see Table 2, page 4);
- Verify the opportunities and risks identified for each strategic option, for each CDF and consider whether risks are acceptable;
- Verify the adequacy of proposed planning and management, monitoring and governance guidelines for each opportunity / risk to reduce the risks and enhance the opportunities that may result from the proposed grid architecture. If necessary, quantify these opportunities / risks in order to develop more fit-for-purpose guidelines;
- Apply the guidelines to grid development.

The following examples attempt to illustrate what this subsequent stage of SESA may look like.

Example of assessment and comparison of two hypothetical grid architectures - “Grid A” and “Grid B”:

Assume the following as the preferred options for a hypothetical pan-european "Grid A" architecture:

- A1. RES as the dominant energy source in the overall energy mix;
- A2. Centralised and large-scale RES generation located where profitability is higher (Wind, Biomass and PV all over Europe, with off-shore wind dominant in the North and Baltic seas. Hydro mainly in Northern, Central and Southern Europe. CSP in South and Southwest Europe and North Africa if Desertec exists);
- A3. New nuclear and fossil facilities, with CCS, would be close to demand;
- A4. Centralized Pumped Hydro as the main storage technology;
- A5. Transmission technology uses underground and submarine HVDC and well as overhead HVAC/UHVAC with FACTS, depending on regional technical feasibility and public acceptance.

Table 30 illustrates the application of the SESA methodology to this possible grid solution, and what the assessment results would be using the methodology. Equivalent results would be achieved with other possible grid solutions, of course with different risks and opportunities – and hence guidelines – resulting from the assessment.

Table 30 - Example of SESA assessment results for hypothetical “Grid A”

Grid A Characteristics	CDF 1 - Social acceptance and acceptability	CDF 2 - Energy security and technologies	CDF 3 - Geo-Political Economy and regional equity	CDF 4 - European Regional Governance
A1) RES Dominance	(+) Even access to energy system benefits, EU-internal energy system less vulnerable to external volatility.	(+) Promotes a low-carbon economy and contributes to RES EU goals.	(-) Withdrawal of MS RES support schemes may delay or threaten implementation.	n.a
A2) Large scale RES	(-) Affects integrity of landscapes, ecosystems, communities of species, habitats and individual species populations.	(+) More efficient generation and competitive RES vs. fossil fuels, promoting low-carbon energy; (-) Centralized generation as single option against EU macro-policies.	n.a.	(+) Increase MS interest and adherence to RES policies.
A3) New	n.a.	(+) Fosters local	(-) Dependence on	(+) Opportunity

Grid A Characteristics	CDF 1 - Social acceptance and acceptability	CDF 2 - Energy security and technologies	CDF 3 - Geo-Political Economy and regional equity	CDF 4 - European Regional Governance
nuclear & Fossil close to demand		thermal autoproduction - more efficient.	external fossil and nuclear fuel leaves Europe in fragile negotiating position.	to change political landscape (and discourses) on regulations for the development of new technologies.
A4) PHS Storage	(-) Loss of efficacy during droughts - likely to affect centralised hydro storage in Southern Europe and South Central Europe (e.g. infrastructure in the French Alps) in particular.	(-) Threatened by limited availability of PHS locations, high investment costs and long lead times reducing the capacity of EU to create additional storage capacity.	(-) Real estate values may diminish within areas affected by new infrastructure limiting future local development options.	n.a.
A5) Overhead and Underground HVAC/HVDC transmission	n.a.	(-) National and regional NIMBY effect may threaten transmission expansion.	n.a.	(+) Engage state-level administrations and regulators for collaborative efforts in development of context-related public policy goals.

(+) Opportunities; (-) Risks

Assume the following as the preferred choices for an alternative pan-european “Grid B” architecture:

- B1. RES is the dominant energy source in the overall energy mix;
- B2. Small-scale RES generation facilities are close to demand.
- B3. No new nuclear or fossil capacity is developed and facilities replace existing ones.
- B4. Existing PHS capacity is considered but additional storage capacity is achieved through centralised CAES and decentralised, medium to small-scale batteries, including electric vehicles.
- B5. The pan-European grid connecting additional capacity is developed mainly using overhead lines, in both HVAC/UHVAC with FACTS and HVDC.

As above, Table 31 illustrates the application of the SESA methodology to this possible grid solution.

Table 31 - Example of SESA assessment results for Grid B

Grid B Characteristics	CDF 1 - Social acceptance and acceptability	CDF 2 - Energy security and technologies	CDF 3 - Geo-Political Economy and regional equity	CDF 4 - European Regional Governance
B1) RES Dominance	(+) Even access to energy system benefits, EU-internal energy system less vulnerable to external volatility.	(+) Promotes a low-carbon economy and contributes to RES EU goals.	(-) Withdrawal of MS RES support schemes may delay or threaten implementation.	n.a
B2) Small scale RES close to demand	(+) Provide equal access to energy system benefits and costs.	(+) Capture and re-use locally generated heat, through CHP plants.	(-) Not viable in all locations resulting in electricity price differentials across the EU.	(-) Dependence on (insufficient) national mechanisms for coordination and innovation.
B3) No new nuclear & Fossil	n.a	(-) Inhibit CCS and nuclear energy technological development.	n.a	(-) Success depends on regional security coordination among stakeholders (risk of increasing political tension).
B4) Mixed scale storage	(+) Mixed strategy is less reliant on centralised hydro storage therefore less exposed to related climate risks.	(-) Rare materials (batteries) imported, aggravating energy system's dependence from imports.	(+) Even distribution of storage infrastructure costs and benefits.	(+) Diversify relations and share responsibilities between existing and new public or private entities.
B5) Overhead HVAC/ HVDC transmission	(-) Poor public acceptance and acceptability of transmission infrastructure.	(-) National and regional NIMBY effect may threaten transmission expansion.	(-) Real estate values may diminish within areas affected by new infrastructure.	(+) Engage state-level administrations and regulators for collaborative efforts in de development of context-related public policy goals.

(+) Opportunities; (-) Risks

Table 32 illustrates the different outcomes in terms of energy security and technologies (CDF2) of the two alternative (hypothetical) grids. This analysis allows comparing the two solutions from this CDF's perspective.

Table 32 - Opportunities and risks for Grids A and B, from CDF2's perspective

Grid Characteristic	CDF 2 - Energy security and technologies	
	Grid A	Grid B
Energy Mix	(+) Promotes a low-carbon economy and contributes to RES EU goals.	(+) Promotes a low-carbon economy and contributes to RES EU goals.

Grid Characteristic	CDF 2 - Energy security and technologies	
	Grid A	Grid B
RES Scale	(+) More efficient generation and competitive RES vs. fossil fuels, promoting low-carbon energy; (-) Centralized generation as single option against EU macro-policies.	(+) Capture and re-use locally generated heat, through CHP plants.
Nuclear and Fossil	(+) Fosters local thermal autoproduction - more efficient.	(-) Inhibits CCS and nuclear energy technological development.
Storage	(-) Threatened by limited availability of PHS locations, high investment costs and long lead times reducing the capacity of EU to create additional storage capacity.	(-) Rare materials (batteries) imported, aggravating energy system's dependence from imports.
Transmission	(-) National and regional NIMBY effect may threaten transmission expansion.	(-) National and regional NIMBY effect may threaten transmission expansion.

(+) Opportunities; (-) Risks

Table 32 exemplifies guidelines resulting from Grid A's set of opportunities and risks. These results are the main outcomes of the SESA to be used in future grid design and management.

Table 33 - Example of SESA assessment guidelines for Grid A.

CDF	Grid A Char.	(+) Opportunities / (-) Risks	Planning and Management Guidelines	Governance Guidelines	Monitoring Guidelines*
1	A1	(-) Loss of efficacy during droughts – likely to affect centralised hydro storage in Southern Europe and South Central Europe in particular.	Consider the use of CAES technology at vulnerable locations instead of PHS; Consider key climatic vulnerabilities in the planning and design of large scale, centralised RES.	<u>Regulators:</u> Use capacity market design and management to reduce regional energy system climate change vulnerability.	Monitor energy system infrastructure vulnerability to extreme climatic events.
2	A2	(-) Centralized generation as single option against EU macro-policies.	Mix centralised and decentralised storage and enable load management (including DSM) technologies.	<u>Regulators:</u> Develop clear connection requirements to enable large share of decentralized investment.	Monitor the economic and social efficiency of energy generation, storage and transmission.
3	A3	(-) Dependence on external fossil and nuclear fuel leaves Europe in fragile negotiating position.	Keep a significant share of RES in the energy mix.	<u>Finance, funds and banks:</u> Promote the EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative, particularly to MS with poor credit ratings.	EU vulnerability to external energy supply chain shocks.
4	A5	(+) Engage state-level administrations and regulators for collaborative efforts in development of context-related public policy goals.	Promote cooperation and co-ordination of regulator activities / regulations to overcome possible uncertainty on transmission planning.	<u>ENTSO-E:</u> Support the EC in setting interconnection objectives for a better-connected power system; <u>NGOs:</u> Promote public awareness and the participatory involvement of civil society in energy policy-making.	Monitor the harmonisation of regulations to ensure an equitable burden sharing affordable for all MS.

(+) Opportunities; (-) Risks

* For monitoring, specific indicators are also produced to support the guidelines

7.2. How to apply the SESA to 2030 and 2040 scenarios

For 2030 and 2040 scenarios the SESA methodology will apply overall in a similar way, however adjustment of the methodology may be necessary due to possible different issues and aspects between the 2050 and 2030/2040 timeframes. Depending on these differences it may be necessary to reconsider other priorities, and consequently other strategic options, regardless of the same scenarios and overall objectives for 2050 remaining the same.

It is our view that the strategic assessment framework (CDF) could be the same, as well as the trend analysis already developed. Assuming this is the case, and assuming **new strategic options could be necessary**, the following steps would need to be undertaken to complete the assessment for 2030 / 2040:

- Identify the strategic options (where these may differ from those already identified);
- Assess them against the SRF considering the critical trends already identified. Further elaborate on the trend analysis where necessary;
- Identify risks where the strategic options may go against the macro-policy goals or opportunities where they may favour achieving these goals;
- Develop guidelines for planning and management of the grid – considering its implementing time-frame (e.g. 2030 – 2040 / 2040 – 2050) – as well as governance and monitoring guidelines to ensure that opportunities are enhanced and that risks are avoided or reduced;
- Apply the guidelines to intermediate grid designs.

8. Conclusions

e-highway2050's Strategic Environmental and Sustainability Assessment (SESA) assessed the plausible **strategic options** that may result in different grid architectures, according to the five 2050 scenarios established by WP1. Sixteen different strategic options were identified in relation to four main themes:

- Generation and regional balance;
- Storage;
- Transmission; and
- International strategy.

The assessment itself was structured around four critical decision factors (CDFs) which were identified, through the SESA process (see Section 1), as the most relevant determinants for success:

- Social acceptance and acceptability;
- Energy security and energy technologies;
- Geo-political economy and regional equity; and
- European regional governance.

e-highway2050's strategic options were then assessed against these CDFs with reference to the macro-policy objectives and targets (considering the main trends associated with key environmental and sustainability themes) and key drivers of change. The assessment also considered governance arrangements and policy conflict issues that may have implications for e-Highway2050 decisions. This assessment was undertaken from the perspective of each CDF.

Table 34 summarises the main conclusions of SESA in terms of both the main risks and opportunities according to the main four themes of strategic options considered, which are further discussed below.

Table 34 -Summary of key opportunities and risks from 2050 strategic options

Strategic Theme	Risks	Opportunities
Generation and regional balance	<p>Highly centralized system may:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - be ineffective from a spatial, environmental and social perspective; - be vulnerable to extreme climatic and other events; - override MS level planning processes; - inhibit decentralised or small scale energy options; - contribute to uneven distribution of energy system costs and benefits between MS. <p>High energy flows may establish tense dependence relations among EU regions.</p> <p>Highly decentralized system may:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lead to public opposition due to dispersed impacts on landscapes and ecosystems; - reduce need for investment in pan-European grid; - discourage international trade initiatives; - aggravate electricity price differentials. <p>Non-RES dominance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - may aggravate energy import dependence and public acceptance issues. - thermal and nuclear generation infrastructure in Southern Europe increasingly vulnerable to extreme climatic events (heat waves, drought). Increased volume of nuclear waste and concerns over its storage/management and implications of any accidents for biodiversity, landscapes and ecosystem services. 	<p>Centralised system more efficient and manageable, making RES more competitive than fossil.</p> <p>Decentralized system promotes even distribution of energy system costs and benefits, public participation, reduction of energy consumption and it is more redundant and flexible.</p> <p>RES dominant system less vulnerable to external political and market volatility. Also promotes the use of waste as an energy source, reducing the pressure on landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services.</p> <p>Forest biomass as energy source may help deliver multiple benefits for landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services.</p>

Strategic Theme	Risks	Opportunities
Storage	Dominance of traditional storage options may lock out EV and smart grids and limit EU's storage capacity , for limited availability of sites and loss of efficiency during droughts (Southern Europe and South Central Europe).	Mixed scale storage: - likely to have greater environmental and social benefits - maintaining pressure on landscape, biodiversity and aquatic ecosystems at current levels; - increase overall system's flexibility ; - reduce system's vulnerability to climate change.
Transmission	Relying mostly on overhead transmission may lead to public opposition towards grid development. Underground transmission options also face risks including vulnerability to climate change -related droughts.	Developing FACTS may reduce the need for new lines . HVDC particularly efficient for long-distance transmission. Underground HVDC reduces pressure on landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services .
International strategy	Maintaining significant imports from the East maintain EU's vulnerability to political instability in the East. Connections with North Africa may increase the pressure on marine resources and ecosystems .	Expansion of EU energy markets . Greater opportunities for international energy trade .
<i>(All Themes)</i>	Aggravated pressure over natural resources and ecosystems ; Diminishing of real estate value within areas affected by the infrastructure, especially in areas where this value is influenced by landscape quality - potentially affecting local development options .	

Strategic Option Theme 1: Generation and regional balance

Risks and opportunities associated with a centralized energy system

EU macro-policy favours a mix of both centralized and decentralized solutions for the energy system (e.g. the Energy 2020 and Energy Roadmap 2050). A **highly centralized system** (for both generation and storage) may be very effective purely from an energy system perspective, but not really from an integrated spatial, environmental and social perspective. It discourages small producers, contradicting policy priorities, and may act to override MS level planning processes. It may also result in an uneven distribution of energy system costs and benefits between MS, reducing social engagement at regional and local levels. Such a system is also more vulnerable to extreme climatic events, terrorism and technical accidents and it may not be the most cost-efficient solution for isolated regions with respect to the European energy grid (energy islands) with transmission restrictions. Relying strictly on this strategy may also inhibit the technological development of decentralised/small-scale solutions, thus limiting future options.

On the other hand a centralized system (generation and storage) is more efficient and manageable. It makes RES more competitive than fossil fuels reducing energy import dependency at EU level, fostering a low-carbon economy. It may also increase MS adherence to EU level RES policy and promote institutional reforms to match different RES technologies.

The **high energy flows** resulting from a centralized system are likely to leave some regions energy-dependent and vulnerable to energy market fluctuations and create tensions within Europe – namely between countries with more generation capacity and those that would depend on them for energy supply (e.g Northern Europe and Central Europe respectively). However, any system that results in high energy flows relies on and promotes greater electricity market integration and the strategic alignment of MS strategies on energy and technological development, while also fostering regional cooperation and coordination, which can be seen as an opportunity.

Risks and opportunities associated with a decentralized energy system

Conversely, a **highly decentralised system** may lead to greater public opposition namely because of dispersed impacts on landscapes and ecosystems. This strategy risks overall electrical efficiency and may create management issues, threatening RES competitiveness against fossil fuels. It may also reduce the need for the investment in a pan-European grid and inhibit R&D investment in large-scale technologies such as centralized solar power (CSP) and next generation windmills foreseen in EU macro-policy (SET-Plan, 2012). This strategy also discourages international trade initiatives and access to international markets, weakening EU's international competitiveness. Unequal access to finance or unviable decentralised solutions in every location may result in electricity price differentials and regional inequity. The resulting **low energy flows** may reduce energy market competition and increase market inefficiency, also decreasing MS and regional cooperation. This may decrease the sharing of responsibilities among MS namely for

technological innovation. It may also aggravate conflicts between stakeholders in the energy sector, as detailed in section 6.2(CDF4).

On the other hand, a **decentralized energy system** results in a more even distribution of energy system costs and benefits and promotes public participation in energy planning at regional and local levels. It promotes DSM and smart grid technologies and increased awareness of energy use, which in turn may reduce overall energy consumption, GHG emissions and foster the uptake of greener/energy efficient behaviours. A decentralised energy system is also less vulnerable to external, physical risks (e.g. accidents, natural hazards, terrorism etc.) due to its greater redundancy and flexibility. Furthermore, energy losses in transmission are reduced. This strategy promotes the technological development of innovative storage solutions possibly adequate to solving energy islands and may push new, improved support schemes for RES.

Risks and opportunities associated with non-RES dominance

Having fossil fuels as a dominant energy source in a **RES non dominant** energy mix goes against macro-policy objectives, namely in terms of reducing energy import dependence especially if locally available resources are not considered in the energy mix, maintaining Europe's vulnerability to external market and political instability. This strategy may also find opposition from countries with solid RES strategies (and vice-versa in case of RES dominance) and problems of public acceptance and acceptability are critical in this case.

In this case, the energy system would be increasingly vulnerable to climate change (heat waves, namely in Southern Europe) reducing generation efficiency. It would also inhibit a more efficient use of EU RES capacity and the development of RES related technologies, while most possibly pushing for other technologies which have received great international attention as a concern with respect to biophysical and social environments (e.g. hydraulic fracturing or tar oil sands). Non-RES dominance could also foster the maintenance of support schemes for fossil fuels that the EU wants to eliminate.

Keeping fossil fuelled generation with **no CCS** would aggravate GHG emissions and associated climate change impacts on ecosystems, landscapes, natural habitats and human health. But having no additional nuclear or fossil facilities may threaten the overall reliability of supply, especially in regions where RES is not productive.

On the other hand, developing **new nuclear and fossil facilities with CCS** may be threatened by current trends of nuclear decommissioning and funding cuts. There are also concerns about the increased volume of nuclear waste and over its storage and maintenance as well as the implications of nuclear accidents. This strategy is likely to rely on CCS maturity which, conversely, may demote/delay the development of energy efficient technologies and processes.

But **RES non-dominant** energy also offers opportunities. The mix pushes CCS development, next generation nuclear, nuclear safety and flexible gas technologies that may also be exported by the EU. It also contributes to eliminating energy islands without requiring significant transmission investment and reduces overall vulnerability to RES

intermittence increasing the reliability of supply. Also wider international trade links and initiatives are reinforced due to the necessary import of fuel. Developing **fossil facilities with CCS** may increase the acceptability of thermal generation and mitigate climate change risks.

Risks and opportunities associated with RES as dominant energy source

A **RES-dominant energy mix** offers opportunities that must be considered. For example, it makes the energy system less vulnerable to external political and market volatility. Also, exploring the use of waste and biomass generation technologies may deliver benefits for landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services by reducing the volume of waste going into landfill, thus reducing the pressure on natural resources. This strategy drives district heating and cooling (DHC) deployment (further reducing CO₂ emissions) and may help bring down RES costs and contribute to international technology trade and support the expansion of the Energy Community.

Strategic Option Theme 2: Storage

Risks and opportunities associated with large scale storage

A storage strategy based strictly on large-scale **PHS and CAES** not only limits future options by inhibiting the development of other technologies such as EV and smart grids, but is also threatened by limited availability of adequate locations, high investment costs and long lead-in times reducing the capacity of EU to create additional storage capacity. Also, CAES competes for the same locations as CCS, so it may be less viable when CCS is used in conjunction with thermal generation. Relying only on PHS may cause a loss of efficacy during droughts. Moreover, increasing large-scale storage capacity, PHS in particular, may aggravate pressures affecting the integrity of landscapes, ecosystems, communities (of species), habitats and individual species populations

On the other hand, **PHS** is readily available, and using **CAES** in addition promotes the technological development and commercial deployment of adiabatic CAES – more efficient than existing diabatic and not requiring gas – and overall storage capacity and energy security. PHS can also reduce the need for thermal and nuclear peaking units, potentially improving the overall public acceptance and acceptability of the energy system

Risks and opportunities associated with mixed scale storage

Having a **mixed scale** / technology storage system may increase system complexity that may result in significant inefficiency and new investment policies being necessary due to high costs associated to small-scale application of batteries. Conversely, such a storage system creates positive trade-offs between storage efficiency, transmission losses and overall system reliability exploring the high electrical efficiency of PHS and CAES and the modular characteristics of batteries, possibly more viable to solve energy islands. It also supports redundant, reliable backup systems, making the energy system less vulnerable.

This mix may also reduce the need for additional centralised storage, maintaining pressure on landscape, biodiversity and aquatic ecosystems at current levels (i.e. no net increase) possibly being more socially acceptable due to the lesser environmental impacts. This strategy is also less exposed to drought related climate risks. Decentralised storage also enables DSM (namely smart grids that rely on batteries), allowing consumers to shift consumption from peak-hours and promoting/facilitating the uptake of greener/energy efficient behaviours. In conjunction with these benefits, a reduction in GHG emissions can be achieved through the promotion and greater uptake of EV.

Strategic Option Theme 3: Transmission

In terms of transmission technologies, **HVDC** is more efficient than HVAC in long-distance energy transmission and the technological development of HVDC components is essential for developing meshed grids – adding up to the system’s flexibility.

On the other hand, HVAC using **FACTS** reduces the need for new lines, while making existing transmission infrastructure more efficient.

Relying **mostly on overhead transmission** may lead to public opposition towards grid development. The land take due to large buffer distances that can’t be developed is one reason for such opposition. This solution also limits HVDC usage (which is more efficient than HVAC) and it is vulnerable to accidents and weather-related incidents.

Underground cabling reduces transmission losses even further and supply disruptions are less frequent than in overhead lines, thus increasing the reliability of supply. But **underground transmission** options also face risks including vulnerability to climate change-related droughts due to geotechnical issues around soil stability, a risk that is more prevalent in Southern and South-Central Europe. The high costs associated with underground transmission may affect transmission cost-efficiency, restricting the use of more efficient HVDC underground cables, namely in remote, less populated areas, aggravating inconsistent energy pricing across Europe.

Strategic Option Theme 4: International strategy

Both **international strategy options** would maintain significant energy import from the East, not only of electricity but also fuels, sustaining EU’s vulnerability to political instability in this region. Developing relevant **connections with North Africa** may increase the pressure on marine resources and ecosystems as well as on ecosystem services (including fisheries). This strategy is also exposed to Desertec Industrial Initiative’s low interest in exporting solar power to Europe.

On the other hand, both strategies – and the latter in particular – enable the expansion of EU energy markets creating greater opportunities for international energy trade, potentially strengthening the EU’s position in international energy (promoting EU policies beyond its borders). They also foster EU internal electricity market strategy and improve policy coherence and complementarity between MS objectives and instruments.

General aspects

We have attempted to highlight the main opportunities and risks associated with the different strategic options that were analysed and assessed through the SESA. The intention is that e-highway2050 decision-makers will consider these risks and opportunities in the development and design of grid architectures, ensuring that opportunities are capitalised on and risks avoided where possible.

All energy infrastructure development has the inherent risk of infrastructure pressure over natural resources and ecosystems and diminishing of real estate value within areas affected by the infrastructure, especially in areas where this value is particularly influenced by landscape quality (e.g. tourism areas) hence affecting local development options.

Several planning and management, governance and monitoring guidelines have been presented to help reduce or avoid highlighted risks and enhance the identified opportunities. The following summarises relevant planning and management guidelines for grid development:

- To provide for EU and MS level energy security, centralised and decentralised energy system solutions must be integrated (depending on adequacy and appropriateness given local conditions) and technologies must be enabled to reduce overall energy consumption and expand future options;
- The viability of market-based options for importing 'foreign' RES must be assessed;
- Extensive cost-benefit analysis with environmental valuation must be performed when planning fossil and nuclear fuel facilities and its viability with RES must be compared, in order to support the business case for investors and enhance political and social acceptance;
- International cooperation for nuclear safety must be promoted;
- Local stakeholders should be engaged to develop innovative, local generation solutions, especially where RES are not very productive;
- Risk/benefit profiles for decentralized RES solutions should be defined and their performance against RES benchmarks should be monitored;
- Continued engagement with the public and affected communities must be ensured during implementation to promote increased awareness of climate change and sustainability issues, promote green behaviours and to capture data on changing community needs to ensure continued service delivery improvements (e.g. by TSOs, energy companies etc.);
- MS and relevant stakeholders at regional and national levels must be engaged to encourage their active participation in the planning of a pan-European grid in order to try to avoid or reduce potential conflicts;
- Constraints analysis and existing planning mechanisms (e.g. spatial planning and SEA/EIA) must be used to guide new infrastructure deployment to the most suitable locations;
- Alternative, multi-scale storage technologies must be considered and enabled depending on its adequacy to local conditions and storage needs, bearing in mind the economic rationale of investment. Where geophysical conditions allow, the use of CAES storage technology at vulnerable locations (e.g. watercourses with high

recreational or biodiversity value) should be considered instead of PHS, to enhance the public acceptability of a centralised energy system;

- Grid development must seek to avoid first, then reduce and only as a last resort compensate for loss of biodiversity and other ecosystem services essential to local development;
- Price/market coupling projects and agreements must be developed in conjunction with energy system infrastructure improvements and additional energy market tax and incentive mechanisms should be considered to protect and promote market integration and regional equity. Also, sufficient transmission and storage capacity must be provided to address potential regional imbalances and tensions, also potentially helping to reduce possible MS-level objections.

The object of this assessment was the strategic options for grid architectures for 2050. The methodological approach used [1] for this Strategic Environmental and Sustainability Assessment can be adapted to assess 2030 and 2040 scenarios as well as other strategic-level decision-making processes during grid implementation, as long as adjustments are made to the specific context and options at stake. As grid design choices are made, influenced by desirable scenarios, other strategic options may emerge. After all we are looking into an almost 40 years timeframe, during which many policy and technological developments may take place. Hence, it is essential that the strategic options are constantly assessed.

9. References

- [1] Partidário MR. Strategic environmental assessment better practice guide - methodological guidance for strategic thinking in SEA. Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente e Redes Energéticas Nacionais. Lisboa. 2012. (http://ec.europa.eu/environment/eia/pdf/2012%20SEA_Guidance_Portugal.pdf)
- [2] e-Highway2050. Consultation document on the selection of energy scenarios for the e-Highway2050 project. September 2012. (http://www.e-highway2050.eu/uploads/media/The_selection_of_energy_scenarios_for_e-Highway2050.pdf)
- [3] stoRE Project. D2.1 Report summarizing the current status, role and costs of energy storage technologies. Final Version. March 2012.
- [4] (IEC) International Electrotechnical Commission. Electrical energy storage - white paper. December 2011. (<http://www.leonardo-energy.org/sites/leonardo-energy/files/documents-and-links/IEC%20White%20Paper%20Energy%20Storage.pdf>)
- [5] REALISEGRID Project. Deliverable 3.7.1 - Review of existing transmission planning and approval procedures and coordination of infrastructure developments between TSOs. October 2010. (<http://realisegrid.rse-web.it/Publications-and-results.asp>)
- [6] e-Highway2050. Task 3.2: Technology assessment - HVDC technology assessment report - LCC, VSC, DC breakers, tapping equipment, DC/DC converters. 2014.
- [7] Global CCS Institute. Strategic Analysis of the Global Status of Carbon Capture and Storage - Existing Carbon Capture and Storage Research and Development Networks around the World. 2009. (<http://cdn.globalccsinstitute.com/sites/default/files/publications/5751/report-4-existing-carbon-capture-and-storage-research-and-development-networks-around-world.pdf>)
- [8] stoRE Project. D3.2 - Recommendations for furthering the Sustainable Development of Bulk Energy Storage Facilities. October 2012. (http://www.store-project.eu/documents/results/en_GB/recommendations-for-furthering-the-sustainable-development-of-bulk-energy-storage-facilities)
- [9] REALISEGRID Project. D3.6.1 - Evaluation of electricity infrastructure development, investment needs, regulation and policy recommendations. June 2011. (<http://realisegrid.rse-web.it/Publications-and-results.asp>)
- [10] Peter S. Modelling a renewable energy system for 2050 based fully on autonomous, decentralised structures. 2013. (<http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en/press/pressinformation/decentralised-renewable-energy-supply-is-ok-self>)
- [11] <http://www.ecee.org/policy-areas/competitiveness> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [12] UK Parliament. Science and Technology Second Report. July 2005. (<http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld200506/ldselect/ldsctech/21/2102.htm>)
- [13] UK Energy Research Centre. The rebound effect: an assessment of the evidence for economy-wide energy savings from improved energy efficiency. October 2007. <http://www.ukerc.ac.uk/Downloads/PDF/07/0710ReboundEffect/0710ReboundEffectReport.pdf>
- [14] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Environmental indicator report 2013. November 2013. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/environmental-indicator-report-2013>)
- [15] <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/total-primary-energy-intensity-1/assessment> [accessed 16/12/13]
- [16] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Consumption and the environment – 2012 update. June 2012. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/consumption-and-the-environment-2012>)
- [17] DG Internal Policies. European Renewable Energy Network. January 2012. (http://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2009_2014/documents/itre/dv/renewable_energy_network_/renewable_energy_network_en.pdf)

- [18] Eurostat. Gas and electricity market statistics. 2007.
(http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/cache/ITY_OFFPUB/KS-GB-07-001/EN/KS-GB-07-001-EN.PDF)
- [19] (IPCC) Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Summary for Policymakers. *In* Managing the Risks of Extreme Events and Disasters to Advance Climate Change Adaptation. Cambridge University Press. 2012. (http://ipcc-wg2.gov/SREX/images/uploads/SREX-SPMbrochure_FINAL.pdf)
- [20] Fischer C. Feedback on household electricity consumption: a tool for saving energy?. *Energy Efficiency*. 2008, (1): 79-104.
- [21] <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/tgm/table.do?tab=table&plugin=1&language=en&pcode=ten00115> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [22] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Environmental tax reform in Europe: Implications for income distribution. 2011. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/environmental-tax-reform-in-europe>)
- [23] (EC) European Commission. Commission staff working document: energy prices and costs report. SWD (2014) 20 final/2. (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/doc/2030/20140122_swd_prices.pdf)
- [24] Thomson H and Snell C. Quantifying the prevalence of fuel poverty across the European Union. *Energy Policy*. 2013, (52): 563-72.
- [25] (EC) European Commission. The European Platform against Poverty and Social Exclusion: A European framework for social and territorial cohesion. COM (2014) 758 final. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2010:0758:FIN:EN:PDF>)
- [26] EPEE Project. Tackling fuel poverty in Europe: recommendations guide for policy makers. 2009. (http://www.fuel-poverty.com/files/WP5_D15_EN.pdf)
- [27] <http://press.pwc.com/global/power-industry-blackout-risk-alert-on-the-rise-/s/72f2fce8-d577-405b-a646-09c80fc3621b> [accessed 16/12/13]
- [28] Walker G and Day R. Fuel poverty as injustice: Integrating distribution, recognition and procedure in the struggle for affordable warmth. *Energy Policy*. 2012, (49): 69-75.
- [29] (EC) European Commission. Eurobarometer 66: public opinion in the European Union. September 2007. (http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/archives/eb/eb66/eb66_en.htm)
- [30] UK House of Commons. Devil's bargain? Energy risks and the public. July 2012. (<http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201213/cmselect/cmsctech/428/428.pdf>)
- [31] e-Highway 2050. Milestone M1.4 - Political, Socio-Political and Environmental Boundary Conditions. February 2013
- [32] (EEA) European Environment Agency. EU 2010 Biodiversity Baseline. October 2010. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/eu-2010-biodiversity-baseline>)
- [33] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Land Use – SOER Thematic Assessment. November 2010. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/europe/land-use>)
- [34] van Delden H *et al.* Exploring land use trends in Europe: a comparison of forecasting approaches and results. *Proceeding of the 2012 International Congress on Environmental Modelling and Software*. Germany. 2012. (http://www.iemss.org/sites/iemss2012//proceedings/F1_0998_van%20Delden_et_al.pdf)
- [35] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Land use scenarios for Europe: qualitative and quantitative analysis on a European scale. June 2007. (http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/technical_report_2007_9)
- [36] (EC) European Commission. A new EU Forestry Strategy, for forests and the forest-based sector. COM (2013) 659 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/forest/strategy/communication_en.pdf)
- [37] (EC) European Commission. LIFE and Europe's wetlands – Restoring a vital ecosystem. 2007. (<http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/publications/lifepublications/lifefocus/documents/wetlands.pdf>)

- [38] (EC) European Commission. A Budget for Europe 2020. COM (2011) 500 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/where/octs_and_greenland/documents/20130327-note10.2.pdf)
- [39] Maes J *et al.* A spatial assessment of ecosystem services in Europe: methods, case studies and policy analysis – phase 2 synthesis report. 2012. (http://www.peer.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/publications/PEER_report_4_phase_2.pdf)
- [40] (EC) European Commission. Green Infrastructure (GI) – Enhancing Europe’s Natural Capital. COM (2013) 249 final. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2013:0249:FIN:EN:PDF>)
- [41] (EC) European Commission. A Blueprint to Safeguard Europe’s Water Resources. COM (2012) 673 final. ()
- [42] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2012. November 2012. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/climate-impacts-and-vulnerability-2012/>)
- [43] DG Energy. Investment needs for future adaptation measures in EU nuclear power plants and other electricity generation technologies due to effects of climate change. March 2011. (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/nuclear/studies/doc/2011_03_eur24769-en.pdf)
- [44] Poumadère, M., Mays, C., Le Mer, S. and Blong, R. (2005), The 2003 Heat Wave in France: Dangerous Climate Change Here and Now. *Risk Analysis*, 25: 1483–1494. doi: 10.1111/j.1539-6924.2005.00694.x
- [45] Lindner M *et al.* Impacts of climate change on European forests and options for adaptation. November 2008. (http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/analysis/external/euro_forests/full_report_en.pdf)
- [46] Mangoyana R and Smith T. Decentralised bioenergy systems: a review of opportunities and threats. *Energy Policy*. 2011, (39): 1286-95.
- [47] (ESHA) European Small Hydropower Association. Small Hydropower Roadmap: Condensed research data for EU-27. 2012. (http://streammap.asha.be/fileadmin/documents/Press_Corner_Publications/SHPRoadmap_FIN_AL_Public.pdf)
- [48] <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/tgm/table.do?tab=table&plugin=1&language=en&pcode=ten00087> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [49] <http://streammap.asha.be/6.0.html> [accessed 18/02/14]
- [50] <http://streammap.asha.be/14.0.html> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [51] (EC) European Commission. Proposal for a Directive on energy efficiency and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC. COM (2011) 370 final. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:52011PC0370:EN:NOT>)
- [52] Official Journal of the European Union. Directive 2012/27/EU. October 2012. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:EN:PDF>)
- [53] Wesselink B, Harmsen R, Eichhammer W. Energy savings 2020 - How to triple the impact of energy saving policies in Europe. 2010. (<http://www.roadmap2050.eu/attachments/files/EnergySavings2020-FullReport.pdf>)
- [54] (EC) European Commission. Action Plan for Energy Efficiency: Realising the Potential. COM (2006) 545 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/action_plan_energy_efficiency/doc/com_2006_0545_en.pdf)
- [55] (EEA) European Environment Agency. Trends and projections in Europe 2013. Tracking progress towards Europe’s climate and energy targets until 2020. October 2013. (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/trends-and-projections-2013>)
- [56] Eurostat. Sustainable development in the European Union: 2013 monitoring report of the EU sustainable development strategy. 2013. (http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/cache/ITY_OFFPUB/KS-02-13-237/EN/KS-02-13-237-EN.PDF)
- [57] Official Journal of the European Union. Directive 2010/31/EU. May 2010. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>)

- [58] Enerdata. Energy Efficiency Trends in industry in the EU: lessons from the ODYSSEE MURE project. September 2012. (<http://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/br/Industry-indicators-brochure.pdf>)
- [59] Eurostat. Driving forces behind EU-27 greenhouse gas emissions over the decade 1999–2008. October 2011. (http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/cache/ITY_OFFPUB/KS-SF-11-010/EN/KS-SF-11-010-EN.PDF)
- [60] Eurelectric. Power statistics & trends 2012: synopsis. December 2012. (http://www.elecpor.pt/pdf/Power_Statistics_and_Trends_2012_synopsis.pdf)
- [61] http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/ets/index_en.htm [accessed 03/02/14]
- [62] http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-14-54_en.htm [accessed 03/02/14]
- [63] RE-Shaping Project. Long term potentials and costs of RES - Part I: potentials, diffusion and technological learning. May 2011. (<http://www.reshaping-res-policy.eu/downloads/Long-term%20potentials%20and%20cost%20of%20RES%20-%20part%20I%20%28Re-Shaping%20report,%202011%29.pdf>)
- [64] DG Internal Policies. Decentralized Energy Systems. June 2010. ([http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/etudes/join/2010/440280/IPOL-ITRE_ET\(2010\)440280_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/etudes/join/2010/440280/IPOL-ITRE_ET(2010)440280_EN.pdf))
- [65] Cross Border Bioenergy Project. EU Handbook - District Heating Markets. October 2012. (http://www.crossborderbioenergy.eu/fileadmin/crossborder/DH_MarketHandbook.pdf)
- [66] <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/efficiency-of-conventional-thermal-electricity-generation-1/assessment> [accessed 14/02/13]
- [67] DHC+ Technology Platform. District Heat and Cooling: a vision to 2020 – 2030 – 2050. March 2012. (http://www.dhcplus.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/05/120529_Vision_DHC_final.pdf)
- [68] <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/co2-so2-and-nox-emissions-and-electricity-and-heat-production-eea-1> [accessed 14/02/14]
- [69] (EC) European Commission. Roadmap to a Resource-Efficient Europe. COM (2011) 571 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/environment/resource_efficiency/pdf/com2011_571.pdf)
- [70] www.eco-innovation.eu [accessed 14/02/14]
- [71] <http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/leadership-enabling-and-industrial-technologies> [accessed 17/02/2014]
- [72] (EC) European Commission. European Competitiveness Report 2013 - Towards knowledge-driven reindustrialisation (2013) Commission Staff Working Document SWD(2013)347 final (http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/industrial-competitiveness/competitiveness-analysis/index_en.htm)
- [73] (EC) European Commission. Preparing for our future: Developing a common strategy for key enabling technologies in the EU. COM (2009) 512 final. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:52009DC0512:EN:NOT>)
- [74] Larsen P *et al.* Cross-sectorial analysis of the impact of international industrial policy on Key Enabling Technologies. DG Enterprise and Industry. March 2011. (http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/ict/files/kets/ket-report_en.pdf)
- [75] (EC) European Commission. Energy challenges and policy: Commission contribution to the European Council of 22 May 2013. (http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/pdf/energy2_en.pdf)
- [76] Jagemann C, Fursch M, Hagspiel S, Nagl S. Decarbonizing Europe's power sector by 2050 - Analysing the implications of alternative decarbonisation pathways. September 2012, (http://www.ewi.uni-koeln.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Publikationen/Working_Paper/EWI_WP_12-13_Decarbonizing_Europes_Power_Sector.pdf)
- [77] Johnson, L and Wilson R. Strategies for Decarbonizing the Electric Power Supply. The Global Power Best Practice Series. November 2012. (www.raponline.org/document/download/id/259)

- [78] International Energy Agency. World Energy Outlook 2009 (2009)
(<http://www.worldenergyoutlook.org/media/weowebiste/2009/WEO2009.pdf>)
- [79] (EASE) European Association for Storage of Energy. Activity Report 2011-2012. 2013.
(http://www.ease-storage.eu/tl_files/ease-documents/EASE%20Activity%20Reports/RA%20EASE%202012_final_rev2.pdf)
- [80] (EC) European Commission. EU Energy, Transport and GHG Emissions – Trends to 2050; Reference Scenario 2013. December 2013.
(http://ec.europa.eu/energy/observatory/trends_2030/doc/trends_to_2050_update_2013.pdf)
- [81] (EWEA) European Wind Energy Association. Saving water with wind energy. March 2014.
(http://www.ewea.org/fileadmin/files/library/publications/reports/Saving_water_with_wind_energy.pdf)
- [82] Carlos F and Partidário MR. SEA role in energy planning: towards matching of energy systems. Conference Proceeding 32nd Annual Meeting of the International Association for Impact Assessment. Porto. June 2012.
(<http://www.iaia.org/conferences/iaia12/uploadpapers/Final%20papers%20review%20process/Carlos,%20Filipa.%20%20SEA%20role%20in%20energy%20planning,%20towards%20matching%20of%20energy%20systems.pdf?AspxAutoDetectCookieSupport=1>)
- [83] Carlos F. Evaluating Strategies for the Planning of Sustainable Energy Systems at Regional/Local Level, Sustainable Development Evaluations in Europe: From a Decade of Practices, Politics and Science to Emerging Demands. Conference Proceeding EASY-ECO Conference. Brussels. November 2010
- [84] Giordano V *et al.* Smart Grid projects in Europe: lessons learned and current developments. European Commission, Institute for Energy and Transport. Luxembourg. 2013.
(http://www.smartgridnews.com/artman/uploads/2/Smart_Grid_projects_in_Europe_Lessons_Learned.pdf)
- [85] Giordano V and Bossart S. Assessing Smart Grid Benefits and Impacts: EU and U.S. Initiatives. European Commission, Institute for Energy and Transport. Luxembourg. 2012.
(http://ses.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/ses.jrc.ec.europa.eu/files/documents/eu-us_smart_grid_assessment_-_final_report_-_online_version.pdf)
- [86] Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Managing Large-Scale Penetration of Intermittent Renewables. MIT Energy Initiative Symposium on Managing Large-Scale Penetration of Intermittent Renewables. April 2011 (<https://mitei.mit.edu/system/files/intermittent-renewables-full.pdf>)
- [87] Gimeno-Gutiérrez M and Lacal-Aránzategui R. Assessment of the European potential for pumped hydropower energy storage: a GIS-based assessment of pumped hydropower storage potential. Luxembourg. 2013.
(http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/jrc/downloads/jrc_20130503_assessment_european_phs_potential.pdf)
- [88] http://ec.europa.eu/energy/infrastructure/index_en.htm [*accessed 25/02/14*]
- [89] http://ec.europa.eu/energy/energy2020/infrastructure/index_en.htm [*accessed 25/02/14*]
- [90] stoRE Project - Facilitating energy storage to allow high penetration of intermittent renewable energy. D2.1 Report summarizing the current Status, Role and Costs of Energy Storage Technologies. Final Version, Updated March 2012
- [91] (EC) European Commission. Action plan for North-South Energy Interconnections in Central-Eastern Europe. 2011.
(http://ec.europa.eu/energy/infrastructure/doc/2011_north_south_east_action_plan.pdf)
- [92] http://ec.europa.eu/energy/infrastructure/pci/pci_en.htm [*accessed 24/02/14*]
- [93] (EC) European Commission. Connecting Europe: the energy infrastructure for tomorrow. 2012.
(<http://ec.europa.eu/energy/mff/facility/doc/2012/connecting-europe.pdf>)
- [94] (Dii) Desertec Industrial Initiative. Desert Power 2050: the case for Desert Power. Munich. June 2012.
(http://www.dii-eumena.com/uploads/media/dp2050_exec_sum_engl_web.pdf)

- [95] <http://www.euractiv.com/energy/desertec-abandons-sahara-solar-p-news-528151> [accessed 25/02/14]
- [96] (ISSUE) European Union Institute for Security Studies. Energy moves and power shifts. EU foreign policy and global energy security. February 2014.
(<http://www.iss.europa.eu/publications/detail/article/energy-moves-and-power-shifts-eu-foreign-policy-and-global-energy-security/>)
- [97] Dreyer I, Erixon F, Winkler R. The quest for gas market competition. Fighting dependency on Russian gas more effectively. ECIPE Occasional Paper 1/2010. 2010.
(http://www.ecipe.org/media/publication_pdfs/the-quest-for-gas-market-competition.pdf)
- [98] http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEX-14-0204_en.htm [accessed 03/02/2014]
- [99] (EC) European Commission. EU Energy in Figures: Statistical Pocketbook 2013. Luxembourg. 2013.
(http://ec.europa.eu/energy/publications/doc/2013_pocketbook.pdf)
- [100] http://ec.europa.eu/energy/strategies/2010/2020_en.htm [accessed 02/04/14]
- [101] BP. BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2013. June 2013.
(http://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/pdf/statistical-review/statistical_review_of_world_energy_2013.pdf)
- [102] Schweinfurth S. An Introduction to Coal Quality. In The National Coal Resource Assessment Overview. Edts. Brenda Pierce and Kristin Dennen. 2009.
(<http://pubs.usgs.gov/pp/1625f/downloads/ChapterC.pdf>)
- [103] (UNEP) United Nations Environment Program. UNEP 2012 Yearbook: Closing and Decommissioning Nuclear Power Reactors. 2012.
(http://www.unep.org/yearbook/2012/pdfs/UYB_2012_CH_3.pdf)
- [104] Dumas P. Geothermal integration in Smart cities: Key Innovation in Smart Thermal Grids. Conference Proceeding 4th European Conference on Renewable Heating and Cooling. Dublin. 2013.
(http://www.rhc-platform.org/fileadmin/2013_RHC_Conference/Presentations/Tuesday_23rd_April/Session_G/1/Philippe_Dumas_Smart_cities_-_Solution_Proposal_Smart_thermal_grid.pdf)
- [105] <https://www.entsoe.eu/about-entso-e/market/balancing-and-ancillary-services-markets/> [accessed 02/04/14]
- [106] <http://www.enernoc.com/our-resources/term-pages/what-is-an-ancillary-services-market> [accessed 02/04/14]
- [107] <http://www.reportlinker.com/p0196491/Energy-Storage-Systems-for-Ancillary-Services.html> [accessed 02/04/14]
- [108] Eurelectric. Power statistics & trends 2012: full report. December 2012.
(http://www.eurelectric.org/media/113657/power_statistics_2012_hr-2012-180-0002-01-e.pdf)
- [109] <http://energytransition.de/2012/10/747/> [accessed 24/02/14]
- [110] (CEER) Council of European Energy Regulators. Guidelines of Good Practice on Estimation of Costs due to Electricity Interruptions and Voltage Disturbances. December 2010.
(http://www.energy-regulators.eu/portal/page/portal/EER_HOME/EER_PUBLICATIONS/CEER_PAPERS/Electricity/2010/C10-EQS-41-03_GGP%20interruptions%20and%20voltage_7-Dec-2010.pdf)
- [111] (EC) European Commission. Energy Markets in the European Union in 2011. Belgium. November 2012.
(http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/20121217_energy_market_2011_lr_en.pdf)
- [112] <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/sources-of-uranium-delivered-to-1> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [113] <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/tgm/table.do?tab=table&plugin=1&language=en&pcode=tsdcc310> [accessed 12/12/13]

- [114] http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/statistics_explained/index.php/Energy_production_and_imports [accessed 12/12/13]
- [115] Energy Community. Energy Community Facts in Brief. 2013. <http://www.energy-community.org/pls/portal/docs/2422185.PDF>
- [116] http://www.energy-community.org/portal/page/portal/ENC_HOME/ENERGY_COMMUNITY/What_we_do [accessed 12/12/13]
- [117] http://www.energy-community.org/portal/page/portal/ENC_HOME/MEMBERS/PARTICIPANTS [accessed 12/12/13]
- [118] <http://www.inogate.org/> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [119] <http://jia.sipa.columbia.edu/russia-and-europe%E2%80%99s-mutual-energy-dependence> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [120] (Dii) Desertec Industrial Initiative. Getting Started: Questions & Answers. 2013. (http://www.dii-eumena.com/fileadmin/Daten/Downloads/Getting%20Started/FAQ/FAQ_Getting%20Started_EN.pdf)
- [121] http://www.desertec.org/fileadmin/downloads/media/pictures/DESERTEC_EU-MENA_map.jpg [accessed 12/12/13]
- [122] (EC) European Commission. 2009-2010 Report on progress of creating the internal gas and electricity market. Brussels. June 2011. (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/legislation/doc/20100609_internal_market_report_2009_2010.pdf)
- [123] <http://www.nordpoolspot.com/How-does-it-work/European-Integration/Price-coupling-of-regions/> [accessed 19/03/14]
- [124] <http://www.nordpoolspot.com/Message-center-container/Exchange-list/2013/12/No-712013---NWE-Price-Coupling-to-launch-4-February-2014/> [accessed 19/03/14]
- [125] <http://www.nordpoolspot.com/How-does-it-work/European-Integration/NWE/> [accessed 19/03/14]
- [126] (PCR) Price Coupling of Regions. PCR Project: Main Features. Presentation 09/01/2014. (http://www.nordpoolspot.com/Global/Download%20Center/PCR/PCR-presentation_09012014.pdf)
- [127] (EC) European Commission. Renewable Energy: A major player in the European energy market. COM (2012) 271 final. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52012DC0271&from=EN>)
- [128] (CEER) Council of European Energy Regulators. Status Review of Renewable and Energy Efficiency Support Schemes in Europe. 2013. (http://www.energy-regulators.eu/portal/page/portal/EER_HOME/EER_PUBLICATIONS/CEER_PAPERS/Electricity/Tab2/C12-SDE-33-03_RES%20SR_25%20June%202013%20revised%20publication.pdf)
- [129] Haas R *et al.* A historical review of promotion strategies for electricity from renewable energy sources in EU countries. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. (2011), (15): 1003-34.
- [130] <http://www.renewableenergyfocus.com/view/15892/status-of-feed-in-tariffs-in-europe-2010/> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [131] <http://www.renewablesinternational.net/eu-energy-commissioner-criticizes-german-energy-policy/150/537/59979/> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [132] <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2013-12-02/u-nations-approve-pact-with-china-on-solar-panel-trade.html> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [133] <http://eib.europa.eu/products/project-bonds/index.htm> [accessed 12/12/13]

- [134] Standard & Poor's Rating Services. How Europe's New Credit Enhancements For Project Finance Bonds Could Affect Ratings. 2012. (http://www.eib.europa.eu/attachments/standardpoors_new_credit_enhancements_for_projects_20121113.pdf)
- [135] http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_BEI-13-117_en.htm [accessed 12/12/13]
- [136] <http://eib.europa.eu/projects/press/2013/2013-204-institutional-investor-support-for-greater-gabbard-offshore-transmission-link-encouraged-by-first-use-of-project-bond-credit-enhancement-scheme-in-uk.htm> [accessed 12/12/13]
- [137] (EC) European Commission. 30th Annual Report on Monitoring the Application of EU Law 2012. COM (2013) 726 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/eu_law/docs/docs_infringements/annual_report_30/com_2013_726_en.pdf).
- [138] Official Journal of the European Union. Decision No 406/2009/EC. April 2009. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009D0406&from=EN>)
- [139] (EC) European Commission. A policy framework for climate and energy in the period from 2020 to 2030. COM (2014) 15 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/doc/2030/com_2014_15_en.pdf)
- [140] <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/en34-energy-subsidies> [accessed 13/12/14]
- [141] e-Highway2050. Deliverable D1.1 - Review of useful studies, policies and codes. February 2013.
- [142] KPMG International. Taxes and incentives for renewable energy. June 2012. (<http://www.kpmg.com/Global/en/IssuesAndInsights/ArticlesPublications/Documents/taxes-incentives-renewable-energy-2012.pdf>)
- [143] (EC) European Commission. Energy Economic Developments in Europe. January 2014. (http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/publications/european_economy/2014/pdf/ee1_en.pdf)
- [144] (OECD) Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Inventory of estimated budgetary support and tax expenditures for fossil fuels 2013. January 2013. (<http://www.oecd.org/site/tadffss/48805150.pdf>)
- [145] Official Journal of the European Union. Directive 2009/72/EC. July 2009. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0072>)
- [146] (EC) European Commission. Single Market Scoreboard Transposition: Reporting Period 11/2012 – 05/2013. 2013. (http://ec.europa.eu/internal_market/scoreboard/_docs/2013/infringements/2013-scoreboard-infringements_en.pdf)
- [147] Official Journal of the European Union. Regulation (EC) No 714/2009. July 2009. (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:211:0015:0035:EN:PDF>)
- [148] <http://www.europeanenergyforum.eu/events/completing-iem-and-paving-way-towards-2030-through-network-codes> [accessed 27/02/14]
- [149] ENTSO-E. European Network Code Development: the importance of network codes in delivering a secure, competitive and low carbon European electricity market. March 2013. (https://www.entsoe.eu/Documents/Network%20codes%20documents/General%20NC%20documents/130327_NC_development_final.pdf)
- [150] http://www.ceer.eu/portal/page/portal/EER_HOME/EER_ACTIVITIES/EER_INITIATIVES/ERI [accessed 27/02/14]
- [151] (EC) European Commission. Guidance on the use of renewable energy cooperation mechanism. SWD (2013) 440 final. (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/com_2013_public_intervention_swd_05_en.pdf)
- [152] (EC) European Commission. European Commission guidance for the design of renewables support schemes", SWD (2013) 439 final.

- [153] http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/glossary/civil_society_organisation_en.htm
[accessed 27/02/14]
- [154] (EC) European Commission. An Energy Policy for Consumers. SEC (2010) 1407 final.
([http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/forum_citizen_energy/sec\(2010\)1407.pdf](http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/forum_citizen_energy/sec(2010)1407.pdf))

Annex 1 – Strategic Reference Framework

Table 35 - SRF relevant objectives and targets

CDF1: Social Perception and Acceptance	
Environmental and sustainability objectives	Relevant Targets
<p>Social equity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empower people and help build a cohesive society through high levels of employment, investment in skills and education, R&D, poverty alleviation, modernised labour markets, labour mobility, training, entrepreneurship and social protection systems (Europe 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011); • Promote transparency and public participation in electricity grid-development (European Grid Declaration, 2011); • Inform and engage citizens in the decision-making process, while technological choices need to take account of the local environment (Energy Roadmap 2050); • Ensure that pricing schemes remain transparent and understandable to final consumers (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Ensure that all customers enjoy uninterrupted, universal availability of energy products at prices which are affordable, transparent and non-discriminatory, whilst being cost-reflective and contributing to the EU’s wider social objectives and maintain appropriate safety nets for vulnerable consumers (Directive 2009/72/EC; ETI, 2013; Energy 2020, 2010); • Apply the principles of ‘user pays’, ‘beneficiary pays’ - in terms of cross-border cost-benefit allocation, and ‘tax payer pays’ - burden-sharing for commercially nonviable and ‘EU-wide benefit’ infrastructure (Energy 2020, 2010); • Provide specific support to vulnerable consumers to enable them to finance necessary investments to improve energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC); • Promote the fair distribution of costs and benefits from pan-European electricity-grid (Energy 2020, 2010); • Promote innovative and carefully considered use of taxation and pricing to encourage behaviour change or to fund investments (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy 2012); • Increase transparency and enhance public trust in energy infrastructure decision-making processes (Energy 2020, 2010; Directive 2009/72/EC) and provide the conditions to allow consumers and other 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ By 2020, 75% of the EU population aged 20-64 should be employed (Europe 2020, 2010); ✓ By 2020, 20 million less people should be at risk of poverty (Europe 2020, 2010).

<p>stakeholders to participate in energy debates at local, regional and national levels (Energy 2020, 2010; Directive 2009/72/EC; ETI, 2013);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the use of innovative approaches and technologies (e.g. social accountability) to promote demand reduction, increased energy efficiency and reduced fossil fuel reliance (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Directive 2009/72/EC; SET-PLAN, 2007; ECSER, 2012). 	
<p>Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the sustainable management and use of all resources including biodiversity/ natural capital, energy, land and marine resources (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Forestry Strategy, 2013); • Ensure that electricity grid-development supports a high level of protection for Europe’s biodiversity and natural environment (European Grid Declaration, 2011); • Conserve, enhance and properly value Europe’s natural resource base (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Resource Roadmap, 2011), natural processes and the ecosystem services they provide (GI Strategy, 2013); • Protect and enhance ecologically sensitive areas and all species and habitats covered by EU nature legislation (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; European Grid Declaration, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013); • Reduce fragmentation and degradation of forest landscapes and restore degraded forests (GI Strategy, 2013); • Balance the need for energy forestry with traditional forest uses (Forestry Strategy, 2013); • Ensure that energy production related water use is within environmental limits (Water Resource Blueprint, 2012); • Ensure the protection and enhancement of the marine environment (Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013) and prevent its deterioration reducing damaging inputs and marine pollution risks (MSFD, 2008; Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013); • Protect, enhance and restore soils and prevent further soil degradation, especially soil erosion and loss of soil organic matter, preserving soil functions (Soil Strategy, 2006). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Halt biodiversity loss and degradation of ecosystem services by 2020, including in the marine environment (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; Resource Roadmap, 2011; Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013); ✓ Fully implement the Birds and Habitats Directives and halt the deterioration in the status of all species and habitats covered by 2020 (Biodiversity 2020, 2011); ✓ By 2020, good environmental status of all EU marine waters is achieved (Resource Roadmap, 2011); ✓ By 2020, natural capital and ecosystem services will be properly valued and accounted for by public authorities and businesses (Resource Roadmap, 2011).
<p>Vulnerabilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the development of ecosystem and green infrastructure based approaches to climate change mitigation and adaptation, to disaster risk reduction (Biodiversity 2020, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013) and integrate climate risk into maritime activities (Resource Roadmap, 2011); • Ensure climate resilient coastal and marine areas (Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013); • Improve Europe’s resilience to climate change impacts including production systems and physical infrastructure (CC Adaptation Framework, 2009); • Promote legally binding nuclear-safety, security and non-proliferation standards worldwide (Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ By 2020, overall efficiency in the transport sector will deliver greater value with optimal use of resources and reduced impacts on climate change, noise, health and accidents (Resource Roadmap, 2011).

<p>2020, 2010) and develop systems for safe nuclear power (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011), transport of radioactive substances, as well as for the management of nuclear waste (Energy 2020, 2010; ETI, 2013);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step up efforts to accelerate the development and early deployment of electrification, and in general, of alternative fuels and propulsion methods, for the whole transport system as a means of improving air quality (RLCE2050, 2011); • Protect forests and biodiversity from the significant effects of storms, fires, water resource scarcity and pests, all of which may be exacerbated by climate change (Forestry Strategy, 2013); • Prioritise measures that are beneficial for both climate change mitigation and adaptation (CC Adaptation Framework, 2009); • A broader and more coordinated EU approach to international energy relations must become the norm, including redoubling work to strengthen international climate action (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Ensure that all climate financing contributes to "climate proof" development opportunities (RLCE2050, 2011). 	
CDF2: Energy Security and Technologies	
Environmental and sustainability objectives	Relevant Targets
<p>Energy efficiency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pave the way for large scale use of renewable energy in the decades beyond 2020 (Energy 2020, 2010); • Promote the balanced, multifunctional role of forestry in Europe’s bio-economy including the appropriate use of forest biomass for electricity (Forestry Strategy, 2013); • Promote a more resource efficient, green and competitive economy (Europe 2020, 2010); • Promote and improve energy efficiency and use of renewable energy and green infrastructure in Europe’s transport, housing and industry infrastructures (Resource Roadmap, 2011; GI Strategy, 2013; Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; RLCE2050, 2011); • Reduce the need for new electricity grid infrastructure and optimize the use of electricity through improved energy efficiency and smarter use of electricity (European Grid Declaration, 2011) supporting innovative integrated energy solutions at local level contributing towards transition to ‘smart cities’ (e.g.: energy management services, innovative pricing formulas, intelligent metering systems of smart grids) (Directive 2009/72/EC; Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; RLCE2050, 2011); • Elaborate long-term low carbon energy roadmaps with key partners to support technological, research, and industrial cooperation (EU EP, 2011); • Reinforce efficiency in energy supply and ensure that the ETS plays its full part in developing a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ By 2020, economic growth and wellbeing is decoupled from resource inputs (Resource Roadmap, 2011); ✓ By 2020, energy recovery from waste is limited to non-recyclable materials (Resource Roadmap, 2011); ✓ By 2020, increase energy efficiency by 20% (Europe 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011); ✓ Nearly two thirds of the electricity coming from low carbon sources by the early 2020 (Energy2020, 2010); ✓ By 2020, reduce GHG emissions by at least 20% compared to 1990 levels or by 30% if the conditions are right (Europe 2020, 2010); ✓ By 2030, reduce GHG emissions by at

<p>secure, competitive and fully decarbonized power sector (Energy 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the decarbonisation of the European energy market and a shift towards locally produced energy sources (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; RLCE2050, 2011); • Elaborate alternative visions and transition strategies towards the development of the Trans-European energy networks and other systems necessary to support the low carbon economy of the future (SET-PLAN, 2012); • Substitute coal and oil with gas, together with CCS, for a low-carbon technology for electricity generation (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Promote micro generation creating a degree of independence for consumers and empower consumers as micro producers with a stronger sense of ownership and control over their energy use (Renewable Energy 2012). 	<p>least 40% compared to 1990 (Energy and Climate 2030, 2014; RLCE2050, 2011);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ By 2050 reduce 80–95% domestic GHG emissions compared to 1990 levels (Energy2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011); ✓ By 2020, increase the share of renewable energy sources in our final energy consumption to 20% (Europe 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011); ✓ By 2030, increase the share of renewable energy sources in our final energy consumption to 27% (Energy and Climate 2030, 2014); ✓ 30% of RES in gross final energy consumption in 2030 and 75% in 2050 and a share of RES in electricity consumption reaching 97% in 2050 (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011).
<p>Innovation and technological development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speed up development and demonstration projects, as well new and flexible infrastructures, for the main technologies (2nd generation biofuels, smart grids, smart cities and intelligent networks, CCS, electricity storage and electro-mobility, next generation nuclear, renewable heating and cooling, flexible gas capacities) (Energy 2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Invest in new renewable technologies, such as ocean energy, concentrated solar power, and 2nd and 3rd generation biofuels, as competitive alternatives to fossil fuels respecting the sustainability of their production (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; SET-PLAN, 2007), considering their contribution to the stability and security of the grid on a level footing with conventional electricity generators (Renewable Energy 2012); • Give ocean technologies, advanced materials and manufacturing for renewable energy technologies higher priority in future research (Renewable Energy 2012); • Give energy storage technologies high priority in future research, achieving a breakthrough in its cost-efficiency (Renewable Energy 2012; SET-PLAN, 2012); • Deliver sustainable alternative fuels to the European transport fuel mix (ETI, 2013); • Make off-shore wind as lead application, doubling the power generation capacity of the largest wind turbines (SET-PLAN, 2007); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ By 2020, 3% of the EU’s GDP should be invested in R&D (Europe 2020, 2010); ✓ Apply CCS from 2030 onwards (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain competitiveness in fission technologies, together with long-term waste management solutions (SET-PLAN, 2012); • Uphold security and safety considerations in the development and deployment of new energy technologies (Energy 2020, 2010); • Promote the development of an economy, and economies of scale, based on knowledge, research and innovation capacity building (Europe 2020, 2010; ETI, 2013); • Support the development and take-up of innovative financing solutions for renewable energy and energy efficiency, including financing for their deployment (ETI, 2013), enabling market actors to drive down the costs of renewable energy through improved research (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Ensure more cooperation on 'public good' research, as well as on longer-term frontier research (SET-PLAN, 2012); • Increase effort to remain at the forefront of the booming international market for energy technology and step up cooperation with third countries in specific technologies (Energy 2020, 2010); • Set up strategic alliances for industry to share risks and benefits of research and demonstration and exploit the synergies between technologies enabling the pooling of resources to develop new technologies that offer huge potential but are currently far from market competitiveness and are beyond the means of individual countries (SET-PLAN, 2012); • Reinforce the role of technology and innovation within energy policy, not just with specific technologies, but also by triggering new business models, market and social adaptation and energy system improvements that offer a longer term strategic perspective for investments (ETI, 2013); • Provide the necessary framework and initial incentives for rapid investments in smart grid technologies to support competitive retail market, well-functioning energy services, energy savings and efficiency, the massive integration of renewable and decentralized energy sources, and to accommodate new types of demand (like EV) (EPI 2020, 2010; SET PLAN, 2007), bringing to mass market more efficient energy conversion, end-use systems and the application of ICT in energy and transport and for smart urban applications (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Enable commercial use of technologies for CO₂ capture, transport and storage through demonstration at industrial scale, including whole system efficiency and advanced research (SET-PLAN, 2012); • Adopt an open and flexible approach to further develop a portfolio of cost-effective and sustainable energy options (ETI, 2013). 	
<p>Energy security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in decentralised renewable power generation and ensure integration of large scale generation from renewable sources (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011, RLCE 2050); • Guarantee energy security of supply (Energy 2020, 2010); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Overall increase of interconnection capacity by 40% up to 2020 (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); ✓ Fully eliminate energy islands in the EU

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver competitive solutions for a clean, sustainable, secure, flexible and efficient energy system (ETI, 2013); • Ensure the continuity of electricity supply and rationalise demand for infrastructures (ETI, 2013); • Develop market and regulatory models, internal and cross-border infrastructure, interconnectors across maritime areas and smart grids to ensure the EU's stability and security of supply (Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; RLCE2050, 2011) as well as the support to distributed generation from small producers (Renewable Energy, 2012); • Secure Europe's energy supply by promoting the development of marine energy sources and the interconnection of energy networks (Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive, 2013); • Accommodate ever-increasing wind surplus generation (Northern and Baltic Seas), increase renewable generation (East and South of Europe, and North Africa), connect new generation hubs with major store facilities (Nordic countries and the Alps) and with major consumption centres (Central Europe) (EIP 2020, 2010); • Diversify fuels, sources of supply and transit routes - namely for natural gas - essential for EU security (Energy 2020, 2010)), strengthen the safety and security framework and lead international efforts in this field (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Keep an European presence in domestic oil refining (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011), ensure the security of oil supply, support private investments in possible alternative infrastructures, in order to reduce oil transport by sea and reduce environmental risks (EIP 2020, 2010) and open the Southern Corridor as a matter of urgency (EU EP, 2011); • Strengthen the regional network in North-South and East-West power flows directions, in order to assist market and renewables integration, including connections to storage capacities and integration of energy islands (EIP 2020, 2010); • Develop a tri-partite cooperation at political and administrative level with Russia and Ukraine to ensure stable and uninterrupted gas supplies through the Eastern Corridor (EU EP, 2011). 	<p>by 2015 (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Be in a position to rely on significant additional energy supply sources and routes by 2020 (Energy 2020, 2010).
<p>CDF3: Geo-Political Economy and Regional Equity</p>	
<p>Environmental and sustainability objectives</p>	<p>Relevant Targets</p>
<p>International competitiveness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop cooperation to build international partnerships on a broader basis: expand and diversify links between the European network and neighbouring countries with a particular focus on North Africa, address the import of carbon-intensive energy (, notably electricity and enhance cooperation towards creating a level playing field concerning market and carbon regulation (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Efficiency must become a profitable business in itself, leading to a robust internal market for energy- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ By 2020, EHS will be phased out (Resource Roadmap, 2011); ✓ By 2020 a major shift from taxation of labour towards environmental taxation, including through regular adjustments in real rates, will lead to a substantial increase in the share of environmental

<p>saving techniques and practices and commercial opportunities internationally (Energy 2020, 2010);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take a strong, effective and equitable position on the international stage to secure energy, while promoting free and transparency energy markets and contributing to greater security and sustainability in the energy production and use (EU EP, 2011); • Build up the external dimension of EU internal energy market (EU EP, 2011) and ensure that EU neighbours can access and reap the benefits of the enlarged EU internal market and create a more stable environment for economic activity (ENP, 2006); • Deepen the existing dialogues with major energy suppliers and extend new dialogues with emerging energy producers to include, for example, renewable energy and liquefied natural gas (EU EP, 2011); • Consider additional multilateral agreements in energy and transport, strengthen the existing ones and work for the extension of the EU energy and transport networks to neighbouring countries, as well as interoperability (ENP, 2006); • Scale up efforts for achieving the EU-Africa 2020 energy targets of reliable and secure supply of energy and increased access to sustainable energy services by: enabling full use of cooperation mechanisms, interconnecting the South Western Europe system to accommodate wind, hydro and solar, and developing connections with Central Europe to make best use of existing infrastructure in the Southern Mediterranean and explore Northern Africa’s renewable energy sources (EIP 2020, 2010; EU EP, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012); • Work towards a gradual development of global carbon markets (RLCE2050, 2011) promoting EU’s global role in the development of a future low-carbon energy market (Energy 2020, 2010); • Encourage third countries to implement ambitious energy efficiency and renewable energy policies and carbon pricing, while ensuring a level playing field for the power sector (EU EP, 2011); prepare joint approaches towards China, India, Brazil, and South Africa, to promote policies and technologies in the areas of low carbon energy and demand management, and upgrade existing bilateral dialogues to encompass sustainable modernisation paths and energy security aspects (EU EP, 2011); • Pool efforts with US, Japan and other industrialized partner countries to accelerate the development of ambitious policies with low carbon technologies and energy efficiency, including regulatory cooperation, joint R&D projects, researchers mobility, and joint work on better performing materials and standards for critical and emerging technologies (EU EP, 2011); • Engage with Russia on the implementation of the EU 2050 Energy Roadmap and promote the viability and continuous functioning of the existing oil and gas infrastructure in the East (EU EP, 2011); • Promote concrete action on offshore drilling safety, nuclear safety and low emission development strategies in the G-8/G-20 energy agenda and cooperate with third countries to address the volatility of energy prices (EU EP, 2011); 	<p>taxes in public revenues, in line with the best practice of MS (Resource Roadmap, 2011).</p>
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainstream “energy security, access and sustainability” in the post-2013 EU external financial frameworks (EU EP, 2011); • Call for a systematic industry participation in the EU energy dialogue with strategic partner countries (EU EP, 2011); • Negotiate EU-level agreements with third countries where necessary to facilitate large-scale infrastructure projects (EU EP, 2011); • Create a forum with interested partners in the Mediterranean for actively promoting the highest offshore oil and gas safety standards in the region (EU EP, 2011); • Exploit further synergies with the International Energy Agency's work on energy forecasts, market analysis and technology collaboration (EU EP, 2011); • Establish a mechanism for increased transparency and information exchange on MS bilateral energy agreements with third countries (EU EP, 2011); • Extend nuclear safety assessments to the EU neighbours and strengthen cooperation on nuclear safety to promote convergence on regulatory framework and standards (EU EP, 2011); • Formalise the principle whereby MS act in the benefit of the EU as a whole in bilateral energy relations with key partners and in global discussions (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011); • Ensure the consistency and mutual reinforcement of EU external energy policy with other EU external activities (development, trade, climate and biodiversity, enlargement, Common Foreign and Security Policy and others) (Energy Roadmap 2050); • Step up international cooperation on climate change adaptation (CC Adaptation Framework, 2009); • Ensure an active EU participation and leading role in the global energy governance debate, through its regular presence in relevant international energy initiatives and frameworks (EU EP, 2011), while respecting the rule of law and the protection of EU and foreign investments in energy producing for energy security (Energy 2020, 2010). 	
<p>Market dynamics and regional equity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote pan-European electricity market integration and ensure integration of large-scale generation from renewable sources (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Energy 2020, 2010), namely by integrating MS national markets at one or more regional levels, as a first step towards the creation of a fully liberalised EU market (Directive 2009/72/EC); • Support and promote the implementation of a well-functioning carbon pricing and trading system (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011) and maintain incentives that reward low carbon investments and drive innovation (RLCE2050, 2011); • Integrate the Baltic States into the European market through reinforcement of their internal networks and strengthening of interconnections with Finland, Sweden and Poland (EIP 2020, 2010); 	<p>✓ By 2050, build a pan-European integrated energy market and guarantee security of supply.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote a market driven energy technology sector and the faster market roll-out of sustainable energy technologies (SET-PLAN, 2007; ETI, 2013; Renewable Energy, 2012); • Promote and improve the competitiveness and transparency of energy markets including the establishment of appropriate environmental standards (Energy 2020, 2010) promoting the use of market based instruments that incentivise sustainable production and consumption (e.g. green tax reforms) (Resource Roadmap, 2011); • Create synergies between energy objectives and other policies and instruments including trade, bilateral agreements, and development cooperation instruments and vice-versa (Energy 2020, 2010); • Eliminate barriers to trade such as "local content rules" or partial closure of public procurement markets (Renewable Energy, 2012); • Support regional cooperation to stimulate development of clusters constituting the first stage of a possible, future integrated European network CCS (EPI 2020, 2010); • Efficiency must become a profitable business in itself, leading to a robust internal market for energy-saving techniques and practices and commercial opportunities internationally (Energy 2020, 2010); • Maintain cost-effective, well-targeted public and private support schemes that are sustainable, consistent with technological progress, that provide access to capital for the energy sector at reasonable costs, including through new financing models where appropriate (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; RLCE2050, 2011), expose producers to market risks, do not hinder innovation or competition and include phase-out provisions, namely of inefficient and environmentally harmful subsidies (Resource Roadmap, 2011; Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012); • Improve support schemes (e.g. reduce administrative/capital costs, ensure appropriate levels of public funding) and ensure greater consistency, convergence and transparency in national approaches to avoid internal market fragmentation (Renewable Energy, 2012; Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050); • Upgrade energy infrastructure particularly in MS that joined as of 2004 as well as in less developed regions (Energy 2020, 2010); • Ensure access to markets for flexible suppliers of all types (including new players and SMEs) and ensure that the market rewards flexibility (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012); • Restore macro-economic stability and address macro-imbalances (Europe 2020, 2010). 	
CDF4: European Regional Governance	
Environmental and sustainability objectives	Relevant Targets
<p>Policies and politics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote sustainable economic growth and public finances (Europe 2020, 2010); 	

- Ensure that landscape issues are considered in the development and implementation of international policies and programmes including transboundary initiatives (ELC, 2000);
- Support the integration and cooperation on national and regional maritime and coastal policies and objectives (**Proposed MSP & ICZM Directive**, 2013);
- MS must implement adequate policies for energy efficiency and make the most of National Energy Efficiency Action Plans (**Energy 2020**, 2010);
- Integrate climate change adaptation into EU policies (**CC Adaptation Framework**, 2009);
- Forest-linked EU policies should fully be taken into account in national forest policies (**Forestry Strategy**, 2013);
- Reflect the social aspects of energy pricing in the energy policy of MS (**Energy Roadmap 2050**, 2011);
- MS should soon develop national low carbon Roadmaps (**RLCE2050**, 2011), ensuring the optimization and harmonization of low carbon integrated system across the EU and its neighbouring countries (**SET-PLAN**, 2007);
- Ensure that MS-level policy development is supportive of a pan-European electricity market integration and that policy developments in MS do not create new barriers to electricity - or gas - market integration (**Energy Roadmap 2050**, 2011);
- Mainstream energy in all EU development policy instruments, and tailor support schemes and financing instrument to the specific needs of the sector, by privileging capacity development and technology transfer, including through research and innovation, stimulating decentralised renewable power production, promoting private initiatives and maximising the local value added (**EU EP**, 2011);
- Take full account of how each national electricity system is affected by decisions in neighbouring countries, as well as their energy markets and regulatory frameworks, in the development of energy policy (**Energy Roadmap 2050**, 2011);
- Facilitate strategic planning at both the technology and energy system levels to ensure a common approach to problems that have a cross-border dimension, such as networks (**SET-PLAN**, 2012);
- Improve and streamline significantly the existing rules and procedures for projects of European interest, while respecting the principles of public acceptance and existing environmental legislation (**Energy 2020**, 2010);
- Develop a unified policy framework that would synchronise all instruments from research and innovation policies to deployment policies to support early R&I efforts (**Energy Roadmap 2050**, 2011);
- Promote the alignment of European financial institutions' instruments with EU external energy policy priorities in order to improve visibility and impact of EU intervention in third countries (**EU EP**, 2011), ensuring effective solidarity, responsibility and transparency among all MS (**Energy 2020**,

<p>2010);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Formalise the principle whereby MS act in the benefit of the EU as a whole in bilateral energy relations with key partners and in global discussions (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011);• Ensure improvements to the regulatory framework for energy cooperation in the Mediterranean (Maghreb region) (Renewable Energy, 2012);• Strengthen partnerships for secure, safe, sustainable and competitive energy (EU EP, 2011; Energy 2020, 2010).	
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Responsibilities and competencies

- Enhance the support for reforms and efforts to improve trade and economic regulatory environment, e.g. by strengthening economic integration and cooperation in key sectors (**ENP, 2006**);
- Encourage cross-border and trans-national cooperation and development, locally and regionally, including strengthening of all forms of economic, legal and social cooperation across the borders, especially between regional and local authorities and within civil society (**SET-PLAN, 2007**);
- Ensure that actions at the EU and MS level supports EU 2020 and its flagship initiatives (**Europe 2020, 2010**);
- Deepen and extend the validity of the Energy Community Treaty beyond 2016, and focus on effective implementation (**EU EP, 2011**);
- Support more coherent, effective and efficient decision-making processes for electricity transmission investments needed to integrate renewable electricity supplies (**European Grid Declaration, 2011**);
- Engage policy-makers in active discussion with business and civil society about the policy conditions necessary to overcome the barriers to resource efficiency, working towards stronger multilateral mechanisms for a global governance of Public Goods (**Resource Roadmap, 2011**);
- Promote a regulatory framework that supports the attainment of common objectives, through engagement with political and policy forums, administrations and regulatory bodies at all levels of jurisdictions, umbrella groups, affiliates and subsidiary partners, contractors, costumers, the media and the public (**European Grid Declaration, 2011**);
- Scale up public authorities' capacity to work constructively with civil society, increasing trust and competencies to build up dialogue and opportunities for partnerships (**ECSER, 2012**), and increase focus in all dialogues on good energy governance and investment, sustainable energy and energy efficiency (**EU EP, 2011**);
- Provide transparency and facilitate participation of the public in the decision-making process by ensuring open and transparent debates at local, regional and national level to enhance public trust and acceptance of electricity installations (**EIP 2020, 2011**; **European Grid Declaration, 2011**), promoting access to environmental information and public participation, in the spirit of the Aarhus Convention (**European Grid Declaration, 2011**);
- Include all concerned actors (such as CSOs, private sector, partner governments, local authorities, parliaments, national institutions) in national or sectorial policy dialogues (**ECSER, 2012**);
- Ensure the implementation of intelligent metering systems that shall assist the active participation of consumers in the electricity supply market, and foster the consistency of regional legal, regulatory and technical framework to create a competitive internal market in electricity (**Directive 2009/72/EC, 2009**);
- Enhance access to public fund of regions and MS that constructively engage and succeed in

<p>facilitating the timely construction of projects of European interest (Energy 2020, 2010);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Permit a better gathering and sharing of data and information to support sound energy technology policy making and guide investment decision (SET-PLAN, 2007);• Promote the increased use of the cooperation mechanisms, allowing MS to achieve their national binding targets by trading renewable energy and so lowering their costs (Renewable Energy, 2012);• Ensure the existence of recourses (by TSOs) in order to carry out a proper and efficient transmission, and develop and maintain an efficient, secure and economic transmission system (Directive 2009/72/EC, 2009; European Grid Declaration, 2011), ensuring greater responsibilities for system costs among producers, in addition to TSOs (Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011) and coordination of all network codes for the relevant TSOs and other market actors (Directive 2009/72/EC, 2009);• Promote cooperation between NGOs and TSOs to enable timely grid development, knowledge brokerage and trust in order to develop better approaches and find best practices for the implementation of laws and regulations, enabling a more effective and efficient planning and decision-making procedures (European Grid Declaration, 2011);• Increase local CSOs capacity to perform their roles as independent development actors more effectively, support them as service providers in collaborative multi-actor partnerships coordinated with national authorities, with the long-term objective of promoting more accountable, effective and sustainable systems at the service of populations and promote a meaningful and structured participation of CSOs in domestic policies, in EU programming cycle and in international processes (ECSER, 2012);• Support international arrangement to promote and monitor and enable environment for CSOs (ECSER, 2012).	
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Annex 2 – Trend Analysis

CDF1 - Social Acceptance and Acceptability

The objective / scope of CDF1 on Social Acceptance and Acceptability is all factors that affect a sense of **well-being**, and consequently determine **acceptance** and **acceptability** of grid development, including **social equity, individual and community benefits, environmental limits** related to issues such as noise, health issues, biodiversity, ecosystem services and **landscape, urbanisation, energy related** behavioural trends, as well as **vulnerability to climate change** and extreme events.

Social Equity

One aspect of social equity is access to energy system benefits and costs to all citizens. Between 1990 and 2001, there was an apparent decoupling of energy consumption and economic growth (GDP) within Europe. GDP has been rising though gross inland energy consumption³⁵ has remained stable. **Primary energy intensity**³⁶ has therefore decreased (Figure 6). This decoupling is led by increases in GDP that are helping to drive increases in energy efficiency. Also, increased energy efficiency is being encouraged as a means of increasing Europe's competitiveness [11]. However an alternative school of thought suggests that cost savings made through energy efficiency gains release money that can then be spent on other goods [12], including energy intensive goods such as heat and mobility. This phenomenon is sometimes referred to as the 'rebound effect' [13] and/or Jevon's paradox.

³⁵ Gross inland energy consumption is the total energy demand of a country or region i.e. the quantity of energy necessary to satisfy inland consumption of the geographical entity under consideration: http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/statistics_explained/index.php/Glossary:Gross_inland_energy_consumption [accessed 19/02/14].

³⁶ Primary energy intensity is the ratio between gross inland energy consumption (see above) and GDP. Decoupling of energy consumption from economic growth may result from reducing the demand for energy services (e.g. heating, lighting, transport), by using energy in a more efficient way (thereby using less energy per unit of economic output) or a combination of the two: <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/total-primary-energy-intensity-1> [accessed 19/02/14].

Figure 6 - Energy intensity in the EU-27 [14]

Additionally, decreased energy intensity is also an effect of structural changes within Europe's economy including a shift from industry to services (which are typically less energy intensive) and a shift within the industrial sector from energy intensive industries to hi-tech, value added, less energy intensive industries [15]. As much of Europe's energy intensive manufacturing industry has now been effectively outsourced (e.g. to the Far East), access to energy system benefits is maintained whilst some costs have been exported. This may affect the overall social equity inherent to Europe's energy system.

In the EU-27, final **household energy consumption** per person decreased by 0.6% between 2006 and 2010. However, household electricity consumption increased by 2.5% during this period with the largest increases in Eastern Europe. This increase is due to changing energy **consumption behaviours** e.g. increased household appliances, consumer electronics, information and communication equipment, in addition to increasing disposable income [16]. In essence, there is a trend of increased household electricity consumption driven by increased disposable income and access to electrified household appliances, consumer electronics etc.

Electricity consumption may also increase if there is electrification of the transport sector, though the pace of electrification is likely to be dependent on affordability and the availability of recharging facilities / infrastructure. There are also concerns that transport related electricity consumption could increase further due to the 'rebound effect' (see above) as electricity is cheaper than petrol as a transport fuel [17]. Given these issues, there is a concern that access to the benefits and costs of an increasingly electrified transport sector may not be evenly distributed for all individuals and areas. As a result, some parts of the EU may be subject to volatile petrol prices, whilst missing out on the health and financial benefits of cleaner / cheaper EV.

In southern Europe, MS' electricity consumption increased between 1990 and 2005 in Portugal (by 160%), Cyprus (141%), Spain (124%) and Greece (123%) attributed to an increase in air conditioning systems usage [18]. Climate change is predicted to intensify droughts in central and southern Europe and in the Mediterranean region, and lead to “more frequent, longer and / or more intense” heat waves in Europe [19]. These changes may further increase electricity consumption in these areas. On the other hand, household electricity consumption behaviours may become more efficient if there is greater use of smart meters in the future to monitor electricity usage, noting that smart meters could help reduce consumption across the range of household electrical appliances and not just air conditioning. Average electricity consumption savings of between 5-12% have already been reported as a result of smart meter usage though the benefits are debated. For example some studies have found energy savings ranging from as low as 1.1% to greater than 20% while other studies have found no savings at all [20].

Electricity prices (EUR per kWh) for household consumers in the EU-27 have risen by an average of 40% from 2005 to 2013. Between 2002 and 2013 there were large increases in Cyprus (increase of 169.5%), Malta (155.9%), Ireland (121.0%), Estonia (117.5%), Spain (104.0%) and Greece (101.7%) [21] (Table 36). There is often public opposition to fuel price rises which can disproportionately affect lower income households as they spend a large proportion of their income on energy [22].

Table 36 - Electricity prices for household consumers ordered by highest percentage change [21]

Member State ³⁷	2002 Price (EUR per kWh)	2013 Price (EUR per kWh)	Percentage Change (%)
Cyprus	0.0845	0.2277	169.47
Malta	0.0631	0.1615	155.94
Ireland	0.0883	0.1951	120.95
Estonia	0.0457	0.0994	117.51
Spain	0.0859	0.1752	103.96
Greece	0.0580	0.1170	101.72
Czech Republic	0.0642	0.1249	94.55
Sweden	0.0701	0.1359	93.87
United Kingdom	0.1031	0.1658	60.81
Finland	0.0697	0.1102	58.11
Austria	0.0932	0.1413	51.61
Denmark	0.0865	0.1300	50.29
Hungary	0.0723	0.1061	46.75
Netherlands	0.0923	0.1333	44.42
Poland	0.0818	0.1155	41.20
Belgium	0.1137	0.1583	39.23
Slovenia	0.0858	0.1177	37.18
Luxembourg	0.1148	0.1447	26.05
Germany	0.1261	0.1493	18.40
France	0.0923	0.1007	9.10

³⁷ These MS were used as there is data available on the 2002 and 2013 prices. Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Croatia and Romania were omitted as the former four had data from 2004 and the latter two from 2005.

Italy	0.1390	0.1498	7.77
Portugal	0.1223	0.1210	-1.06

Increases in electricity and energy (household gas) prices can have particularly adverse effects on lower income households who are more vulnerable to price fluctuations. This is a particular issue in terms of access to energy system benefits and costs for all citizens. Defining and identifying vulnerable customers is inherently difficult as there are many causes of vulnerability. Also, vulnerability is unlikely to be static and may evolve in parallel to energy sector developments [23]. Key drivers and exacerbating factors of vulnerability are set out at Figure 7. Tracking the dynamics of these drivers can support an understanding of potential trends and fluctuations in energy price vulnerability though it has not been possible to identify any discernible trends as part of this study.

	Market Conditions	Individual Circumstances	Living Conditions	Social/Natural Environment
Drivers	Final energy price levels	Income level	Under-occupancy	State of economy
	Level of competition	Health and disability	Type of heating system	Climate
		IT skills/internet access	Quality of housing stock	
Exacerbating factors	Debt policies	Age	Equipment efficiency (boilers etc.)	Governance (local/regional/national)
	Selling and pre-contractual practices	Single-parent/ large family/ carer	Location	
	Bill transparency/ accessibility	Retired/unemployed	Tenancy	Social inclusion
		Available payment methods	Immigrant or ethnic minority	
	Inclusiveness of corporate system designs and service provision	Prepayment meters		

Figure 7 - Key drivers and exacerbating factors of energy price vulnerability [23]

High energy prices can also exacerbate existing inequalities through fuel poverty³⁸ which has been found to exist across Europe [24]. Fuel poverty is another “manifestation of severe deprivation” and can deprive households of heating, cooling, hot water, lights and other domestic necessities [25]. Fuel poverty is driven by the three interacting injustices of procedural injustice, distributional injustice and injustice in recognition (see Figure 8). There is no universal definition of **fuel poverty** or method by which it can be measured. However, one attempt used four scenarios to estimate composite levels of fuel poverty across the EU-25 (see Table 37). There are estimated to be 50 to 125 million people across Europe in fuel poverty and these figures are expected to rise in the near future [26]. Based on a survey of 72 power and

³⁸ This refers to the inability of sectors of the population to afford to keep warm and is demonstrated when the home is cold or when fuel debts accumulate – see Thomson (2012).

utilities companies in 43 countries, fuel poverty is a key European energy industry concern that is anticipated to worsen over the next 20 years [27].

Figure 8 - The three forms of injustice and their component parts in fuel poverty (left) and the interacting distributional injustices (right) [28]

Table 37 - Composite levels of fuel poverty across the EU-25 (% of households) [24]

Member State	Scenario 1 ³⁹	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
Austria	6.2	5.9	8.2	6.7
Belgium	9.2	8.5	11.9	9.8
Bulgaria	31.1	31.2	30.5	30.6
Cyprus	23.8	17.8	22.8	21.2
Czech Republic	7.5	6.4	9.2	7.6
Denmark	2.7	3.3	4.8	3.6
Estonia	6.8	8.1	11.0	8.5
Finland	3.8	4.7	4.3	4.2
Germany	7.6	6.9	9.4	7.9
Greece	16.8	16.6	17.5	16.8
Hungary	16.2	16.4	21.3	17.8
Ireland	7.3	8.2	9.5	8.2
Italy	13.8	14.0	16.1	14.5
Latvia	18.9	17.0	20.6	18.6
Lithuania	19.9	15.1	19.8	18.1
Luxembourg	4.5	4.6	8.1	5.7
Netherlands	5.5	5.5	8.9	6.6
Poland	19.0	15.7	19.0	17.7
Portugal	23.4	15.3	19.5	19.2
Romania	24.6	24.0	24.4	24.1
Slovakia	6.4	5.7	7.2	6.3

³⁹ Fuel poverty is difficult to measure; here it is based on questionnaire responses to three questions on the fundamental symptoms of fuel poverty. The four scenarios are based on the responses to three questions, but with higher weightings given to the question on their ability to “pay to keep their home adequately warm” (scenario 1), if their household is “in arrears on utility bills” (scenario 2), or has “leaks, damp or rot” (scenario 3), and then where an equal weighting is given to all three question responses (scenario 4).

Slovenia	14.2	15.7	20.2	16.5
Spain	7.6	7.1	10.3	8.2
Sweden	4.1	5.0	5.5	4.8
United Kingdom	6.5	5.0	8.4	6.6

Based on the 2006 Eurobarometer survey [29] (see Figure 9), the European public were most in favour of using renewable energy sources, such as solar (80% in favour) and wind (71% in favour) for energy generation. A lower percentage favoured fossil fuels (42% in favour of gas, 27% oil and 26% coal) and nuclear energy (20%). Therefore solar was the most favoured technology and nuclear the least favoured⁴⁰. The **public's acceptance** of energy technologies is likely to be influenced by their perception of risk and may differ in individual cases based upon feelings of place attachment, procedural justice⁴¹ and accountability⁴². Unique events such as the 2011 Fukushima nuclear power station failure have negatively impacted public perception of nuclear energy, which in turn led to several MS taking a policy decision to phase out nuclear energy programmes [30]. Unique events are very difficult to predict, but can affect public acceptance. Feelings of place attachment may explain public opposition towards new energy technologies based on risks to landscape integrity through visual impacts. Procedural justice and accountability can also drive public opposition towards energy infrastructure projects if the decision-making process is characterised by a lack of transparency around the roles of private companies, governments and regulators [31].

⁴⁰ The data available on public acceptance is limited and based upon a 2006 Eurobarometer survey (ibid) which may be repeated. Future iterations of ehighway2050 should account for more recent Eurobarometer surveys where available.

⁴¹ Procedural justice refers to the “perceived fairness, equity, and transparency of decision-making processes” (Devine-Wright, 2012:3, <http://eab.sagepub.com/content/early/2012/04/10/0013916512440435.full.pdf+html> [accessed 12/12/13]).

⁴² Accountability refers to “the quality or state of being accountable; especially an obligation or willingness to accept responsibility or to account for actions. In this context accountability is in relation to institutions related to decision making around energy technologies: private companies, governments and regulators.” E-Highways 2050 WP1.4.

Figure 9 - EU citizens' acceptance of different sources of energy [29]

Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services

Three specific ecosystems are considered here as they are particularly important for providing ecosystem services (fuel), regulating services (climate, erosion and water regulation) or both. Provisioning services are crucial as biomass may be an important component of the electricity generation mix in 2050. Regulating services are crucial as they provide people and infrastructure with natural protection against extreme climatic events. Ecosystems⁴³ considered are: 1) agro-ecosystems; 2) forests; and 3) wetlands⁴⁴. Table 38 provides key summary data for each of these ecosystems. Further relevant detail is provided in the text below.

Table 38 - Change in extent, conservation status and key ecosystem services provided by agro, forest and wetland ecosystems in the EU-27[32], [33]

Ecosystem	Total area change (1990 – 2006)		Conservation status (2008)	Key ecosystem services provided and management issues
Agro	Quant. data	-17,087km ² -0.9%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 76% habitats assessed as unfavourable 70% of species assessed as unfavourable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Semi-natural/mixed cultivated land agro-ecosystems can provide a greater range of ecosystem services including water and climate regulation Large scale/intensively managed productive agro-ecosystems provide key provisioning services (e.g. food and fuel) but regulating and cultural service provision is more limited
	Trend	↓		

⁴³ Most of the data used in this section is of relevance to the EU-27 although some data is limited to other geographical scopes.

⁴⁴ This does not preclude consideration of risks/opportunities for other ecosystems. Rather, these three ecosystems are the focus for trends analysis.

Forest	Quant. data	+5,378km ² +0.6%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 63% habitats assessed as unfavourable • 52% of species assessed as unfavourable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forests have the potential to provide a diverse range of ecosystem services including key provisioning services (e.g. wild food and fresh water) and regulating services (e.g. erosion, water and climate regulation) • Forest ecosystem services can be degraded by intensified agricultural practices, use of non-native species and increased uniformity
	Trend			
Wetland	Quant. data	+394km ² +0.5%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 73% habitats assessed as unfavourable • 64% of species assessed as unfavourable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate regulation (carbon storage) • Water purification • Water regulation • Erosion regulation
	Trend			

Agro-ecosystems

The importance of agro-ecosystems goes beyond their function supplying key provisioning ecosystem services such as food and fuel⁴⁵. As per Table 38 agro-ecosystem extent is decreasing and several EU land use outlook studies to 2020 predict continued decrease in arable land cover though the area used to grow oilseeds is predicted to increase⁴⁶, in line with EU biofuel targets [34]. Driving forces affecting the extent and integrity of agro-ecosystems are urbanisation, afforestation and land abandonment. Semi-natural/mixed cultivated land agro-ecosystem types provide a greater diversity of ecosystem services including water and climate regulation. An additional driver affecting the loss and degradation of these types of agro-ecosystem is conversion to intensive agriculture systems. Future European and global socio-economic driving forces (e.g. population growth and biofuel demand) will continue to drive the simplification of farming systems and concentration on more productive areas. Whilst this will enhance certain provisioning services, regulating and cultural services are more likely to be degraded [33].

⁴⁵ As well as providing important provisioning services (including fuel), agro-ecosystems provide a reservoir of biodiversity with a range of rare and specialised species and characteristic managed habitats, supporting important functions such as pollination and recycling of organic matter. Agro-ecosystems are of fundamental importance to biodiversity protection in the EU e.g. 38% of the area of the Natura 2000 network is comprised of agro-ecosystems: EEA (2010) EU 2010 Biodiversity Baseline <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/eu-2010-biodiversity-baseline> [accessed 09/12/13].

⁴⁶ A recent study found that converting areas of grassland, extensive agriculture and wetland to biofuel crop production to meet EU biofuel targets would have negative impacts on farmland birds, particularly in Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary, France, Spain, Portugal and Italy. Bird populations in general may decrease by 10% with farmland bird populations projected to decrease even more: Nowicki et al (2009) Update of analysis of prospects in the Scenar 2020 study http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/analysis/external/scenar2020ii/report_en.pdf [accessed 10/12/13].

Forest ecosystems

The extent of forest-ecosystems⁴⁷ in Europe is increasing (see Table 38). This is being driven primarily by afforestation and natural regeneration [33]. Increases are predicted to occur on wetland and agricultural land and along tree margins in mountain and boreal areas [35]. A key driving force affecting the extent and management of forest ecosystems is EU policy on bio-energy production. Where EU-internal supply cannot meet demand, this policy may also impact land use/management outside the EU. Growing demand for forest biomass must be met through coordinated EU level policy to ensure that forests are managed sustainably for multiple benefits [36].

Forest ecosystems can provide a diverse range of ecosystem services though this is dependent on the environmental quality of forests which has been reduced in recent decades due to intensified silvicultural practices, use of non-native species and increased uniformity. For the period 1990-2010, the status of key provisioning services (wild food and fresh water) was degraded with negative trends identified whilst that of key regulating services (erosion and water regulation) was mixed with no discernible trends identified [36]. There is a concern that key driving forces affecting forest ecosystems may result in continued degradation of wider forest ecosystem services in favour of specific provisioning services. In many parts of the EU, key pressures are contributing to the fragmentation of forest ecosystems⁴⁸ which can reduce ecological connectivity and degrade certain landscape scale ecosystem processes (see Figure 10). Future electricity grid infrastructure and increased management of forests for biomass may further fragment and homogenise forest landscapes, reducing forest ecosystem biodiversity and ecological integrity.

⁴⁷ The majority of forest ecosystems in the EU are comprised of semi-natural stands and plantations of native or non-native species. Half of European forests are predominantly coniferous, a quarter predominantly broadleaved and a quarter mixed: EEA (2010) EU 2010 Biodiversity Baseline <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/eu-2010-biodiversity-baseline> [accessed 09/12/13]. Another recent study of forest biodiversity at the EU level found that most of the forests surveyed were 40-80 years old and mainly composed of one to three tree species: Hiederer and Durrant (2010) Evaluation of BioSoil Demonstration Project http://eusoils.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esdb_archive/eusoils_docs/other/EUR24258.pdf [accessed 09/12/13].

⁴⁸ Key pressures include urban sprawl, expanding transport networks and forest harvesting activities that break core forest areas into smaller, less connected patches: EEA (2010) EU 2010 Biodiversity Baseline <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/eu-2010-biodiversity-baseline> [accessed 09/12/13].

Figure 10 - Core forest fragmentation between 1990 and 2000 [32]

Wetland ecosystems

Although the extent of wetland ecosystems in Europe is increasing (see Table 38), this was attributed to an increase in the area of watercourses/bodies. Crucially, the area of marshes/bogs (which provide the broadest range of wetland ecosystem services) decreased by 5.0% (1,267km²)[32]. Driving forces affecting the extent and integrity of wetland ecosystems are agricultural intensification/development⁴⁹ and conversion to forest and semi-natural areas by commercial planting and natural succession [32]. Climate change is the main driver of natural succession in wetland ecosystems due to water regime changes and consequent drying out [37]. Wetland ecosystems provide a range of ecosystem services and are particularly important for carbon sequestration. For the period 1990-2010, the status of water regulation services was enhanced with positive trends identified whilst that of key regulating services (water purification and hazard regulation) was mixed with no discernible trends identified. Crucially, the status of climate regulation services was degraded though no discernible trend was identified [32]. Given that the key driving forces affecting wetland ecosystems (climate change and afforestation) are likely to persist, there is a concern that current trends related to wetland ecosystem extent, integrity and services may continue.

Land use

Examples of ecosystem specific **land use** issues are outlined above. Land use trends more generally are indicated in Figure 11. For the period 2000-2006, the greatest rate

⁴⁹ Resulting in degradation of marshes/bogs (including peatlands) due to burning, peat extraction, overgrazing and over exploitation of groundwater resources.

of change in a specific land cover type was for artificial areas⁵⁰ which increased by over 3% (circa 6,000km²). The key driving forces behind this trend are increases in European population and higher living standards/increased demand for per capita living space. For the same period, the most significant trends in rural land use change relate to forested land (an increase of circa 0.1% or 1,000km²) and arable land (a decrease of circa 0.25% or nearly 3,000km²)[33]. The key driving force behind both of these trends is afforestation, which is being undertaken primarily to meet increasing demands for bioenergy [32].

Figure 11 - Net land cover changes 2000-2006 in Europe [33]

Policy drivers

There are a number of current and emerging policy drivers in the EU that will affect land use/management and ecosystem service provision (not least EU energy policy and the ehighway 2050 initiative itself). Through CAP reform, 30% of direct payments (Pillar 1) will become conditional on the adoption of greening measures [38] (including maintenance of ecological set aside areas, crop rotation etc.), potentially contributing to improved management of agro-ecosystems and enhancement of key ecosystem services including climate/water/erosion regulation, habitat provision/connectivity and certain cultural services [39]. The continued development of GI strategy in the EU [40] and integration of GI based approaches in key policy areas⁵¹ is expected to enhance several ecosystem services of direct relevance to ehighway 2050 including those listed above. Finally, improved water resource management [41] combined with the accelerated implementation of water management related GI measures (especially wetland restoration) is also expected to

⁵⁰ Comprised of the following categories: 1) housing, services and recreation; 2) industrial, commercial units and construction; 3) transport networks and infrastructures; and 4) mines, quarries and waste dumpsites: EEA (2010) Land Use – SOER Thematic Assessment <http://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/europe/land-use> [accessed 09/12/13].

⁵¹ Including regional and cohesion policy, climate change and disaster risk management policy.

enhance provision of e-Highway2050 relevant ecosystem services, including those listed above.

Vulnerabilities

Potential **vulnerability to climate change** is expected to vary at a regional scale across Europe (see Figure 12). The majority of regions identified as having ‘medium’ and ‘highest’ vulnerability to climate change are in southern Europe due to hotter and drier climatic conditions. Predicted sea level rise, increases in ocean acidification / surface temperature and changes in marine species dynamics are predicted to make coastal regions more vulnerable in the future; especially those that are highly populated with a high dependency on summer tourism. Mountainous regions with high dependence on tourism and cities with high population densities, which may be at-risk of problems, are also regions that would be vulnerable [42]. Regions exposed to river flooding may also be highly vulnerable to climate change impacts.

Figure 12 - The potential vulnerability of Europe to climate change based upon the aggregate impacts of climate change and adaptive capacity to climate change⁵² (left) and the distribution of vulnerable people across Europe (right) [42]

In addition to increased vulnerability, there may be changes in adaptive capacity⁵³ in the future. Western European and Scandinavian regions are identified as having a high **adaptive capacity**, whilst south-east European and Mediterranean regions are lower in this regard [42]. Europe has an ageing population⁵⁴ and the elderly are considered to be more sensitive / vulnerable to climate change (see Figure 12).

⁵² The potential vulnerability to climate change has been calculated by combining the aggregate impacts of climate change (based on physical, economic, social and cultural factors) and adaptive capacity to CC.

⁵³ Adaptive capacity is based on existing knowledge, awareness, economic resources and technological, infrastructural and institutional capacity.

⁵⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=738&langId=en&pubId=5936&furtherPubs=yes> [accessed 11/12/13].

Climate change may also drive increased demand for temperature control technologies within Europe as the population attempts to reduce the effects of extreme temperatures. Whilst it is ‘very likely’⁵⁵ that there will be a decrease in the number of cold days in Europe, it is predicted that heat waves will become “more frequent, longer and / or more intense” [19]. It is predicted that the decrease in cold periods will result in a reduced demand for heating in Northern and North Western Europe, but the increase in heat wave frequency, duration and intensity will lead to an increased demand for cooling in southern Europe [42]. This increase may lead to an increase in the number of Europeans using air conditioning systems and a subsequent increase in energy consumption in the future. Signs of this are already apparent, with electricity consumption increases between 1990 and 2005 in southern Europe (Portugal, Cyprus, Spain and Greece) being attributed to an increase in air conditioning usage [18].

Europe’s electricity transmission infrastructure is expected to be at risk from climate change impacts in the future, including both overhead and underground lines. The North Sea, Baltic and Mediterranean regions are some of the areas predicted to be affected⁵⁶. Southern Europe is expected to be at increased risk of river flow drought events [42] with resultant effects on soil and ground movement potentially damaging underground cables [43].

Crucially, MS that rely on electricity generation from **sources at risk from climate change** impacts may be more vulnerable. Heat waves are a threat to nuclear and fossil-powered electricity generators as the increased temperatures reduce the efficiency of cooling mechanisms [42]; nuclear power stations generate 85% of France’s electricity, but the 2003 European heat wave caused them to reduce operations and led to over a 50% decrease in *Electricité de France’s* power exports [42]. Drought conditions in southern regions of Europe can reduce hydroelectric power generation and reduced water availability can adversely affect solar power generation. Climate change impacts on temperature and river flow are predicted to decrease the capacity of thermoelectric power plants by 6-19% in the 2040s compared to the 1980s [18]. Offshore wind farms are also predicted to be adversely impacted by sea level rises and an increase in the frequency of storm events [43]. There is also potential for biomass to be adversely affected by climate change impacts. In particular, it is anticipated that climate change will result in implications for forest ecosystems including forests that are managed for the production of biomass for energy generation. This is likely to include a range of biotic (e.g. changes in the frequency and consequences of pest / disease outbreaks) and abiotic (e.g. changes in

⁵⁵ The IPCC report assesses the likelihood of the outcome on a scale of 0-1% probability (exceptionally unlikely) to 99-100% probability (virtually certain). ‘Very likely’ describes the likelihood of the outcome being 90-100% probability (of occurring).

⁵⁶ Rademaekers et al (2011) present a more in-depth description of the effects of rising wind speeds, increasing temperatures, drought and flood events on electricity transmission infrastructure in Europe http://ec.europa.eu/energy/nuclear/studies/doc/2011_03_eur24769-en.pdf [accessed 12/12/13].

fire occurrence, changes in wind storm frequency and intensity) impacts on forest ecosystems [45].

Although there is little literature on the climate change resilience benefits of decentralised energy systems, there is some evidence on related benefits e.g. the use of local feedstock in decentralised bioenergy systems reduces the transportation distances involved in acquiring raw materials for energy production [47][46]. In this regard, decentralised systems may be less vulnerable to climate change related disruption of transport networks.

As mentioned above, drought conditions and reduced river flow are expected to increase, making small hydropower plants particularly vulnerable. The **number of small hydropower plants**⁵⁷ in the EU-27 increased by circa 21.1% between 2000 and 2010 [47]. During this period, total annual gross electricity generation (GWh) from all types of power plants in the EU-27 increased by 10.6%, however, the **proportion of total annual gross electricity generated (GWh) by small hydropower plants** in the EU-27 has increased from 1.45% to 1.46% from 2000 to 2010 [48]; this shows that whilst there has been an increase in the amount of electricity generated by small hydropower plants, this growth has not seen a substantial increase in its overall contribution to total gross electricity generation in the EU-27.

The European Hydro Database [49] contains energy data from 2007 on small hydropower plant installations and their gross installed capacity⁵⁸ (MW). Since 2007 the majority of European countries have undergone increases in their gross installed capacity of their small hydropower plants (see Table 39). However, between 2007-2012, Luxembourg experienced no change and Lithuania's installed capacity decreased. From 2007-2011, both Finland and Denmark also experienced decreases in their gross installed capacity.

In 2010⁵⁹, Germany had the highest number of small hydropower plant installations (more than 34.84% of EU small hydropower capacity), then Austria (11.32%) and Italy (11.25%); however, Italy (20.45%), France (15.77%) and Spain (14.40%) had the largest installed capacity (MW) [50] (see Table 40). It is predicted that by 2020 the number of plants may increase by 11.19% and the installed capacity by 29.32%⁶⁰.

⁵⁷ Small hydropower plants are described here as installations that are equal to or less than 10MW.

⁵⁸ This is defined as "the total gross installed generating capacity of all hydropower plants of the MS at the end of the reporting year (Y-1), measured in MW" http://streammap.asha.be/fileadmin/documents/Methodological_notes/Methodology_final_2011.pdf [accessed 18/02/14].

⁵⁹ The number of small hydropower installations (<=10 MW) and their gross installed capacity is analysed for 2010. Recent and complete data is not available for all countries; 2010 has been chosen as a trade-off between having a high number of countries providing data and using the most recent data possible.

⁶⁰ A combination of data of Gross Installed Capacity in 2010 from the STREAM Map HYDI Energy Database (<http://streammap.asha.be/14.0.html>) and predictions from the European Small Hydropower Association (2012) [accessed 12/12/13]

Table 39 - The percentage change in the gross installed capacity (MW) of small hydropower plants (<=10 MW) [49]

Country	2007 - 2012 Change (%)	Country	2007- 2011 Change (%)	Country	2007- 2010 Change (%)	Country	2007- 2009 Change (%)
Netherlands	36.4	Greece	103.1	France	2.8	Ireland	18.4
Slovakia	28.6	United Kingdom	20.4			Bulgaria	11.8
Estonia	27.3	Portugal	13.5				
Romania	27.1	Slovenia	6.3				
Austria	25.7	Spain	4.8				
Italy	18.4	Belgium	1.3				
Hungary	16.7	Germany	1.1				
Czech Republic	10.9	Finland	-0.6				
Poland	9.9	Denmark	-3.2				
Sweden	2.6						
Latvia	2.4						
Luxembourg	0.0						
Lithuania	-3.6						

Note: The change is calculated from 2007 and is based upon available data; some countries do not have full data sets to 2012 and their data is calculated for the years available e.g. France had data from 2007 to 2009 and the change has been calculated as 2007-2009).

Table 40 - Ranked gross installed capacity of small hydropower plants (<= 10 MW) in Europe and ranked number of small hydropower plants (<= 10 MW) in Europe in 2010 [49]

Gross installed capacity of small hydropower plants			Number of small hydropower plants		
Country	Gross Installed Capacity (MW)	Proportion of EU total (%)	Country	Number of Power Plants	Proportion of EU total (%)
Italy	2735	20.45	Germany	7516	34.84
France	2110	15.77	Austria	2441	11.32
Spain	1926	14.40	Italy	2427	11.25
Germany	1723	12.88	France	1935	8.97
Sweden	1268	9.48	Sweden	1853	8.59
Austria	1109	8.29	Czech Republic	1452	6.73
Portugal	449	3.36	Spain	1047	4.85
Romania	387	2.89	Poland	722	3.35
Finland	317	2.37	Slovenia	465	2.16
Czech Republic	297	2.22	Slovakia	279	1.29
Poland	275	2.06	Romania	274	1.27
UK	216	1.61	Belgium	232	1.08
Greece	183	1.37	Portugal	154	0.71
Slovenia	117	0.87	Finland	153	0.71
Slovakia	80	0.60	UK	152	0.70
Belgium	64	0.48	Latvia	142	0.66
Luxembourg	34	0.25	Greece	92	0.43

Lithuania	29	0.22	Lithuania	87	0.40
Latvia	26	0.19	Estonia	41	0.19
Hungary	13.8	0.10	Denmark	38	0.18
Denmark	9	0.07	Luxembourg	31	0.14
Estonia	7	0.05	Hungary	24	0.11
Netherlands	2.3	0.02	Netherlands	15	0.07

CDF2 - Energy Security and Technologies

CDF2 - Energy security and technologies' objective is to focus on clear trends towards favouring **EU and national policies concerning RES, technological enhancement** to favour **complementary, interconnectivity, smart initiatives** that reduce costs and increase benefits and ensure **energy security across and within MS policy and practice**.

Energy Efficiency

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) published in 2011 [51] (revised in 2012 [52]) requires the MS to set national indicative energy efficiency targets for 2020, which can be based on different indicators such as primary energy consumption (Figure 13), or final **energy savings** (Figure 14). The EU has set a policy target of achieving 20% energy savings by 2020 [51], as compared to *business as usual* energy use (Figure 13). Albeit the trends showing a considerable improvement in energy savings regarding both primary and final energy consumption (Figure 14), the EU remains ambivalent with respect to this target and reformulated it as “moving towards a 20% increase in *energy efficiency*” [53] as a result of evidence suggesting that the energy savings target will be missed by a wide margin (Figure 13, Figure 14 [53],[54]). In 2011, the EU-28 **primary energy consumption** (Figure 15) was 14.4% above the 2020 target of 1 483 Mtoe while final energy consumption was only 1.6 % above the 2020 target of 1 086 Mtoe [55]. The EU is moving towards the 2020 target of improving energy efficiency by 20%, but sustained efforts may be required [56].

However, it is important to note that the recently achieved reduction in primary energy consumption is only partly due to efficiency improvements. The original projections of 2007 assumed that GDP would grow steadily after 2007 [56]. Since GDP growth is one of the key drivers of energy consumption, the low economic performance in the EU partly explains the observed reduction. Structural changes and fuel switches also contributed to lower primary energy consumption [52].

Figure 13 - EU 28 Trends in Energy Savings regarding Primary Energy Consumption and the 2020 targets [53]

Figure 14 - Variation (%) on the EU 28 Energy Savings regarding Primary Energy Consumption (sP) and Final Energy Consumption (sF) [56]

Figure 15 - Primary Energy Consumption, EU27 1990-2020 [56]

The energy efficiency policy landscape has changed in many MS in recent years (Figure 16) but the different sectors are not addressed equally. The building sector received particular attention through a process driven by the implementation of the

2010 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive [57]. Measures addressing appliances and the transport sector are limited to the minimum requirements set in European legislation in many countries. A significant part of the effort is expected to come in many MS from policies already implemented due to the repealed Energy Services Directive. Some countries expect that the continuous impact of the economic crisis will contribute towards the target. Four MS (Bulgaria, Denmark, France and Germany) are making good progress in reducing energy consumption and primary energy intensity through well-balanced policy packages across relevant sectors.

Figure 16 - Final energy consumption in 2011 and targets for 2020 in EU MS [55]

Looking specifically at the **manufacturing industry** as a key sector regarding technological innovation for achieving the 2020 targets, its energy intensity is in line with the overall reduction mentioned in CDF1 (Figure 18). But its average **energy efficiency** between 2000 and 2010 reduced by -3%/year (-12% overall). Even though the sector's energy efficiency improved rapidly between 2000 and 2007 (1.8%/year at EU level) [58] (Figure 17), because of the economic crisis, there was no more progress after 2007 with even a rising trend in 2009 and 2010 which leads to the conclusion that the energy intensity improvements in this sector are not mainly driven by improvements on efficiency but by economic activity.

Figure 17 - Energy efficiency index in manufacturing industry (EU) [58]

Figure 18 - Trends in the energy intensities of manufacturing industry [58]

In 2009 a 20% reduction target for EU total **GHG emissions** compared to 1990 was also established. In 2011, GHG emissions of the EU-27 were down by 17% (Figure 19). Despite this positive trend, the average annual emission reductions between 2000 and 2011 are not sufficient to put the EU on a pathway to meeting its long-term commitment¹ to reduce GHG emissions by 80-95 % by 2050 compared with 1990 levels (Energy2020, 2010; RLCE2050, 2011) so additional effort is necessary. A large portion of the achieved emission reduction occurred during the early 1990s as a result of economic restructuring in Eastern Europe from heavy manufacturing industries to more service-based economies [55] as mentioned above (CDF1). The relatively low emissions reductions achieved between 2000 and 2008 were partly driven by a fuel switch in power generation from coal to natural gas and, to a minor extent, renewable energies. Significant reductions were also made in the waste sector through waste treatment processes with a lower carbon footprint. In the agricultural sector, declining numbers of livestock and less nitrogenous fertilisers also helped cut emissions (Figure 20) [59].

Figure 19 - GHG Emissions in UE 27 1990-2020 [56]

Figure 20 - GHG Emissions by sector, 2011. EU-27 [56]

Also the challenge of reducing SO₂ and NO_x emissions has been taken up successfully by the industry during the 1990s and the first decade of the XXIst century, with emission reductions of 62% between 1990 and 2007 for SO₂ and 39% for NO_x, despite an increase of electricity generation and heat by 32% in the same period. The deployment of abatement techniques and the switch from coal- and oil-fired generation to gas-fired generation are the main factors behind this trend. Thus the clear decoupling between energy demand increase and emissions (Figure 21) [60].

Figure 21 - Sectorial trends and projections of EU GHG emissions [55]

Note: Solid lines represent historic GHG emissions up to 2012 and with existing measures projections from 2010 onwards. Dashed lines represent with additional measures projections. The projected trends were calibrated to the 2010 year of the latest inventory data, which is the base year for the projections for most MS.

On January 2014, the EC presented the new EU framework on climate and energy for 2030 in order to reinforce the strategy for a competitive, secure and low-carbon EU economy (for detailed objectives, see Trend Analysis CDF4). The new common binding **GHG reduction target** is the centrepiece of the EU's energy and climate policy for 2030, and the target of a 40% emissions reduction below the 1990 level is to be met through domestic measures alone. The annual reduction in the 'cap' on emissions from EU ETS (Emissions Trading System) [61] sectors⁶¹ will be increased from 1.74% now to 2.2% after 2020. Emissions from sectors outside the EU ETS need to be cut by 30% below the 2005 level (2009 policy meant only a 14% reduction compared to 2005), and this effort is to be shared equitably between the MS. The EC invites the Council and the European Parliament to agree by the end of 2014 that the EU should pledge the 40% reduction in early 2015 [62]. Regarding the EU-wide binding **renewable energy target** of at least 27% in 2030, this is to be driven by a more market-oriented approach with enabling conditions for emerging technologies. However, it would not be translated into national targets through EU legislation, thus leaving flexibility for MS to transform the energy system in a way that is

⁶¹ EU ETS has covered, above certain capacity thresholds, power stations and other combustion plants, oil refineries, coke ovens, iron and steel plants and factories making cement, glass, lime, bricks, ceramics, pulp, paper and board. As for greenhouse gases, until 2013 only covered carbon dioxide emissions, with the exception of the Netherlands, which has opted in emissions from nitrous oxide. As from 2013, the scope of the ETS has been extended to also include CO₂ emissions from petrochemicals, ammonia and aluminium and N₂O emissions from the production of nitric, adipic and glycolic acid production and perfluorocarbons from the aluminium sector. The capture, transport and geological storage of all greenhouse gas emissions is also covered. These sectors will receive allowances free of charge according to EU-wide rules, in the same way as other industrial sectors already covered. As of 2012, aviation is also included in the EU ETS (http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/ets/faq_en.htm).

adapted to national preferences and circumstances [62]. On the matter of energy efficiency, this will be further considered in a review of the EED due to be concluded later on 2014.

On the issue of developing competitive, affordable and secure energy, the EC proposes a set of key indicators to assess progress over time and to provide a factual base for potential policy response. These indicators relate to, for example, energy price differentials with major trading partners, supply diversification and reliance on indigenous energy sources, as well as the interconnection capacity between MS, in order to also support policy measures towards research, development and innovation [62].

Considering the type of **RES used** until 2013, Hydropower dominates current RES-E generation in most EU countries, followed by wind, biomass, biogas and biowaste. The largest **RES-E potential** is found in wind energy (40%) followed by photovoltaic (PV) (17%) and biomass (15% - as aggregate of solid and gaseous biomass as well as biowaste), as well as promising future options such as tidal & wave (13%) or solar thermal energy (11%) (Figure 22) [63].

Figure 22 - RES-E as a share of the additional realisable potential in 2030 for the EU-15 - by country (left) as well as for total EU-15 (right) [63]

In the NMS, currently, almost 88% of the electricity from RES is generated by hydro power plants and 10% by solid biomass, mainly co-fired in thermal fossil fuel-based power plants. Only a minor part is provided by novel technologies such as wind energy and biogas. In line with the EU-15, the largest potential for these countries exist in wind energy (32%) and photovoltaic (25%) followed by solid biomass (19%) (Figure 23). Unlike the situation in the EU-15, the refurbishment and construction of large hydro plants holds significant potentials (4%). District heating solid fuel CHP's have only recently come down in size mainly driven by support for RES. Small CHP's are able to exclusively use biomass as a fuel, while larger units have difficulty procuring adequate amounts of biomass at reasonable prices within reasonable distances (distance correlates strongly with price) [64]. In short, renewable energies, driven by climate change, fuel security and other motives, will be providing more and more of our electricity in the future.

Figure 23 - RES-E as a share of the additional realisable potential in 2030 for the NMS - by country (left) as well as for total NMS (right) [63]

In terms of the **efficiency of conventional energy production technologies** (thermal generation) energy is produced mainly from fossil fuels (50.4 % produced from coal, gas and oil in 2010) but also from biomass, waste, geothermal and nuclear. The outputs from conventional thermal power stations consist of gross electricity generation and also of heat sold to third parties (in CHP plants) by conventional thermal public utility power stations as well as autoproducer thermal power stations [66]. For public thermal power plants the average efficiency increased in most EU-27 countries over the period 1990-2010, resulting in a net efficiency increase from 50.3% in 2005 to 50.4% in 2010 (48.6% excluding district heating) possibly due to increased fuel efficiency and/or installation design (Figure 24). For autoproducers the average efficiency also increased in most EU-27 countries over the period 1990-2010, resulting in a net efficiency of 57.9 % by 2010. The higher efficiency for autoproducers is largely explained by the fact that the installations of autoproducers are often designed to be more suitable for the heat and electricity demand on a location. Although overall improvements in electricity and heat generation efficiency were seen over the period 1990 to 2010, a marginal stagnation in the late 1990s and a decline in efficiency in the last four years was observed. This was due primarily to an increased utilisation of existing lower efficiency coal plants due to fast increase in electricity consumption, which is growing at an average rate of 1.4 % per year since 1990 [66].

Figure 24 - Efficiency of conventional thermal electricity and heat production. Left: including district heat; Right: excluding district heat [66]

Also determinant for the efficiency of thermal electricity and heat production are the DHC systems, designed for distributing heat generated in a centralized location for residential, industrial and commercial heating requirements such as space and water heating. In the previous decades, the heat was often obtained from a cogeneration plant burning fossil fuels but on the last decade, there's an increasing use of biomass, geothermal heating, and centralised solar heating, as well as nuclear power [67]. DHC plays a significant role in the supply of low-carbon heating and cooling in Europe (Figure 25). Currently, on average, over 80% of heat supplied by district heating originates either from RES or heat recovery. A 9.3% CO₂ reduction is possible with more DHC across the 32 European countries [67].

With 5000 systems supplying more than 10% of the total EU-27 heat demand, district heating is particularly widespread in North, Central and Eastern Europe, where market shares often reach 50% and more [65]. Overall, this technology is primarily used in the residential sector: in cities like Copenhagen, Helsinki, Warsaw, Vilnius and Riga as much as 90% of residential heat demands are satisfied by district heating. In Austria and Norway the service sector uses a large percentage of district heating whereas in the Czech Republic the industry sector is also using it [66]. The European share of district heating in industry is about 3.5% with higher shares (10-15%) in Hungary, Poland, Finland, Netherlands, and Czech Republic. Regarding cooling, due to the use of resources that otherwise would be wasted or difficult to use, district cooling systems reach efficiencies that are between 5 and 10 times higher than with traditional electricity-driven equipment. They can greatly contribute to avoiding electricity peak loads during summer, which are increasingly occurring due to cooling demands in all European regions, particularly in Southern Europe. District cooling currently has a share of 2% of total cooling market in Europe (some 3TWh) but this share is increasing fast: over the last decade the growth in installed capacity

increased tenfold, representing a considerable driver to reduce GHG emissions mainly coming from the residential sector [67].

Figure 25 - CO₂, SO₂ and NO_x emissions and electricity and heat production in the EEA-32, 1990-2008 [68]

The EC has launched the **Resource-Efficient** Europe as one of its seven flagship initiatives under the Europe 2020 Strategy publishing the Roadmap to a Resource-Efficient Europe [69], henceforth referred to as the Roadmap. According to the Roadmap, in terms of resource efficiency coupled to energy production and final use, the four main groups to be considered are GHG, water, biodiversity and ecosystems and the natural resources that provide energy, including electricity. Relevant trends concerning ecosystem services, namely those related to energy production, have been addressed in CDF1 Trend Analysis. The Eco-Innovation Index (Figure 26) [70] is the result of the combination of 16 indicators that jointly respond to three main critical aspects, namely technological development, resource efficiency and production. To the present date, there is not enough data to establish a trend, nevertheless, this indicator could deliver relevant information regarding the further assimilation of technological innovation in the resource efficiency policies and measures.

Figure 26 - Eco-Innovation Index in EU-27, 2011⁶² [70]

Innovation and technological development

The main driving force behind technologic developments regarding energy generation and storage are the KETs, such as nanotechnology, micro- and nanoelectronics including semiconductors, advanced materials, biotechnology and photonics [71]. They play an important role in the **R&D, innovation** and cluster strategies of many industries and are regarded as crucial for ensuring the competitiveness of European industries in the knowledge economy[73]. The EC defined its strategy to boost the industrial production of KETs-based products, e.g. innovative products and applications of the future[73]. There are some cross cutting issues for all the KETs - the following market and system failures are of importance for the industrial deployment of KETs [74]:

Basic research: Public funding is often available for KET research, but merits for researchers are typically based on the number of articles published in international research journals rather than the ability of transferring research into products on market. Incentives are required to ensure that research is carried out with a focus on market needs and commercialisation.

Applied research and proof of concepts/demonstration projects: Bringing the research results into commercial use implies (large) investments in further development, e.g., prototyping, testing and scaling up to full scale production facilities, but the available funding is not meeting the demand in this stage of the innovation process. Public funding for R&D in Europe is available from many different sources (CIP, FP, structural funds, etc.). This makes it difficult for companies to navigate. Also, the funding opportunities for research are characterised by long waiting periods.

The readiness level of technologies depends heavily on the **investment on technology R&D** resulting in a patent, and then a market approach, a proxy to this

⁶² 2012 results show minimal variation: <http://database.eco-innovation.eu/#view:scoreboard/indicators:269/countries:249,15,22,34,57,58,59,68,73,74,81,84,99,105,108,121,127,128,136,155,176,177,181,200,201,206,212,232/rScales:/chartType:BarGraph/year:2012/indicatorTabs:269,270,271,272,273,274/order:269> [accessed 18/12/14].

indicator could be the statistics on patents in technology (e.g., manufacturing technologies) which have been steadily growing in Europe for the last decades (Figure 27).

Figure 27 - Number of advanced manufacturing technology patent applications [72]

If a company has a patent or a basic prototype, this would translate into a TRL of 2 to 4 on a 1 to 9 scale (1 being “Basic principles observed and reported” and 9 “Systems ready for full scale deployment”). Progress has been achieved, but there is still work to be done to get the new technology or innovation to a technological readiness level of market maturity. There are two major barriers towards industrial deployment of KETs: large-scale demonstrators and pilot test facilities and lack of support to commercialise results of research.[73] [74]

Regarding financial instruments to support energy policies, it is important to look at the overview of **R&D investment in energy**, namely of EU funds dedicated to support energy policies and research developments, by programme and financial instruments for the period 2014-2020 (Figure 28).

Amounts in M€		Funds allocated within financial perspectives 2007-2013			Commission proposal for Funds allocation within financial perspectives 2014-2020		
		Total			Total		
		Electricity & gas infrastructure (1)	Sustainable energy (2)	Nuclear (3)	Electricity & gas infrastructure (1)	Sustainable energy (2)	Nuclear (3)
EU funds	Trans-European Networks Energy (TEN-E)	155					
	Connecting Europe Facility				9 121		
	which includes financial instruments				(1 000)		
	European Energy Programme for Recovery (EEPR)	2 267	1 712		-	-	
	Which includes financial instruments (European Energy Efficiency Fund)		(265)				
	CIP-Intelligent Energy Europe Programme	-	730 (A)		-	(B)	
	which includes ELENA (technical assistance)		(132)				
	Structural Funds	1 607	10 100			17 000	
	RTD Framework Programme		2 350 (C)			6 500	
	Risk Sharing Finance Facility (EC-EIB)		1 400 (D)				
	Enlargement Policy Funding		112				
	Nuclear EURATOM FP7 Fission			1 382			1 080
	Nuclear FP7 Fusion			4 155			3 282
	Decommissioning (LT,SK,BG)			2 848			860
SUB TOTAL	4 029	16 404	8 385	9 121	23 500	5 222	
TOTAL		28 818			37 843		

A. includes ELENA in cooperation with EIB, CEB, EBRD and KfW
 B. part of the new Research Framework Programme ("Horizon 2020")
 C. RTD 2007-2013: funds allocated to non-nuclear energy research in general
 D. 14% of total Risk Sharing Finance Facility (RSFF) envelope, which are mainly for solar and wind energy

Figure 28 - Overview of EU financial instruments to support energy policies [75]

A decrease is observed in terms of funds allocated to nuclear from 2007-2013 to 2014-2020 programme instruments. The opposite is observed for electricity and gas infrastructure and sustainable energy (e.g. RES) (Figure 29). The gross amount of funding is for sustainable energies in both of the two periods of EU programmes and financial instruments.

Figure 29 - Total Energy Budget for RD&D (Million USD) in European OECD countries between 2003 and 2011⁶³

Given the power sector's comparatively high technological and economic potential for cutting CO₂ emissions, it could heavily support Europe's decarbonisation targets by developing and including CCS [76]. CCS refers to a number of technologies that can be used to capture CO₂ from a point source such as a power plant, compress it, transport it by pipeline, and inject it deep underground for storage [77]. CCS is still in development stage for application in the electric sector. According to the International Energy Agency, in order to reach the goal of stabilizing global emissions at 450 ppm by 2050, CCS will be necessary [78]. As other technological developments, Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage technologies are also supported by KET. Table 41 shows the existing CCS projects up to date.

Table 41 - Pilot EU CCS Projects-identified by Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2011[77]

Project Name	Size (MW)	CO ₂ Storage	Start Date	Location
SchwarzePumpe	30	Depleted Gas	2008	Germany
Lacq	35	Depleted Gas	2010	France
Puertollano	14	Recycled	2010	Spain
Brindisi	48	EOR	2011	Italy
Ferrybridge	5	Depleted Oil	2012	United Kingdom
Mongstad	0.1 MT/y CO ₂	Saline	2012	Norway
Belchatow	250	Saline	2014	Poland
Compostilla	30	Saline	2015	Spain

European MS, together with Norway are part of the first movers in the use of CCS. It is home to numerous projects at various scales which have been initiated over the past 20 years. The UK and the Netherlands have the largest number of projects in Europe. But it is Norway that remains the most advanced country in storing CO₂ in Europe, with Sleipner and Snøhvit collectively storing around 1.7 million tonnes of

⁶³ OECD Statistics <http://stats.oecd.org>

CO₂ per annum from their natural gas processing activities. Significant projects are also underway in Germany, Spain, Italy, Poland and Romania⁶⁴. In fact, applying CCS from 2030 onwards is an EU goal present in the Energy Roadmap 2050.

The patterns of energy supply and consumption are changing rapidly. The main factors of this evolution are a fast increase of intermittent RES and distributed generation, changing market regulations and stringent environmental targets [79]. Given this scenario, **energy storage technologies** can deliver a number of strategic services both on the regulated and deregulated energy market, addressing five major challenges [79]:

1. Balancing demand & supply;
2. Managing transmission & distribution grids;
3. The increasing need for energy efficiency;
4. Promoting demand side management;
5. Contributing to competitive & secure electricity supply.

Different storage solutions reflect different technical requirements depending on whether a larger number of small, local storage facilities or a smaller number of large, centralised facilities are to be used. Presently, mechanical pumped hydro is the **storage technology** with most facilities in the pilot or demonstration stages in the EU followed by electrochemical batteries (Figure 30).

Figure 30 - Electricity Storage Technologies in TRL 4-8, EU, 2014.⁶⁵ [79]

Energy storage can be integrated at different levels of the electrical system: from power generation, transmission and distribution to the consumer. Hence, the final

⁶⁴ CCS in Europe. Global CCS Institute. <http://www.globalccsinstitute.com/location/europe> [accessed 28/01/14].

⁶⁵ Electrochemical Batteries including Classic & Flow Battery Lithium Ion & Vanadium Redox, Classic Lithium Ion, Lithium Ion Phosphate, Sodium Nickel Chloride, Sodium-Sulphur; Flow Battery - Vanadium Redox and Zinc Bromine; Note2: Mechanical other include Adiabatic Compressed Air, Diabatic Compressed Air and Cryogenic; Note3: Thermal include Heat, Molten Salt and Smart Electrical).

consumer also plays an important role in the future energy storage landscape through ownership of devices either domestically or through vehicle-to-grid technologies [79].

Regarding the **final energy consumption mix**, there are three major trends: increasing role of electricity in the overall demand (see Trend Analysis CDF1), the increasing share of RES and the decreasing amount of final energy coming from oil (Figure 31). This shift is driven by the binding targets on RES and energy efficiency policies until 2020 with effects continuing until 2030, and by the ETS even beyond 2030 (e.g. Energy Roadmap 2050). The share of oil is expected to decrease, but remain at a relatively high level as transportation is projected to remain dominated by oil. Consumption of solid fuels declines considerably throughout the projection period [80].

Figure 31 - EU Final Energy Consumption [80]

A good example comes from the **technological integration** with wind power and the positive **resource efficiency** derived from the same. Energy production (primarily cooling water) uses the highest amount of water in the EU (44%). Wind energy avoided the use of 1.2 billion cubic metres (bn m³) of water in 2012 – equivalent to the average annual household water use of almost 22 million EU citizens [81]. The 1.2 bn m³ of water use avoided by wind energy would avoid a cost of €2.4 bn, which could mean that by 2030 wind energy will avoid between 4.3 bn m³ and 6.4 bn m³ of water according to calculations based on the Energy Roadmap 2050's projections.

It is also relevant to analyse how primary energy production matches final energy consumption in terms of efficiency and sustainability. The current use of energy, in terms of the energy chain, from supply to demand-side, does not consider the quality of energy delivered to the end-users, provided their needs are satisfied [82]. Energy matching (Figure 32) consists of a reorganisation of the energy demand, shifting towards more adequate energy vectors and end-use technologies for the required energy service translating into an efficient use of resources, promoting the matching between the available energy resources and the existing energy demand [83].

Figure 32 - Energy Matching - Matching the endogenous resources with the energy needs [83]

In the last few years, initiatives like the **Smart Grids**, with different aims and results, have been growing in number and scope throughout Europe. Substantial public and private investments have been made in R&D, demonstration and deployment activities. The number of R&D and demonstration projects grows constantly while the number of deployment projects has not increased dramatically since the first project in 2001. The constant growth of demonstration projects is particularly important as it shows an increasing confidence in the viability of Smart Grid projects (Figure 33). There is a clear need to survey the implemented projects in order to monitor the direction Europe is taking, to benchmark investments, and to tackle challenges and possible distortions from an early stage. Sharing the results of these projects can also contribute in increasing the stock of knowledge and accelerate the innovation process [84]. Smart Grid projects are not uniformly distributed across Europe. Most of the projects and investments are located in EU15 countries, while EU12 MS still lag behind (Figure 34).

Figure 33 - Smart Grids - trend of the different maturity stages over time [84]

The uneven geographical distribution of projects and the different pace, at which Smart Grids are being deployed across Europe (Figure 34), could make trade and cooperation across national borders more difficult and jeopardize the timely achievement of the EU energy policy goals [84].[4]. Most Smart Grid benefits are

systemic in nature as they arise from the combination of technological, regulatory, economic and behavioural changes [84] and meet several EU main policy objectives (e.g., European Grid Declaration, 2011; Europe 2020, 2010).

Figure 34 - Geographical distribution of investments and project categories for Smart Grids [84]

Energy Security

One key aspect of energy security is the development and deployment of **storage technology solutions and facilities**. Large-scale penetration of intermittent renewables is expected to have profound implications on many aspects of power systems planning, operation and control, as well as on the corresponding regulation [86]. Key energy storage research areas include technology-specific issues, namely **mechanical storage, electrical storage and thermal storage** [4]:

- **Mechanical Storage:** the most common systems are pumped hydroelectric power plants (PHS), CAES and flywheel energy storage (FES) [4]. PHS has existed for a long time and the efficiency of PHS plants is in the range of 70% to 85%. Advantages are the very long lifetime and practically unlimited cycle stability of the installation. Main drawbacks are the dependence on topographical conditions and large land use. Meanwhile, most of the places

that are suited to pumped hydro already have it, new facilities are not cheap and there are geographical limitations to where you can put them [87]. With CAES typical underground storage options are caverns, aquifers or abandoned mines. The advantage of CAES is its large capacity; disadvantages are low round-trip efficiency and geographic limitation of locations. Considering flywheels, the main features of are cycle stability and long life, little maintenance, high power density and the use of environmentally inert material. However, flywheels have a high level of self-discharge due to air resistance and bearing losses and suffer from low current efficiency[4];

- **Electrochemical Storage.** Most of them are technologically mature for practical use, such as secondary battery types - lead acid, NiCd/NiMH, Li-ion, metal air, sodium sulphur and sodium nickel chloride – and two sorts of flow battery[86], [4]. Lead acid battery (LA) is the world's most widely used battery type. Their typical applications are emergency power supply systems, stand-alone systems with PV, battery systems for mitigation of output fluctuations from wind power and as starter batteries in vehicles. The drawbacks are lower energy density and the use of lead, a hazardous material prohibited or restricted in various jurisdictions. Lithium ion (Li) batteries have become the most important storage technology in the areas of portable and mobile applications. Li generally have a very high efficiency, typically in the range of 95 % - 98 %. Metal air battery (Me-air) is a satisfactory, electrically rechargeable metal air system that potentially offers low materials cost and high specific energy, but none has reached marketability yet. Sodium sulphur batteries (NaS) are economically used in combined power quality and time shift applications with high energy density. These batteries are suitable for applications with daily cycling. As the response time is in the range of milliseconds and NaS batteries meet the requirements for grid stabilization, this technology could be very interesting for utilities and large consumers. Sodium nickel chloride battery (NaNiCl) better known as the ZEBRA (Zero Emission Battery Research) battery, is a high-temperature (HT) battery. These have been successfully implemented in several electric vehicle designs and are an interesting opportunity for fleet applications. Present research is in developing advanced versions of the ZEBRA battery with higher power densities for hybrid EV, and also high-energy versions for storing renewable energy for load-levelling and industrial applications. Other option is the flow batteries, where energy is stored in one or more electroactive species which are dissolved in liquid electrolytes. Flow batteries can be fitted to a wide range of stationary applications[4];
- **Chemical Energy Storage:** Hydrogen and synthetic natural gas (SNG). The main purpose of such a chemical energy storage system is to use “excess” electricity to produce hydrogen via water electrolysis. Once hydrogen is produced different ways are available for using it as an energy carrier, either as pure hydrogen or as SNG. Although the overall efficiency of hydrogen and SNG is low compared to storage technologies such as PHS and Li-ion, chemical energy storage is the only concept which allows storage of large amounts of energy, up to the TWh range, and for greater periods of time – even as seasonal storage. Various R&D projects carried out over the last 25 years have successfully demonstrated the feasibility of hydrogen technology;

- **Wind energy** is used to produce hydrogen via electrolysis if the power cannot be directly fed into the grid. On demand, the stored hydrogen is added to the biogas used to run a gas motor. Regarding SNG, the main advantage is the use of an already existing gas grid infrastructure. Pure hydrogen can be fed into the gas grid only up to a certain concentration, in order to keep the gas mixture within specifications (e.g. heating value) [4];
- **Thermal Energy Storage:** Available heat by different means in an insulated repository for later use in different industrial and residential applications, such as space heating or cooling, hot water production or electricity generation. Thermal storage systems are deployed to overcome the mismatch between demand and supply of thermal energy and thus they are important for the integration of renewable energy sources.

Figure 35 summarizes the main properties of electricity storage technologies.

Technology	Typical Capacity	Response time	Discharge time	Efficiency	Life time	Development stage	Application ¹²
Pumped hydro energy storage (PHES)	5 MW – 2 GW	1 min (if standing still) 10 sec (if spinning)	4 - 100 h	55-85%	50+ years	Mature	Primary ¹³ / secondary / tertiary control, energy arbitrage
Compressed air energy systems (CAES)	25 MW – 2.5 GW	15 min from cold start	2 - 24 h	40-70%	15-40 years	Mature / premature (AA-CAES)	Tertiary control, energy arbitrage
Batteries	1 kW – 50 MW		1 min – 3 h	65-75%	2-10 years	Premature / mature	Uninterruptible power supply, RES-E fluctuation reduction, primary / secondary control
Flywheels	5 kW – 20 MW		4 sec - 15 min	90-95%	~20 years	Mature	Primary control, power quality
Hydrogen Fuel Cell Storage System (HFCSS)	1 kW – 10 GW	Depends on fuel cell	0.01 sec-days	20-40%	5-10 years	Prototype	RES-E fluctuation reduction, tertiary reserve
Super magnetic energy storage (SMES)	10 kW – 1 MW		5 sec – 5 min	95%	~30 years	Premature	Uninterruptible power supply, power quality
Supercapacitors	< 150 kW		1 sec – 1 min	85-95%	~10 years	Premature	Uninterruptible power supply, power quality

Figure 35 - Main properties of electricity storage technologies [90]

Figure 36 summarizes the maturity of the storage technologies.

Figure 36 - Maturity and state of the art of storage systems for electrical energy [4]

The EU aims to make sure that **strategic energy networks and storage facilities** are completed by 2020 [89]. It concerns energy production, transmission and storage. The EC has identified a series of priority corridors and areas for electricity, gas, oil and future CO₂ transport networks, and is promoting projects to implement them [88]. The Energy Infrastructure Package, established by the EIP 2020 and successively by the adopted Regulation on Guidelines for Trans-European Energy Infrastructures (TEN-E Guidelines), has identified a range of **priority corridors for electricity, gas and oil** (Figure 37):

- For electricity and Gas:
 - Completion of the Baltic Energy Market Interconnection Plan – BEMIP⁶⁶ in electricity and in gas - to connect Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia to wider EU energy networks (Figure 38).
- For Electricity:
 - Northern Seas Offshore Grid - an integrated offshore electricity grid in the North Sea, the Irish Sea, the English Channel, the Baltic Sea and neighbouring waters to transport electricity from renewable offshore energy sources to centres of consumption and to storage capacity in the Alps or Nordic countries (Figure 39);
 - South Western Interconnections - to ensure the adequate integration of new capacities, mainly from renewables, in South Western Europe and Northern Africa and to reduce the “energy island” effect in the Iberian Peninsula (EIP 2020);
 - Central / South Eastern Connections - to cope with necessary “huge North-South transit capacities” resulting from increased capacity in the north and expected demand increases in the south (EIP 2020).

⁶⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/infrastructure/bemip_en.htm [accessed 12/12/13].

- For Gas:
 - Southern Gas Corridor – aimed at directly linking the EU gas market to the largest deposit of gas in the world (the Caspian / Middle East basin) (EIP 2020);
 - North-South Gas Corridor in Western Europe - from the Iberian Peninsula and Italy to North-west Europe, designed to better interconnect the Mediterranean area and thus supplies from Africa and the Northern supply Corridor with gas supplies from Norway and Russia.
- For Gas and Oil:
 - North-South gas interconnections in Eastern Europe - linking the Baltic Sea area (including Poland) to the Adriatic and Aegean Seas and further to the Black Sea.

Figure 37 - Priority corridors and areas covering electricity, gas, oil networks [89]

Figure 38 - BEMIP maps, main corridors (left) and detailed development (right)

Figure 39 - Northern Seas offshore grid⁶⁷

The **North-South Interconnections in Central and South Eastern Europe** ("North-South East") are also among these priority corridors (Figure 40). The North-South initiative in electricity aims to strengthen regional networks in North-South and East-West power flow directions, support an appropriate balancing system and solve infrastructure gaps, especially those related to increasing generation from RES. In gas, the objective is to enhance security of supply and promote market integration, meaning through diversification of sources and routes to connect gas supply sources

⁶⁷ http://www.3e.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/11/DirectDesign_NonTechnical_Legend_Logos_2.jpg [accessed 28/02/14].

of the Baltic, Adriatic and Black Seas, as well as through necessary internal market actions. In oil, the objective is to provide access to the Baltic, Black and Adriatic Seas in order to increase security of supply and a high level of interoperability of the regional oil pipeline network [91].

Figure 40 - The North-South Interconnections in Central and South Eastern Europe - areas for developing project concerning electricity (left) and natural gas (right) [91]

To implement these corridors, the first list of PCIs was established in 2013, by the EC. It includes 248 key energy infrastructure projects that will benefit from faster and more efficient permit granting procedures and improved regulatory treatment. For a project to be included in the list, it has to have significant benefits for at least two MS; contribute to market integration and further competition; enhance security of supply, and reduce CO₂ emissions [92] (Figure 41 and Figure 42).

Figure 41 - PCI Interactive Map - Electricity⁶⁸Figure 42 - PCI Interactive Map - Natural Gas⁶⁸

In terms of investment needs, for each priority corridor and thematic area major expected investment gaps and amounts are needed to stimulate the investment and prevent the gap. Even though the estimates are very conservative, over EUR 9.12 billion are necessary [93] (Figure 43).

Priority corridors	Total investment need (bn EUR)	Estimated investment gap (bn EUR)	Average co-financing ratio need	Likely need for funding (bn EUR)
Northern Seas offshore grid	30	8	0.10	0.80
North-South electricity interconnections in Western Europe	30	5	0.10	0.50
North-South electricity interconnections in Central Eastern and South Eastern Europe	40	12	0.20	2.40
BEMIP electricity	5	3	0.50	1.50
North-South gas interconnections in Western Europe	20	1	0.10	0.10
North-South gas interconnections in Central Eastern and South Eastern Europe	26	5	0.20	1.00
Southern Gas Corridor	22	8	0.10	0.80
BEMIP gas	3	2	0.50	1.00
Oil supply connections in Central Eastern Europe			0	0.00
Priority thematic areas				
Smart grids deployment	40	20		1.00
Electricity highways	included in electricity corridors			
Cross-border CO ₂ network (if technology viable)	2.5	2		0.02
TOTAL	218.5	66		9.12

⁶⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/infrastructure/transparency_platform/map-viewer/ [accessed 28/02/14].

Figure 43 - Interconnectivity - Investment needed [93]

Note: These are approximate figures, mainly from the EC's DG Energy, calculations based on data from PRIMES (as a partial equilibrium model for the European Union energy markets, PRIMES is used for forecasting, scenario construction and policy impact analysis up to the year 2030), ENTSOs, KEMA, etc. [93]

Another corridor under discussion on the Energy Roadmap 2050 is the connection to the Middle East and North Africa. The Desert Power 2050 Report [94] examines the future energy challenges of Europe as well as the Middle East and North Africa. The idea that renewable electricity should be produced in areas with optimal resources and exported to regions with high demand has become known as the Desertec vision (Figure 44)⁶⁹, which suggests that Europe could source some of its electricity production from the deserts on the southern shore of the Mediterranean, from solar and wind resources [94]. However, the Desertec Industrial Initiative (Dii) has recently abandoned its strategy to export solar power generated from the Sahara to Europe. Although the industrial alliance was set up to develop renewable energy supplies in the Maghreb to feed up to 20% of European electricity demand by 2050, Dii concedes that Europe can provide for most of its needs indigenously [95]. Desertec's initial business model was set to work on the basis of exports, but this initial 'export' approach has been reconsidered, for two main reasons: a) there are still missing lines and capacities for export and building these is technically difficult because of the deep waters in the Mediterranean. Moreover, Spain is already struggling with its own excess RES production. Spanish lines would need to be strengthened, with a view to moving excess electricity to France. But the interconnection at the Spanish-French border is also congested; b) it is difficult to argue that the EU needs the additional RES capacity, since the it is currently witnessing a situation in which RES capacity is competing to replace existing conventional plants. This shift requires solving plenty of system issues, including the resynchronisation of the system consecutive to the development of RES, in particular variable wind and photovoltaic. Although variability is not a problem in itself, it obliges the system to change its way of functioning, which also means giving time to the technical, economic, and regulatory framework to adjust. Adding even more RES from Desertec in the meantime would probably not support this move [95].

⁶⁹ <http://www.desertec.org/>

Figure 44 - 'DESERTEC' Generation and interconnector capacity, Delayed Expensive Grid Scenario [94]

On the political side, tensions on global hydrocarbons markets and the 2006 and 2009 gas crises pushed supply security up the policy priority list in Europe. This concern is unlikely to go away as the EU's import dependency on gas is expected to rise to close to 80% in the next twenty years, up from 67% today [96]. During the 2006/2009 gas crises, due to disputes over gas pricing with transit country Ukraine, Russian gas stopped flowing to Europe, leaving many Central and Eastern European MS in the cold. The crises were a wake-up call to the levels of **energy dependency from abroad**, namely from the East (Figure 45). The crises revealed how much the persistent national compartmentalisation and the monopolistic nature of energy markets, especially in Central and Eastern Europe, have contributed to the vulnerability of this region to supply disruptions [97]. In the aftermath of the crises and in an effort to protect MS from the risks of supply disruptions and unfair price differentials, in February 2011 the EU Council set the goal of achieving the single market in energy by the end of 2014 [98]. A series of measures were introduced in the aftermath of these events. A regulation on security of gas supplies (Regulation (EU) No 994/2010) introduced common standards for infrastructure and consumer protection in case of crisis. The second pillar of the EU's response has been to develop a more active international gas security strategy [96].

Figure 45 - EU-27 Imports by Country of Origin, as a percentage of Gross inland consumption, 2010 [99]

A determinant factor for the security of the European electricity grid is the variations in **energy import dependency rate**⁷⁰, which describes the extent to which an economy relies on imports to meet its energy needs. Between 2000 and 2011, the EU-27's energy dependence increased by 15% (Figure 46).

Figure 46 - Energy Import Dependency in EU 27 (source: Eurostat)

However, the rising trend levelled off in 2006 due to lower energy demand in the EU. The share of total energy needs provided by imports from non-EU countries increased significantly over the past two decades, reaching 53.8% in 2011. Between 2000 and 2011 the level of dependence was highest for petroleum products, but increased most for natural gas followed by hard coal. The rise in energy imports is driven by the decline of oil and gas production within the EU, mainly in the North Sea [56]. Being reliant on non-EU energy sources exposes the European economy to high price volatility, significant costs and the risk of supply shortage (Figure 47, Figure 48). Securing energy supplies is therefore high on the EU's agenda (EIP 2020;

⁷⁰ The proportion of energy (%) that an economy must import. Defined as the net energy imports divided by gross inland energy consumption and international maritime bunkers (amount of fuel delivered to any ship engaged in international navigation from the country). http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/statistics_explained/index.php/Glossary:Energy_dependency_rate [accessed 12/12/13].

Energy 2020[100], EU Sustainable Development Strategy, EU Climate and Energy Package).

Figure 47 - Energy Efficiency - Shares of imports in energy supply of the top 10 more dependent EU27 countries [70]

Figure 48 - Energy Efficiency - Shares of imports in energy supply of the top 10 less dependent EU27 countries [70]

By analysing the **energy reserves and installed capacity within Europe or the neighbouring countries**, it is possible to read that, in the case of oil, the reserves existing within European borders, namely UK and Norway are slightly decreasing, with the Kazakhstan assuming the role of a strategic partner since 2006, increasing the importance of the Eastern-European corridor (Figure 49).

Figure 49 - Oil Proved Reserves History in Europe and neighbouring countries [101]

Considering natural gas reserves, the inland reserves in the UE have been decreasing since 2000, with less than half of the proved reserves in 2012 when compared with 12 years ago. Even the Norwegian reserves are showing a tendency for stagnant growth, while the UK reserves are plunging. This trend may add pressure in the need to explore unconventional sources of gas (shale gas, frozen methane, liquefied natural gas - LNG) either inbound or imported (Figure 50).

Figure 50 - Gas proved reserves history [101]

Regarding coal production (including lignite), the overall values have been stable, despite the indications that the calorific value per ton is decreasing in average [102]. The European reserves are heavily dependent on Germany's and Poland production, with Kazakhstan and Ukraine assuming a determinant role in maintaining an inbound stability of coal availability (Figure 51).

Figure 51 -Coal (all types) Production [101]

Nuclear energy production is obtained from fission of Uranium atoms, and Uranium is not an abundant source, aggravated by the increasing pressure for closing and decommissioning nuclear power reactors in the EU, following the Fukushima accident as previously mentioned (see Trend Analysis CDF1). In fact, Germany has decided to end its programme entirely and France is developing its own decommissioning programme [103]. Thus being considered, added to the insignificant uranium reserves within Europe and the increasing rivalry for this resource coming from China, India and Russia, the European position regarding nuclear power is on a trend of increasing fragility (Figure 52).

Figure 52 - World Uranium production by country [101]

In terms of biofuels, the overall EU production exponentially increased from 2000 to 2009 driven by the demand for RES, but after the credit crunch and the food crisis, the pressure for biofuel production decreased, with production also decreasing in the main producers, namely Germany and France. The future tendency for biofuel production will be linked with the Common Agriculture Policy criteria and demands and also related with food safety and environmental performance, and also

dependent on R&D investment in non-food derived advanced biofuels⁷¹ (Figure 53).

Figure 53 - Biofuels production in European countries [101]

On the issue of geothermal power capacity, the installed capacity is strictly site dependent and is mostly linked with island countries or regions with significant volcanic activity like Iceland, the Azores and Sicily or thermal waters like Austria, Germany, Turkey and Hungary (Figure 54). The trend towards further integration of geothermal seems positive in the overall but could be more directly correlated with strategies supporting DHC and smart grids [104].

Figure 54 - Cumulative installed geothermal power capacity [101]

Regarding solar power, namely PV, there is a clear trend towards the exponential increase in cumulative installed power, with countries like Germany and Italy leading the way, followed by Spain and Portugal (Figure 55).

⁷¹ European Biofuels Technology Platform: <http://www.biofuelstp.eu/eibi.html>

Figure 55 - Cumulative installed PV [101]

In the matter of wind turbine capacity, the trend is a geometrical increase at the EU level, mainly in Germany, Spain, UK and Italy (Figure 56).

Figure 56 - Cumulative installed wind turbine capacity [101]

Another aspect that reinforces the importance of the technological development of storage options in order to provide solid support for possible further RES integration is the **ancillary services market development** [60]. As utilities and grid operators increase their reliance on intermittent renewable generation capacity, additional balancing resources are required to address any inconsistencies in generation and providing more guaranties regarding energy security, for example when sufficient wind and sun are not available. Ancillary services products address these short-term imbalances in electricity markets by dispatching resources within seconds or minutes of an unacceptable imbalance, and demand response practitioners have a role to play in helping to balance the system on a short-term basis. Demand response can act as an ancillary service that responds just as quickly as an ancillary power plant would, in under a second or within minutes, depending on the type of ancillary service required. These conditions afford demand response practitioners an opportunity to tap into an additional payment stream for their participation ancillary services [106].

There is a clear global and EU trend of increased installed capacity of ancillary services (Figure 57).

Figure 57 - New installed capacity of energy storage for ancillary services by region, world markets: 2013-2023 [107]

Looking at **power outages** in the EU, considering the availability of the fossil-fired power plants between 2009 and 2011, a small variation of the time and the energy availability at around 84% and 83% respectively is observed. On the other hand, the utilisation is lower than the availability (around 57% of energy utilisation over three years). The analysis of ten years shows the impact on the supply system of the increase of renewables and the required priority dispatch of renewables: utilisation of conventional plants has fallen [60].

The decrease of annual operating hours for conventional plants leads to severe difficulties in covering the cost of generation and removes any incentive for the building of new thermal power capacities. The **planned and unplanned outages** are good indicators of the technical status of each installation (Figure 58). The duration of a planned outage is determined by the level of repair work on damaged or aged components as well as the retro-fit measures taken to upgrade the plant performance. Unplanned outages, which can be further divided into postponable and not-postponable, illustrate the real operation of the plant and/or its components. The ratio of planned to unplanned outages indicates the quality of the maintenance work undertaken to avoid any damage during plant operation. Furthermore, the possibility to postpone an unplanned unavailability in times of ever increasing RES-E generation is an indicator of the stability and flexibility of the system [108].

Figure 58 - Power Outages - Availability and unavailability indicators (EU countries AT, CZ, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT) [108]⁷²

Most of the unplanned unavailability is caused by the heat generation itself, aggravated by climate change (see Trend Analysis CDF1). It can also be due to suspicion of failure on a reactor safety component, which prompts the immediate shutdown in the case of a nuclear unit. The generator itself causes around 1% of the total unplanned unavailability for all thermal power stations.

Historically, Germany has had by far the most reliable power supply in Europe every year from 2006 to 2010, the last year for which reliable statistics are available (Figure 59) [109]. Technically, the solutions for avoiding systematic power outages are three: a combination of national and international grid extension and optimization, a power plant mix combining a variety of renewables, flexible backup capacity, a strategic reserve of power plants, demand management, and, ultimately, storage [109]. The challenge now is financial: for the future, the power sector is calling for capacity payments to ensure that enough backup generating capacity remains in service [109]. In an overall, power outage duration in EU has been decreasing, even considering the increase in RES generation (Figure 59) which is in line with Energy 2020's objective of guaranteeing energy security of supply.

⁷² AT – Austria; CZ – Czech Republic; DE – Germany; FR – France; IT – Italy; NL – Netherlands; PL – Poland; PT – Portugal.

Figure 59 - Grid reliability - Minutes of power outages per year [110]

CDF3 - Geo-Political Economy and Regional Equity

The objective / scope of CDF3 on Geo-Political and Regional Equity to focus on **European competitiveness** in its **geo-political environment** considering **energy**, balanced by the need to ensure **regional equity** within European MS concerning **sources of energy**, **market accessibility** and **distributional equity**, and implications for national / local **economies** and **development options**.

International Competitiveness

As in the Trend Analysis of CDF2, the **energy import dependency rate** (Figure 46) has increased 15% within the EU-27 from 46.7% in 2000 to 53.8% in 2011. Russia and Norway were the main sources of EU-27 fossil fuel imports in 2010 (see Figure 45) but there were also imports from Africa, the Americas and the Middle East [111]. The main sources of uranium in 2010, for nuclear energy generation, were Australia (22%), Russia (20%) and Canada (19%) [112]. In Europe, Norway and Denmark are the only net exporters of energy, whilst the UK has gone from being a net exporter in 2000 to a net importer in 2011 [113]. The increase in imports is driven by a decline in the primary production of fossil fuel based energy sources such as hard coal, lignite, crude oil, natural gas, and more recently nuclear energy in the EU-27 [31]. Further decline in fossil fuel reserves, and their eventual depletion, in MS may lead to further increases in energy imports unless internal capacity (e.g. renewables etc.) is increased to meet the EU-28's energy needs.

The main **European joint energy agreement** is the Energy Community that was formed in 2006, linking the EU's internal energy network to the Western Balkans⁷³, Moldova and the Ukraine. The overall objective of the agreement is to "create a

⁷³ The Western Balkans includes Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Republic of Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia and Kosovo.

stable regulatory and market framework” that can: attract investment in power generation and networks; create an integrated energy market; enhance the security of supply; improve the environmental situation; and enhance competition at a regional level [115]. The Energy Community has allowed the EU to increase regulation and security of the energy network by introducing policies on cartel prohibition, binding renewable energy source targets, energy efficiency and environmental impact of fuels [116].

Any EU member can elect to participate in the Energy Community which has expanded from 10 MS in 2006 to 17⁷⁴ as of October 2013 [117]. Bulgaria, Romania and Croatia, originally ‘contracting partners’, became ‘participants’ upon their accession to the EU. Armenia, Norway, Turkey and Georgia are ‘observers’ with Georgia in the progress of joining as a participant. In the future other contracting partners and observers may become participants if they join the EU-28 (Turkey are in the process). Whilst Norway is an ‘observer’, several projects are underway that aim to increase Norway-EU transfer capacity by 5.6 GW. Iceland and the UK signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) in 2012 to begin feasibility studies in exporting geothermal power to the European market.

These agreements are driven by the need for security of supply, affordability, sustainability and foreign policy [31]. Energy agreements can be driven by MS seeking to gain additional capacity to meet high national demand and to provide options for utilising oversupply during lower demand, thereby allowing MS access to a secure energy supply along with a cost-effective process of meeting high demand and utilising oversupply.

There are several existing and planned **European Energy trade flow agreements with third parties** such as North Africa, the Middle East and Russia (see Figure 60). These include the MedRing (from North African and Arabian countries up to Turkey), Union for the Mediterranean (from 16 partner countries from North Africa, the Balkans and the Middle East) and Mediterranean Solar Plan (North Africa). The EU has also developed international energy partnerships to promote international energy cooperation with its Eastern neighbours⁷⁵ through the INOGATE [118] programme. These agreements help Europe meet its energy needs in addition to supporting energy policy cooperation between the EU and neighbouring countries.

⁷⁴ The 17 MS are Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom.

⁷⁵ INOGATE partner countries are Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and the Russian Federation (observer status).

Figure 60 - Gas pipeline projects throughout Europe [111]

There are plans to increase the renewable energy sources used to generate electricity for European consumption. The proposed Desertec project aims to harvest large renewable energy sources from where they are located and could be beneficial for the European energy sector, especially in southern Europe [120] (see Figure 61).

Figure 61 - The Desertec Project [121]

Market Dynamics and Regional Equity

The EU Third Energy Package adopted in 2009 introduced several directives⁷⁶ containing common rules for internal (European) energy markets [122]. This package aims to increase cross-border exchange of energy and increase access to a diverse range of energy sources. However, the transposition⁷⁷ of the Third package has been

⁷⁶ Directive 2009/72/EC and Directive 2009/73/EC

⁷⁷ Transposition involves turning EU level directives into national or regional legislation at the MS level.

poor with no MS having issued transposition notices and only 4 MS having filed partial notifications (see also Trend Analysis CDF4).

Interconnection capacity impedes national and cross-border energy movements. There have been increases in the interconnection capacity, a “slight increase” being reported between 2002 and 2009, in response to a 2002 EU Council target to increase electricity interconnections to at least 10% of their installed production capacity by 2005 [122]. However, the interconnection capacity between MS varies across Europe and the Baltic States, Iberian Peninsula and Great Britain are “largely isolated” from other MS [122].

Market coupling is the “integration of two or more electricity markets from different areas through an implicit cross-border allocation mechanism” and an important market-based tool in harmonising Europe’s energy market [111]. A comparison can be drawn between the Central Western Europe (CWE) markets where market coupling took place in 2010 and the Central Eastern European (CEE) region where there is limited market coupling between only two countries⁷⁸. In CWE markets, when market coupling was introduced there was a steep fall in adverse **power flows** and these became non-existent from 2011 onwards. Additionally, there was a high ratio of hourly converging prices with a difference in hourly power prices of less than 1% in 64% of all hourly price observations (indicating a very integrated wholesale power market). In the same period of time in the CEE region, there were high adverse flow ratios and a low proportion of price-converging hours among the regions’ markets with the difference in hourly prices of less than 1% occurring in only 3-15% of all observations in 2011 [111].

There has been progress towards harmonising the European energy market through several **price-coupling projects** that have been initiated by Transmission System Operators and Power Exchanges. This is based upon the Price Coupling of Regions (PCR) initiative, which developed a single price coupling algorithm (called Euphemia) to calculate electricity prices across Europe. The PCR initiative began in 2009 and is described as being “crucial to achieve the overall EU target of a harmonized European electricity market” [123] as it allows the fair and transparent calculation of electricity prices across Europe and the allocation of daily cross-border capacity.

The PCR system is being introduced through several coupling initiatives across European Regions such as the North Western Europe (NWE) Price Coupling project and the South Western Europe (SWE) Coupling Project [124]. The NWE project couples the markets across Central West Europe⁷⁹, Great Britain, the Nordic countries, the Baltic countries, and the SwePol link between Sweden and Poland; the SWE project is between French, Spanish and Portuguese energy markets [125].

⁷⁸ Slovakia and the Czech Republic.

⁷⁹ The markets covered by the NWE project are also a result of a harmonisation between the Central-West region and the northern market in 2010. [EC (2011) 2009-2010 Report on progress of creating the internal gas and electricity market].

Figure 62 -The next steps towards a single European market through PCR. Regions are coloured to signify the power exchange group that they belong within [126]

Renewable energy initiatives can encourage cross-border energy transfers. The RED allows MS to count renewable energy produced in another MS towards their 2020 renewable energy targets. It aims to encourage this energy movement between MS through cooperation mechanisms that, if fully utilised, could lead to savings of up to €8 billion per year⁸⁰. Only two MS have indicated that they would use these cooperation mechanisms to meet their own targets and only ten MS have signalled that they will have additional renewable energy to supply to other MS [127].

MS aim to increase the proportion of their electricity that is generated by **RES** and are using a variety of **support schemes**. These differ between MS and include general taxation, non-tax levies, passing the cost to end users through suppliers' costs and passing the cost on through the wholesale electricity prices [128].

MS have been promoting RES through the use of Green Certificates and **feed-in tariffs**. Green certificates have been issued by renewable energy producers to certify that power is generated from renewable sources and are sold separately from the produced power. Energy users that purchase green certificates⁸¹ can then claim that they have purchased renewable (green) energy, which might correspond to their ethical values, corporate social responsibility aims etc.

Renewable electricity feed-in tariffs are also used as a method of subsidising energy generation by renewable energy sources and of supporting their integration into the energy mix. Since 1989, the tariffs have been used to encourage the uptake of renewable energy generation by offering a fixed price for renewable electricity that

⁸⁰ The EUR 8 billion figure is through the calculation of 'optimal trade in renewables' through these cooperation mechanisms. [EC (2012) Renewable Energy: A major player in the European energy market].

⁸¹ Green certificates are used in Belgium, Italy, Poland, Romania and the UK currently.

reflects the higher production costs and provides price certainty in the long-term (see Figure 63).

Historical overview on promotion strategies for electricity from renewables in EU countries.				
Year	Country	Type of strategy	Program name	Technologies addressed
1979–1989	DK	Investment subsidies		Wind, biogas
1989–1996	DE	Investment subsidies plus feed-in tariffs	"100/250 MW Wind Program"	Wind
1991–1993	DE	Investment subsidies plus feed-in tariffs	"1000-Dächer-Program"	PV
1990–1999	UK	Tendering system	NFFO/SRO/NI-NFFO	Selected technologies
1990–present	DE	Feed-in tariffs	"Einspeisetarif"	PV, wind, biomass, small hydro
1992–1994	AT	Investment subsidies plus feed-in tariffs	200 kW PV-Program	PV
1992–1997	IT	Feed-in tariffs	"CIP 6/92"	All technologies
1991–1996	SE	Investment subsidies/tax relief		Wind, solar, biomass
1992–1999	DK	Feed-in tariff		Wind, biomass
1992–1999	DE, CH, AT	Feed-in tariffs	"Kostendeckende Vergütung"	PV
1994–present	GR	Investment subsidies	1994-now: Operational Program for Energy and Competitiveness	PV, wind, biomass, small hydro, geothermal
1994–present	ES	Feed-in tariffs or fixed premium systems	"Royal Decree 2366/1994" resp. "Royal Decree 436/2004"	All technologies (except large hydro)
1996–present	DE, CH, NL, AT, UK	Voluntary green tariffs	Various brands	Selected technologies
1996–present	CH	Voluntary stock exchange	"Solarstrombörse"	PV
1997–present	FI	Tax incentives	Energy tax	Wind, mini hydro (<1 MW), wood based fuels
1998–present	DE	Labelled "Green Electricity"	TÜV, Grüner Stromlabel e.V., Öko-Institut	PV, wind, biomass, small hydro
1999–present	DE	Soft loans	"100,000 Dächer-Programm"	PV
1999–2000	NL	(Voluntary) green certificates		All technologies (exempt municipal waste incineration)
1979–1989	DK	Investment subsidies		Wind, biogas
1989–1996	DE	Investment subsidies plus feed-in tariffs	"100/250 MW Wind Program"	Wind
1991–1993	DE	Investment subsidies plus feed-in tariffs	"1000-Dächer-Program"	PV
1990–1999	UK	Tendering system	NFFO/SRO/NI-NFFO	Selected technologies
1990–present	DE	Feed-in tariffs	"Einspeisetarif"	PV, wind, biomass, small hydro
1992–1994	AT	Investment subsidies plus feed-in tariffs	200 kW PV-Program	PV

Source: Haas et al. [7] and own investigations.

Figure 63 - A historical overview on promotion strategies for electricity from renewables in EU countries [129]

Across the EU-27 there are a range of different renewable energy support measures in place (see Figure 64). The Figure also shows that numerous MS changed or adapted their support measures from 1997 to 2008. From 1997 to 2008 the number of MS that used renewable policy support systems increased from 14 MS to all 27 MS in 2008. The use of feed-in tariffs is widespread with 18 MS using them as the main renewable energy support system from 1997 to 2008, a further two used feed-in tariffs along with another support system, six MS employed the use of quota systems and five MS used tax incentives/investment grants. As of 2010, 23 MS of the EU-27 used feed-in tariffs; 20 MS used feed-in tariffs as the main renewable energy programme whilst three MS limited their use to certain technologies [130].

Figure 64 - Overview of support systems for renewable energy by EU-27 MS from 1997 to 2008 [129]

There are some calls, including from EU politicians [131], to reduce or phase out feed-in tariffs where they are seen as a hindrance to innovation and competition⁸². Their phasing out will be driven by the speed at which the cost of renewable technologies decreases due to scale and market. A key driver for reducing or phasing

⁸² Resource Roadmap, 2011; Energy 2020, 2010; Energy Roadmap 2050, 2011; Renewable Energy, 2012.

out feed-in tariffs is their potential detrimental effect on competitiveness between utility companies in MS. For example, the use of feed-in tariffs has helped to reduce wholesale power prices in Germany, but this has led to neighbouring countries such as Switzerland and the Netherlands importing this cheaper energy [131]. The impact of this competition has led to Swiss and Dutch power plants producing less electricity. The rate at which renewable technologies progress, to a point where they will not require subsidies, can also be accelerated by several factors. The maturation of renewable energy technologies can lead to decreased costs and economic maturity that results in the technology being fully commercial; from 2005 to 2010 the average cost of photovoltaic systems decreased by 48% and those of associated modules by 41% [127]. Additionally, non-EU imports of cheaper renewable energy technologies can decrease costs and make renewable energy more financially competitive. For example, Chinese imports of cheap solar technology has led to an increase in the profitability of the technology for EU solar technology businesses, however, a new EU trade agreement has increased these import costs [132].

The use of feed-in tariffs may increase if they are able to support key policies (such as Energy 2020, Energy Roadmap 2050, Energy infrastructures priorities for 2020 and beyond, Energy Technologies and Innovation and Roadmap) for moving to a competitive low carbon economy in the future. If these policies are met then there is likely to be greater regional equity.

The sovereign debt crisis and pressure on banks have constrained sources of long-term infrastructure financing in Europe [75]. An **EU-EIB Project Bond Initiative** was established in 2012 to enhance the credit quality of the debt to make it more attractive to private investors [134]. It allows private investors to provide financial support for large EU infrastructure projects in exchange for bonds. The initiative is supported by the provision of credit from the EIB in the form of either a loan or an unconditional letter of credit and is hoped to promote growth and job creation. The Castor energy storage project in Spain has benefited from this initiative and the EIB provided a €200 million liquidity line in addition to purchasing EUR 300 million of the bonds as an anchor investor [135]. The initiative has led to projects receiving a 'rating uplift of one notch' compared to their credit quality without EIB support [136]. The enhancement of credit quality can help to increase equal access to funding for structural investments across Europe.

CDF 4 - European Regional Governance

CDF4 European Regional Governance has the objective of assessing the European **governance conditions**, to operationalize the European internal market of electricity distribution and management of the e-highway2050 concept, including the **harmonization among MS of legislations and regulations and national policies strategic priorities**, as well the responsibilities and competences across the Union for **coordination and management of the electricity European grid, institutional cooperation among MS and engagement of key stakeholders** at European and national level.

Policies and Politics

The Lisbon Treaty entered into force in 2009 with specific objectives for the EU energy policy (Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Part 3, Article 194), being the first founding Treaty considering specific provisions “*on EU intervention in the field of energy*”⁸³. The Treaty recognizes the importance of an EU energy policy, and sets that EU cannot step in on MS choices related to energy resources and energy supply sources. With the Treaty entering into force, specific legal basis were introduced in the EU energy framework for energy policy to be developed ahead.

Prior to the publication and enforcement of the Third Energy Package (in 2009) the European Council, in 2007, adopted three energy and climate change objectives for 2020 (considered in the elaboration and structure of the Third Energy Package): reduce GHG emissions by 20%, increase the share of RES to 20%, and improve in 20% the energy efficiency⁸⁴. These objectives were translated into the Energy 2020 Strategy, published in 2010, structured by five priorities⁸⁵:

- Achieve an energy-efficient Europe;
- Build a pan-European integrated energy market;
- Empower consumers and achieve the highest level of safety and security;
- Extend Europe’s leadership in energy technology and innovation; and
- Strengthen the external dimension of the EU energy market.

To achieve the policy objectives on the area of energy, the correct application of effective law in MS is essential. By the end of 2012, 93 infringement cases on energy policy were open (56 less compared with 2011). These infringements of the transposition of Directives are restricting factors to governance conditions to future operationalization of the European internal market of electricity distribution and management, especially when the large number of transposition infringements (MS not meeting the obligations of community rules) is in EU Laws on internal market for electricity and natural gas (Figure 65).

⁸³ http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/institutional_affairs/treaties/lisbon_treaty/ai0024_en.htm

⁸⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/strategies/2010/2020_en.htm [accessed 13/12/14].

⁸⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/publications/doc/2011_energy2020_en.pdf [accessed 13/12/14].

Figure 65 - Infringement cases in the area of energy in 2012 [137]

The adoption of the so called “20-20-20” targets was considered an important milestone on the cross-sectorial integration of energy and climate policy in the EU. The major change was felt on the European energy governance with the creation of a timeframe for MS to deliver policy objectives of their legally binding obligations. The way to put in place the 2020 objectives passed through the adoption of regulations, development of fit-to-purpose plans and projects, the promotion of technological markets, among others, to meet social expectations in a way that citizens felt involved in the prosecution of Europe’s vision for the internal market.

Subsequent to the Energy 2020 strategy, Europe’s energy policy goes beyond the 20-20-20 objectives and develops a long-term European framework for 2050 – the Energy Roadmap 2050. Published in 2011, the Energy Roadmap 2050 presents a technology framework for an effective application of the energy policies by 2050 in order to comply with the objective of decarbonising the energy system: “a European approach to the energy challenge will increase security and solidarity and lower costs compared to parallel national schemes by providing a wider and flexible market for new products and services” (Energy Roadmap 2050)⁸⁶. Relevant stakeholders of the energy system are considered important players in the European framework for 2050.

Despite the differences between MS energy mix⁸⁷, as a consequence of geographical conditions and policy options (e.g. access to natural resources, national policy choices, nuclear decisions, financial incentives, decarbonisation requirements,

⁸⁶ COM (2011) 885 final (<http://www.ipex.eu/IPEXL-WEB/dossier/document/COM20110885.do>).

⁸⁷ In 2011, even with a high share of petroleum and derivate products in the final gross consumption at EU-level, MS energy mixes presented significant differences, like Cyprus, Malta or Luxembourg following EU trend on petroleum, Estonia, and Poland with a high share of solid fuels, Italy and Netherlands of gas, France of nuclear heat, and Latvia, Austria and Sweden of renewables (see: http://ec.europa.eu/energy/publications/doc/2013_pocketbook.pdf).

internal markets), MS share three similar energy policy objectives, based on future scenarios defined by the EC [75]:

- Reduce the energy bill for households and business (“*competitiveness*”) (see Trend Analysis CDF1);
- Ensure a reliable and uninterrupted supply of energy (“*security of supply*”) (see Trend Analysis CDF2);
- Limit the environmental impact of energy production, transport and use (“*sustainability*”).

The main GHG targets applicable to MS under EU commitments (KP and ESD) and 2020 goals are presented in Table 42. Although the target is fixed on a reduction by 20% of the GHG emissions, the current trend is that by 2020 the EU will reduce by 24%⁸⁸, 4% more than what is expected.

Each MS has fixed targets defined in the Decision No 406/2009/EC of the European Parliament and the Council, of 23rd April 2009. From the 28 MS, only Croatia has a temporary target based on 1990 levels regarding 2020 GHG fixed targets. For the other 27 MS, regarding the 2005 levels of GHG emissions, 44.4% can increase their GHG targets, while 55.6% had to decrease their GHG emissions to achieve the expected target.

Table 42 - Main national binding targets on GHG emissions [55]

Country	2020 GHG fixed targets (compared to 2005 levels) [138]	KP target under Burden Sharing Agreement (2012 of base year) [138]	KP individual target (2012 of base year) [138]	National GHG targets under ESD [55]
EU-27	-20%			
Belgium	-15%	-7.5%		
Bulgaria	20%		-8%	
Czech Republic	9%		-8%	
Denmark	-20%	-21%		
Germany	-14%	-21%		
Estonia	11%		-8%	
Ireland	-20%	13%		
Greece	-4%	25%		
Spain	-10%	15%		
France	-14%	0%		
Italy	-13%	-6.5%		
Cyprus	-5%			
Latvia	17%		-8%	
Lithuania	15%		-8%	
Luxembourg	-20%	-28%		
Hungary	10%		-6%	
Malta	5%			
Netherlands	-16%	-6%		
Austria	-16%	-13%		

⁸⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/commission_2010-2014/president/news/archives/2014/03/pdf/presentation_en.pdf [accessed 02/01/14].

Country	2020 GHG fixed targets (compared to 2005 levels) [138]	KP target under Burden Sharing Agreement (2012 of base year) [138]	KP individual target (2012 of base year) [138]	National GHG targets under ESD [55]
Poland	14%		-6%	
Portugal	1%	27%		
Romania	19%		-8%	
Slovenia	4%		-8%	
Slovakia	13%		-8%	
Finland	-16%	0%		
Sweden	-17%	4%		
United Kingdom	-16%	-12.5%		
Croatia	-5% ^{a)}		-5%	
Other Countries				
Iceland			10%	
Liechtenstein			-8%	
Norway			1%	
Switzerland			-8%	
Turkey				

Note:

- 2012 non-ETS emissions were below the 2013 ESD targets and 2020 non-ETS emissions are projected to be lower than the 2020 ESD target with existing measures
- 2012 non-ETS emissions were below their 2013 ESD targets and 2020 non-ETS emissions are projected to be lower than the 2020 ESD target only if planned measures are implemented
- 2012 non-ETS emissions were above the 2013 ESD targets or 2020 non-ETS emissions are projected to be higher than 2020 ESD target even if planned additional measures are implemented

No target / Not applicable

- a) Temporary target. The Croatia target shall be replaced by arrangements in line with and part of the EU mitigation effort. Based year calculation: 1990.

Regarding the KP targets (the EU-28 does not have KP target considering the ratification of the protocol in 2004), 7.1% (Cyprus and Malta) have no KP target defined but are parties to the KP, 53.6% have KP target under Burden Sharing Agreement (all the EU-15 MS), while the other 39.3% have individual GHG reduction targets under the KP (all targets being legally binding under EU law).

In 2011, the EU RES share in the final energy consumption was 13.0%, 4,5% above 2005 values. On the **EU binding targets on energy consumption to come from RES**, Figure 66 presents MS 2020 RES targets and the countries' progress towards 2011-2012 trajectories under the RED and MS 2010 national renewable energy action plans (NREAP).

Figure 66 - National binding targets on RES share in gross final energy consumption [55]

Note:

- 2011 shares (for Norway and Switzerland the values are from 2010)
- Indicative 2011-2012 target (RED)
- ▲ Expected 2011-2012 trajectory (NREAP) (value for EU-28 assumed to be identical to EU-27)
- 2020 target

EU has established the target of 20% share of renewable energy in the EU's gross final energy consumption, expecting to reach 21% by 2020⁸⁹. In 2011, RES contributed with 13% to gross final energy consumption in the EU-28, exceeding the indicative target for 2011-2012 (10.8%).

Of the EU-28 countries, 46.4% have binding targets on at least 20% RES share (e.g. 49% Sweden, 40% Latvia, 31% Portugal, or 20% Croatia). For Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Romania and Lithuania, in 2011, the percentage of RES share was higher than the indicative target of the RED for 2011-2012 and the expected value of MS 2010 NREAPs. In Latvia and France the opposite is observed, the 2011 share is lower than both targets defined by RED and NREAP. Estonia already exceeded its national 2020 target. In the cases of Bulgaria, Germany, Italy, Slovakia and Hungary (where the 2020 binding target is inferior to 20%), the 2011 RES share exceeded their average 2011-2012 (RED and NREAP).

For EU-28 the growth in renewable energy has increased between 2005-2011 (see Trend Analysis CDF2). In a recent report ("Energy challenges and policy", 22 May

⁸⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/commission_2010-2014/president/news/archives/2014/03/pdf/presentation_en.pdf [accessed 08/01/14].

2013), the EC identified four areas to increase the efforts to raise the share of RES in energy consumption [75]:

- Energy market;
- Support schemes;
- Cooperation mechanisms between MS;
- Cooperation in the Mediterranean.

On January 22nd 2014 the “*Policy framework for climate and energy in the period from 2020 to 2030*”⁹⁰ was published with new targets and objectives to be reached by 2030⁹¹:

- Reduce EU domestic GHG emissions by 40% (effort to be shared equitably between MS);
- Increase the share of renewable energy to at least 27% (EU-level target, with no translation into national targets);
- Continue to improve energy efficiency (EU policy to be review in 2014);
- Reform the EU emissions trading system by establishing a market stability reserve at the beginning of the next trading period in 2021.

The 2030 framework is based on the full implementation of the 20-20-20 targets and, among others, on the simplification of the European policy framework (seeking coherence between policy objectives and policy instruments; simplified by the reduction of complexity of the existing framework where multiple targets and overlapping measures existed), on the empowerment of MS in the choice of their energy mix and the flexibility of policy transitions towards decarbonisation strategies, cooperation between MS to meet energy and climate targets, application of cost-effective approach to the use of renewables, and market integration. The energy and climate governance model changed, with the establishment of EU-wide targets to be met by the EU as a whole and not directly transposed into national goals. Further, a major change relative to the previous frameworks is a three-element dedicated governance model:

- The development of national plans for competitive, secure and sustainable energy;
- A set of indicators and objectives, and
- A monitoring programme to keep up with MS national plans consistency and compliance⁹².

The proposal of ending the national binding targets for renewables after 2020 can prove to be hard to apply. According to the EC, GHG emissions in 2011 fallen to 16,9% below the 1990 levels, and to 18% in 2012, being expected to reduce by 24% and 32% in 2020 and 2030, respectively, “*on the basis of current policies*” [139]. Also the share of renewables in final energy consumed has increased to 13% in 2012, being expected to rise to 21% and 24% in 2020 and 2030, respectively [139].

⁹⁰ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/doc/2030/com_2014_15_en.pdf [accessed 08/01/14].

⁹¹ http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/2030/index_en.htm [accessed 08/01/14].

⁹² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52014DC0015&from=EN> [accessed 08/01/14].

To achieve the new targets and objectives to be reached by 2030, and considering the expected values don't fully commit the new targets, the EC defined that the 2030 policy framework should be based on the “*fully implementation*” of the 2020 framework and in the:

- Simplification of the European policy framework while improving complementarity and coherence between objectives and instruments;
- Strengthening regional cooperation between MS to help meet common energy challenges while developing market integration;
- Development of policy based on a more cost-effective approach (market instrument approach) to reinforce European dimension;
- Improving energy security, while delivering a low-carbon and competitive energy system;
- Fair sharing of efforts between MS which reflected their specific circumstances and capacities.

Other important matter in the 2020-2030 framework is the approach proposed to the development/improvement of new/existing policies responsible (or directly related) for EU security of supply. It is defined in the Communication of January 2014 that the approach needs to follow and consider [139]:

- 1) Further exploitation of indigenous energy sources as a necessity by the objective of decreasing EU oil and gas production, considering for that renewable sources, domestic reserves and nuclear;
- 2) A collective act between MS to diversify their supply countries and routes for fossil fuels imports, market liberalization, cross-border interconnectors to ensure security of supply, and PCI's meeting 10% level of interconnectors as a share of installed capacity;
- 3) An improvement of energy intensity and energy performance of buildings, products and processes to generate energy savings.

The main driver for the proposal of this approach was the increasing EU vulnerability to fluctuations in energy supply, and the differences across EU in energy prices due to MS free choice of national energy mixes and MS specifications of energy systems.

A justification of the 2030 policy framework, considered by the EC, is: “*experience with the current 2020 framework indicates that while European and national targets can drive strong action by the MS and growth in emerging industries they have not always ensured market integration, cost-efficiency and undistorted competition*” [139]. The following stage will comprise an agreement between MS for new national GHG emissions as well as for the share of energy from renewable sources for 2030, contributing to what is established in the Energy 2020 and Energy Roadmap 2050 of promoting convergence in MS national policies.

In the period of 1995 to 2001 an estimate of EUR 125 billion [144] was invested in **subsidies to the energy sector** in the EU-15. For 2001, the EU-15 had an indicative estimate of total energy subsidies (excluding external costs) above EUR 29 billion [140], with 8% of the total amount allocated to nuclear, 19% to renewables, 30% to oil

and gas, and 43% to solid fuels. In general, for the evolution of subsidies fossil fuels and nuclear it is possible to observe [141], [142], [143], [144]:

- Fossil fuels (see Figure 67): in EU-15 the most relevant funding scheme is for the coal industry despite its pressures on the environment. In 2010, six countries were responsible for an amount of EUR 3.2 billion in coal subsidies: Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Spain. Annually, fossil fuels take about 75% of total EU energy subsidies. State subsidies rationale for coal mines sift to protect high-cost domestic industries from competition. In 2001, countries like Germany and Spain continued to have subsidies for coal industries, while in countries like Portugal and France ceased out. In the same time frame, UK and the Netherlands had expenditure on oil and gas subsidies, and Finland and Germany had a higher amount allocated to coal production. On oil production, transport or storage, there's no on-budget aid due to the largely privatized level of such industries. In 2011, the subsidies for fossil fuels in the EU amounted to EUR 26 billion, with Denmark, Ireland and Poland (e.g.) being the countries with the share of fossil fuel support allocated only to coal;
- Nuclear power: the on-budget subsidies for nuclear energy came normally from R&D grants by MS (mainly France, Germany and Italy) and European Community. In 2005, nuclear R&D expenditure accounted approximately to 45% of EU total energy R&D spending's.

Figure 67 - Shares of fossil fuel support by fuel for 2009-2011[144]

In July 2009 Directive 2009/72/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the **common rules for the internal market in electricity** was published, specifically for the generation, transmission, distribution and supply of electricity in MS. It defines common rules for organization and functioning of the electricity sector, open access to the market, criteria and procedures applicable to calls for tenders, authorization and the operation of systems, service obligations, rights of electricity consumers, and competition requirements [145] (Table 43), promoting cooperation among MS and the intended development of an internal electricity market. The rules were published aiming to create a more competitive and sustainable market of electricity, and also to ensure that MS are accountable and transparent on their final costumers. This strategy for future energy sector in Europe meets objectives defined by the SET-PLAN 2007 and the RED on cross-border cooperation and converges of MS energy regimes, respectively.

Table 43 - Common rules for the internal market in electricity defined by the Directive 2009/72/EC [145]

Common rules for the internal market in electricity
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Generation	<p>MS shall define criteria for the construction of generating capacity in their territory, considering :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The security and safety of electricity networks; • The protection of health and public safety; and • The contribution made towards the EC's "20-20-20" objectives.
Transmission	<p>From March 2012 MS had to unbundle transmission systems and TSOs; TSOs are mainly responsible for :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the long-term ability of the system to meet demands for electricity; • Ensuring adequate means to meet service obligations; • Contributing to security of supply; • Managing electricity flows on the system; • Providing to the operator of any other system information related to the operation, development and interoperability of the interconnected system; • Ensuring non-discrimination between system users; • Providing system users with the information they need to access the system; • Collecting congestion rents and payments under the ITC.
Distribution	<p>MS shall designate DSOs or require undertakings that own or are responsible for distribution system to do so; DSOs are mainly responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring long-term capacity of the system in terms of the distribution of electricity, operation, maintenance, development and environmental protection; • Ensuring transparency with respect to system users; • Providing system users with information; • Covering energy losses and maintaining reserve electricity capacity.
Supply	<p>Costumers have the right to choose their electricity supplier; Costumers have the right to receive relevant consumption data; Electricity suppliers are obliged to inform customers on the contribution of each energy source, the environmental impact caused, and their rights in the event of dispute; MS are obliged to ensure the monitoring of security of supply</p>
Regulation	<p>MS shall designate a regulatory authority at national level, independent and with impartial power; Regulatory authority is mainly responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fixing transmission or distribution tariffs; • Cooperating in regard to cross-border issues; • Monitoring investment plans of the TSOs; • Ensuring access to customer consumption data.

The deadline for the transposition by the MS of the Directive was March 2011. In March 2013, Estonia, Slovenia, Ireland and Finland hadn't transposed this Directive to their internal legislation [146]. In February 2014, only Ireland had failed in transpose the EU rules on this matter⁹³. With is, is expected that by the end of the current year all MS have transposed the Directive, this being a positive trend to the establishment of 2020, 2030 and 2050 EU energy frameworks.

⁹³ http://ec.europa.eu/ireland/press_office/news_of_the_day/ireland-referred-to-court-failure-transpose-eu-energy-rules_en.htm [accessed 10/01/14].

In November 2013 the EC released a Communication (C(2013) 7243 final) with some guidance for MS to deliver the internal electricity market concerning the state intervention on complying EU objectives of security of supply and climate change. The main aspect of the guidance is the importance given to public intervention, and because of that, the main guidelines given are⁹⁴:

- Support schemes for renewables – expose renewables to market prices thus removing RES support;
- Adequate generation capacity – for security of supply and possible generation fluctuation due to climate events;
- Role of consumers – role of consumers in ensuring energy flow.

If MS apply correctly these guidelines, in future it is possible to increase predictability for policy-makers (and important for future possible investors), to create cost-effective solutions in order to comply with EU objectives of security of supply; to reach market stability; and promote EU at international eyes as a region without fragmentation on its internal market.

Responsibilities and competences

The Regulation 714/2009/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, of July 2009, set the “**rules providing a framework for cross-border exchanges in electricity**” [23]. These network codes were to be developed by the ENTSO-E working with Framework Guidelines developed by the ACER.

The network codes development had to take into account each regional specificities, namely in terms of network security, network connection rules, interoperability rules, operational procedures, capacity allocation and congestion management rules, transparency rules, or energy efficiency regarding electricity networks. The intention was to complement existing national rules with the creation of a coherent and coordinated framework, implemented by common rules with cross-border impact. The main areas of development of network codes are the grid connection, system operator, and market (Figure 68). For each of these three areas, a set of network codes are under development (Table 44). It is expected that the development of all the network codes will be completed ahead of 2014, followed by a ‘formal’ adoption by the EU and the process of formalizing it in legally binding rules. As a consequence, are expected harmonized rules to regulate “*the operation of the electricity transmission network*”, integrate renewable production among parties, and ensure security of supply.

⁹⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/ireland/press_office/news_of_the_day/ireland-referred-to-court-failure-transpose-eu-energy-rules_en.htm [accessed 10/01/14].

Figure 68 - Internal Energy Market and importance of Network Codes [148]

Table 44 - Contribution of network codes to deliver future energy sector rules [149]

Network Code	Content
Requirements for Generators (RfG)	Sets requirements which new generators connecting to the network (both distribution and transmission) – and existing generators (in very limited cases) – will need to meet, as well as responsibilities on TSOs and DSOs.
Demand Connection (DCC)	Sets requirements for new demand users and distribution network connections to the network, outlines basic demand side response capabilities for meeting Transmission System needs, as well as responsibilities on TSOs and DSOs.
High Voltage Direct Current Connection (HVDC)	Sets requirements for HVDC connections and offshore DCC connected generation.
Operational Security (OS)	Sets common rules for ensuring the operational security of the pan-European power system.
Operational Planning and Scheduling (OPS)	Sets requirements, ranging from the year ahead timeframe to real time, for assessing the adequacy and operational security of the interconnected power system and for planning outages required by TSOs and grid users when they have cross borders impacts on power flows.
Load Frequency Control & Reserves (LFCR)	Provides for the coordination and technical specification of load frequency control processes and specifies the levels of reserves (back-up) which TSOs need to hold and specifies where they need to be held.
Capacity Allocation & Congestion Management (CACM)	Creates the rules for operating pan-European day ahead and intraday markets, explains how capacity is calculated and explains how bidding zones will be defined. Is based on four elements: intraday markets, day ahead markets, and a coordinated approach to capacity calculation.
Balancing (EB)	Sets rules to define the roles and responsibilities of TSOs and market parties to procure and exchange balancing products to balance the system from day ahead to real time in the most efficient way. It also includes financial principles for the payment of these services.
Forward Capacity Allocation (FCA)	Sets rules for calculating and buying capacity in timescales before day ahead and for hedging price risk between bidding zones in long-term timeframes.

Another concern is the consistency of the network codes with other elements of European energy policy (Figure 69). The most significant consistency between the network codes and European energy policy regulations are [149]:

- Regulation on fundamental electricity data transparency – both have rules for publishing data;
- Guidelines on governance – both determines the sharing of responsibility between TSOs;
- Market on Financial Instruments Directive (MIFID) and Regulation on Electricity Market Integrity and Transparency (REMIT) – both articulates the products offered via forward markets;
- Energy Efficiency Directive – both promote energy efficiency and demand side response;
- Smart Grid Initiatives – both have potential and future importance of the demand side and smart grids;
- Both work with standardisation bodies.

The consistency above presented is a positive indicator for, in the next years, reach harmonization under EU energy policy instruments.

Figure 69 - Links between network codes and broader policy areas [149]

Now a day ENTSO-E integrates 41 TSOs, representing 34 countries. Each TSO has the responsibility of the national system control and security, with the arrangements being susceptible to national specifics. To promote the **regional cooperation between the TSOs**, the European Regulators’ Group for Electricity and Gas (EREG) launched the ERI with the intention of promoting the creation of a single-EU electricity market from the integration of MS national markets on seven regions [150]. Each region considers regulators, companies, MS, the EC and other parties, and has similar aims and priorities that reflect their specific interests (Table 45). The intention is to create a more operational coordination among TSOs, anticipate the mitigation of

possible risks, and incorporate the level of complexity of the grid coordination on its operational arrangements.

Table 45 - Electricity Regional Initiative [150]

Region	Countries	Aims and Priorities
Baltic	Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania	Potential to function as the link between Central-East and Northern European regional markets. The key priorities of this region are to promote cooperation between network operators, grid access, balancing rules and transparency in the sector.
Central East	Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia	The key priorities are to promote cohesion within the region regarding EU policies, congestion management, and transparency, reducing barriers to market entry and developing regulatory competences.
Central South	Austria, France, Germany, Greece and Slovenia	The key priorities are the harmonization of congestion management methods, inter TSO coordination, transparency, integration of intra-day, and balancing markets and assessment of regulatory competences.
Central West	Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands	Harmonization and improvement of auction rules, implementation of a day-ahead, flow-based market coupling, implementation of cross-border intraday trade, maximization of the cross-border capacity, and transparency are the key priorities of this region for their internal market.
Northern	Denmark, Finland, Germany, Norway, Poland, and Sweden	This regions aims to promote good practice in terms of market arrangements, investment for interconnections, transparency, information availability and accessibility to market actors, and joint intraday and balancing market.
South-West	France and the Iberian peninsula	Promote the cohesion among France market and the Iberian Electricity Market (dated from 2007), and the regulatory convergent between Spain and Portugal. The key priorities are transparency, auction platform, or cross-border balancing among TSOs.
France-UK-Ireland	France, UK, and Ireland	The key priorities are cooperation and coordination at the European level, interconnections and compliance with the Congestion Management Guidelines, intraday trading, reciprocal access to balancing market, and wholesale market transparency.

The RED (Directive 2009/28/EC) sets the current cross-border **cooperation mechanisms** for intra-European cooperation and third countries cooperation [151]:

- Statistical transfer: MS governments may agree to transfer statistical information on quantity of renewable energy produced from one MS to another;
- Joint projects: two or more MS can agree to finance a jointly project on RES, sharing the costs and benefits of it. It is also defined by Article 9 of the RED

that is possible for MS to physically import RES-electricity from a third country (NMS);

- Joint support schemes: two or more MS can decide to coordinate their national support schemes, allowing that a MS amount of renewable sources produced can be transfer through an agreed distribution rule allocations contributions.

The idea inherent to the cooperation mechanisms is to allow adding a mechanism that will improve MS national support schemes in a short- or long-term commitments between different MS. Also, is intended that the cooperation mechanisms can be a valuable asset to encourage the so wanted regional market, and then the Pan-European approach to European internal electricity market to achieve an “*Europeanization (...) for electricity market*” [152]. Currently, these cooperation mechanisms have not been used sufficiently used [11] (only North of Europe for wind energy and South-west of Europe for solar energy made use of the mechanisms provided in the RED), representing a challenge to market integration [152]. Also in RED was required the creation by the EC of an online public Transparency Platform⁹⁵ to enhance and facilitate cooperation between MS concerning statistical transfers and joint projects. The platform has the objective of increasing the share of information, promoting transparency on energy policy issues, and promote cooperation and coordination among MS.

For the EU, **civil society** represents individuals or groups (like civil society organizations) who are “*neither connected to, nor managed by, the State*” [153]. The importance of civil society participation is recognized by the Article 15 of the Lisbon Treaty as essential to prosecute good governance in Europe.

In 2007 the EC, associated with the Energy Commissioners, launched the Citizens’ Energy Forum as a regulatory platform designed to implement and carry out consumer rights in energy issues across EU. It aims, ultimately, to address consumer problems and propose practical and realistic solutions. The Forum brings together the regulation and consumer perspectives, and established two groups: the Vulnerable Consumer Working Group, and the Price Transparency Working Group. The Vulnerable Consumer Working Group (active since 2012) is an example of governance instrument with the intention to guide social and other policies through current energy issues encountered by vulnerable consumers and other relevant stakeholders on six headings: household energy efficiency, financial support, protection, information and engagement, information sharing between stakeholders, and physical measures⁹⁶. One of the major groups active in the Forum is the European Consumer Consultative Group on Energy, a network of representatives of national consumer organizations, with one member from each European consumer organization (BEUC and ANEC), two associate members (EUROCOOP and COFACE), and two EEA observers (from Iceland and Norway) [154].

⁹⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/renewables/transparency_platform/transparency_platform_en.htm [accessed 09/01/14].

⁹⁶http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/forum_citizen_energy/20140106_vulnerable_consumer_report.pdf [accessed 09/01/14].

Regarding consumers, and the general public, one important programme is likely to fully develop until 2016: the European Energy Dialogue. This initiative is based on the vision that, “by 2016 citizens and civil societies organisations will be engaged in the European Energy Dialogue, a co-ordinated multi-level conversation within ad across all MS. It will be recognised as having a measurable influence on policy-making across all form of energy and be stimulating convergence at EU level, linking with the post-2020 energy and climate framework”⁹⁷. The main objective is to close the gap between the technical and economic developments within the energy sector and what is politically and socially accepted by civil society. The European Energy Dialogue was issued by an opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) in 2013, where is stated that “citizens need to be more efficiently involved in the strategic direction of major policy choices – beyond their role as energy consumers – because preparing the energy transition goes beyond the important market issues”⁹⁸. The main expected result from this initiative in the establishment of a common framework for energy dialogue applied throughout the EU.

⁹⁷ <http://www.eesc.europa.eu/resources/docs/european-energy-dialogue-20130209.pdf> [accessed 09/01/14].

⁹⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52012AE2366&from=EN> [accessed 09/01/14].

Annex 3 – Relevant stakeholders for e-Highway2050

Table 46 - Relevant stakeholders for e-Highway2050

Interest Groups - relevant stakeholders		
European Commission (EC)	DG Energy	Commissioner Director-General
	DG Environment	
	DG Regional Policy	
	DG Research and Innovation	
	DG Agriculture and Rural Development	
	DG Climate Action (CLIMA)	
European Parliament (EP)	Committee on Industry, External Trade, Research and Energy (ITRE)	
	Committee of the Regions	
	Members of the EP	
Finance, funds and banks	European Local Energy Assistance (ELENA)	
	European Investment Bank (EIB)	
	European Investment Fund (EIF)	
	European Association of Energy Service Companies (eu.ESCO)	
	INFOREGIO Managing Authorities	
European agencies	European Environment Agency (EEA)	
	EURATOM Supply Agency (ESA)	
	Fusion for Energy (European Joint Undertaking for ITER and the Development of Fusion Energy)	
	Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER)	
International associations	Renewable Energy Organizations	(e.g.: European Biomass Association; European Bioethanol Fuel Association; European Geothermal Energy Council; European Small Hydropower Association; European Renewable Energy Council; European Ocean Energy Association; European Wind Energy Association; International Renewable Energy Agency; Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21 st Century; The Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Partnership)
	Energy Community	
	General	(e.g.: International Energy Agency; European Energy Network; European Network for Cities and Regions for the Social Economy; Energy Cities; European Business Council for Sustainable Energy Future)

	Other relevant international associations/agencies
National Associations	European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment (FEDARENE)
	Intelligent Energy
	European Association for Information on Local Development (AEIDL)
	Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR)
	Energy in Central and Eastern Europe (enerCEE)
	Baltic Sea Region Energy Co-operation (BASREC)
	Other relevant MS associations/agencies (e.g. Austrian Energy Agency; Centre for Renewable Energy Sources CRS; Ente per le Buove Technologies ENEA; Sustainable Energy Ireland SEI)
National Governments	MS Public Authorities (representatives' bodies)
Regulators	Council of European Energy Regulators (CEER)
	MS Regulatory Bodies
TSOs	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) Assembly
	ENTSO-E Member Companies (Countries TSOs)
DSOs	European Distribution System Operators for Smart Grids (EDSO)
	Union of the Electricity Industry (EURELECTRIC)
	European Voice of Local Energy Distributors (GEODE)
	CEDEC
Sectorial Entities (Public and Private)	Institutional Investors Group on Climate Change (IIGCC)
	Climate Alliance
	Industry Representatives (EU and MS-level)
	Other relevant private entities
Other relevant entities	Friends of the SuperGrid
	European Alliance to Save Energy
	Global CCS Institute
	European Federation of Intelligent Energy Efficiency Services (EFIEES)
	Sustainable Nuclear Energy Technology Platform (SNETP)
	European Suppliers of Waste to Energy Technology
	European Federation of Energy Traders (EFET)
	International Federation of Industrial Energy Consumers (IFIEC Europe)
	European Power Plant Suppliers Association (EPPSA)
	European Association for the Promotion of Cogeneration (COGEN)
	European Union of the Natural Gas Industry (EuroGas)
	European Association for Storage of Energy (EASE)
	Smart Energy Demand Coalition (SEDC)
	European Nuclear Energy Forum members
Energy Partnership	

	Renewable Grid Initiative
	Electricity producers (generation entities)
	University Institutes, Education and R&D performers
	European Consumer Organization (BEUC)
	Other Consumer Associations (MS-level)
	MS authorities with specific environmental responsibilities (defined under MS SEA legislation)
Third Party Countries	Relevant entities from third party countries
NGOs	Climate Action Network Europe (CAN-E)
	Bird Life Europe
	European Climate Foundation
	European Habitats Forum (EHF)
	European Wildlife
	Green-10
	Health and Environment Alliance
	Naturefriends International (NFI)
	Platform of European Social NGOs
	Transport and Environment (T&E)
	Greenpeace European Unit
	WWF European Policy Office (WWF-EPO)
	Friends of the Earth Europe (FoEE)
	European Environmental Bureau (EEB)
	Third Generation Environmentalism (E3G)
	International Network for Sustainable Energy
	European Renewable Energies Federation
European Platform Against Windfarms	
Partners for Euro-African Green Energy (PANGEA)	
Other relevant NGOs (EU and MS-level)	
Media	ENDS Europe
	EurActiv
	European Voice
	Europe's World
	The Parliament Magazine
	viEUws
	Other relevant media
Civil Society	European Civil Society Organizations
	Civil Society individuals (electricity consumers)
	Local Producers

Table 47 - Responsibilities and competences of relevant stakeholders

Relevant stakeholders		Responsibilities and Competences
EC	DG Energy ⁹⁹	Develop and implement an European energy policy; Contribute to set up an energy market providing citizens and businesses with affordable energy, competitive prices and technologically advanced energy services; Promote sustainable energy production, transport and consumption in line with the EU 2020 targets and with a view to the 2050 decarbonisation objective; Enhance the conditions for secure energy supply in a spirit of solidarity between MS; Promote the complementarity and integration between energy policies and other sectorial EU policies.
EC	Other DG's (e.g. DG CLIMA, DG Environment)	Accomplish the development and implementation of its respective policy in relation to the established objectives for its sector of development; Promote the complementarity and integration between its sector policies and other sectorial EU energy policy.
European Parliament		Under the Lisbon Treaty, the EP is the lawmaker with the Council (with equal rights) in the area (among others) of energy security. With the Council, the EP has the responsibility to decide on the content of EU laws and officially adopt them (process of 'Ordinary Legislative Procedure') ¹⁰⁰ ; Debate and pass European laws, with the Council ¹⁰¹ ; Scrutinize other EU institutions, particularly the Commission, to make sure they are working democratically ¹⁰⁰ ; Debate and adopt the EU's budget, with the Council ¹⁰⁰ .
Finance, funds and banks (e.g. EIB, EIF, ELENA)		Support projects and invest in future partner countries; Assist in attract private capital to finance energy projects; Examine the scale of investments required and financing option to energy development proposals.
European Agencies	ACER ¹⁰²	Issue an opinion on the draft statutes, the list of members and the draft rules of procedure of the ENTSO for electricity and gas, and monitoring the execution of the tasks; Role in drafting the framework guidelines which the network codes must comply with; Monitor regional cooperation between TSOs in the electricity and gas sectors, and the execution of tasks by the ENTSO for electricity and gas;

⁹⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/energy/mission_en.htm [accessed 22/01/14].

¹⁰⁰ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/aboutparliament/en/0042423726/Parliament-and-the-Lisbon-Treaty.html> [accessed 22/01/14].

¹⁰¹ http://europa.eu/about-eu/institutions-bodies/european-parliament/index_en.htm [accessed 22/01/14].

¹⁰² Regulation (EC) No 713/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 (http://europa.eu/legislation_summaries/energy/internal_energy_market/en0013_en.htm) [accessed 22/01/14].

		<p>Adopt, under certain conditions, individual decision on technical issues and make recommendations with the aim of promoting the exchange of good practice between regulatory authorities and market players;</p> <p>Provide a framework for cooperation between the national regulatory authorities;</p> <p>Analyse the compliance of regulatory authorities with the applicable Community rules;</p> <p>Determine, under certain conditions, the terms and conditions for access to and operational security of electricity and gas infrastructure, which connects at least two MS;</p> <p>Terms and conditions for access applicable to cross-border infrastructure including a procedure for capacity allocation, a time-frame for allocation, a shared congestion revenues, and the levying of charges on the users of the infrastructures;</p> <p>Monitor the internal markets in electricity and natural gas, in particular the retail prices of electricity and natural gas.</p>
	<p>Other¹⁰³ (e.g. EEA, ESA)</p>	<p>Perform the specific tasks under EU law for their sector of activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out technical, scientific or managerial tasks that help the EU institutions make and implement policies; • Support cooperation between the EU and national governments by pooling technical and specialist expertise from both the EU institutions and national authorities. <p>EURATOM: coordinate national nuclear research programme for peaceful purposes; provide knowledge, infrastructure and funding for nuclear energy; ensure sufficient and secure supplies of nuclear energy.</p>
<p>International associations</p>	<p>Energy Community¹⁰⁴</p>	<p>Organise the relations between Parties and create a legal and economic framework in relation to Network Energy (general task);</p> <p>Create a stable regulatory and market framework capable of attracting investment in gas networks, power generation, and transmission and distribution networks, so that all Parties have access to the stable and continuous energy supply that is essential for economic development and social stability;</p> <p>Create a single regulatory space for trade in Network Energy that is necessary to match the geographic extent of the concerned product markets;</p> <p>Enhance the security of supply of the single regulatory space by providing a stable investment climate in which connections to Caspian, North African and Middle East gas reserves can be developed, and indigenous sources of energy such as natural gas, coal and hydropower can be exploited;</p>

¹⁰³ http://europa.eu/about-eu/agencies/index_en.htm [accessed 22/01/14].

¹⁰⁴ http://www.energy-community.org/portal/page/portal/ENC_HOME/ENERGY_COMMUNITY/Legal/Treaty [accessed 22/01/14].

		<p>Improve the environmental situation in relation to Network Energy and related energy efficiency, foster the use of renewable energy, and set out the condition for energy trade in the single regulatory space;</p> <p>Develop Network Energy market competition on a broader geographic scale and exploit economies of scale.</p>
	Other (e.g. IEA, EEN, IREA)	<p>Provide an organized framework for international cooperation;</p> <p>Provide guidance and recommendations under their sector of activity;</p> <p>Act as policy advisor to its MS.</p>
National Associations (e.g. FEDARENE, AEIDL, BASREC)		<p>Ensure the fulfilment of EU rules and regulations on energy policy in relation to their areas of activity and institutional context;</p> <p>Legitimate the process of existing development projects and future ones.</p>
National Governments		<p>Timely and comprehensive transposition of the Third energy package Directives and implementation of the Third energy package Regulations¹⁰⁵;</p> <p>Rigorous application of the internal energy and competition rules¹⁰⁵;</p> <p>Enhance effectiveness of Regional Initiatives and their contribution to the integration of the internal energy market¹⁰⁵;</p> <p>Prepare national action plans for swift deployment of smart grids¹⁰⁵;</p> <p>Stimulate competition by developing infrastructure in support of cross-border activity and eliminate market entry barriers¹⁰⁵;</p> <p>Seek to cease regulating electricity and gas prices for all consumers, including households and SMEs, taking into account universal service obligation and effective protection of vulnerable customers¹⁰⁵.</p>
Regulators (CEER and state-level)		<p>CEER¹⁰⁶:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the creation of a single, competitive, efficient and sustainable internal market for gas and electricity; • Act as a platform for cooperation, information exchange and assistance between Europe’s national energy regulators and is their interface at EU and international level; • Work closely with (and supports) the ACER; • Strive to share regulatory best practice. <p>MS regulatory bodies¹⁰⁸:</p> <p>Fixe or approve, in accordance with transparent criteria, transmission or distribution tariffs or their methodologies;</p> <p>Ensure compliance of transmission and distribution system operators and, where relevant, system owners, as well as of any electricity undertakings;</p> <p>Cooperate in regard to cross-border issues with the regulatory</p>

¹⁰⁵ COM (2012) 663 final (http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/doc/20121115_iem_0663_en.pdf) [accessed 22/01/14].

¹⁰⁶ http://www.ceer.eu/portal/page/portal/EER_HOME/EER_ABOUT/CEER [accessed 22/01/14].

	<p>authority or authorities of the MS concerned and with the Agency; Comply with, and implement, any relevant legally binding decisions of the Agency and of the Commission; Report annually on its activity and the fulfilment of its duties to the relevant authorities of the MS, the Agency and the Commission; Ensure that there are no cross-subsidies between transmission, distribution, and supply activities; Monitor investment plans of the transmission system operators; Monitor compliance with and reviewing the past performance of network security and reliability rules and setting or approving standards and requirements for quality of service and supply or contributing thereto together with other competent authorities; Monitor the level of transparency, including of wholesale prices, and ensuring compliance of electricity undertakings with transparency obligations; Monitor the level and effectiveness of market opening and competition at wholesale and retail levels; Help to ensure, together with other relevant authorities, that the consumer protection measures are effective and enforced; Ensure access to customer consumption data, the provision, for optional use, of an easily understandable harmonised format at national level for consumption data, and prompt access for all customers to such data; Monitor the implementation of rules relating to the roles and responsibilities of transmission system operators, distribution system operators, suppliers and customers and other market parties; Monitor investment in generation capacities in relation to security of supply; Monitor technical cooperation between Community and third-country transmission system operators.</p>				
<p>Transmission System Operators (TSOs)</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="375 1368 571 1787"> <p>ENTSO-E¹⁰⁷</p> </td> <td data-bbox="571 1368 1398 1787"> <p>Pursue coordinated, reliable and secure operations of the electricity transmission network; Promote the development of the interconnected European grid and investments for a sustainable power system; Offer a platform for the market by proposing and implementing standardized market integration and transparency frameworks that facilitate competitive and truly integrated continental-scale wholesale and retail markets; Facilitate secure integration of new generation sources, particularly growing amounts of renewable energy and the achievement of the EU's greenhouse gases reduction goals.</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="375 1787 571 1818"> <p>State-level</p> </td> <td data-bbox="571 1787 1398 1818"> <p>Ensure the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>ENTSO-E¹⁰⁷</p>	<p>Pursue coordinated, reliable and secure operations of the electricity transmission network; Promote the development of the interconnected European grid and investments for a sustainable power system; Offer a platform for the market by proposing and implementing standardized market integration and transparency frameworks that facilitate competitive and truly integrated continental-scale wholesale and retail markets; Facilitate secure integration of new generation sources, particularly growing amounts of renewable energy and the achievement of the EU's greenhouse gases reduction goals.</p>	<p>State-level</p>	<p>Ensure the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable</p>
<p>ENTSO-E¹⁰⁷</p>	<p>Pursue coordinated, reliable and secure operations of the electricity transmission network; Promote the development of the interconnected European grid and investments for a sustainable power system; Offer a platform for the market by proposing and implementing standardized market integration and transparency frameworks that facilitate competitive and truly integrated continental-scale wholesale and retail markets; Facilitate secure integration of new generation sources, particularly growing amounts of renewable energy and the achievement of the EU's greenhouse gases reduction goals.</p>				
<p>State-level</p>	<p>Ensure the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable</p>				

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.entsoe.eu/about-entso-e/inside-entso-e/mission-and-vision/> [accessed 22/01/14].

	TSOs ¹⁰⁸	<p>demands for the transmission of electricity, operating, maintaining and developing under economic conditions secure, reliable and efficient transmission systems with due regard to the environment;</p> <p>Ensure adequate means to meet service obligations;</p> <p>Contribute to security of supply through adequate transmission capacity and system reliability;</p> <p>Manage electricity flows on the system, taking into account exchanges with other interconnected systems;</p> <p>Provide to the operator of any other system with which its system is interconnected sufficient information to ensure the secure and efficient operation, coordinated development and interoperability of the interconnected system;</p> <p>Ensure non-discrimination as between system users or classes of system users, particularly in favour of its related undertakings;</p> <p>Provide system users with the information they need for efficient access to the system;</p> <p>Collect congestion rents and payments under the inter-transmission system operator compensation mechanism.</p>
Distribution System Operators (DSOs)¹⁰⁸		<p>Ensure the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable demands for the distribution of electricity, for operating, maintaining and developing under economic conditions a secure, reliable and efficient electricity distribution system in its area with due regard for the environment and energy efficiency;</p> <p>Provide system users with the information they need for efficient access to, including use of, the system;</p> <p>Procure the energy it uses to cover energy losses and reserve capacity in its system according to transparent, non-discriminatory and market based procedures, whenever it has such a function;</p>
Sectorial Entities (e.g. IIGCC, Climate Alliance)		<p>Ensure the fulfilment of EU rules and regulations on energy policy in relation to their areas of activity and institutional context;</p> <p>Legitimate the process of existing development projects and future ones;</p>
Other relevant entities (e.g. Friends of the SuperGrid, EFET, SEDC, COGEN)		<p>Promote fair competitiveness in the European internal energy market;</p> <p>Active participation in future energy initiatives and policy-making.</p>
Third Party Countries		<p>Provide information about their interests in European energy initiatives on the contexts of the existing agreements;</p> <p>Cooperate with the Energy Community and relevant International Associations/Organizations in relation to current and future international agreements;</p> <p>Respect the terms of the trade relationship and agreements with the EU, and International Associations/Organizations where EU plays an important role;</p>

¹⁰⁸ Directive 2009/72/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:211:0055:0093:EN:PDF>) [accessed 23/04/14].

	Develop voluntary instruments, together with the EU, to improve the status relation and the quality of global energy governance.
Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) ^{109, 110}	Contribute to a democratic development of the European energy policy together with decision-makers, market entities, and civil society; Engage in regular dialogue with public authorities to pursuit a better implementation of EU energy initiatives and policies; Promote public awareness and the participatory involvement of civil society in energy policy developments and policy-making; Active participation in future energy initiatives and policy-making.
Media	Disclose of information to all the existing relevant stakeholders and to those with particular interest in the developments of the European energy sector.
Civil Society ¹¹¹	Ensure the fulfilment of the several energy policies; Help mobilise resources and social capital into energy dialogues; Active participation in future energy initiatives and policy-making to ensure inclusive and effective policies.

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.coe.int/t/dghl/standardsetting/cdcj/ONG/Fundamental%20Principles%20E.pdf> [accessed 23/04/14].

¹¹⁰ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=330> [accessed 23/04/14].

¹¹¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2012:0492:FIN:EN:PDF> [accessed 23/04/14].

Annex 4 – Stakeholder Engagement Results

Annex 4.1 - Consultation 1 Results: Online Questionnaire, October/November 2013

Responses were elicited from ten stakeholders, including e-Highway consortium members, NGOs, and industry representatives. The methodology adopted in consultation 1 is detailed at section 4.1.

4.1 Key environmental and sustainability issues to be taken into account in the strategic environmental and sustainability assessment as identified by questionnaire respondents

Drivers

The main drivers of long-term electricity grid development in Europe, as identified respondents to the consultation, are as follows:

- Security of supply;
- RES integration [balancing energy systems with high shares of variable RES (interconnection / HVDC links)];
- Development of new technologies;
- Market integration;
- Mitigation drivers.

Risks and opportunities

Key, risks and opportunities for sustainable development posed by long-term grid-development in Europe identified by respondents to the consultation are outlined in Table 48.

Table 48 - Risks and opportunities

Risks	Opportunities
Weak harmonization of strategies and rules among MS	Energy independence
Big investment needed	New technology development
Low fuel and CO ₂ prices	Substantive RES deployment
Public opposition	Energy and resource efficiency
Extreme weather events	New market designs

Respondents made additional comments in relation to risks and opportunities:

- In order to grasp the full potential that energy storage can deliver to the system, all system services must be priced in a transparent manner and the services they provide must be recognized and properly valued by markets or existing regulation;
- Need for legal and regulatory harmonization to ensure equity across member countries;
- Grid development is necessary for successful (economic and technical viability, political and social acceptability) decarbonisation of Europe's energy systems. However there is a significant risk that grids development will be approached without adequate consideration for environmental protection, efficiency, transparency, public participation, accountability and respect for due process. There are also risks of failure to envision and plan for an efficient and environmentally sensitive roll out of a grid system that will work for a sustainable future energy system. Innovation in smart grid technologies and demand response are essential to minimise overall new investment required. Through lack of vision and forward strategic planning, there is a risk of pursuing a piecemeal and therefore ineffective and excessively costly network. Undergrounding must be promoted where this reconciles grid development with nature protection requirements. Excessive focus on cost cutting could reduce public acceptability, for example if attempts are made to weaken regulations protecting health and safety or nature protection in order to cut costs. These problems will worsen public acceptability problems and planning delays, and as a result could jeopardise decarbonisation (NGOs).

Priority policies

Respondents were asked to highlight and rank the top five priority policies of relevance to long-term electricity grid development in Europe (Table 49).

Table 49 - Policies identified by questionnaire respondents and how they were ranked in order of importance

Rank	Respondent Reference									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Internal market for electricity and gas	Enhancement of competition	Energy policy	Security of supply	Full implementation of RED	To ensure security, adequacy and to increase the interoperability of the transmission system operation on EU level	Measures to engage people for the implementation of the electric network infrastructure (needs and benefits of the electric network infrastructure)	Energy policy	CO ₂ reduction	Post 2020 climate and energy package
2	Climate and energy package 2020	Grid Optimization, Innovation and Intelligence -> Smart Grid	Environment policy	80-95% fossil free Europe in 2050	Full implementation of Infrastructure Guidelines	To remove the constrains for RES penetration	Long-term stable energy policy	Environmental and climate change policy	Renewable generation	Internal energy market reforms
3	Climate and energy package 2030	Facilitation of renewable energy use	Climate policy	Internal electricity market	Full implementation of SET-Plan (Integrated Roadmap)	To provide the condition and tools to create market integration, competition and system flexibility	To give back a long-term carbon signal	Macroeconomic policies	Grid Security	Energy Infrastructure Regulation
4	Energy roadmap 2050	New Market, Energy efficiency measures	Investment policy		Adaptation of capacity allocation mechanisms.	To set European rules on health protection and environmental safeguard and to improve public acceptance of new infrastructures	Assessment to ensure the feasibility and coherency of all climate and Energy objectives, mechanisms and framework. The tools to implement policy objectives should capture the technical challenges in achieving the goals.	Industrial policies	Energy efficiency	Habitats Directive
5	Public intervention on electricity and gas markets	Modernisation to meet increasing demand	Technology policy			To promote Research and Innovation	Coordination of energies policy at national level and between national vs. European policy levels	Competition policies	European Energy Single Market	Aarhus Convention

4.1.2 Responses on the proposed assessment framework

All eight respondents answered ‘Yes’ to the question: ‘Does the proposed assessment framework reflect the fundamental factors that need to be considered in decision making in order to support the design of a more sustainable electricity grid for 2050?’

Additional comments to this question:

- The mutual influence of elements of the grid should be assessed somehow;
- Some criteria are quite approximate like “consumption behaviour”, “green behaviour”, “future legacy”, “smart grid”...and need more accuracy to be well understood. I would suggest adding a definition to each criterion (in a glossary for example), this could be very useful if these criteria have to be quantified. In CDF 1, the resource preservation is missing (reflects individuals and community benefits) in addition of efficiency measures;
- The assessment criteria are not quite clear, they may be interpreted in different ways. Sometimes some words are missing to define the goal of the criteria (e.g.: International energy trade European contribution rather than “International energy trade”);
- The fundamental factors are well captured, however some adjustments are needed especially on the assessment criteria of CDF 2 relative to technologies. The below corrections are made with regard to what was developed in WP3. We would suggest to distinguish generic assessment criteria and specific ones;
- Generic assessment criteria for the category “innovation and technological development” of CDF 2 relate to issues such as “maturity of new technologies for medium to long term implementation”, “investment in R&D”, “standards”, “interoperability”, “market and supply chain” issues, etc.;
- Specific assessment criteria for the same category shall distinguish:
 - i. Specific factors for TRANSMISSION related technologies such as reliability, controllability, increase in transmission capacity, system losses reduction, reduced environmental impact of innovative transmission technologies;
 - ii. Specific factors for DEMAND-related technologies such as “technology efficiency”, “socio-economics and demography”; “shift to/from electricity” i.e. any change in electrification or to new uses (or shift from industry to services), “ICT and power”;
 - iii. Specific factors for GENERATION/STORAGE-related technologies such as flexibility and efficiency.
- Regarding terminology, the wording “options” is also used in WP1. Consistency check should be ensured;
- Grid development is necessary for successful (economic and technical viability, political and social acceptability) decarbonisation of Europe’s energy systems. However there is a significant risk that grids development will be approached without adequate consideration for environmental protection, efficiency, transparency, public participation, accountability and respect for due process. There are also risks of failure to envision and plan for an efficient and environmentally sensitive roll out of a grid system that will work for a sustainable future energy system. Innovation in smart grid technologies and demand response are essential to minimise overall new investment required. Through lack of vision and forward

strategic planning, there is a risk of pursuing a piecemeal and therefore ineffective and excessively costly network. Undergrounding must be promoted where this reconciles grid development with nature protection requirements. Excessive focus on cost cutting could reduce public acceptability, for example if attempts are made to weaken regulations protecting health and safety or nature protection in order to cut costs. These problems will worsen public acceptability problems and planning delays, and as a result could jeopardise decarbonisation.

The questionnaire then asked respondents to highlight any other critical issues that should be covered in the assessment framework. The following issues were raised:

- Energy storage is a key instrument to increase grid flexibility;
- Grid infrastructure vulnerability to climatic extreme events;
- Harmonization between legislation and regulations;
- Different authorization procedures could be a limit to the development of a European Transmission Network Plan. Also, different applications, in different countries of SEA could be a risk factor;
- Resource preservation: energy consumption management by population, environment impacts consequences;
- Respect for environmental limits;
- Respect for social equity and the needs of the poorest in society;
- Building trust and social acceptability;
- Some of the CDFs look like issues that should really be addressed in the 'operational assessment', in particular those relating to technologies and energy security (CDF2). Also in CDF1 'grid infrastructure vulnerability to climate extremes' seems an operational rather than a sustainability consideration. These issues are presumably central to designing the grid architectures under consideration, so an additional step to check for them in the SESA is redundant (or double counting);
- It is an excellent approach for such a highly strategic exercise. We support the overall approach, and urge the project team to ensure the SESA is as thorough and robust as possible. That means devoting resources to gathering robust evidence wherever possible, and engaging thoroughly with stakeholders. Care is needed to ensure the assessment retains an environment and sustainability focus.

4.1.3 How was consultation 1 taken into account?

The outcomes of consultation 1 played a key role in fine-tuning the development of the CDFs, assessment criteria and indicators in the SESA assessment framework.

Annex 4.2 - Consultation 2 Results: Web Conference, 29 November 2013

Despite wide and repeated dissemination of the invitation to participate in the consultation, only four stakeholders attended from outside of the WP4.2 project team. Based on such low attendance, the results of the workshop cannot be classified as representative or significant. This should be taken into account when reviewing the following results of the consultation and in consequence, consideration is also given to limitations and learning from the web conference approach. Consultation 2 methodology is detailed in section 4.2.

This section focuses on web conference attendees' feedback on the key risks and opportunities identified by **consultation one**, suggestions for additional risks and opportunities, and comments on the CDFs.

Please note, each discussion session was preceded by a short introductory presentation.

4.2.1 Key points from discussions

Risks

'Big investment needed' stimulated the response by one participant in the consultation 2 web conference that, 'avoidable impacts on biodiversity will occur if the environment is not taken into account at the higher planning level or if corners are cut and a cheaper infrastructure is chosen.' Another participant felt that 'extreme weather events' should be extended to account for the risks posed for the grid infrastructure and populations by increasing temperature and sea level rises, as continuous phenomena.

Web conference attendees advised the project team to consider and address the following additional risks in the more detailed SESA assessment:

- Failing to plan ahead and develop an adequate infrastructure that can adapt to technological advances in the future;
- Decarbonisation will be delayed if issues are not addressed effectively;
- Price volatility could be introduced by a high share of renewables in the generation mix.

Opportunities

Attendees suggested that the proposed e-Highway2050 grid architectures present the following opportunities in addition to the results of consultation one:

- Climate change adaptation and mitigation;
- Energy system decarbonisation;
- Electrification of heating and transport;
- Ecological enhancement associated with power line corridors.

CDFs

One participant stated that as only one of four CDFs focuses on social and environmental issues, ‘Too much emphasis is placed on economic and operational issues’ rather than ‘environmental limits, social equity and addressing the needs of the poorest in society.’ He underlined the need to ‘ensure that people understand that the impacts on biodiversity are real: real nature, real deaths, etc.’. Finally, he advised the project team to, ‘Be careful of the use of the word ‘acceptance’ [in CDF1] and ensure that people are aware of the real issues of acceptability.’

Annex 4.3 - Consultation 3 Results: Workshop, 6 May 2014

The 40 workshop participants included e-Highway consortium members, academics, TSOs, NGOs and DG Research and Innovation. The workshop reflected on the draft SESA assessment findings for each CDF including potential risks, opportunities and guidelines. This formed the basis for discussion during the workshop. This section summarises comments and feedback from participants as part of a ‘carousel’ exercise in the workshop on CDFs 1 to 4 and associated draft risks, opportunities and SESA guidelines. Table 50 to Table 53 and Figure 70 to Figure 73 present supporting information. The tables show all the information on draft risks and opportunities that was discussed at the workshop - pale pink cells represent risks and pale green cells represent opportunities. The figures then summarise participant responses to these draft risks and opportunities including suggested guidelines for addressing risks and capitalising on opportunities. The figures are structured around the example strategic options discussed at the workshop for a given CDF and use the same colour coding for risks and opportunities as the tables. Section 4.3 in the main report details the methodology adopted in Consultation 3.

Table 50 - Consultation 3: CDF 1 and associated draft risks and opportunities and SESA guidelines on which participants provided comments as detailed in Figure 70.

CDF 1: Social Acceptance and Acceptability	
G1: Centralised and large scale RES	(-) Uneven distribution of some of the environmental costs (e.g. landscape, biodiversity) associated with large scale centralised RES based system [Social equity].
	(-) Increasing vulnerability to extreme climatic events, depending on infrastructure location and specific local climate change impacts [Vulnerabilities].
G2: Decentralised and small scale RES	(+) Help promote increased awareness of energy usage and relationships with climate change and other sustainability issues, potentially encouraging greater uptake of greener behaviours [Social Equity].
	(+) Small scale production of forest biomass likely to be compatible with multiple benefits for landscapes, ecosystems and ecosystem services [Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services].
G4: RES non-dominant	(-) Could face problems of public acceptance and acceptability as nuclear and thermal generation technologies are not favoured by EU citizens [Social equity].
	(+) May have a smaller land take footprint per unit of energy produced. Reduce energy development related pressure on land resources, the availability of land use/management options [Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services].
G5: Nuclear and fossil without CCS near existing capacity	(+) Thermal and nuclear generation technologies sited close to demand with no loss of efficiency producing a constant supply of electricity, helping to maintain fair access to energy system benefits across Europe [Social Equity].
S1: Centralised hydro	(-) Increased storage infrastructure pressure affecting the integrity of landscapes, ecosystems, communities (of species), habitats and individual species populations, (e.g. alteration of morphology, flow and other ecosystem processes such as fish spawning [Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services].

Figure 70 - Comments received from Consultation 3 participants on CDF 1

Table 51 - Consultation 3: CDF 2 and associated draft risks and opportunities and SESA guidelines on which participants provided comments as detailed in Figure 71.

CDF2: Energy Security and Technologies	
G1: Centralised and large scale RES	(-) Long distance transmission might result in high energy losses and requires higher consumption of raw materials for cabling [Energy Efficiency].
	(-) Contrary to European macro-policies that favour an increase in distributed generation from small producers (EU Policy) [Energy Security].
G2: Decentralised and small scale RES	(+) Decentralised generation may improve the energy system's robustness to extreme climatic events, security issues and other risks thus contributing energy security.
G3: Dominant RES	(-) Inhibit the development of technologies not related to RES such as CCS and flexible gas technologies [Innovation and Tech. Development].
	(+) Promotion of low-carbon economy and RES incorporation goals [Energy Efficiency].
G4: RES non-dominant	(-) Could face problems of public acceptance and acceptability as nuclear and thermal generation technologies are not favoured by EU citizens [Social equity].
	(+) May have a smaller land take footprint per unit of energy produced. Reduce energy development related pressure on land resources, the availability of land use/management options [Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services].
S1: Centralised hydro	(-) Limits future options by inhibiting technological development of other storage technologies [Innovation and Tech. Development].
S2: Decentralised DSM	(+) Reduce vulnerability to supply disruptions [Energy Security].

Figure 71 - Comments received from Consultation 3 participants on CDF 2

Table 52 - Consultation 3: CDF 3 and associated draft risks and opportunities and SESA guidelines on which participants provided comments as detailed in Figure 72.

CDF3: Geopolitical Economy and Regional Equity	
G1: Centralised and large scale RES	(-) Unbalanced dependence on market access to energy supply, electricity price and real estate value [Market dynamics and regional equity].
	(+) Viability/ease of management in terms of EU energy export and import potential and the development of energy trade agreements with third countries [International competitiveness].
G2: Decentralised and small scale RES	(-) Discourage international trade initiatives and access to international energy markets (EU Policy) [International competitiveness].
G4: RES non-dominant	(-) Vulnerable to external market and political volatility due to energy import reliance (e.g. Russian gas and uranium) [International competitiveness].
G7: High to very high flows from South and North to Central Europe	(-) Threatens regional equity [Market dynamics and regional equity].
	(+) Support to greater energy market integration [Market dynamics and regional equity].
G9: Low energy flows	(+) Energy self-sufficiency at MS and local levels [Market dynamics and regional equity].

Figure 72 - Comments received from Consultation 3 participants on CDF 3

Table 53 - Consultation 3: CDF 4 and associated draft risks and opportunities and SESA guidelines on which participants provided comments as detailed in Figure 73.

CDF 4: European Regional Governance	
G1: Centralised and large scale RES	(-) Centralization and large scale RES may determine regional imbalances and provoke unsustainability, because of biased competitive internal market of electricity (EU Policy) [Policies and Politics].
	(-) Discourage small producers and local generation and a decreased empowerment and engagement of small-scale energy initiatives [Responsibilities and Competences].
	(+) Determine cross-border regulatory mechanisms (harmonized trades and subsidies rates) [Policies and Politics].
G2: Decentralised and small scale RES	(+) Public coordination and cooperation through new context-influenced public policies to RES [Policies and Politics].
G3: Dominant RES	(+) Promote national strategies for European coordination in energy issues [Responsibilities and Competences].
G4: RES non-dominant	(-) Could face problems of public acceptance and acceptability as nuclear and thermal generation technologies are not favoured by EU citizens [Social equity].
	(+) May have a smaller land take footprint per unit of energy produced. Reduce energy development related pressure on land resources, the availability of land use/management options [Biodiversity, landscape and ecosystem services].
G5: Nuclear and fossil without CCS near existing capacity	Additional risks suggested.
G6: Nuclear and fossil with CCS close to demand	Additional risks suggested.
	Additional opportunities suggested.

Figure 73 - Comments received from Consultation 3 participants on CDF 4

4.3.1 How was Consultation 3 taken into account?

The consultation 3 workshop played a key role informing and refining the draft assessment of risks and opportunities and also the SESA guidelines in terms of planning/management, governance and monitoring. The workshop results were written-up, collated and analysed to identify: 1) suggested tweaks/refinement to existing risks, opportunities and guidelines; 2) suggestions for additional risks, opportunities and guidelines; and 3) suggestions for removal of risk, opportunities and guidelines e.g. where stakeholders feel that some issues had been over emphasised in the draft assessment. Overall therefore, Consultation 3 has had a significant impact on and influenced the final strategic assessment presented in this report at Section 6.

Annex 4.4 - Stakeholder Video Interviews: Results

Table 54 lists the six interviewees, their affiliations, and key themes elicited from their responses. The videos can be viewed at <https://www.youtube.com/user/eHighway2050>

Table 54 - Video interviewees and key themes captured from interviews

Interviewee	Affiliation	Key Themes
Ana Aguado	Friends of the Supergrid	Reducing electricity bills; internal electricity market; anticipation and flexibility in a new system.
Ivan Pineda	European Wind Energy Association (EWEA)	Increased trade and competitiveness in the power system; decrease in consumer electricity prices; connect renewable energy sources to consumers; social acceptance as an important aspect and a risk to the project; need for comprehensive risk assessments; encourage public participation; important for everyone to get involved in planning our future energy grid.
Dr. Ivan Scrase	Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB), Renewables Grid Initiative (RGI)	Enable decarbonisation in Europe; risk of 'stranded assets'; enabling renewable energy to be incorporated into the energy system; more involvement desired from environmental NGOs and from civil society.
Jonathan Gaventa	Third Generation Environmentalism (E3G)	Modernising Europe's power system; supporting decarbonisation; improving energy trade from plentiful sources to high demand areas; need to make sure new energy system is responsive to the changes we are seeing; now is the right time to be asking these questions about our energy future given the time it will take to deliver a future energy system; need to bring in as many stakeholders as possible to help identify and understand all of the risks being faced; members of the public need to get involved.
Jamila Madeira	Redes Energéticas Nacionais (REN)	More efficient delivery will benefit all European citizens; need big investments and need new financial to attract investors; involve all stakeholders at an early stage: national regulatory authorities, producers and consumers.
Lisa Drossler	Swiss Grid	Opportunity to distribute Europe's renewable energy resources; need to design a transparent and inclusive process that is open to adapting and able to react to unforeseen developments; regulators need to be involved.